

An Exploration of the Relationship between Disclosures and Disclosure Responses; Help-seeking Behaviours and Outcomes for Victims of Stalking

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DECLARATION OF ORIGINALITY

This is to certify that I am responsible for the work submitted in this thesis, that the original work is my own except as specified in acknowledgements or in footnotes, and that neither the thesis nor the original work contained therein has been submitted to this or any other institution for a degree.

ABSTRACT

Previous research investigating the criminal act of stalking has indicated that engaging all sectors involved with victims through informed practice is essential to effectively address personal biases, stereotypes, and myths surrounding stalking. This understanding can enhance the ability of the general public, support agencies, law enforcement, criminal justice systems, and legislative decision-makers to more effectively recognize and respond to victim disclosures.

However, existing literature has not adequately explored how victim and societal perceptions and responses to victims disclosures influence victim acknowledgment, reporting, and access to support for both male and female victims, or how these factors interplay with the stalking outcome (whether the stalking is continuing or has stopped). This research identified gaps in understanding how perceptions and disclosure responses influence stalking acknowledgment and help-seeking decisions, particularly through the lens of The Social Learning Theory and The Social Reaction Theory. Addressing factors such as social stigma, fear of escalation, and prior negative experiences is crucial for developing effective support systems for both male and female victims.

Stalking is a significantly under-reported, under-disclosed crime that can lead to long-term psychological harm for victims. This research aimed to explore the perceptions of stalking, help-seeking decisions, and the impact of the responses victims receive when disclosing their stalking experiences, including the relationship of these disclosures to the stalking outcome. Focusing on key areas such as victim acknowledgment, factors and perceptions involved in victim help-seeking decisions, the relationship between acknowledgment of the stalking to disclosures, and the responses received to further help-seeking, and the interplay between help-seeking and the stalking outcome.

This study utilized a qualitative method, gathering data from both a cross-sectional web-based survey and face-to-face interviews. These methods were employed to gather insights from victims about their experiences and perceptions. Adopting the qualitative research design, adhering, although not strictly, to General Inductive Thematic Analysis as a strategy of inquiry.

The results from this study found that social learning influenced stalking acknowledgment either dissuading or delaying the acknowledgment of this crime, for victims and those they disclosed to. Social learning was also found to influence the response received upon disclosing. Findings of this study indicate that predicted and perceived social reactions such as negative responses to disclosures can create barriers to acknowledgment of the victims experience, and discourage further

help-seeking, while predicted and perceived positive responses encourage victim's acknowledgment of the stalking, and encourage additional disclosures, aligning with previous research conducted. This research also found that action facilitated the stalking stopping, whilst inaction facilitated the stalking continuing.

The current study's findings also support researchers who noted that victims may endure numerous stalking behaviours before seeking assistance, as well as literature that found that law enforcement often fails to take the crime seriously, exacerbating the victims' negative experience. Importantly, this study found that responses to disclosures and subsequent actions by both the victims and those they disclosed too can affect whether or not the stalking itself stops. However, achieving consistent positive/helpful responses from law enforcement remains a significant barrier for victims. In contrast, validating a victim's experience can enhance the likelihood of victims seeking further help and may reduce the long-term psychological impact of stalking and affect the overall stalking outcome.

This research underscores the necessity of understanding both the barriers to and factors that promote help-seeking decisions in order to develop effective support systems and interventions that validate the victims' experience. Ultimately, this research aims to contribute to the literature, inform policymakers, and stakeholders, emphasizing the importance of recognizing and addressing stalking victimization and pervasive consequences to both the victim and society as a whole.

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Chapter 1: Introduction to the Stalking Victim's Journey

In 2021, a 23 year old woman named Gracie Spinks was murdered by her former co-worker Michael Sellers. Mr. Sellers had been stalking Miss Spinks over a period of time. While visiting the home of Miss Spinks to deliver items she had requested, Mr. Sellers kissed her and attempted to sexually assault her. Miss Spinks asked him to cease and leave. The following day, Miss Spinks made it clear to Mr. Sellers that she was not interested in a relationship and proceeded to block him on social media. However, Mr. Sellers persisted and intensified his actions stalking Miss Spinks. This included inundating her with messages, monitoring her movements through company CCTV, and even enlisting a co-worker to spy on her. Four days after the incident of attempted sexual assault, Mr. Sellers parked near the paddock where her horse was kept to survey her movements. Miss Spinks spotted him, panicked and drove by without stopping, and reported the incident to her work supervisors. Managers at Miss Spinks work initiated an internal investigation and determined that Mr. Sellers showed no remorse for his actions, he was then dismissed.

Miss Spinks had reported Mr. Sellers' obsessive behaviour and stalking, including waiting for her near the field where she cared for her horse. Miss Spinks reported Mr. Sellers' behaviours to Police using the non-emergency 101 number. She informed the call handler that Mr. Sellers became increasingly odd. He's been witnessed watching her on work cameras. He had also been known to target other girls at the workplace. An inexperienced constable then spoke to Sellers but did not conduct a formal interview, and bodycam footage of their interaction was not saved. Despite her concerns, police classified her case as low risk after the verbal discussions with both parties. Crucially, the workplace disciplinary records for Mr. Sellers were not requested. The police decided to close the stalking investigation, and Sellers was classified as a standard risk because he hadn't made any threats of violence and was not previously known to the police. As a result of these decisions, Mr. Sellers received only a verbal warning regarding his behaviour.

On May 6, 2021, a dog walker discovered a bag of weapons across the road from the field where Miss Spinks kept her horse and handed it in to the police. The brown rucksack contained knives, an axe, and a hammer, and a note, pertaining to lying. Officers dismissed the weapons as bush craft tools. The dog walker had expressed her shock at the officers' lack of concern regarding the items. No further action was taken.

On the morning of June 18, 2021, Miss Spinks left home early to visit her horse. Shortly after 8 a.m., she was found lying on the ground, having been stabbed ten times. Paramedics attempted to save her but she suffered catastrophic bleeding due to a fatal stab wound to her neck. A knife was

discovered near her. Miss Spinks was pronounced dead around 8:50 a.m., and Mr. Sellers was found dead in a nearby field about two hours later. Police do not consider his death suspicious but confirmed that the two incidents were connected.

In the wake of Miss Spinks death, her parents, Alison Heaton and Richard Spinks, presented a petition to MPs advocating for more support for stalking victims. The petition, which had gathered over 105,000 signatures, called for funding for police forces to provide advocates for victims and to enhance the investigation of stalking cases. Mr. Spinks has suggested that the process of reporting, logging, and investigating needs to be changed (ITV. News, 2023). Gracie's story is sadly not uncommon.

Miss Spinks case brought about public outcry and highlighted some very important considerations for research into the phenomenon of the crime of stalking. Firstly, according to media reports, Miss Spinks did not use the word 'stalking' when reporting to police, rather she was uncomfortable and knew that Mr. Sellers' behaviour was not normal and dangerous. Which begs the question of whether or not she herself recognized the course of conduct as stalking. The police did not investigate the behaviour as stalking, so it can be assumed that they did not acknowledge her experience as stalking.

Cases such as this underscore the central contribution of this thesis: pervasive misconceptions and misunderstandings about stalking among victims, the wider public, and criminal justice actors operate as cognitive and institutional barriers across the stalking trajectory. These barriers impede acknowledgment (recognizing patterns of unwanted pursuit as stalking), delay or deter disclosure, distort responses at the point of reporting, and ultimately suppress timely protective action against an insidious, escalating crime. By tracing the journey of stalking victimization from initial recognition through disclosure, institutional engagement, and outcomes, the thesis examines how social reactions, cognitive biases, and procedural practices shape whether stalking is interrupted or allowed to persist. In doing so, it analyzes the mechanisms through which validating or invalidating responses influence victims' coping and the mobilization of action. This process oriented lens clarifies how misinformation and stereotype based gatekeeping sustain continuation, whereas informed, action-oriented responses facilitate the cessation of the stalking.

Definitions of Stalking

Stalking is a pervasive and often misunderstood crime, the behaviour is characterized by repeated, unwanted attention and surveillance directed at an individual, leading to feelings of fear

and distress (Baum et al, 2009; Longpré et al, 2023). Stalking behaviour can manifest through various forms, including physical following, persistent communication, and online harassment, significantly impacting the victim's mental and emotional well-being (Buhi et al, 2009; Weekes et al, 2025). Despite a somewhat ambiguous agreement about what constitutes stalking, there is no universally accepted definition of the crime. Stalking is generally understood as unwanted, repeated, obsessive behaviours that instils fear and distress in victims (Baum et al, 2009; Longpré et al, 2023). Initially the act of stalking was typically perceived as a crime primarily affecting celebrities and the association of celebrity stalking arose in the 1980's and 1990's.

Definitions of stalking in law in England and Wales are set out in the Protection from Freedom Act 2012 (Gov.uk, 2012) which states that the criminal offence of stalking occurs when an individual engages in a course of conduct directed at a person that amounts to stalking and/or harassment (2a) which is without fear of violence, and stalking (4a) with fear of violence, or serious alarm or distress affecting day to day activities on at least two occasions. Some of the behaviours defined in this legislation give examples of; following, contacting, or attempting to contact by any means, publishing statements, monitoring the use of the internet, email or any other form of electronic communication, loitering (whether public or private), interfering with property in and watching or spying.

Whereas in Scotland, Sec.39 of the Criminal Justice and Licensing Act 2010 (Scottish Government, 2010) deems stalking as a standalone crime when an individual engages in a course of conduct directed at a person causing fear and alarm. Some of the behaviours listed that define the course of conduct are; following, contacting, or attempting to contact by any means, publishing any statement or other material, monitoring the use of the internet, email or any other form of electronic communication, entering any premises, loitering in any place (whether public or private), interfering with any property, giving anything to or leaving anything where it may be found, watching or spying, acting in any other way that a reasonable person would expect would cause to suffer fear or alarm, and the course of conduct involves conduct on at least two occasions.

Since the turn of the century stalking has gradually begun to be recognized as an act that is far from confined to the rich and the famous, and instead is considered as a serious offense that affects the common public as well (Mullen et al, 2009). Despite the seriousness of the acts severity, research indicates that stalking remains significantly under-reported (Brady, 2022). In the United Kingdom, and the United states, it is estimated that only about 30% of stalking victims disclosed their experiences to family and friends, a figure that has remained fairly consistent since the 1990's (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2014). This is notable given that contacting law enforcement has been

identified as a key factor to the cessation of stalking behaviours, yet contacting law enforcement has also found to be underutilized (Brady, 2022).

Stalking Prevalence

In England and Wales, the Domestic Abuse Act of 2021 (Gov.uk, 2021) was implemented and included further measures to tackle domestic abuse, a specific area of this legislation that aligns with stalking behaviours are the measures implemented to tackle control and coercion post separation (Augustyn et al, 2020). However, the effectiveness of these added measures have yet to be evidenced. For example, in 2024, The Office of National Statistics (ONS) reported the prevalence of stalking in England and Wales to be around 1 in 5 for females and around 1 in 11 for men over sixteen years of age having experienced some form of stalking. The Suzi Lamplugh Trust on behalf of The National Stalking Consortium in 2022 filed a super complaint due to concerns about stalking being misidentified by police and investigations were often not occurring;

'The high prevalence of stalking cases which are misidentified and poorly investigated point to the fact that this is a deep-rooted systemic issue across police forces in England and Wales.' (Suzi Lamplugh Trust 2022, pg. 4)

In 2021, the Crown Office and Procurator Fiscal Service (COPFS) in Scotland reported that approximately 11.8% of adults experience some form of stalking and harassment annually. According to the Scottish Public Health Observatory (ScotPHO) in 2021, the adult population of Scotland for over 16's was estimated at 4.6 Million, putting into perspective the estimated 11.8% of adults experiencing some form of stalking/harassment annually, which equates to approximately 542 800 adult victims . However, in Scotland there were only 1045 stalking charges put forward to the Crown Office in 2021. Stalking was also found to be prevalent in approximately 57% of domestic abuse identifiers in 10,000 cases reported, according to the Scottish Crime and Justice Survey (2021). However, the difference between the prevalence of cases reported and charges put forth may be partly due to the combined categorization of stalking with harassment and the introduction of the Domestic Abuse Scotland Act (2018) (DASA), which came into force in 2019. Since the introduction of the DASA, many behaviours previously charged as stalking under Section 39 are now prosecuted under the broader Section 1 domestic abuse offence. This grouping can blur the boundaries of what constitutes stalking, leading to misclassification and misunderstanding of its distinctive, course of conduct pattern, something that is already difficult for the public and law enforcement to recognize (Logan & Walker, 2009; Brady, 2022). Furthermore, many stalking behaviours are deemed as non-criminal, and fall under such categories as loitering on a public street, or the sending of gifts, which

when considered in isolation, are not deemed as criminal acts, therefore not considered as a part of the course of conduct (Logan and Walker, 2009; Brady, 2022).

In addition to the ambiguity of definitions, the overlapping of behaviour with other criminal legislation, etc., stalking can be difficult to define, and even more so to prosecute, due to not only the type of behaviours associated with stalking, but also the wide range of behaviours. This was exemplified in the non-exhaustive list of stalking behaviours in both the England & Wales and Scottish legislation for the crime of stalking detailed above. The focus in the legislation of a subjective list of a possible range of behaviours associated with stalking has potentially created an environment for misinterpretation. For example, The Independent Office for Police Conduct (IOPC) published a qualitative report taken from 9 interviews in 2024, following the Suzi Lamplugh (2022) Super complaint, finding several themes that victims deemed as a negative experience when reporting the stalking to police, two of which were; police understanding of stalking, and officer understanding and perceptions of cyber stalking. In regard to the misunderstanding of stalking and the misidentification of the crime, the report states;

‘The majority of victims interviewed provided details of experiences they had where the police did not recognise the behaviours they had experienced as stalking – sometimes misidentifying it as other crimes.’ (IOPC, 2024, pg. 11)

In relation to officers’ understandings of, and perceptions of cyberstalking the report highlighted that several victims who experienced cyberstalking felt the officer’s responses showed a lack of understanding of the crime. There is no easy answer to address perceptions and misconceptions, however the report did highlight the importance of training in stalking and cyberstalking to mitigate these misconceptions.

The term traditional stalking typically refers to offline behaviours which may include, but by no means is limited to acts such as following, approaching, loitering outside the workplace or home of the victim (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011). However, in the years preceding the millennium, technological advances have since seen the increase of internet availability and usage. As such, the rise of digital media and social platforms have allowed the act of stalking to move online. This is typically referred to as cyberstalking (Becker et al, 2020). Cyberstalking can encompass a range of online behaviours, such as sending private messages, emails and social media contact (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011; Becker et al, 2020). However, the lack of recognition of stalking is found not just amongst law enforcement, but also for victims themselves in the ability to recognize their experience as stalking, and unfortunately not an uncommon phenomenon (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011; Nicastro, 2020). The lack of victim recognition for acknowledging their victimization within a

stalking campaign is a very real barrier for reporting, as evidenced in the case study of Miss Spinks earlier in the chapter.

Nicastro (2020) suggest stalking to be a serious social concern, and as such the need to understand the barriers to recognition, reporting and action are a vital aspect of tackling stalking behaviour as a social issue. Misconceptions, social biases, gender norms, and the romanticizing or minimizing of stalking behaviours are a phenomenon rooted in social learning that impacts both victims and society at large (Tjaden and Thoennes, 1998; Becker, 2020). Misconceptions can include perceptions that stalkers are only strangers that target celebrities, stalking behaviour is romantic, only males perpetrate stalking, and only females are victims of stalking, to name just a few. These perceptions are largely shaped by social representations about stalking in news media, films, television, social media, and in general societal understandings of stalking (Fox et al, 2011; Becker et al, 2020). However, research indicates that these factors can be overcome, leading to recognition of stalking (acknowledgment) when certain correlates, such as psychological reactions including fear and anxiety regarding the seriousness of the behaviours are present (Reyns and Englebrect, 2011).

In addition to the issues outlined, including the overlap with other criminal legislation, and lack of victim recognition of the act itself, a significant barrier to help-seeking is a victims' acknowledgment or recognition of their experiences as stalking (Baum et al, 2009; Becker et al, 2020). Fisher et al (2007) and Jordan et al (2007) both note this lack of recognizing the threat levels posed by stalkers are often attributed to social norms, myths about stalking, and stereotypical perceptions, rooted in the social representations previously mentioned. Indeed, help-seeking decisions are often linked to the type of perpetrator pursuit victims may experience, such as offline or online behaviours (Brady et al, 2023). Specifically, victims who were physically followed were more likely to recognize their experiences as stalking, when compared to those followed or surveilled online. However despite this, just over 30% reported to police. This highlights the importance of understanding how perceptions, biases, and norms may influence help-seeking decisions, responses to disclosures, and ultimately the outcomes of stalking incidents.

Ultimately, the criminal act of stalking is an under research phenomenon. A significant amount of stalking literature focuses on ex-intimate and sexual crimes, the prevalence and psychological consequences of stalking, statistical reporting data and help-seeking decisions conducted over a decade ago (Mullen et al, 1999; Baum et al, 2009; Buhi et al, 2009; Reyns and Englebrect, 2011,2014). Yet, while under researched, there does remain a handful of studies that has explored the help-seeking decisions and processes concerning stalking victimization. Research tended to identify a number of factors such as the desire for validation, potential retaliation, and fear of death

or physical violence, as reasons for not reporting the crime (Taber-Smith, 2017). Studies such as these (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2014, 2024; Ngo, 2014, 2018, 2020; Taber-Smith, 2017) highlight the importance of exploring victims experiences to understand these barriers to seeking support.

Barriers to acknowledgment and reporting

The importance of understanding the facilitators and barriers to acknowledgment and reporting within stalking victimization and the seriousness of the consequences of stalking perpetration are underscored by findings indicating that 94% of femicides involved stalking prior to the murder taking place (Monkton-Smith et al, 2017). Important to this consideration, as mentioned in the above paragraphs, is the fact that there are factors that can encourage victims to acknowledge and take action, such as seeking help to mitigate the stalking incidents (Brady et al, 2022).

'Research has identified several strategies victims adopt to deter unwanted conduct from stalkers. Whether such strategies are effective, however, is relatively unknown.' (Brady, 2022, pg.1)

This encouragement to take action is also exemplified in research on the potential power and control dynamics which can also apply to stalking victimization, and relate to a victims perceptions of the seriousness of the stalking they are experiencing (Tittle, 1995; Parkhill et al, 2022). Power and control dynamics can explain stalker motivations which are related to factors such as control and retaliation, which can promote victim disclosures and help-seeking behaviours (Taber-Smith, 2017, Brady, 2022).

Furthermore, a stalker's previous offenses and the perceived seriousness of their behaviours align with the Theory of Rational Choice Perspective (Gottfredson & Gottfredson, 1998). The Rational Choice Perspective was brought into the context of stalking victimization by Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010). Reyns and Englebrecht posited that victims will make rational choices of action and help-seeking to mitigate the stalking when specific factors such as the perceived seriousness of the stalking behaviours and the reactions experienced by victims have been met for both offline and online stalking.

Logan (2023) conducted research on online stalking, filling a gap in the research of female victims of acquaintance stalking. The study highlighted the rising prevalence of online stalking due to increased technology use. The study found that women who were monitored online faced higher levels of threats, harassment, and control from their stalkers compared to those who were harassed but not monitored. These monitored victims experienced more severe negative outcomes, including emotional distress and job interference, and were more likely to seek help. However, there was a

general reluctance among participants to seek formal assistance due to fears of disbelief or exacerbating the situation, highlighting the need for greater awareness of the complexities and severe impacts of online stalking. The study underscores the importance of addressing both online harassment and monitoring strategies to better support victims.

Whereas, Fissel (2021) examined the decision-making processes of cyberstalking victims regarding reporting their victimization and seeking help utilizing Gottfredson and Gottfredson's Rational Choice Theory, finding victims experiencing cyberstalking for one month to less than a year were more likely to report to law enforcement. Victims were less inclined to report if the stalker was someone they knew closely, such as an intimate partner, and males were more likely to report than females. The study highlights that the seriousness of the offense and the victim-offender relationship significantly affected victims' help-seeking decisions, emphasizing the need for research to understand the unique challenges faced by cyberstalking victims.

Stalking Disclosures

A disclosure can be defined as an interaction between two individuals in which one person shares personal information about themselves with the other (Greene et al, 2006). According to Knox and Hill (2016), all forms of human communication involves some level of disclosure, whether through verbal or non-verbal methods. Most individuals are quite deliberate about what and how much they share with others. Knox and Hill suggest that one factor influencing disclosure decisions is the nature of the relationship to whom they are disclosing to. For example, friendships tend to involve mutual disclosure, with both parties sharing roughly equal amounts, whereas disclosure patterns may be less balanced in other types of relationships, such as those that involve some form of authority (Knox and Hill, 2016). Disclosures can be viewed along a continuum: at one end, a person shares everything openly, including all conscious thoughts and feelings; at the other end, a person does not disclose at all and may even actively conceal or lie. Few individuals operate at these extremes, as it is nearly impossible to either fully share or completely withhold all thoughts and feelings. Additionally, it is important to understand that disclosure is a state rather than a characteristic, meaning that even someone who is generally open may choose not to disclose in a specific situation (Knox and Hill, 2016). For the purpose of this research, the term disclosure pertains to victims and participants acts of telling about their stalking experience, whether in whole or in part, with the assumption that what is being disclosed is the persons' personal truth and understanding of their experience.

Research on the responses to stalking disclosures has been limited to date. For instance, in professional settings, Ngo (2020) emphasized the significance of an employer's duty of care when a victim discloses stalking. However, Jutasi and McEwan (2021) found that victims often perceive their employers as unhelpful in such situations. There is even less information about how victims are responded to when they disclose to law enforcement. Previous studies (Tjaden and Thoennes, 1998) have shown that 50-80% of stalking cases go unreported, with arrest rates estimated between 8-24% (Baum et al, 2009; Brady 2024). These inconsistent findings highlight the need for further investigation into disclosure research and the inclusion of broader participant groups beyond college and university settings to gain a better understanding of the topic.

Negative responses such as an invalidating reaction to a victim's disclosure can hinder further help-seeking, while positive responses which validate the experience can encourage additional disclosures, (Ullman, 2010; Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011; Edwards et al, 2014; Lietzau et al, 2023). However, Sheridan et al, (2003) posited that victims may endure hundreds of different stalking behaviours before seeking assistance. Similarly, (Jordan et al, 2003; Ngo, 2020) indicated that law enforcement often leaves victims feeling that the crime of stalking is not taken seriously, with police inaction frequently worsening the situation. Furthermore, there is some agreement that achieving a consistent positive police response to stalking disclosures presents a significant barrier for both male and female victims, (Fisher et al, 2003; Taylor-Dunn, 2019). In contrast, validating a victim's experience can enhance the likelihood of seeking help and reduce the long-term psychological impact of stalking (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011; Lietzau et al, 2023). When victims are validated and encouraged to report stalking, they become reliant on the decisions and actions of the criminal justice system, which is heavily influenced by Focal Concerns Theory (Brady and Reyns, 2024). Positive actions can lead to improved outcomes for victims, whereas inaction can deter them and jeopardize their safety.

There is limited research into disclosure responses that stalking victims receive following disclosures and the relationship of these to the stalking acknowledgment. There is also a gap in the literature investigating and comparing how a disclosure response can influence further help-seeking decisions for male and female victims of stalking, particularly in the context of the Bandura (1977) Social Learning Theory (SLT) and the Ullman (2010) Social Reaction Theory (SRT) in the context of stalking victimization (Lietzau et al, 2023; Cordellieri et al, 2024).

The current study proposes that interaction within the social environment frames our understanding of different constructs, such as stalking, and it is these understandings that shape stalking acknowledgement (recognition of the experience) in both the victim and within wider

society, which in turn shapes the social reaction to this type of victimization. Perceptions are important for understanding both the actual responses received and the expected social reactions to a victims' disclosure of their experience. However, despite the potential applications of the SLT to understanding the journey of stalking victimization, no recent research has explored SLT in the context of stalking (Cordellieri et al, 2024). This is a critical area of study as it is only through robust empirical research and literature that we can identify and understand the factors associated with the areas of disclosure decisions and responses that may help a victim and their family to achieve the support required following a stalking victimization, and create more positive outcomes.

Understanding the facilitators and barriers that influence victims' help-seeking decisions is crucial for developing effective support systems and interventions. The current research proposes that factors such as social stigma, fear of escalation, lack of awareness about available resources, and prior negative experiences with disclosures can hinder a victim's willingness to seek help. By addressing these challenges and promoting a supportive environment, we can empower victims to take action, ultimately aiding in their recovery and enhancing community safety. This understanding can help the general public, support agencies, law enforcement, criminal justice systems, and legislative decision makers to better recognize and respond to victim disclosures. Such an approach may lead to more positive outcomes for all parties involved in stalking cases, especially for the victims, through early intervention. The current literature published on the topic of stalking has not sufficiently explored victim disclosures to understand what the relationship of disclosure responses can have on victim acknowledgement, reporting and accessing support for male and female victims of stalking, and how this may or may not affect the stalking outcome.

The Current Research

The main purpose of this research is to understand the facilitators and barriers in the journey of victimization in relation to help-seeking decisions of stalking victims. This exploration includes the impact of these decisions to the stalking outcome (whether the stalking has stopped or continued). In addition to investigating the help-seeking decision making processes, the research also explores a number of secondary points. The secondary point arose from the exploration of literature included in the literature review, such as, does the type of stalker or the amount of stalking behaviours a victim experiences influence discourse, and whether there are gender differences within the primary and secondary questions.

The objectives to this study, is to understand the factors that may be either a facilitator or a barrier to a victim of stalking in the context of help-seeking decisions, disclosure discourse and the stalking outcome, in order to inform academia, policy-makers, educational programs and society in general about the importance of understanding stalking victimization. Therefore, the research questions under exploration in this study were:

Primary Questions:

- * *How do disclosure responses influence a victim's acknowledgment of stalking?*
- * *How does a positive and negative disclosure response impact further help-seeking decisions?*
- * *Does disclosing impact whether or not the stalking behaviour stops or continues?*

Secondary Questions:

- * Are the amount of stalking behaviours a factor in what disclosure response is received?
- * Does typology (stalker type) impact the disclosure response?
- * Are there any gender differences for the above questions?

The primary questions were formulated to explore stalking victims' experiences of their victimization from acknowledgment through to the help-seeking decisions that victims may or not make as a result of their perceptions of the disclosure response, including the relationship of these perceptions to the stalking outcome. This is an area that has not yet been researched and is vital to understand the factors involved not only in the recognition of the crime, but also how these factors of perceptions and social reactions interplay with further help-seeking and, whether or not the stalking has stopped or continued. The secondary questions were chosen from the insights provided from existing literature to gain further clarity of how victims perceive the amount of behaviours and type of stalker interplay with the perceptions and social reactions of others to the victims disclosures, which is an under researched area. The gender exploration was chosen to understand the gender experience of perceptions and social reactions to highlight any potential differences in all the explored questions.

Thesis Overview

This thesis delves into the complex experiences of stalking victims, focusing on the Barriers and facilitators to acknowledgment of the crime, help-seeking behaviours and how these relate to the stalking outcome. Chapter 2 provides a literature review that establishes a foundation for understanding stalking. It explores the literature on the general characteristics of stalking, legislative understandings, and the motivations behind the behaviours exhibited by stalkers. A key emphasis is

placed on the importance of acknowledgment in victims' decisions to seek help, the prevalence of stalking, its psychological effects, the dynamics surrounding victim disclosures, and the critical nature of responses received post-disclosure. Chapter 3 outlines the research design, detailing the methodology and the researcher's positionality. It discusses theoretical perspectives and reflexivity while presenting the qualitative approaches employed for data gathering and analysis. Chapter 4 presents the qualitative findings from the survey and interviews, organized into four primary themes: Acknowledgment, Help-Seeking Decisions, Disclosure Responses, and Stalking Outcomes. Each theme is further dissected into sub-headings that emerged from the collected data. Chapter 5 engages in a discussion of the findings, highlighting how societal perceptions of stalking shape the victimization experience. It examines the journey from acknowledgment of victimization through help-seeking and disclosure, identifying barriers and facilitators that influence the outcomes of the stalking. Chapter 6 concludes the thesis by summarizing key findings in relation to the research aims, discussing their significance and contributions to the field. It also addresses limitations of the study and proposes future research directions to further explore this crucial area of barriers to victim support.

In summary, this research emphasizes the significance of stalking awareness to overcome misconceptions and misunderstandings of this crime, particularly within discussions among victims and wider society. This study reveals that validating and supportive discourses promote the likelihood of victims seeking further help for both male and female victims. Specifically, it illustrates that an encouraging and validating social reaction to a disclosure can empower victims to continue seeking assistance for the stalking, regardless of their individual circumstances, aligning with Ullman's (2010) Social Reaction Theory. Such validating interactions help victims overcome obstacles like acknowledgment, shame and the fear of being victim-blamed, enabling them to connect with support tailored to their needs and boosting their confidence in seeking additional support. This study also illustrates support for Ullman's social reaction theory in respect to invalidating discourse discouraging victims from taking action and seeking help, which in turn leaves victims isolated, and in many cases suffering continued stalking.

This research highlights the critical role of both policy and practice in addressing stalking in the workplace. For example, it advocates for the development of educational materials that explain the complexities of stalking, as well as establishing clear guidelines on how employers should respond when they are made aware of such behaviour. These recommendations have significant implications for organizational policy, emphasizing that companies have a duty of care to ensure a safe and supportive environment for their employees. Specifically, organizations of all types should

implement policies that go beyond standard anti-bullying and harassment protocols to explicitly address stalking, whether it occurs internally or externally, to protect their employees' safety and well-being.

Furthermore, legislative policies that address stalking training and awareness among law enforcement and criminal justice systems will empower victims to seek help and result in more action taken to tackle this crime. Using academic research to inform decision-makers of appropriate validating social reactions to a disclosure, which can include actions to take, or to avoid, can make the world safer, more peaceful, and more equitable for victims and wider society.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Literature Overview

This chapter presents a review of the relevant literature on the topic of stalking. The purpose of this review is to establish: (a) a general understanding of the phenomenon of stalking; (b) the motives and behaviours associated with the act; (c) why acknowledgement is important to victims' help-seeking decisions; (d) the prevalence of stalking; (e) the psychological consequences of stalking; (f) victims help-seeking decisions in relation to disclosing and (g) the importance of the responses received following a disclosure of a stalking experience. For the purpose of this review, a victim's disclosure involves any communication or conversation whereby the victim provides information to another regarding their stalking victimization.

The review will begin with exploring some general understandings of stalking and the legislative definitions in UK law of this crime. The theory of self-control in relation to stalker typologies and motivations. The control balance theory in relation to stalking perpetration and victimization will also be outlined. Stalking acknowledgement, cognitive biases and the social learning theory will be explored, as well as the ways in which the barriers of acknowledgement and disclosure responses in relation to the social reaction theory can create difficulties for a victims' help-seeking decision processes. This chapter will explore the prevalence and psychological consequences of stalking, stalking perceptions, while exploring the theory of rational choice and its relation to victim help-seeking decisions and actions. Finally, the focal concerns theory will be explored to unpack potential issues with formal disclosures to the criminal justice systems for victims of stalking.

The Crime of Stalking

The general understanding of the crime of stalking began with early research interest in the public perceptions of stalking in the United States of America during the 1980's and 1990's. Interest in the subject arose following significant media coverage in a rising number of pursuits of celebrities. In some cases, celebrities were physically assaulted or threatened by their stalkers. Media narratives at the time tended to represent stalkers as 'crazed fans' (Nadkarni and Grubin, 2000, pg. 1486). A clear example of this can be seen in the case of pop singer Madonna in 1996. Following the escape of Robert Dewey Hoskins from a mental institution in Southern California. The individual sought out company with Madonna in an effort to coerce her into marriage. However, Hoskins was also prepared to commit murder should the marriage proposal fail. Lawrence was subsequently sentenced to 10 years imprisonment in 1996 following a failed attempt to break into the home of

Madonna (Whitcomb, 2012). At the time, the concept of stalking was still in relative infancy, and only after this period did it start to gain social prominence. The subsequent discussions at the time resulted in a re-conceptualization of stalking narrative as a serious crime (Sheridan and Davies, 2001). Initially stalking was still thought to primarily revolve around men committing crimes against women (Spitzberg and Cadiz, 2002). The majority of the research on stalking in the 90's included small samples of known stalkers, or small underrepresented cohorts of victims, including anti-stalking statute effectiveness studies (Tjaden and Thoennes, 1998).

As public interest in stalking grew, the focus of academic research took a different direction, and aimed to understand the prevalence of stalking (Tjaden and Theonnes, 1998), who do stalkers target (Mullen et al, 1999), how often are victims overtly threatened by the stalker, how often do victims report to police (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010; 2014), and the psychological and social consequences of stalking (Tjaden and Thoennes, 1998). In 1998, Tjaden and Thoennes reported findings from the first ever American national crime survey on stalking data from 8000 women and 8000 men over the age of 18 years. The scholars found the prevalence of victimization was approximately 8% of women and 2% of men. Despite the participants declaring this crime a legitimate public and criminal justice health concern in the survey, only about half of victims had reported to police. Tjaden and Theonnes also found 30% females and 20% males declared they had sought counselling for their victimization.

At the time in the United States, stalking was primarily characterized as harassing or threatening behaviour whereby a perpetrator engages in repeated and threatening behaviour directed at a specific individual. The criteria for what constituted stalking were inclusive and encompassed a variety of behaviours. These included, but were not limited to: following the victim, showing up at their home or workplace, making harassing phone calls, leaving unwanted written messages or objects, and vandalizing the victim's property (Tjaden and Thoennes, 1998, p. 1). Researchers noted that such actions often came with threats of serious harm and could serve as warning signs for potential physical assaults or, in extreme cases, even murder.

Over time, the understanding of stalking evolved significantly. By the 2000s, stalking began to be recognized as a broader societal issue, reframed from a phenomenon affecting mainly public figures to being acknowledged as a form of domestic violence. This shift marked a significant change in how stalking was perceived, leading to its recognition as a commonly perpetrated crime affecting individuals across various demographics (Garthe et al, 2025). This evolution in understanding not only highlighted the seriousness of stalking behaviours but also underscored the need for comprehensive legal frameworks and societal awareness to address and mitigate these harmful actions effectively.

Following the development of the term stalking in the U.S. context, a generalized understanding of the phenomenon was applied further afield in the European continent and in the United Kingdom. This understanding occurred following the stalking of public figures in Europe (Hoffman, 2009). The phenomenon of stalking is now generally considered as a course of conduct that is unwanted and harassing and includes repeated contact attempts and behaviours, aimed at a target person (Sheridan et al, 2003). These unwanted behaviours are known to be fixated, repeated and obsessive and can occur online, offline or in combination (Sheridan et al, 2003; Baum et al 2009; Garthe et al, 2025).

Over the past two decades, modern societies have shifted to a digital landscape characterized by the widespread use of the internet and mobile devices (Fraser et al, 2010; Fissel, 2021). Technology has significantly advanced within modern society, but it has also increased risks for stalking victims and provided stalkers with more tools at their disposal (Fraser et al, 2010; Fissel, 2021). However, the challenge with technology lies in the ability to equip stalkers with additional resources, making their methods more intrusive. While research on technology related to stalking is limited, studies have indicated that over 25% of victims reported the stalkers employed some form of technology to carry out the stalking (Baum et al, 2009). According to Baum and colleagues, among those who experienced electronic stalking, 83% reported being targeted via e-mail, while 35% cited instant messaging. Furthermore, 46% noted that hidden cameras were used by their stalkers for surveillance purposes, and 10% mentioned the use of tracking technology used by the stalkers to monitor movements (Baum et al, 2009). As new technologies continue to develop, it becomes increasingly easier for perpetrators to stalk their victims (Fraser et al, 2010; Fissel, 2021).

Ultimately, the term stalking is commonly used and often misapplied in everyday life (Longpré & Stefanska et al, 2023). There is a considerable lack of awareness about what stalking actually is and what it may entail. This lack of understanding is not only apparent within the general public, but also among criminal justice systems, professionals and sometimes even victims (Sheridan et al, 2003; Tjaden, 2009). Adding to the confusion, despite some agreement and consensus of the term, there are still differences in definitions about what stalking is and how it is applied within criminal legislations. Legislative differences are dependent on the context, and country, with many countries having no stalking legislation at all (Nicastro, 2000).

Legislative Understanding of Stalking

Having chronologically discussed the general development of stalking as a term and concept since the 1980s, from the US to the UK, the literature will now focus on the implementation of the

act into law. The recognition of stalking as a significant social concern is increasingly evident in the expanding body of laws addressing this behaviour within various criminal justice systems. Over the years, more jurisdictions have taken steps to establish comprehensive stalking legislation, reflecting a societal commitment to tackling this issue effectively (Nicastro, 2000).

The first stalking legislation was passed in California, U.S.A in 1990 (Tjaden and Thoennes, 1998). The California Penal Code defines stalking as the willful and malicious act of harassing or repeatedly following another individual, coupled with making a credible threat intended to instill a reasonable fear for the victim's safety or that of their immediate family (California Legislation, n.d.). Following California's pioneering implementation of stalking legislation, every one of the 50 states, as well as U.S. territories and the federal government, have developed and enacted their own laws aimed at addressing and prohibiting stalking behaviour (Brady & Nobles, 2017). This widespread legislative response reflects a growing recognition of the serious nature of stalking and its impact on victims. This is reflected in lawmakers across the American nation to establish legal frameworks that not only define stalking but also provide necessary protections for individuals at risk. As a result, these statutes vary in their specifics but collectively contribute to a more comprehensive approach to combatting stalking and ensuring the safety of potential victims (Brady & Nobles, 2017).

A comprehensive analysis of stalking legislation was conducted by Van der Aa (2018) which highlighted that since the implementation of stalking into the U.S. legislation, 28 nations within Europe followed suit and subsequently established their own stalking laws. The extrapolation of stalking legislation into the U.S., European and UK contexts demonstrates the recognition of the serious threat posed by stalking across international jurisdictions.

Similarly, Patterns (2000) noted that in response to the US and subsequent European stalking legislations being implemented, Australia followed suit. However, and similar to the US and UK, there are variations between the Australian regions. Patterns (2000) developed a report for the Criminology Research Centre in Australia focusing on stalking in the context of legislative, policing and prosecution patterns which highlighted that each jurisdiction in Australia had crafted its own specific statutes regarding stalking. Using a range of existing research, case studies and regional policies and policing statistics, Pattern found the lack of uniformity across Australian regions demonstrates the difficulty in reaching an agreed unanimous term. Cultural, social and geo-political differences may be profound and have direct impact on stalking applications. As with the US, Australia and Europe, the United Kingdom has similarly sought to develop its own specific legislative definition as to what constitutes as stalking. Although, like the US and Australian regions, there are differences within the country itself as the UK comprises of 4 home nations, and as such Northern

Ireland and Scotland retain some degree of independence in their legislative framework and judiciary. This has created slight differences in terms of the legislative definitions of stalking and the workable conceptualization of the act that accompanies policing.

In the UK, stalking was initially framed within the wider Protection from Harassment Act (1997). This act sought to make stalking a criminal offence but enshrined it within wider harassment framework. This act was amended in England and Wales in 2012 to specifically draw out the act of stalking as a crime within its own right, separate from the act of harassment. This legislation defined stalking as a 'course of harassing conduct' that results in fear, alarm or distress for the targeted person, whereby the person conducting the behaviour knows or ought to know that the course of conduct amounts to harassment of the other person (2A offence). The 2012 legislative amendment also included a fear of violence stalking charge (4A offence) where the conduct causes another to fear (on at least two occasions) that violence will be used, or causes serious alarm or distress resulting in a substantial adverse effect on the recipients' usual day-to-day activities (Legislation Gov, 2012). The 2012 amendment reflected the growing acknowledgment of the prevalence of harm that stalking behaviours can generate for its victims.

According to the 2010 Criminal Justice and Licensing Scotland Act, the offence of stalking occurs when one person targets another. The course of conduct consists of two or more unwanted contacts and/or behaviours. A course of conduct that induces fear and alarm for the recipient of these behaviours; where the perpetrator ought to have known the conduct would cause fear and alarm (Scottish Government, 2010). The Scottish Government also recently acknowledged the frequent domestic abuse elements of emotional and psychological abuse found in many stalking cases. The legislative policymakers addressed this acknowledgment by introducing the Domestic Abuse (Scotland) Act 2018 (DASA), whereby the act defines domestic abuse as a course of conduct with or without physical violence (Gov.uk, 2021). However, despite the acknowledgement of this course of conduct and the resulting fear and alarm by some criminal justice systems (CJS) like England, Wales and Scotland, the uniqueness of the crime of stalking can make it exceedingly difficult for law enforcement to act when this crime is disclosed (Logan and Walker, 2009).

The arrest rates of the crime of stalking highlight such difficulties described by Brady & Nobles (2017). Brady and Noble proposed that legislative implementations have occurred due to the consideration of stalking to be a significant social issue, however, the prevalence of stalking has not been echoed within official reported prevalence data and those reports that represent stalking arrests. For example, in England & Wales and Scotland the following table details the reporting prevalence compared to arrest rates:

England & Wales	England & Wales	England & Wales	Scotland	Scotland	Scotland
Police recorded crime (March 2021-2022)	Arrest Rates (March 2021-2022)	Convictions Stalking & Harassment 2021-2022	Police recorded crime 2023-2024	Arrest Rates	2023 Sec.39 Convictions
118,411 cases reported*	5,948 charges*	2,537****	30,503**	2690**	39****

Table 1 *Suzi Lamplugh (2022) Super Complaint (2022)

**COPFS (2024) Domestic Abuse and Stalking Charges

*** Gov.uk (2023) Statistics

****CPS (2023) Data summary

The data represented in the table supports the claim of Brady & Nobles (2017) who examined stalking reporting and arrest rates from the Houston Police Department in America and found in an 8-year period, 2005 to 2013, a total of 3,756 stalking calls for service were reported and 66 stalking-related incident reports were recorded, and only 12 arrests for stalking resulted. These figures from America and from the UK highlight that despite the acknowledgment of stalking as a serious issue, the official reporting prevalence and arrest rates highlight serious disparities, particularly when you consider the estimation that 1.5 million adults over the age of 16 in England and Wales alone are estimated to experience stalking annually (ONS, 2024). As previously mentioned in Chapter 1, The Suzi Lamplugh super complaint highlighted that one potential reason for the disparity between reporting and arrest rates, may be the lack of recognition by police regarding the crime of stalking.

Stalking has been commonly conceptualized through the classification of specific acts. Many researchers have divided stalking tactics and behaviours into clusters of direct and indirect contact attempts and behaviours such as following, watching, monitoring, surveying, sending or leaving unwanted items and gifts, sending threatening, abusive and/or begging letters and messages (Buhi et al, 2009; Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011; 2014). These stalking behaviours can also include trying to gain information about the victim through third parties, damaging the victim's personal property, defaming the victim and issuing direct and/or indirect threats (Hirtenlehner et al, 2012). While these classifications of behaviours facilitate a standardized measurement of stalking behaviours, they cannot fully encapsulate the different manifestations of stalking behaviours and contextual characteristics. Furthermore, the behaviours associated with stalking also encompass both criminal and non-criminal acts of online and/or offline repeated, unwanted behaviours and contact attempts. These behaviours, especially the non-criminal acts can make it extremely difficult for victims, law enforcement officers and courts to recognize the overall course of conduct as a crime of stalking (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011; 2014; Fissel, 2021).

When considering the potential difficulties that police and courts may have in acting on a victims stalking disclosure; the length of time the stalking episodes can last is an important consideration. This is because, if the stalking experience is not recognized early, for example, when reported to the police, the repeated and targeted behaviours will likely continue for a victim. This concern was originally exemplified by Baum et al (2009) who reported on the American Nation Crime Victimization Survey (NCVS) that contained the first Stalking Victimization supplement (SVS). The survey found that of approx. 1600 participants, 11% of these respondents experienced the stalking behaviours and unwanted contacts for 5 years and over. This length of time is a substantial amount of time to experience repeated victimization, especially when considering the resulting fear, alarm and distress associated with stalking (Janickyj et al, 2009).

Reporting Prevalence

In addition to the issues outlined, the difficulties with criminal justice system responses and the lack of victim recognition of the act itself, research has shown that even when acknowledgment occurs, not all victims choose to disclose their experience (Buhi et al, 2009). Buhi and colleagues examined the help-seeking behaviours among college women in the U.S., and found that only 7.3% of nearly 400 women reported their stalking experience to the police. This cohort was made up of a convenience sample of women at college level education only and the reporting prevalence may have reflected the societal understanding of stalking at this time, however this was not explored. Examining the prevalence of formal and informal help-seeking decisions of victims of stalking, Reyns and Englebrecht (2014) applied the same data as the Baum et al (2009) study from the 2006 NCVS-SVS and found the figures were different compared to the Buhi and colleagues' results. Reyns and Englebrecht found that 31% of N=1591 respondents had asked friends and family for help, whilst 29% had reported to the police. The differences in the reporting prevalence between the Buhi et al (2009) and Reyns and Englebrecht (2014) studies may have been due to the sample of college women compared to the wider sample of the national survey data. An Important consideration however, is as Reyns and Englebrecht had suggested; the responses received from friends and family following the disclosures, may have influenced whether the victim chose to further disclose their experience to the police or other organizations such as support agencies.

In an investigation to further examine the prevalence of reporting, Addington (2022) investigated data from the American 2010 National Intimate Partner and Sexual Violence Survey (NISVS), 477 emerging adults aged 18-25 years responded to interpersonal victimization such as, intimate partner violence (IPV), stalking, and sexual violence. The study revealed that many

emerging adults tended to seek help from informal sources. This included friends and family, as opposed to formal services like police or counseling. In addition, Addington also noted that a significant portion of victims did not seek any help at all. The research compared the help-seeking behaviours between college-attending and non-college-attending emerging adults. Addington proposed that the non-college group is under-represented in research, and they face higher risks for victimization, due to the association of riskier behaviour. A study investigating sexual harassment victimization in America was conducted by Clodfelter et al (2010) of 24 American college students found similar risk factors to be prevalence amongst their own sample group. The findings of the Addington (2022) study indicated that both groups relied heavily on informal sources for help, although the college students used formal help more frequently. The victims from both groups who sought help from friends reported them as helpful, while perceptions of formal sources, particularly police, were mixed and often viewed as unhelpful. Overall, these studies emphasized the critical need for more research on non-college attending emerging adults of both genders to understand the victims' help-seeking patterns, highlighting implications for future research and policy-making.

Juarros-Basterretxea et al (2024) conducted a study which used data from the Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) Survey conducted by the Chilean National Institute of Youth in 2018, which included a nationally representative sample of 1,112 Chilean young adults. The focus was on the responses from 479 women aged 18-29. Key variables included their experiences with IPV, perceived reportability of IPV behaviours, and their choices regarding help-seeking sources. The research employed structural equation modelling to analyze the relationships between IPV victimization, acceptance, and supporting behaviours with perceived reportability and help-seeking choices. Findings indicated that women's perception of reportability significantly influenced their choice to seek help from the police. Higher levels of victimization correlate with lower perceived reportability. This suggests that as women endure more IPV, they may normalize the abusive behaviours, leading to a diminished recognition of these behaviours as reportable incidents. Therefore, the women who accept or support IPV are less likely to perceive such situations as reportable. This underscores the need for educational interventions aimed at changing societal attitudes toward IPV, helping individuals recognize abusive behaviours as unacceptable. The study also found that women may favor informal sources of help (family and friends) over formal ones (psychologists, public services) and the police when they do not perceive their experiences as serious enough. Hence, improving the understanding of when and how to report IPV is crucial. Overall, the study highlights the importance of addressing psychological, social, and legal aspects that influence the reporting of IPV, emphasizing the need for targeted educational and support programs. This is particularly important due to the strong and deeply concerning link between stalking and intimate partner violence. Stalking

frequently occurs alongside IPV and can signal the presence or risk of other forms of abuse. It is also commonly used as a tactic of power and control during and after an abusive relationship (SPARC, 2018).

In addition to the lack of stalking research on different age demographics, there have been many studies that argue that stalking is a gender-based crime, affecting female victims considerably more than male victims (Tjaden and Theonnes, 1998; Proctor, 2018). According to the ONS (2024), one in five women and approx., 1 in 11 men aged 16 years and over has been a victim of stalking. However, despite the statistical research that supports stalking affecting predominantly females, there is little consensus that stalking itself is a gender based crime (Proctor, 2018). For example, Tjaden and Theonnes (1998) and Purcell et al (2001) had asserted that stalking is a gender-neutral phenomenon, emphasizing that a significant number of men experience stalking and the effects on male victimization can be equally as severe as those found for female victims. Research also indicates that the consequences of stalking can be fatal, particularly for women. For example, Sheed et al (2024) conducted a study in Australia to understand stalking precipitated homicide as a recognized but understudied phenomenon. This study analyzed 855 homicide deaths in Victoria, Australia, from 1997 to 2015, focusing on how often stalking played a role. Findings showed stalking was involved in about 6.4% of all homicides and was particularly prevalent in cases involving ex-partners (63%). The majority of victims were female, with the majority of offenders male. These homicides often involved planning, triggering events, and last-resort decisions. Additionally, evidence of coercive control was more common in ex-partner stalking homicides than in other cases.

Furthermore, research conducted by Logan & Walker (2019) using survey data from 2719 participants in America revealed that women are more concerned about personal safety and feel more vulnerable to crimes than men, highlighting a gender fear gap. Factors that were highlighted like environmental risks and prior victimization influenced these concerns. Logan & Walker used a five-item stalking measure to explore how stalking affects fear of personal safety, perceived vulnerability, and post-traumatic stress. Results revealed that 30% of women and 12% of men experienced stalking under a high-fear standard, which is twice the national average. Stalking related fear was linked to increased safety concerns, perceived risk, discomfort, and PTSD symptoms in both genders. Even after accounting for stalking, gender differences persisted in some female victim outcomes, supporting the existence of a gender fear gap.

In an Executive Summary conducted by the Surrey Council (2025) for the Surrey Violence Against Women and girls needs Assessment 2024-2025, victims of stalking often felt ashamed or embarrassed about their experiences, making them hesitant to contact the police or seek help from

others. They were found to fear being judged or blamed, especially if the perpetrator is someone they knew or if the stalking occurred online. Some victims lacked confidence in the effectiveness of police or support services, particularly if they have had negative encounters with the criminal justice system in the past. Others might not have seen their situation as serious enough to report, especially when it involves online harassment or ongoing unwanted contact. As a result of these factors, many victims of stalking and other forms of violence against women and girls (VAWG) choose not to report their experiences to authorities.

To better understand male victimization in relation to the experiences of stalking in Portugal, Goncalves et al (2021) addressed the common perception of stalking as a gendered crime, primarily affecting women while emphasizing that men can also be victims, a similar suggestion as the previously mentioned studies. Goncalves and colleagues suggested that males compared to females' experiences may differ significantly due to various factors such as gender stereotypes. The Goncalves study involved 76 men who self-identified as victims of stalking, with a mean age of approximately 41 years. The Stalking Victimization Inventory (SVI) was used to assess various dimensions of victimization, including the stalking behaviours experienced, the impact of the behaviours, and victim help-seeking actions. The findings revealed that the prevalence of the male victimization was reported at approximately 13%, a figure consistent with other previous studies such as Spitzberg and Cupach (2007).

Goncalves et al (2021) reported that the stalking behaviours were diverse, with attempts at unwanted contact and unwanted appearances in frequented places being the most common stalking behaviour experienced by the victims. Participants reported significant negative impacts in various areas, notably intimate relationships and mental health. However, almost half of the male victims reported not feeling fear regarding the stalking experiences. Interestingly, only 25% of victims sought help, with informal support from family and friends being the most common source. The study found that help-seeking behaviour was more likely among those males who experienced a higher diversity of stalking behaviours and a greater perceived negative impact. The authors discussed the implications of their findings and emphasized the need for greater awareness and support for male victims of stalking. They highlighted how traditional gender roles may inhibit men from recognizing their victimization and seeking help, which may explain the lack of fear experienced. The study called for initiatives that validate male experiences and promote accessible support services. Goncalves and colleagues acknowledged the limitations of the study, such as the small sample size and the contextual focus on Portugal, suggesting that further research could explore these dynamics in different cultural and/or legal contexts. It also recommended examining additional barriers and facilitators that may affect help-seeking behaviours among male victims of

stalking. The research addressed a significant gap in the literature about male victims of stalking. Its findings underscored the necessity for gender-inclusive approaches to victim support and the importance of dismantling harmful stereotypes that minimize the experiences of male victims.

A study exploring how harmful perceptions such as gender ideologies, specifically benevolent and hostile sexism, shape public perceptions of stalking beyond the traditional stereotype of the male stalker and female victim was conducted in Italy by Miglietta et al (2021). The authors posited for the 226 participants aged 18+, societal views largely framed stalking as a male-on-female crime, possibly neglecting other types of stalking dynamics, such as female offenders and male victims or same-sex stalking. Findings of this study revealed that the participants rated the male-to-female stalking pair as the most likely, while the same-sex pairs were perceived as less common. However, the study also found that benevolent sexism towards both genders was associated with a higher likelihood of recognizing same-sex stalking pairs. Hostile sexism towards women appeared to limit the recognition of male stalking pairs. The authors suggested that current understandings of stalking are shaped by societal norms that frame the crime within the paradox of primarily male-to-female as a consequence of heterosexual relationships. The researchers advocated for prevention campaigns to broaden awareness of stalking occurrences involving varied gender dynamics. Although, the study's findings may not be generalizable due to its reliance on a convenience sample from a specific demographic in Italy, the study contributes valuable insights into the relationship between gender ideologies and perceptions of stalking. It suggested a need for broader public education on stalking to include various offender/victim relationships, which could foster better support and intervention for all victims, not just those fitting conventional stereotypes.

The existing research has explored has reported mixed findings between genders on the perceptions and the realities of stalking. Scott et al (2019) suggested these contradictory findings are mainly due to victim, public and law-enforcements' inaccurate misconceptions and understandings of the crime of stalking. Scott and colleagues suggested that research is needed to highlight the seriousness of these misconceptions, including the impact that such misconceptions may have for victims. Prior research on stalking perceptions, including Taber-Smith (2017), shows that victims often report greater fear of stranger stalkers than of ex-partners, reflecting common societal misconceptions. This is notable because the most frequently reported stalker typology is the ex-partner/rejected category. Taber-Smith argues that these misconceptions shape how victims interpret their experiences and influence their help-seeking decisions.

Typology and Stalker Motivations

In order to understand and overcome some of the societal misconceptions highlighted previously, it is important to understand the types of stalkers and their motivations to stalk. There are many theories about criminal behaviour that focus on such perpetrator motivations, reasoning why they conduct crime, such as The Theory of self-control (Gottfredson and Hirsch, 1990) which provided an explanation as to why a perpetrator engages in criminal activity. The development of theories of crime and victimization in relation to self-control began with a general theory of crime which stated:

'People who lack self-control will tend to be impulsive, insensitive, physical (as opposed to mental), risk-taking, short-sighted, and nonverbal, and they will tend therefore to engage in criminal and analogous acts' (Gottfredson & Hirsch, 1990. p. 90).

The Control Balance Theory was then developed from the general theory of crime by Tittle (1995) and was created with a focus on the perpetration of crime. This theory concerned itself with the relationship between perceived controls exerted over another by a perpetrator, compared to the control a victim believes to be subjected to.

Given that a number of stalking behaviours and motivations appear to include an element of control, several scholars have been able to apply or modify elements of this theoretical framework to the field of stalking victimization research (Monkton-Smith et al, 2017; McEwan et al, 2018). The Control Balance Theory posits the control dynamic as a ratio on a spectrum ranging from complete control by others (control deficit) to control balance (control exerted and subjected are equal) to complete control over others (control surplus), (Tittle, 1995). Tittle revised the theory in 2004 stating that people with a control deficit or surplus are more likely to engage in crime or deviance in order to obtain, maintain, or escalate their control over others. The issues of maintaining, escalating and obtaining control can be seen within the stalker typologies and motivations which was originally set out by Mullen et al (1999).

However, in the early 2000's research focused on ex-partner stalking with a view to understand why stalkers stalk, such as Cupach and Spitzberg (2007) who proposed that the Relational Goal Pursuit Theory has been utilized to explain the development of stalking behaviours, whereby:

'Obsessive pursuers come to believe that their happiness and self-worth are predicated on successful attainment of the particular relationship that is sought. Consequently, the relational goal takes on exaggerated importance and it is pursued in a vigorous and persistent manner, even in the face of obstacles and resistance.' (Cupach and Spitzberg, 2007, pg. 79)

In contrast to the Relational Goal Pursuit Theory, not all stalkers have a relationship as the end goal for the motivator to stalk a victim, this was highlighted by one of the first clinical studies conducted to understand the stalker psychopathology, behaviours and motivations which was conducted in 1999 by Mullen, Pathé, Purcell, and Stuart. Five types of stalkers were identified, not all driven by relational goals:

1. Rejected stalkers are usually from close relationships (ex-partners, friends, family, or therapists) motivated by a desire for reconciliation or revenge. They can often be persuaded to stop through criminal justice actions, except those driven by intense jealousy.
2. The Intimacy Seekers believe they are in love with their target, often with erotomanic delusions. They become enraged by perceived indifference and are largely unaffected by legal sanctions, viewing them as part of the pursuit of true love.
3. Incompetent Suitors recognize their affection is unreciprocated but continue to hope for intimacy. They tend to be socially and intellectually limited, feeling entitled to their target and easily abandoning current pursuits but at risk of reoffending.
4. Resentful stalkers aim to intimidate or distress their victims, sometimes targeting at random out of grievance or perceived injustice. Legal actions can escalate their sense of grievance and desire for control.
5. Predatory stalkers plan sexual assaults, deriving pleasure from power and control. Often with deviant sexual tendencies and prior convictions, they may stalk for extended periods before attacking, requiring criminal or psychiatric intervention (Mullen et al, 1999).

However, it must be highlighted that the majority of stalkers in the Mullen et al study were unemployed men who had never had any meaningful long-term intimate relationship. Yet despite this limited cohort. More recent literature was conducted by McEwan et al (2018) who set out to investigate the validity and reliability of stalking typologies in respect to Stalker Risk Profiling using a file review of 241 of mainly Australian stalkers. McEwan and colleagues found the typologies set out by Mullen and colleagues to be a valid and reliable tool for understanding stalker motivations and risk to victims.

The typologies framework that Mullen and Colleagues suggested lends some support for the Tittle (1995) Control Balance Theory in relation to the perpetration of stalking, and is supported by research assessing the Control Balance Theory in relation to stalking. This research was conducted using online survey data from 2766 college students in America, conducted by Fox & Noble (2014) who argued that stalking is an interpersonal crime of power and control. The researchers linked stalking perpetration to maladaptive or dysfunctional adult attachment, socialization, or other mechanisms such as poor emotional control, deviance and paraphilia.

The first study of Tittle's (1995) Control Balance Theory attempting to explain victimization rather than perpetration, was offered by Piquero and Hickman (2003). Using a self-reporting survey from 253 American University students, Piquero and Hickman considered two core theoretical predictions: (a) that those with control deficits are targeted for crime because they are vulnerable. Suggesting those with a control deficit lack knowledge, skills, confidence, and/or the self-protective capacity necessary to avoid victimization. (b) Those with a control surplus are more likely to engage in reckless behaviour due to feelings of superiority and invincibility, which can lead to an increased risk of victimization. Among a sample of college students Piquero and Hickman determined that control deficits and surpluses were associated with a general measure of victimization. However, Fox, Nobles and Fisher (2014) framed stalking victimization in a different way to Piquero and Hickman, stating:

'Control balance theory might also explain stalking victimization. On one hand, someone who conveys weakness, submissiveness, and vulnerability (i.e. control deficit) may inadvertently appear to be an attractive target to a stalking perpetrator. On the other hand, someone who exhibits an aura of control and superiority (i.e. control surplus) may inadvertently challenge or embolden a stalking perpetrator to target them in an effort to gain even more control.' (Fox, Nobles, and Fisher, 2014, p.326)

It could also be argued that those with a control surplus, may be more active in disclosing their victimization, as well as to take action in order to mitigate the stalking behaviours. This is relevant to the current research, as help-seeking decisions and how they relate to the stalking outcome is the general focus.

Investigating the perceptions and reactions of victims of stalking, and utilizing 1247 data sets from the American NCVS SVS, 2016, Randa et al (2022) aimed to understand how victims perceived the motivations to stalk regarding their stalkers, and how this perception affected the level of harm they felt. Including how it influenced their responses, and whether they reported the stalking to law enforcement and what protective actions they took. Randa and colleagues found that higher levels of perceived motives associated with power and control correlated with increased perceived harm. Victims who identified relational motivations or the stalker's arrogance perceived less harm. The study also found that the frequency, duration, and invasiveness of stalking behaviours significantly influenced the perceived harm. Increased harm was positively correlated with the likelihood of engaging in protective behaviours such as help-seeking. Despite the study utilizing data from mainly white female victims, it adds to the existing literature by integrating the examination of a victims perceptions of offender motives with victim reactions.

Nonetheless, there are few theories that address victimization through the lens of responses to stalking victimization. Most theories of victimization focus on why a person is a victim rather than

how they cope, and make decisions to mitigate the experience. The journey a victim of stalking undertakes when navigating the repeated, unwanted contact attempts and behaviours needs consideration to fully comprehend help-seeking decisions, regardless of the typology and motivations of the stalker. This journey must begin, albeit possibly pointing out the obvious, but with a victim first realizing they are being stalked.

Stalking acknowledgement

Stalking acknowledgment is the realization that what a victim is experiencing is the crime of stalking (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011). Research has reported that victims who experienced classic stalking, such as by a stranger, with heightened fear, and multiple behaviours were more likely to acknowledge the stalking and then go on to report the episode to the police (Jordan et al, 2007). This is an important area to understand as previous research has also suggested that victims are more likely to be stalked by someone known to them, rather than by a stranger (Tjaden and Thoennes, 1998) underscoring the implications of victims perceptions of stalking acknowledgment and help-seeking.

To understand public perceptions of stalking such as classic offline stalking, Scott et al (2019) conducted 8 online research panels, split between 477 UK university students and explored the influence of ex-intimate typologies in Australia, the U.S. and the U.K. The scenarios used in this study were manipulated as ex-intimate, acquaintance and stranger. This study found support for the suggestion made by Jordan et al (2007), that participants were more likely to acknowledge the stalking conducted by the stranger and acquaintance typologies, rather than with an ex-partner typology as suggested in earlier research by Tjaden and Thoennes (1998). Social biases and normalization of stalking behaviours are a key concern, particularly for stalking victimization as an intentional and repetitive crime, and this topic is a key focus of the current research. Specifically, what factors may or may not influence decision making for a victim, but also in what factors may influence the stalking outcome.

Previous literature on stalking has suggested that women compared to men report a greater fear of strangers, of being outside, and particularly at night, and most violence and stalking episodes are commonly perpetrated by an ex-intimate partner (Tjaden and Thoennes, 1998; Proctor, 2019). The Social Learning Theory originally created by Albert Bandura in 1977 addressed the factors of these types of cognitive biases in relation to stalking victimization. A cognitive bias is considered as:

'A bias (or distortion) to a cognitive process or mental representation.' (Pete. C. Trimmer, 2016 pg. 1)

Mental representation is considered as the categorization of information essential to cognitive processes that enable complex organisms to interpret the overwhelming array of information in their surroundings. These processes are vital for activities such as identifying experiences, objects, making decisions, and forming memories (Roads & Love, 2024). Mental representations or cognitive biases can affect many victims of interpersonal crime and violence. They may not label their experience as victimization until their experience meets specific criteria that underpin their mental representation or cognitive bias, which is often a stereotypical representation of the crime, (Fisher et al, 2003). For example; being followed, watched or spied upon is considered as stereotypical of stalking behaviours according to Fisher and colleagues and this is supportive of the Bandura (1977) Social Learning Theory.

Key theoretical concepts of the social learning theory would suggest that criminal behaviour is more likely to occur if an individual associates with criminal peers, has the same values as their peers and considers the benefits of crime to outweigh the consequences. Despite conceptual overlaps between social learning and victimization, very few studies have extended the social learning theory to understand stalking victimization. Specifically, someone who considers stalking to be ordinary, common, and acceptable behaviour could be more likely to become a stalking victim (Fox et al, 2011).

“Victims can also learn to adopt beliefs, behaviours, and perceptions that may put them at risk of victimization.” (Fox, Nobles, and Akers, 2011, p. 42)

Fox, Nobles, and Akers (2011) used survey data from 2766 American college students and found support in their study for social learning theory as several of the theoretical variables emerged as significant predictors of stalking victimization. Specifically, definitions that normalized or minimized the stalking significantly increased the risk of being stalked. However, there is a deficit in this research exploring how the Social Learning Theory applies to stalking acknowledgment by victims themselves. This can be considered a deficit in the research, because if as suggested the behaviours, beliefs and perceptions potentially influence the likelihood of victimization, as suggested by Fox and colleagues, then it may be possible that this suggestion applies to the acknowledgment of stalking, which is the realization that the repeated unwanted contact attempts and behaviours are actually those of the crime of stalking. Specifically, if the unwanted behaviours are rationalized as normal, or minimized, and not identified as a crime by the victim, it stands to reason that the victimization will therefore continue, putting the victim at risk of further victimization, rather than influencing the risk of being a victim as Fox and colleagues had suggested.

To understand victim acknowledgement, help-seeking behaviours and stalking victimization, Reyns and Englebrecht (2011) conducted research to identify the correlates of stalking acknowledgement. The authors hypothesized that the psychological reaction, seriousness of the stalking behaviour, pursuit behaviours and the relationship between victim and offender will affect a victim acknowledging what they are experiencing as stalking. Furthermore, a victim's acknowledgement would be positively related to help-seeking behaviours and they examined these processes separately for male and female victims. Using the NCVS-SVS, 2006 data of 1265 women and 286 men, of which, 40% of the men and 39% of the women who responded did acknowledge their experience as stalking, (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011).

The results of the Reyns and Englebrecht (2011) investigation revealed four significant predictors for stalking acknowledgement for the male victims; (1) physical attack increased acknowledgement by more than five times. (2) Cyberstalking combined with offline behaviours increased acknowledgement by two and a half times. (3) Stalker appearing at places often frequented by the victim increased acknowledgement by three and a half times. (4) Being spied on increased acknowledgement by more than seven times. The results also suggested that the psychological reactions the male victims experienced had no relationship with stalking acknowledgement, and neither did the help-seeking variable (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011). However, these findings were a contrast to the female data. The female victims suggested (1) seriousness of the crime, specifically illegal entry of the victims home or car increased the acknowledgement likelihood by two and a half times; (2) multiple pursuit behaviours and (3) cyberstalking increased the likelihood by two times. The psychological reactions that were statistically associated with female acknowledgement in the study were; (1) anxiety by one and a half times; (2) fear increased likelihood by almost three times; (3) asking others for help showed a significant result by nearly two times for stalking acknowledgement (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011). The differences in the correlates to stalking acknowledgement for male victims compared to female victims highlight the need for further research to investigate this topic more in-depth to understand why these differences are occurring.

As previously mentioned, research has suggested that stalking acknowledgement must occur before a victim will employ help-seeking decisions. Ngo (2014) used the same data from the NCVS-SVS, 2006, 1265 women and 286 men and four general models of sexual harassment acknowledgement were used to propose a stalking acknowledgement model. (1) Type of experience model, (2) personal characteristics model, (3) victim-perpetrator relationship model, and (4) affect model. The results of this study indicated that stalking acknowledgement is significantly correlated and indicative of the type of stalking behaviours experienced (Ngo, 2014). Whereas, the affect model, which looked at emotional reactions such as fear, anxiety/concern, feeling frightened and

physically ill symptoms had the most significant predictors to stalking acknowledgement. However, the victim-perpetrator model revealed the relationship between the victim and perpetrator did not receive statistically significant results. This suggests that the victim-perpetrator relationship has no bearing on whether a victim acknowledged their ordeal as stalking (Ngo, 2014). These results are contradicting to previous suggestions that typology plays a part in acknowledgment (Tjaden and Theonnes, 1998; Taber-Smith, 2017), but supports the suggestion that stalking behaviours and the emotions they elucidate for the victim do play a role in stalking acknowledgment.

Research has also shown that early intervention is necessary to mitigate the negative consequences of stalking, and for the facilitation of early intervention to occur there must be an acknowledgement of the stalking (Reyns and Englebrecth; Ngo 2014). This is because, if a victim does not realize what they are experiencing is stalking, then seeking help for the victimization will not be a consideration. Taylor-Dunn et al (2018) suggested one way for police to mitigate long-lasting episodes of stalking is for the investigating officers to shift their investigative focus from the perpetrators' behaviours to the psychological consequence on the victims, which may result in faster police acknowledgment of the stalking. A shift of focus such as this may then prompt an early intervention.

Research investigating these factors are of great benefit to the study of stalking by shedding light on the understandings and the underpinnings of stalking acknowledgement. The understanding of stalking acknowledgement will inform support agencies, national ad campaigns and stakeholders in order to address this greatly under disclosed crime and aid victims through education on 'what stalking is' so that support can be accessed early on. This topic as a research focus is important to all stakeholders as an unacknowledged stalking experience can lead to long-term psychological harm, and recognition of the experience early on can help to mitigate these potential consequences. This is because if a stalking experience lasts for more than two weeks it can have a detrimental effect on the victim, such that it can create anxiety and mental health problems (Nicastro et al, 2000).

Prevalence of stalking and the psychological consequences for victims

The Scottish Crime and Justice Survey estimates that in 2019/2020; 1 in 8 adults experienced stalking or harassment (Scottish Government, 2021). The prevalence of the crime of stalking has not reduced over the past few decades with 11% of Americans in the early 2000's reporting experiencing stalking (Baum et al, 2009) and approximately 11.8% of adults in Scotland experiencing stalking and harassment annually (COPFS, 2021). According to Crime Outcomes in England and Wales (2022), only about 5% of all recorded stalking offences led to an arrest in 2021–2022. In Scotland, the adult

(16+) population was estimated at 4.6 million in 2021 (ScotPHO), yet only 1,045 stalking charges were brought that year, despite stalking being present in 57% of cases with a domestic abuse identifier and a total of 33,425 charges reported to COPFS (Scottish Crime and Justice Survey, 2021). In 2023–2024, COPFS received 859 stalking charges, 53% of which carried a domestic abuse identifier, a 7% decrease from 2022–2023 (921 charges).

The figures above leave a serious deficit between the cases of stalking identified and those that were put forward to the Crown Office in England & Wales and in Scotland. The disparity between the cases reported and the estimated victimization within the Scottish adult population, may be partly due to the introduction of the Domestic Abuse Scotland Act (2018) (DASA), which came into force in 2019. As a result of the introduction of the DASA, a number of acts previously attributed to the crime of stalking are now convicted under the Section 1 domestic abuse offence, rather than as a Section 39 stalking offence, and therefore is difficult to quantify as they are no longer reported separately. However, the figures are supportive of the suggestion by Nicastro (2020) that stalking is a serious social concern.

Early research conducted comparing stalking prevalence to harassment prevalence from Baum et al (2009) found that during the previous 12-month period from the survey, approximately 3.4 million people in the USA aged 18 and over had experienced stalking. The data also detailed that 46% of stalking victims experiencing unwanted behaviours at least once a week and 1 in 10 of these victims reported being stalked for over 5 years. This is important, as Ngo (2014) proposed that only half of stalking episodes are reported to police, despite the psychological, social, financial, severe physical and lethal risk factors which are known consequences that stalking has on victims and highlights the importance of understanding the prevalence of stalking in relation to the barriers victims experience to reporting.

Research that pertains to stalking within the context of intimate partner violence (IPV) was conducted by Kim et al (2024) using the data from 8587 respondents to the 2010 National Intimate Partner and Sexual Violence Survey (NISVS) in American and provides several important insights. Stalking is identified as a distinct form of IPV in the research. It constitutes behaviours meant to intimidate or control a partner, which can include actions such as making unwanted phone calls, following, or surveilling the victim from a distance. The study specifically analyzed stalking as one of eight categories of IPV perpetrated by intimate partners. The research indicated that stalking is a notable form of IPV, and included a group of perpetrators who predominantly engaged in stalking behaviours, suggesting that stalking behaviours are prevalent enough to warrant separate classification. According to the results, the stalking group was the smallest among the six identified

classes, comprising 6.6% of all perpetrators. In relation to the other forms of IPV, stalking was highlighted for its unique characteristics. Specifically, victims who experienced stalking sought help from more sources than those who experienced physical abuse. This suggests that stalking may elicit different responses and coping mechanisms from victims, potentially due to the nature of the psychological threat it poses.

The Kim et al (2024) study also indicated that men are more likely to perpetrate stalking than women, with data suggesting that a moderately higher percentage of male perpetrators (7.2%) engaged in stalking compared to female perpetrators (5.8%). This highlights a crucial trend in understanding the gendered dynamics of IPV. The results of this study also found that stalking is associated with notable negative health outcomes for victims with higher instances of needing help due to the mental and physical health consequences linked with these experiences. The study found that 51.5% of those who experienced multiple forms of violence reported negative physical health outcomes, indicating that those who experience stalking may be at an even greater risk depending on the context of their overall IPV experience. The findings from the study stress the importance of recognizing stalking as a significant component of IPV patterns and highlighted the need for specialized interventions aimed at addressing the unique risks and challenges faced by stalking victims which could ultimately lead to improved support, safety, and recovery pathways for those affected.

Mechanic et al (2000) addressed a crucial yet often overlooked aspect of intimate partner violence (IPV), which is the intersection of stalking and physical violence. Using 65 participant interview data sets from acutely battered women in America to compare those who were relentlessly stalked, to women who were battered but experienced infrequent stalking. The researchers sought to shed light on the psychological and physical consequences of extreme stalking behaviours in the context of IPV. The findings of the research indicated that relentlessly stalked women reported significantly higher instances of physical violence, sexual assault, and emotional abuse compared to those who were infrequently stalked. Additionally, post-separation violence and stalking rates were higher among the relentless stalkers. The women in the relentlessly stalked group also exhibited greater levels of psychological distress, including higher rates of depression and Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD). The study noted that rates of PTSD ranged from 31% to 84% among battered women, with the victims of relentless stalkers experiencing more severe symptoms. The relentlessly stalked women were also more likely to engage in various strategic responses to the abuse, such as seeking medical care or obtaining protective orders. The women who were relentlessly stalked also reported a greater number of attempts to leave the abusive relationship compared to their infrequently stalked counterparts. The study addressed an important public

health issue, as stalking among physically battered women has received insufficient attention in existing literature. By linking the severe experience of stalking with various forms of intimate partner violence, the researchers highlighted the complexities that emerge in abusive dynamics. Overall, the study underscored the intricate link between stalking and intimate partner violence, stressing the need for targeted interventions that address the unique challenges faced by relentlessly stalked battered women.

Research has also highlighted the adverse psychological consequences of stalking on those with lived experience of this crime. For example, Baum and colleagues (2009) reported that fear was the most common impact disclosed. Indeed, 29% of victims feared that the stalker would never cease their behaviour, while 30.4% feared physical harm. It was also found that 1 in 10 feared they might be fatally harmed by their stalker. Baum and colleagues also reported that unwanted stalking contacts and behaviours resulted in the victims having to change their daily routines, take time off work to mitigate the behaviours and avoided family and friends. Additionally, 47% of participants reported that the stalking behaviours created feelings of anxiety and concern; 23% felt helpless; over 15% experienced depression and 1.4% felt suicidal because of the stalking. However, as previously mentioned, there are other considerations regarding the level of fear and concern a victim is subjected to as a result of stalking victimization, which is the violent consequences that can occur.

Investigating the prevalence of violent consequences for victims in stalking cases, Monkton-Smith et al (2017) reviewed 358 criminal homicide cases, focusing on the relationship between homicides and stalking in the United Kingdom in the years 2012- 2014 of female victims. Monkton-Smith and colleagues proposed that most of the homicides did not appear to be spontaneous, but rather an emotional journey. This journey appeared to have strong correlations between homicide and stalking behaviours such as; fixation, obsession, surveillance, and control. The results of the study showed that in 94% of the homicide cases, stalking behaviours were present prior to the murders. The stalking behaviours common to these cases were control at 92%, 88% on fixation and 94% on obsession, surveillance was 63%, and escalations were prevalent in 79% of the cases. The control element found in the Monkton-Smith study suggests support for the Control Balance theory as suggested by Tittle (1995) and theoretically applicable to stalking victimization and its relation with the perpetrator's control over the target having fatal consequences.

To further the understanding of interpersonal violence (IPV) which explores the intersection of technology and cyberstalking within the context of domestic violence and homicide; Todd et al (2021) highlighted the increasing role that technology, particularly social media plays in facilitating stalking behaviours that can escalate to more severe forms of violence, including homicide. A

thematic analysis was performed on 41 Domestic homicide reviews and three interviews with victims and/or family members in the UK to identify key indicators of cyberstalking behaviours related to domestic homicide using Domestic Homicide Review (DHR) documents. Whereby 58.5% of cases demonstrated some evidence of cyberstalking or digital behaviours associated with either the perpetrator or the victim. The study identified indicators of cyberstalking, including controlling behaviours, jealousy, and attempts to monitor the victim's online activity. The psychological impacts of the stalking, such as anxiety, depression, and PTSD, were highlighted as significant consequences for the victims. Many victims did not report their experiences to police due to feelings of embarrassment, fear of not being taken seriously, or believing that their experiences were private matters. The study suggested incorporating questions about cyberstalking and digital monitoring in risk assessments to improve early intervention and prevention efforts. The research underscores the critical need for a nuanced understanding of the role of technology in domestic violence and homicide. By recognizing the behaviours and patterns associated with cyberstalking, law enforcement and support agencies can better protect victims and develop effective prevention strategies. The findings also advocate for a broader attention to the integration of technology in domestic violence cases as part of a comprehensive response strategy.

Since the implementation of stalking laws in the late 90's and early 2000's, technological advances have facilitated cyberstalking, and the psychological consequences are found to mirror that of classic/traditional stalking (Todd et al, 2021). The prevalence of Cyberstalking, which is the persistent pursuit of an individual using electronic means, must also be of consideration along with traditional stalking' as many stalking cases can contain online surveillance and offline approaching and non-approaching behaviours. In a qualitative study that supports this theory, Worsley et al (2017) conducted thematic analysis of 100 narratives from an online survey in the UK of self-reported victims, exploring the implications of cyberstalking on mental health and well-being and the coping strategies of the victims. The results proposed that comorbid anxiety and depression were the predominant psychological consequences for the victims and some of the victims had to move home and make changes to their work or life patterns, findings similar to the Todd et al (2021) findings. However, Worsley et al's (2017) study found that avoidant coping, ignoring perpetrators, confrontation, support, help-seeking and cognitive reframing were the most prevalent victim coping responses. Importantly, Worsley and colleagues also acknowledged that the underrepresented perspectives of victims within current literature could provide valuable insights into the coping strategies and disclosure responses victims receive.

Research was also conducted that explored the increasingly relevant issue of cyberstalking, particularly among female victims of acquaintance stalking rather than the frequently researched

relational type stalking, by Logan (2023), using a sample of 338 women in America. Logan proposed there has been a rising interest in understanding online stalking as it has become more common due to increased technology use in daily life. The findings revealed that women who were monitored online reported higher levels of threats, life interference, sexual harassment, jealousy, and control by the stalker, compared to those who were harassed online but not monitored. All participants experienced significant victim harms, but those subjected to online monitoring faced the most severe negative outcomes. These negative outcomes included emotional distress, job interference, and resource loss. Women who were monitored were also more likely to reach out for help. However, a general trend across all participants was a reluctance to seek formal help due to fears of not being believed or escalating the situation. Logan concluded, similar to Todd and colleagues, that there is a need for greater awareness and understanding of the complexities of cyberstalking and its severe impacts on victims. There is a highlighted necessity for law enforcement and the criminal justice system to take online stalking seriously and to improve their responses to stalking cases. Overall, Logan's study provides valuable insights into the experiences of female acquaintance stalking victims, suggesting that both online harassment and monitoring strategies should be taken seriously in addressing the harms experienced by victims.

An exploration of common perceptions of cyberstalking research supports the Social Learning Theory in that victims of cyberstalking suffer similarly to victims of offline traditional stalking (Becker et al, 2020). Becker and colleagues explored men cyberstalking women, and whether stalking typology, gender and/or observers' attitudes played a role in the perceptions of stalking for the layperson. Drawing on data from an original vignette survey of 727 participants in America, the results of this study found that women were more likely to view cyberstalking as less acceptable than the male counterparts and participants were more likely to label the stranger typology (such as the Predatory stalker) as stalking compared to the other typologies. Further supporting the Social Learning Theory in the proposition by Becker and colleagues that stalking behaviours are accepted and romanticized, and cultural beliefs and social perceptions of normative behaviours can perpetuate the stalking behaviour. Importantly, if victims do not recognize the stalking episode, or they deem ex-intimate stalking as less severe than stranger stalking, this can result in dangerous consequences as exemplified by the study of femicides and homicides conducted by Monkton-Smith et al (2017) and Todd et al (2021).

Modern societies have perceptions that have created a culture that romanticize and normalize stalking behaviour according to the previously mentioned research, despite the psychological consequences for the victims. It can be concluded from studies such as those discussed above, that stalking behaviours whether 'traditional/Classic' or 'cyberstalking' are key indicators of serious

potential harm, and therefore early identification and intervention in all stalking cases are crucial to prevent psychological damage, serious harm or even death.

Perceptions and help-seeking

Previous literature (Baum et al, 2009; Buhi et al, 2009; Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010) have suggested that stalking is an under-disclosed crime, and that investigations into the reasons why this is the case should begin with understanding victim and social perceptions and the help-seeking decisions that include both formal (police) and informal (friends/family) disclosures. The importance of this focus is exemplified in the considerable prevalence and potentially enormous psychological consequences that the crime of stalking imposes on its victims. A seminal review of the stalking literature was conducted by Logan & Walker (2009), concluding that the psychological consequences of stalking can in itself pose a barrier to seeking support, as the victim can experience shame, anxiety and depression. Important to this focus, Logan and Walker also proposed that the experience of stigma and shame when divulging the stalking episode to family and friends can potentially negatively influence further help-seeking decisions.

In relation to exploring why the crime of stalking is so under disclosed by victims, Buhi et al (2009) completed a study of stalking victimization and help-seeking behaviours among 391 female college students in the United States. This study found that nearly 50% of the women surveyed did not seek help from either formal or informal sources to mitigate their stalking victimization. The reasons given for the non-disclosures were as follows: 1. they did not feel the situation was serious enough to disclosure, 2. They wanted to handle the situation on their own, 3. They felt that it was a private/personal matter, 4. They did not disclose to police as they felt fearful of revenge, 5. They felt that the police would not believe them. However, this study was conducted on a convenience cohort of female college students, and therefore it is difficult to generalize these findings and victim perceptions to other cohorts, such as male victims. This study does however highlight the importance of perceptions as factors in the help-seeking decisions stalking victims make.

In a study which provided a structured lens to analyze victim decision-making conducted by Menard and Cox (2016) who reported findings to establish a stalking context to the theoretical framework of the 1992 Greenberg and Ruback's social influence model. This model emphasized the complexity of the decision to report crimes, taking into account individual and contextual factors, which is crucial for understanding stalking victimization. The study relied on data from the American 2006 NCVS-SVS, a robust and extensive dataset of 3997 participants, which enhanced the credibility

of the findings and allowed for a significant sample size, which strengthened the statistical analyses, similar to previously mentioned research (Buhi et al, 2009; Reyns and Englebrect, 2010).

Menard and Cox (2016) identified significant predictors of victimization and reporting behaviours, such as severity of stalking incidents, victim sex, and victim-offender relationship. However, there were inconsistent results found on key variables, particularly concerning victim-offender relationships and their impact on reporting. The relationship between victim and offender influenced reporting behaviours. Specifically, victims were more inclined to label their experiences as stalking when the offender was an ex-intimate. However, the dynamics differed for third-party reporting; rural third parties were more willing to contact police for non-intimate stalking cases than urban counterparts. The study provided partial support for Greenberg and Ruback's (1992) model. While severity of the stalking behaviours and gender consistently influenced decision-making, the impact of victim-offender relationship and location produced mixed results. However, this study formed a basis for understanding stalking victimization within the broader context of help-seeking behaviours and criminal justice involvement.

Cho et al (2023) conducted a study which utilized latent class analysis (LCA) to identify distinct subgroups of stalking victims based on their help-seeking behaviours, using data from the American 2016 National Crime Victimization Survey's Supplemental Victimization Survey. The analysis involved 1,459 stalking victims who were assessed on various help-seeking strategies, including reporting to the police, seeking informal help, and taking self-protective measures. The study aimed to investigate the influence of variables such as sex, victim-offender relationship, offense severity, and negative emotions on class membership. A multinomial logistic regression was conducted to explore the relationship between these factors and the classified victim subgroups. The findings revealed three distinct groups of stalking victims: 1. Passive Help-seekers (49.5%): This group reported minimal efforts in seeking help. 2. Informal Help-seekers (32.2%): Victims in this group relied primarily on friends and family for support. 3. Active Help-seekers (18.3%): This group actively sought assistance, including reporting to the police and obtaining legal protection. The findings also indicated that Female victims were more likely to be in the active or informal help-seeking groups compared to males. Victims experiencing more severe stalking behaviours and those whose stalkers had a criminal record were more likely to seek help actively. Negative emotions partially mediated the relationship between victims' perceptions of severity and their help-seeking behaviours. Victim-offender relationship dynamics significantly influenced the type of help-seeking behaviour, with those stalked by intimate partners being less likely to report to the police. Overall, the study highlights the complexity of help-seeking behaviours among stalking victims and the impact of various personal and contextual factors on their decisions.

The theory of Rational Choice perspective is also relevant to the current literature as an exploration of key indicators of harm, persistence and social perceptions found in both traditional stalking and cyberstalking. This is particularly the case when examining the factors that influence a victims' decision whether or not to disclose their experience, and what actions or factors if any influence the stalking outcome. The theory of Rational Choice Perspective in the context of criminal justice was explored by M. R. Gottfredson and D. M. Gottfredson (1988) who proposed that rational decisions are made by both perpetrators and victims. Gottfredson and Gottfredson suggested that victim decision making involved three persistent factors; (1) seriousness of offence, (2) victim/offender relationship, and (3) criminal history of offender. In general, Gottfredson and Gottfredson proposed that the more serious the offence is perceived to be, the more likely it is that the victim would report to police. Consequently, the more serious the offence, the more likely the police would engage in criminal justice action. Conversely, if a victim does not perceive the offence as serious, they will decide not to report to police.

In 2010, The Theory of Rational Choice in the context of stalking victimization and reporting was explored by Bradford Reyns and Christine Englebrecht, who hypothesized that; (a) the more serious the offence is, the more likely a victim will report. (b) Victims will be less likely to report to police if the offender is known to them. (c) A victim may view an offender as more threatening if they are aware of previous offences, and therefore more likely to report to police. Reyns and Englebrecht also investigated if these factors operated differently to traditional stalking victims compared to cyberstalking victims using the 2006 data from the American NCVS-SVS and consisting of 1525 stalking victims. The study found moderate support for the theory in both stalking type groups that (1) seriousness of offence and (2) prior perpetrator offence significantly impacted a victims' decision to report the offence to the police. However, in contrast to the proposition made by Gottfredson and Gottfredson (1998), the victim/offender relationship carried little or no influence on a victims' reporting behaviours, whether they were traditionally stalked, or cyberstalked (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010).

The decision-making processes of cyberstalking victims reporting their victimization and seeking help aimed to identify the factors that influence the choices in reporting to law enforcement and seeking assistance, either from professional services or informal sources was conducted by Fissel, (2021). Similar to the Reyns and Englebrecht (2011) study, this research also utilized the Gottfredson and Gottfredson's 1998 theory of Rational Choice in the United States. Fissel (2021) found that of the 477 survey participants, 57.4% of victims engaged in some form of help-seeking, with informal help-seeking (telling friends or family) being more common (43.8%) than professional help-seeking (24.3%) or reporting to law enforcement (14.5%). The results indicated the factors that affected

reporting were: Victims who experienced cyberstalking for longer durations (1 month to less than 1 year) were significantly more likely to report to law enforcement. Experiencing school-related and work-related consequences also increased the reporting likelihood. However, the victims were less likely to report the crime if the cyber-stalker was someone they knew closely, like a current or former intimate partner.

Fissel (2021) also found that males were more likely to report the cyberstalking compared to females. Similar to the Reyns and Englebrecht (2010) findings, the Fissel (2021) study discussed how the seriousness of the offense played significant role in the decision-making process of the victims. However, in contrast to the Reyns and Englebrecht (2010) research, the nature of the victim-offender relationship also played a significant role in the decision-making process for victims of cyberstalking (Fissel, 2021). This study contributed to the understanding of cyberstalking victimization, highlighting the importance of recognizing the unique challenges victims face in seeking help and the need for research to further explore the factors associated with perceptions and help-seeking..

In consideration of the victim and offender relationship, Gottfredson and Gottfredson (1998) and Fissel (2021) argued that the closer the relationship between the two parties, the less likely a victim would report the offence to the police. Proposing that victims will be reluctant to report because they fear not being believed or that the offence is a private matter because of the close relationship. Gottfredson and Gottfredson also argued that the offender having a previous history of criminality was only influential to those involved within the criminal justice systems when determining if criminal justice action should be taken, rather than a decisive factor influencing the victim in whether or not to report their experience. However, research like the Reyns and Englebrecht (2010) study highlighted significant findings through the use of empirical data, and national surveys such which can readily be generalized to wider populations, highlighting the relevance of theoretical perspectives such as the Rational Choice Perspective in a stalking disclosure context.

Stalking disclosures

The literature so far has discussed the factors involved in stalking perceptions as barriers to acknowledgment, and victims' helps seeking decisions. However, another important consideration in the context of stalking victimization is what happens once the disclosure has been made. It has been suggested in the literature (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010) that victims of crimes will reach out to family and friends rather than to more formal agencies such as the police, for a variety of reasons.

This proposition had also been highlighted by Fisher et al (2003) who reported from an American national study of 4446 participant telephone interviews of female college students, that victims of sexual offences report to family and friends at a rate of approximately 70%, whilst only 3% report to the police. Research has also highlighted that victims perceptions of the potential social reaction to their disclosure dissuades them from seeking help, such as Baum et al, (2009) who proposed that victims feared that they police would not be believed, and disclosing may escalate the stalking behaviour.

On the other hand, Reyns and Englebrecht (2014) investigated the situational characteristics of stalking victims and the impact of informal help-seeking behaviours compared to formal sources. This study utilized the NCVS-SVS 2006 Data of 1591 participants in America. The researchers found that 31% disclosed to family and friends and 29% reported to police. In fact, Reyns and Englebrecht explored the victim's decision to disclose to friends and family as an influencer to the likelihood of formal reporting, finding these decisions unrelated. It is possible that the disclosure response was not sufficient to support further reporting, and/or the seriousness of offence and perpetrator type as previously suggested by Reyns and Englebrecht (2010) were factors in these victims' disclosure decisions. When considering factors that this review has covered so far such as perceptions, seriousness of the crime as determining factors to police reporting, and psychological consequences in relation to stalking, this topic needs further investigation.

The effects of informal responses for victims of violent and non-violent stalking episodes, whom either responded to the stalker themselves or enlisted help was explored by Geistman et al (2013). Data was utilized from a large survey study of American college students with 2174 participants. This study found that 32% of participants who responded to the stalker themselves felt the response made things worse in the non-violent category, compared to 24% of participants who felt their response to the stalker helped. Of those that enlisted informal (friends & family) help for violent episodes of stalking nearly half (49%) felt it helped their situation when the disclosure respondents retaliated, while 19% felt that enlisting the informal help made the stalking worse. What was not explored was the outcome for formal disclosures in this study.

Exploring the factors associated with disclosures decisions, Demers et al (2017) investigated components that may increase the likelihood of disclosing in the context of intimate partner violence and stalking using data from an undergraduate survey with 6472 participants over eight United States universities. The findings from the stalking portion of the study found that 73% of respondents had disclosed their experience to informal sources, which were those the victim had a personal relationship (friend, family member, roommate, etc.). Only 8% of the stalking victims made

a formal disclosure (police), with 3% of these being male victims. However, the gender predictor on reporting was two times greater for females compared to males, and these disclosure odds doubled when a former intimate partner conducted the unwanted contact and behaviours. Similar to the disclosure percentage in the Demers study, 74% of the participants reported to having disclosed to family and friends before seeking help from the police, in a survey study conducted by Galeazzi et al (2009) on help-seeking behaviours of 391 stalking victims from Belgium, Slovenia and Italy. Highlighting that disclosure rates for stalking victims to informal sources has not changed much in the past decade.

A more recent study examining stalker behaviour and victim help-seeking was conducted by Brady (2022). Using the 2016 NCVS-SVS data of 1470 participants in America, Brady found that 67% of victims who had an Inter-personal (previous) relationship with the stalker compared to 40% of no previous relationship, were pursued both online and offline. Results also indicated that the victims were twice as likely to be stalked in-person if there was no prior relationship, compared to those that had a prior relationship with the stalker. Interestingly, the Brady's results also reported that inter-personal victims were moderately more likely to seek help at 64%, compared to 61% of non-intimates, despite the stalking occurring in person. Importantly, contacting the police was the main significant predictor found as to why the victim perceived the stalking had stopped for both groups. This study highlights the importance of understanding the factors involved in stalking victims' formal help-seeking decisions.

Furthermore, the victims' perceptions of their experience also play an important role in help-seeking decisions, as evident in the literature on stalking acknowledgement (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010; Ngo, 2014). It is plausible to consider that if a victim receives a response from an informal source that minimizes their experience, yet they are fearful for their life, they may very well make the rational decision to seek formal help (Reyns and Englebrecht 2010). There is also a possibility that either or both the Rational Choice Theory and Control balance theory may explain the decisions a victim makes when seeking help with their victimization, that may go beyond a disclosure response and promote further disclosing. For example, it would be a rational choice if the behaviours were so serious that one felt fear for their life, and therefore continue on to a formal disclosure, as suggested by Ngo (2014). It may also be a consideration for a victims of stalking to attempt to regain control of their life back that influences a victims' help-seeking decision, as Nichols (2020) had posited. Therefore the perceived seriousness of the crime may play a role in a stalking victims' disclosure decisions (Ngo, 2014).

However, there are other factors such as victims' perceptions and common stereotypes that may also play a role in disclosure decisions. The literature (Lysova et al, 2022) suggests that there are perceptions and common stereotypes which exist within many societies that stalking is not a serious crime and some may even perceive the stalking pursuit behaviours to be romantic. These perceptions can minimize the stalking episode for a victim, creating barriers to disclosures and help-seeking behaviours (McKeon et al, 2015).

The crime of stalking in the context of misconceptions has also been highlighted in research conducted by Weller et al (2013) in the United States, using experimental scenarios given to 132 Police officers and 225 lay participants, who purported that police officers who had no previous experience of stalking cases, were more likely to recognize the stalking course of conduct when the stalking was perpetrated by strangers and acquaintances, and less likely to blame the victim within these specific stalking typologies, compared to ex-intimate stalking. Therefore, understanding perceptions and misconceptions that result in a reaction perceived as victim blame is important to understanding barriers that victims face when disclosing.

What is also important to understand, is the gender differences for victims of stalking, most of the research covered in this review so far has explored the factors involved in female help-seeking decisions, such as seriousness of the crime and stranger stalker perceptions (Buhi et al, 2009; Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010). Investigating how male victims conceptualize, understand and seek help with stalking victimization, Donne et al (2018) indicated the barriers to disclosures and help-seeking behaviours were predominantly due to gender norms (taught to be strong), shame, perceived identity impacts (did not want to view themselves as weak), financial cost, being too busy and finding a trustworthy and relatable professional to disclose to. The findings of Donne and colleagues support the previous suggestions of misconceptions and common stereotypes as barriers to seeking help. Understanding these misconceptions as barriers are important, considering the psychological consequences of stalking previously mentioned.

To tackle this deficit in male victimization help-seeking decisions, research was conducted to understand help-seeking behaviours among men (Lysova et al, 2022). Lysova and colleagues used online focus groups consisting of 41 men from Canada, U.S.A, Australia and the U.K. to explore the internal and external barriers to help-seeking. Lysova and colleagues proposed the majority of males who experienced Intimate partner violence (IPV) do not seek help, as they did not recognize the abuse, or have the ability to assess the risk of harm. Furthermore, Lysova and colleagues suggested that social perceptions such as gender norms and stereotypes were found to be the most common barriers to help-seeking, similar to the Donne et al (2018) study. However, some of the men in the

Lysova et al (2022) study had also reported that they were in fear for their safety, were worried they would be re-victimized within the criminal justice system, and they felt there was a lack of services available to men. This study adds to the small but growing research to aid in the understanding of social perceptions, help-seeking behaviours and barriers experienced by male victims. Psychological consequences also appeared to be a major factor in help-seeking for men as the majority stated that they did not consider reaching out until they realized their daily function had become impaired (Donne et al, 2018).

To further the literature on male victimization in the context of stalking, Ameral et al, (2020) investigated predictors of help-seeking behaviours using a multi-year email survey of 4710 American University students and found that 12.2% male respondents reported help-seeking behaviours and reported more victimization through electronic means compared to female participants. Another study investigating predictors to police reporting, using a survey from 624 American University students conducted by Augustyn et al, (2020) found police disclosure prevalence at only 6% and the main predictor to police reporting was the victims experiencing more than one type of stalking behaviour and/or having to change their regular routine, a finding also similar to the Donne et al (2018) study.

Similar to the research regarding male victimization in the context of stalking, the literature on the stalking of professionals is sparse. The stalking of professionals is considered as a victim targeted through their working profession. In an attempt to shed light on stalking misconceptions and victim reporting, Ngo (2020) drew on data of 464 stalking victims in America that had reported to the police and suggested that professionals who have a duty of care to their clientele were more likely to be a victim of stalking. Studies such as this highlight the need to understand disclosure responses, particularly in these areas where stalking is found to be prevalent yet under-researched.

On the other hand, Jutasi and McEwan (2021) performed a seminal review of the literature comparing professionals' experiences of stalking, the impact the stalking experience had among different professions and responses received from the employing organizations. The results found the stalking episodes and impacts the victims experienced amongst the different professions were similar to each other. Jutasi and McEwan argued the responses received from employers to the victims were commonly unhelpful. Furthermore, Jutasi and McEwan suggested that given the global stalking prevalence and the universal negative consequences for the victims, research on workplace responses is lacking. This study supports the idea that organizations should employ management education programs and implement robust policy and procedures for the crime of stalking within the

workplace to ensure better disclosure outcomes, which will improve overall mental health for the professionals within their organizations.

It is also important to consider the victimization prevalence within minority communities. A literature review was conducted on 47 studies to explore the barriers to help-seeking decisions for BAME females (Black, Asian, Minority ethnic and immigrant) in the context of intimate partner violence by (Hulley et al, 2022). Hulley and colleagues identified 25 barriers to disclosing and 14 facilitators to support. The most common barriers identified were cultural issues, discrimination/racism, issues with documentations and the legal system. The most common facilitators were; family, religion/spirituality, accommodation advocates and advocacy agencies. Hulley and colleagues argued that stalking is a crime that is synonymous with other crimes, such as domestic abuse, and the prevalence of IPV are substantial. Therefore, the barriers a BAME women experiences to help-seeking decisions for IPV can easily be applied to stalking victimization, given the prevalence of stalking in the context of IPV (Kim et al, 2024).

There are further underrepresented communities within research in the context of stalking, such as the LGBTQ+. Fleming et al (2023) attempted to address the literature gap in understanding help-seeking among the LGBTQ+ community using the 2019 American NCVS-SVS. Analyzing and comparing data sets from 1767 heterosexual participants compared to 139 LGBTQ+. The findings from the study suggest that LGBTQ+ group sought help at a higher rate than the heterosexual group (43% compared to 32%) with the LGBTQ+ group reporting experiencing emotional distress due to the stalking compared to the heterosexual group.

The research explored so far in this review has added to the growing knowledge of male and female victimization, communities such as emerging adults, BAME, LGBTQ+ and professionals that perceived seriousness of stalking, contextual relationship with the stalker, fear of further victimization, perceptions and misconceptions regarding stalking as the main dimensions in the help seeking decisions of victims of stalking. As far as a victim journey is concerned, it is understood that acknowledgement needs to occur, and the above factors considered before the decision is made to seek help. The scope of literature on the topic of stalking disclosures has focused mainly on the type of victimization, prevalence and predictors of help-seeking behaviours for victims of stalking. Thus there remains a large gap in the literature exploring how a specific response to a stalking disclosure may either negatively or positively influence the mitigation of psychological trauma, and the stalking outcome.

Research has proposed that not all disclosures are beneficial to a victim, for example, when a disclosure is made by a victim to another person, the other persons verbal and/or non-verbal

reactions may minimize or victim blame causing the victim further trauma (Lietzau et al, 2023). This minimization of the stalking may result from an individuals' attempt to try to fit their own understandings of the crime of stalking into their own worldviews, as suggested by Crome and McCabe (2001). The proposal to align with an existing worldview is similar to Bandura's 1977 Social Learning Theory, as this theory describes how worldviews are formed gradually through an individuals' interactions within their culture and society. However, disclosures may also result in a positive experience, such as an affirmation of the victimization as also suggested by Lietzau et al (2023). Affirming or validating the victims' experience can increase the likelihood of a victim acknowledging the stalking. If a victim acknowledges the crime, they will be more likely to seek-help, and/or report to the police, potentially mitigating the long-term psychological impacts, as Reyns and Englebrecht (2011) have suggested.

Additionally, the minimization or affirmation of a victims experience can be considered as a social reaction. Social Reactions are theoretically described by Ullman (2010) as informal reactions; responses of both verbal and non-verbal reactions to the victims disclosing. These informal reactions can be either subtle or direct. Ullman divided the disclosure response reactions into categories; positive-believing/validating and negative- disbelieving/victim-blaming. Ullman proposed that these responses can have a potentially negatively impact on the attributions and meaning of a victims' experience. Which can result in negative consequences for help-seeking behaviours and for the victims coping mechanisms.

Using the Ullman 2010 Social reaction questionnaire, Edwards et al (2014) conducted a literature review of 41 articles exploring informal disclosures of heterosexual female college students in the context of the crime of stalking. This study found support for their hypothesis that negative disclosure reactions were related to an increase in psychological distress and positive reactions were unrelated to psychological distress. However, the Edwards and colleagues study also found 38% of respondents did not engage in any type of social support. 32% occasionally sought social support. These findings are contrary to the Buhi et al (2009) study of college students help-seeking behaviours which found 90% of participants reported to have sought help from friends and family. Edwards relates the difference in these findings to the fact that although a victim may disclose their stalking experience to family or peers, there is no guarantee that support was received, and this topic was not explored in the Buhi study.

Additionally, a meta-regression analysis was conducted by Dworkin et al (2019) as a meta-review of 51 studies to explore social reactions to disclosures of interpersonal violence and psychopathology, concluding that negative social reactions to a disclosure were associated with a

declined psychopathology for the victim, such as increased anxiety and depression. Whereas, a victim perceiving the reactions positively was associated with less severe psychopathology, however Dworkin and colleagues argued that the positive perceptions' potential benefit appeared to be smaller than the potential risk of a negative reaction. Dworkin and colleagues also argued that interventions which reduce the degree to which survivors receive negative social reactions are needed.

Research was also conducted by Dardis et al (2021) who investigated the impact of social reactions to disclosures of unwanted pursuit behaviours (UPB) on Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) symptoms. The unwanted pursuit behaviours referred to excessive or threatening unsolicited contact from an ex-partner, which can include stalking and harassment. These behaviours often persist after a romantic relationship ends and are recognized as having negative psychological consequences, including PTSD symptoms. The study addressed a gap in literature regarding the disclosure of UPB victimization, the social reactions recipients provide, and the subsequent psychological effects on the victims, particularly focusing on PTSD symptomatology. The sample comprised 318 undergraduate women aged 18-24 in the United States who reported a breakup within the last three years. The findings of the Dardis and colleagues study revealed that approximately 60% of the women reported experiencing UPBs. Nearly all respondents (92.6%) disclosed their victimization to others. This primarily consisted of disclosures to close friends. The participants received more positive social reactions, in the form of support and validation, than negative reactions, such as blame and disbelief. However, the negative social reactions were associated with increased PTSD symptoms, while positive reactions did not seem to correlate with symptom relief, a finding similar to the previously mentioned Edwards et al, (2014) study who also argued that positive reactions to disclosures did not correlate with a reduction in psychological distress.

The results of the Dardis et al (2021) study demonstrated that negative social reactions function as a mediator in the relationship between UPB victimization and PTSD symptoms, confirming the hypothesis that negative responses to disclosures can exacerbate psychological distress. The findings highlight the importance of the type of social reactions that victims receive upon disclosing UPB victimization. As negative reactions were shown to lead to feelings of isolation and increased PTSD symptoms for the victims. The authors postulate that positive reactions do not significantly mitigate these effects, a contrasting finding to the Dworkin (2019) propositions that positive social reactions decreased the psychological distress. Furthermore, the Dardis et al (2021) study emphasized the need for interventions that educate friends and family on how to respond supportively to disclosures of UPB victimization. However, both the Edwards et al (2014) and the Dardis et al (2021) study's

homogenous sample (primarily young, White, heterosexual women) limits generalizability, therefore, future research should focus on more diverse populations and explore the nuanced effects of social reactions and stalking victimization. In addition to the issues outlined, to improve overall responses to stalking disclosures, it is relevant to understand not only how informal reactions to a disclosure, but also how advocacy professionals and criminal justice systems perceive, understand, and react to a victim's stalking disclosure.

Little research has been conducted regarding the barriers a victim of stalking may experience when deciding to disclose, or the responses received following disclosures to advocates and support agencies that service the crime specific topic of stalking. Previous research has shown that victim service workers (advocates) often have difficulties identifying stalking, as Jordan et al (2003) suggested these difficulties in stalking recognition defeat the purpose of providing appropriately supportive responses, as some do not perceive the crime of stalking to be serious or dangerous in nature. Furthermore, victim-blaming attitudes directed towards the stalking victim ostensibly serve as a barrier to receiving support (Botuck et al, 2009).

Victim-blaming is generally considered as any response to a disclosure that places the responsibility on the victim for their victimization. However, a more recent study using a mixed method design of online survey and in-person interviews performed by Taylor-Dunn et al (2018) found that nearly half of participants were signposted to the police after accessing appropriate support services. The differences between the two studies may be due to stalking awareness increasing over time. Moreover, it has also been suggested that agencies working within the realm of stalking such as advocacy agencies, and criminal justice representatives need to be fully trained to provide the relevant information and advice appropriate to the victims' individual and unique circumstances (Backes et al, 2020; Boehnlein et al, 2020). Therefore, stalking advocates trained in the nuances of stalking victimization will be better placed to advise the individual accordingly. This is a crucial point to communicate because currently the burden is placed upon the victims of stalking to not only be in charge of their safety, but also to gather evidence relevant enough for criminal justice systems to acknowledge and act, as argued by Lombard and Proctor (2024).

The perspectives of community and criminal justice advocates were explored by Boehnlein et al (2020) with the aim of identifying barriers to investigations and prosecution successes in stalking cases. The study interviewed 13 criminal justice representatives and victim service agencies in America that had held their position working with either stalking perpetrators or victims for at least five years. The most common theme that emerged was the concept that victims need to be believed, validated, and have a support system that does not minimize the stalking experience. What these

interviews also discovered is that victims need support agencies to offer emotional support, and practical support to ensure correct risk assessment and safety planning, a similar finding to the Backes et al (2020) study.

Additionally, Boehnlein et al (2020) proposed that the public tends to minimize the stalking behaviours, the discrepancies between the legal definition of stalking between different jurisdictions and the victim's perceptions can create barriers to seeking support. As previously suggested by (Boehnlein et al 2020; Lombard and Proctor, 2024), victims of stalking must take a proactive approach as legal systems and offenders cannot be relied upon to stop the stalking behaviour. Therefore, if an advocate can shift the conversations to measures such as safety, and proactive measures, as suggested by Boehnlein et al (2020), this can give a sense of control back to the victim, potentially lessening the psychological impacts of the crime, even in cases without prosecution success.

Research conducted by Bennett-Cattaneo et al (2011) examined the phenomenon of stalking within the context of intimate partner violence (IPV) and its effects on victims over time. The study was conducted by Safe Horizon, a victim assistance organization in New York City, and focused on the experiences of 82 women who had been victims of intimate partner stalking over a period of seven months through monthly interviews. The study found that stalking behaviours, though predominantly chronic, decreased over time on average, although this decrease was only marginally significant. Participants reported a wide range of stalking behaviours, with many experiencing multiple forms simultaneously, highlighting the complexity of each case. Victims reported high levels of distress associated with the stalking, which significantly decreased over time. On average, participants rated their distress as 8.33 out of 9 at baseline, decreasing to 6.45 at the six-month mark. Perceived safety, while showing an increasing trend, did not reach statistical significance. However, the study noted that changes in stalking frequency were correlated with changes in distress and perceived safety, indicating that as the stalking behaviour decreased, perceived safety increased alongside a reduction in distress.

Interestingly, the participants in the Bennett-Cattaneo et al (2011) study primarily sought help from criminal justice sources rather than victim services. Approximately 54% contacted criminal justice agents, while 40% reached out to victim assistance services. Most participants reported having an order of protection at some point in the study, but the usefulness of these orders varied significantly. Only 15.4% felt that the order completely stopped stalking, while 35.3% believed it reduced the behaviour. The authors noted inconsistencies in how practitioners respond to stalking cases, suggesting that a one-size-fits-all approach is inadequate. There is a need for ongoing

education of service providers about the complexities of stalking and its response. The study underscores the necessity of client-centered service models, where victims' perspectives and individual experiences guide intervention strategies. This approach emphasizes that victims possess valuable insights into their situations and that advocates and criminal justice actors should collaborate closely with them.

To further understand advocate responses to stalking in practice, Nichols (2020) explored 26 interviews with domestic violence advocates from 11 organizations in the United Kingdom. The inductive analysis theorized that advocates and stalking support agencies respond to a stalking disclosure with Micro, Mezzo and Macro levels of responses. Micro responses included advising victims to log the unwanted contacts and behaviours. The Backes et al's (2020) study supports this finding as the advocates in their study indicated that the documenting of the stalking contacts and behaviours creates the likelihood of more positive court outcomes, because the log provides an overall picture of the entire stalking experience which courts are more likely to take seriously. The mezzo level practices according to Nichols (2020) included the use of community-level models for improving criminal justice responses to intimate partner stalking. Advocates in this study suggested that working alongside law enforcement is beneficial to the victim by mitigating the contact from the stalker. Macro-level responses were the act of advocating for legal changes to include specific stalking behaviours in order to obtain and enforce protection orders and working on legislative initiatives which have shown to improve overall responses to stalking. These studies provide a start to adding context and meaning for advocates working in the realm of stalking victimization and improving criminal justice responses for victims.

Criminal Justice Responses to Stalking

The framework for historical criminology began in the 1970's. Starting with the Labour History Society in 1972, there emerged a social history of crime that extended the interpretation of crime beyond the legal sphere of riots and smuggling (Knepper, 2013). Since then, criminologists have taken the historical study of crime and criminal justice into diverse areas which reflect both trends in social history and current issues. The range of newer research now includes; crime and violence, women and justice, and interpersonal crimes such as the crime of stalking (Police foundation, 2009). The purpose of modern criminal justice systems in the United Kingdom are understood to provide protection and/or resources to pursue people who commit crimes and to prevent repeat victimization (Victims Commissioner, 2022). Victim decision making has become a key research focus within the field of victimology, however, despite this there has not been much theoretical

development concerning criminal justice help-seeking actions and responses for repeat victimization crimes such as stalking.

To address this research gap, as recently as 2024, P. Brady and B. Reyns set out to better understand the determinants of decision-making by victims to identify potential avenues to improve criminal justice responses for victims in the context of stalking in the United States. Brady and Reyns adopted the focal concerns theory (FCT) as a framework for understanding crime victims' decisions to seek criminal and civil interventions. The FCT according to Steffensmeier et al., (1993, 1998) proposed that criminal justice actors consider three general areas (focal concerns) when deciding the outcome of a complaint; (a) The judges' assessment of the suspects' culpability or blameworthiness (seriousness of the offense, victim harm, availability of evidence); (b) Community protection, the need to protect the community from further harm (weapon use, prior record, lack of remorse); (c) Judges are also required to make decisions within the limits of practical constraints and considerations (alternatives to incarceration, correctional overcrowding).

Importantly, the FCT argues that there are disparities found within criminal case outcomes which are largely due to prior experiences with criminals and cognitive biases that are consciously or unconsciously used in the case processing and decision stages by the criminal justice actors, (Steffensmeier et al, 1993, 1998). The disparity of cognitive biases in criminal justice actors was supported by Korkodeilou (2016) who found that myths and cognitive biases play a large role in responses to stalking behaviours, where police did not recognize the psychological terror the victims experienced unless an actual physical attack occurred. In a more recent study in the United Kingdom, using qualitative interviews from 26 participants, Korkodeilou (2020) found that these myths and cognitive biases within the criminal justice systems extends particularly to victims stalked by acquaintances compared to ex-intimates. Korkodeilou found that police did not recognize or acknowledge the stalking behaviours when there was no prior relationship between the stalker and the victim.

Korkodeilou's (2020) findings are a contrast to the previously mentioned research conducted by Weller et al (2013) where it was suggested that police officers with no previous experience of stalking cases, were more likely to recognize the stalking course of conduct when the stalking was perpetrated by strangers and acquaintances, and less likely to blame the victim within these specific stalking contexts, when compared to ex-intimate stalking cases. This highlights a gap in the research on the role of cognitive biases as barriers to support for victims, particularly in cases where recognition of the stalking is occurring along-side victim blame attitudes and misconceptions in ex-

intimate cases, and also in cases where the stalking is not recognized when perpetrated by a stranger or acquaintance.

According to Brady and Reynolds (2024), the factors highlighted within the Focal Concerns Theory (FCT) that influence a stalking victims' decision to engage the civil and/or criminal-legal systems align with the contextual factors which criminal-legal actors consider during case processing decisions, stating:

'Conceptually, stalking victims' perceptions of blameworthiness, community/self-protection, and practical constraints tap into the course of conduct and fear elements of stalking statutes. From a victim standpoint, blameworthiness represents victims' concern for the seriousness of the perpetrators' conduct and can be captured using measures of the nature, extent, and consequences related to how perpetrators targeted victims (e.g., pursuit type, duration, frequency, co-occurring crimes, and personal/professional consequences).' (Brady and Reynolds, 2024, p.6)

Using the 2019 quantitative data from the American NCVS-SVS, Brady and Reynolds (2024) found support for two of the FCT factors of why stalking victims seek help from legal systems. Specifically, stalking victims were more likely to engage in criminal and civil legal help-seeking after experiencing a greater number of co-occurring crimes; (1) that resulted in fear for themselves or others (blameworthiness), and (2) prior record (community protection). Brady and Reynolds (2024) proposed that future help-seeking research using the FCT is needed, exploring the measures of cognitive perceptions that capture victim and criminal justice actors' cognitive biases in order to improve overall victim help-seeking and criminal justice responses to the crime of stalking.

Research has suggested from previous American NCVS-SVS quantitative data, that victims can experience huge barriers in getting the police to recognize and respond to the stalking (Ngo, 2020; 2018; 2014). Furthermore, Ngo (2014) suggested that victim characteristics such as age, acknowledgement of the crime, characteristics' of the stalking and the level of seriousness/fear play a part in whether a victim chooses to disclose their experience. This is an obstacle for victims as Ngo had suggested, emphasizing that every incident should be logged by officers regardless of the evidential existence. This suggestion supports the Nichols (2020) suggestion that logging every incident could help decrease these barriers to disclosing the stalking experience to police for many victims, simply through the validation that can be achieved facilitating recognition from the log of events. Investigating the context of police responses to stalking disclosures and the relation of these responses to the stalking outcomes, Ngo (2018) found that 18% of victims who had reported; the police spoke with or warned the perpetrator. Interestingly, 16% of these victims reported the

stalking had ceased after the police warning, supporting the suggestion by Brady (2022) that contacting the police is a significant predictor to stopping stalking.

A more recent study involving police action in America and the stalking outcome was conducted by Ngo (2020) who explored the 2006 NCVS-SVS data for correlation and impact of police responses on the crime of stalking from 464 participant data sets who had contacted the police. The study found police responses of taking an official report or speaking to the perpetrator improved reported outcomes for the victim. Furthermore, police inaction was found to compound the stalking situation. Ngo stated that police responses, particularly non-action can dissuade victims from reporting, potentially compromising the victim's safety and adding to the concern of stalking being so under-reported. The Ngo (2020) study also found that police officers were less likely to advise protection measures, such as a restraining or protection order, refer to prosecution or recommend self-protection methods when the offender typology was non-intimate, similar to the findings of Korkodeilou, (2020). These findings support the suggestion that societal perceptions of stalking is still influencing victims of stalking at the disclosure stage.

In the context of normative perceptions, it has been reported that the crime of stalking is regularly misunderstood and unrecorded by police officers and the Crown Prosecution Service, according to (HMIC, 2017). This claim is supported by a study that explored the responses received when stalking victims disclosed to police. Taylor-Dunn & Erol (2022) investigated one of the first U.K qualitative experiments following the implementation of the stalking laws in 2012 in England and Wales using 54 victim cases, 10 police investigative files, and 5 interviews. Taylor-Dunn and Erol suggested that victims are likely to experience barriers to receiving help when reporting to the police. Furthermore, a great deal of victims in this investigation had expressed their dissatisfaction which correlated with the prevalence in which victims are responded to with 'there is nothing we can do', or 'no criminal offence has occurred'. In fact, the findings of the Taylor-Dunn and colleagues' study reported that the majority of the respondents received the following poor responses from police; police inaction, inappropriate action, feeling blamed, and not taken seriously. These finding were similar to the Ngo (2020) study, and an important point to highlight was the reasons for police inaction that Ngo (2020) suggested, the lack of formal stalking training provided to law enforcement to counteract these normative perceptions of stalker types and socially accepted behaviours.

Furthermore, Machado and Santiago (2025) contend that police officers often hold gendered stereotypes, such as masculine biases about intimate partner violence and stalking, which can negatively affect their interactions with male victims. Consequently, male victims are frequently misidentified as perpetrators, leading to wrongful arrests and further marginalization. The

researchers suggest that police officers take a harsher stance on male perpetrators, suggesting that men receive 63% longer sentences, and women are more likely to avoid charges, convictions, and incarceration compared to male counterparts, (Machado and Santiago, 2025). These barriers contribute to a delayed or avoided help-seeking decision, sustaining a cycle in which the true extent of male victimization remains hidden and societal misconceptions are reinforced, hindering the development of appropriate support systems (Lysova et al., 2022). Recent work indicates that police perceptions are not fixed and are beginning to evolve in constructive ways. While stereotypes and constraints persist, there is growing recognition of the complexity of male victimization and the need for gender-sensitive approaches. Acknowledging these positive shifts in police perceptions matters because it signals progress in educating law enforcement about the nuances of interpersonal violence and stalking (Machado and Santiago, 2025).

To understand criminal justice actors' perspectives in America, Boehnlein et al (2020) interviewed 13 participants from different agencies within the criminal justice system who had dealt with cases of stalking. Boehnlein and colleagues stated that because stalking is such a global problem and a barrier to safety, systematic responses to disclosures need to be better understood. Boehnlein and colleagues found officers would only perceive a stalking experience as serious enough to make a report if the stalking behaviour consisted of direct threats of violence. Or if the behaviours resulted in the victim having to change their daily life and work habits, and if the officers were able to obtain physical evidence. The officers interviewed had described wanting the victims to be able to provide the incident dates, specific behaviours, and identify vehicles before a report would be taken. These findings support a recent U.K. study conducted by Lombard and Proctor (2023). Lombard and Proctor used data from 132 survey female participants, and 21 interviews from the survey participants, which suggested that stalking victims not only need to be in charge of their safety, but also must take on the role of investigator.

Furthermore, Boehnlein and colleagues (2020) concluded that in relation to cyberstalking, law enforcement needs to have the technological resources to understand and follow technological advances, as stalking behaviours evolve within these advances. There was also a suggestion by Boehnlein and colleagues that training and education is needed to shift the focal concerns within police forces, judge and prosecution services to increase the wider understanding of what constitutes stalking. The researchers suggested the shift should include the dynamics that interplay between the victim and the stalker. Including how to recognize behaviour patterns and risk and importantly how to assist victims of any gender to convey the implications and complexities of changing day-to-day activities and work patterns, therefore promoting more help-seeking decisions and actions to stop the stalking.

Conclusion

The literature in this review has suggested that stalking victimization is an individual journey with many factors and complexities. Stalking victimization has shown to result in comorbid anxiety and depression in nearly half of victims with many resorting to uprooting their homes and routines, and in more extreme cases resulting in murder, (Baum et al. 2009; Monkton-Smith et al, 2017). Yet it has been highlighted throughout this review that cognitive biases and misconceptions are affecting help-seeking decisions at all stages of the victimization. When considering the importance of early intervention with the crime of stalking, in order to mitigate the long term effects of stalking on its victims, and to create more positive outcomes, it becomes apparent the importance for future education programs, support agencies, law-enforcement, academics, and legislative stakeholders to acquire an in-depth awareness and universal understanding of the crime of stalking.

The central aim of this review is to synthesize research over the past few decades on stalking perceptions, victims' decisions to seek help, and responses to disclosures. The literature has not yet fully explored how social learning and social reactions shape acknowledgement of stalking and subsequent disclosure, reporting, and access to support for both male and female victims. Although work on police responses to stalking is growing, only a limited number of studies have examined how disclosure and help-seeking interact in a nuanced way, leaving a gap that constrains theoretical advancement and practical responses at national and international levels. This deficit highlights the complex interplay among victim beliefs, social reactions, and disclosure processes in shaping acknowledgment, help-seeking, and stalking outcomes. Robust empirical research and theory are needed to reveal how social learning and perceptions influence disclosure responses and help-seeking—and how these, in turn, affect reporting and access to support. Gaining such insights will assist victims and their families, and society at large, in recognizing stalking and taking appropriate action. Moreover, educating the public and professionals involved with victims will help support agencies, police, the criminal justice system, and policymakers recognize and respond effectively to disclosures, promoting more favourable outcomes for victims within the stalking landscape.

A key takeaway from the current state of knowledge is that victim perceptions, the social reactions they encounter, and the responses to disclosures interact dynamically to influence whether stalking is acknowledged, whether help is pursued, and what ultimately happens as a consequence. Advancing understanding in these domains is crucial because it is only through rigorous empirical study and solid theory that we can explain how social learning and perceptual

processes translate into the likelihood and nature of disclosures, and how these disclosures affect reporting rates, access to formal and informal support, and the trajectory of stalking itself. By clarifying these processes, researchers and practitioners can better identify the circumstances under which disclosures are validated, dismissed, or misunderstood, and how those outcomes feed into safety planning, risk assessment, and ongoing victim support.

This knowledge has broad implications. For victims and their families, clearer insight into disclosure dynamics can reduce harm, shorten the time to receive help, and improve safety planning. For communities, enhanced awareness of stalking indicators and appropriate response mechanisms can promote earlier recognition and intervention, reducing the social and psychological costs of stalking. For service providers, law enforcement, prosecutors, healthcare workers, educators, and other actors, improved understanding of how disclosures are received and acted upon will support the development of better training, protocols, and collaboration strategies. At the policy level, this translates into more coherent guidelines, standardized responses to disclosures, and more effective allocation of resources to victim support services.

To translate these insights into practice, public education campaigns and professional training must address the realities of disclosure in diverse contexts, including gender differences, cultural norms, online versus offline stalking, and the role of family, friends, and bystanders in shaping responses. Future research should adopt comprehensive, methodologically robust designs—longitudinal, mixed-methods, and cross-national studies—to capture the temporal evolution of disclosure and help-seeking, and to examine how factors such as severity, duration, relationship with the stalker, and societal attitudes influence outcomes. Important areas for future inquiry include: gender and intersectional analyses to understand potential differential patterns for male, female, and non-binary victims; cross-cultural comparisons to identify universal versus context-specific processes; distinctions between online and offline stalking and their respective disclosure dynamics; the impact of the disclosure recipient (police, witnesses, healthcare providers, family) on help-seeking trajectories; barriers to disclosure and help-seeking (stigma, fear of retaliation, concerns about credibility); the role of social networks and formal support services in shaping recovery and safety outcomes; and the development of evidence-based interventions that align social learning theory with practical response frameworks.

Chapter 3: Research Design

Introduction

This chapter outlines the research design employed to explore the research aims of this study. The main aim of this study is to understand the complexities of stalking victimization and highlight the journey victims of stalking go through when considering whether or not they are being stalked, the facilitators and barriers to disclosing decisions, and the relationship of these factors to the stalking outcome. The research also proposed to explore whether there are gender differences in the factors under investigation. The explorations were achieved using a cross sectional, integrative, qualitative web-based survey alongside person-to-person interviews with victim/survivors of stalking. The scope of the study is to add to the contribution of existing scholarly work, filling gaps in the literature regarding the complex nuances of the stalking journey of help-seeking as a whole for victims experiencing this crime.

This chapter will discuss the methodology, positionality, theoretical perspectives and reflexivity of the researcher. The chapter will then move on to discuss the qualitative research designs used to conduct the study, including the approach taken to analyze the research.

Methodology

Research methods connect the use of techniques and tools that are practiced to accomplish specific research tasks, and methodology refers to the overall guiding principles according to (Guba & Lincoln, 1994). Methodology is also considered as a bridge to the philosophical standpoint relating to the ontology (perspective of) and epistemology (tools used) for the chosen method (Creswell, 2009; Creswell & Poth 2016). When considering research paradigms; methodology can be considered as the unique way of performing research with purpose, data and analysis (Creswell, 2009). Therefore, the methodology chosen directly impacts the methods the researcher will have at their disposal.

The research paradigm and guiding principles of the research encompass the ontological, epistemological, and philosophical understandings which have impacted the chosen methodology and influenced the methods used for a constructivist paradigm in adopting a qualitative research design. The constructivist paradigm according to Adom and colleagues, (2016) states:

'A researcher who carries out a study with the aim of understanding the influence of social behaviour on the attitude of individuals in a particular community can conveniently adopt this approach' (Adom et al, 2016. Pg.6)

The research design adopts an inductive approach to data interpretation in order to understand the participant subjective social realities and experience. The structuring conditions of subjective and objective imposed upon the construction of social reality and experience were considered as the central process in developing the subjective meaning of the research.

Qualitative Approach to Research Design

Qualitative research is an investigative process whereby sense is made on a given social phenomenon through the approach of contrasting, comparing, and classifying that which is being studied as suggested by Miles & Huberman (1994). Qualitative research attempts to make sense of the meaning people attach to their world and their experiences (Merriam, 2009). This typically involves immersing oneself in the experience of the identified phenomenon under investigation. This can be achieved by entering the participants experience and engaging through interaction; a researcher seeks to discover the perspectives and meanings held by the participant as detailed by Creswell (2009).

Qualitative methods allow for a holistic narrative and descriptive account of the social phenomena under investigation to understand the particular social situation, and/or interactions relative to the research aim and purpose (Parkinson & Drislane, 2011). A distinct feature of human experience within the social world is the ability to communicate perceptions, attitudes, values and feelings through the shared meaning of language (Creswell, 2013). The way in which social phenomena are understood by a participant is largely influenced by the perspective viewed from and the meaning attached to the phenomenon (Ritchie & Lewis, 2003).

How experiences are understood and from which future action will be based on, is relevant to an individual's social reality (Schwandt, 2000). Therefore, the researcher's goal of understanding the social phenomenon from the subjective experience would be diluted somewhat should the resulting data be quantified (Creswell, 1998). In order to explore the subjective realities enveloping stalking victimization and help-seeking choices, I adopted a qualitative research design. Initially, I tried to make the research design fit with one of the prominent strategies of inquiry. Giving consideration to these, I thought originally that grounded theory as a strategy of inquiry to be the closest fit with my own research design and position.

'The researcher derives a general abstract theory of a process, action, or interaction grounded in the views of the participants. The process involves using multiple stages of

data collection and the refinement and interrelationship of categories of information'
(Charmaz, 2006, p13)

Grounded theory, specifically focused coding, as suggested by Saldana (2021) can be used as a first and second cycle of coding, a way to identify patterns and themes in the data. The second cycle of the coding explores the explanations and themes from the participants' words to answer the research questions and explain in more depth what the participants' meanings are in their answers.

'the actual formulation of the question arises from the researcher's notions about the nature of reality, the relationship between the knower and what can be known, and how best to discover reality. Thus, the selection of method can be viewed as also arising from the basic philosophical beliefs about inquiry as held by the researcher.' (Annells, 2010, pg.1)

Grounded Theory is the discovery of theory from the acquired data according to Glaser and Strauss (1967). However, this research is not looking to discover new theory, but rather text existing theories. Therefore, the researcher generated categories must be indicated by the data, and be meaningfully relevant to the behaviour under study. Furthermore, the initial stage of coding can therefore be considered open and dynamic. Attaching code labels/words to identify occurrences and meanings of the phenomena until nothing new or interesting emerges, and links between codes begin to cohere. It is through the focused element of the coding that repeated reviewing and coding of the data occurs. This allows for links between the various codes to be made and relationships among categories begin to solidify and become more focused on the phenomenon under study, which is an interpretive inductive and deductive process.

'While deductive research focuses on casualty and testing theory, inductive research focuses on generating theory from collected data'. (William and Moser (2019, pg. 1)

Given the limited research on the topic of stalking, the research was undertaken to reveal raw data from which discoveries could be derived regarding the processes of acknowledgment of the victimization, and how the process of help-seeking decisions relate to stalking outcomes. Grounded theory in the purest sense does not involve any previous reading of literature due to danger of contributing pre-determined findings by the researcher as suggested by Charmaz (2006).

Therefore, I felt that it would be best to consider this research to involve the investigation of existing theoretical fields, which currently lack in connection to existing literature. I believe closely related studies would assist in guiding myself to conduct a deeper investigation of previously highlighted issues. Therefore, while grounded theory was perhaps the closest strategy to consider, the research could not be termed as such given that it was unlikely that the research would be discovering completely new fields, but would rather simply be investigating previously overlooked issues and gaps. Elements of grounded theory such as the focus coding were adopted in the analysis

once the raw data was gathered, it was coded into the categories of exploration, for example acknowledgment, and the victim's experiences in these categories were then combined into the categories and explored further to discover the themes and sub-themes. Thus the strategy of inquiry adopted was much more multi-dimensional and fluid. This research will be exploring the data, not to generate new theory per se, but to explain, support or otherwise apply existing theories in relation to the topics under investigation.

Therefore, the inductive thematic analysis approach was adopted and occurred in the stages of coding, generating the codes from the data, comparing the open-question responses from the survey and interviews against the chosen existing theories. Thomas (2003) suggests the General Inductive Approach is a strategy of inquiry which:

'The general inductive approach provides a convenient and efficient way of analysing qualitative data for many research purposes. The outcomes of analysis may be indistinguishable from those derived from a grounded theory approach. However, unlike grounded theory, there is no emphasis on learning new technical terms such as "open coding" and "axial coding." For this reason, many researchers are likely to find using a general inductive approach more straightforward than some of the traditional approaches to qualitative data analysis.' (Thomas, 2003. Pg. 9)

The general inductive approach captures commonly observed patterns in qualitative data analysis, employing a bottom-up strategy that prioritizes the raw data itself. This general inductive method offers a practical and effective means of analyzing qualitative data for various research objectives. The results of such analysis may closely resemble those produced by a grounded theory approach (Thomas, 2003). The key aim of the inductive approach is to allow research outcomes to surface from the prominent, recurring, or significant themes present in the raw data, free from the limitations of structured methodologies. Thomas also suggested that many important themes can be obscured, reframed, or overlooked due to the preconceptions that arise during data collection and analysis in deductive approaches, such as experimental or hypothesis-driven research.

According to Thomas (2003) the foundational assumptions underlying the use of a general inductive approach are: Data analysis is influenced by both research objectives (deductive) and multiple interpretations of the raw data (inductive), meaning that findings stem from both the researchers' outlined objectives and insights drawn directly from the data. The primary analytical method involves developing categories from the raw data into a framework or model that encapsulates key themes and processes deemed significant by the researcher. Consequently, the findings are shaped by the researchers' own assumptions and experiences. To make the findings actionable, researchers must determine what aspects of the data are more or less significant. The

credibility of findings can be evaluated through various techniques, such as independent replication and comparison with prior research results (Thomas, 2003).

When coding the qualitative data, the following features are developed for each category: Category Label which is a word or short phrase that designates the category which are data excerpts that illustrate the meanings, associations, and perspectives related to the category. The categories may also have connections or relationships with other categories. The category system may be part of a model, theory, or framework (Thomas, 2003). Thus only after key themes emerged from the data would I seek to apply the different theoretical lenses, which best fit the data and kept in accordance with my own philosophical understanding.

Ontology & Epistemology

Philosophical perspectives are often hidden within research, and these perspectives are required to identify paradigms or worldviews as they can considerably influence the research practice according to Creswell (2009). These guiding principles are considered as epistemologies and ontologies, as suggested by Crotty (1998). Worldviews are considered as basic set of beliefs that guide a researchers actions (Guba, 1990). According to Creswell & Poth (2016) these beliefs are general orientations regarding the nature of the world that the researcher holds to be truest, and these paradigms bring about different realities in which the world is socially constructed. However, as Stryker (1967, 2001) argues; when a person defines a situation as real, the situation becomes real, and as such the researcher has to make the effort to see the world from the angle of the participant. Therefore, my own subjective understanding of social reality must be outlined.

The phenomenological perspective states that a subjective reality is the measurement of truth from the individual. As a philosophical approach, ontology concerns itself with assumptions regarding the variety of phenomena in the world which informs the phenomenological perspective. A theory of the very nature of reality, which addresses the nature of what things are (Delanty and Strydom, 2003). Creswell & Poth (2016) suggest that ontological perspectives seek to identify things that actually exist. Ontological paradigms are what bring about different realities or truth (Hitchcock and Hughes, 1989; Morgan, 2022). Paradigms are essentially questions such as: What is existence? What is the nature of existence? The researcher is addressing questions which are inherently ontological.

Social ontology allows for a narrower meaning of the term to be explored as it concerns primarily with the description of what exists within particular fields (Delanty & Strydom, 2003). This concern is not primarily motivated by finding the true essence of what's real. Social ontology

focuses on identifying and naming the parts and processes involved within the system as well as both understanding and describing underlying structural factors which may affect a group or an individuals' experience according to Delanty & Strydom (2003). A social ontological perspective allows for agentic social realities to be investigated within objective and subjective structuring effects within the individuals experiences. Therefore, the phenomenological perspective combined with the social ontology was adopted by the researcher to encompass the subjective social realities as the measurement of the structural factors affecting the individuals' experiences in the research.

Epistemology on the other hand is concerned with the methods deployed in discovering truths. It is a branch of philosophy that has developed into a variety of non-philosophical approaches as suggested by Creswell & Poth (2016). Epistemology addressing possibility, structure, limits, origin, methods and truthfulness of knowledge. Including how knowledge is acquired, validated and applied (Wiersma, 2000). Ultimately, epistemology addresses questions of how phenomena can be made known to the researcher (Wiersma, 2000).

According to Armstrong (2013), positivism and social constructivism are distinct epistemological approaches. Epistemology studies what knowledge is, how we obtain it, and its boundaries. Positivism uses empirical evidence and aims for objectivity; social constructivism relies on social learning and is more subjective. Positivism is often pictured as a machine, whereas social constructivists compare society to a living system.

'Positivism also separates the 'facts' from the meaning people attach to them and the purposes behind their actions. Facts are heavily imbued with the theories and values which permit them to be considered facts in the first place.' (Armstrong, 2013. Page. 31)

A central issue is the positivist assumption that researchers can study social phenomena without influencing the outcome, simply by observing. Question framing steers respondents to think in particular directions and also assumes the question will contribute value to the inquiry. In contrast, social constructivism argues that findings are generated through the interaction between researcher and participants as the investigation unfolds. As the researcher engages with the system to learn about it, new ideas arise, and members of the system develop fresh insights and interpretations they may act upon. Because researchers operate within the system, their ethics and values become critically important, (Armstrong, 2013).

'Constructivism is a confusing term and often used interchangeably with the term constructionism. Social constructionism differs from radical constructivism in that the former focuses on collective generation of meaning, while the latter suggests that the individual mind is active exclusively in the meaning-making activity.' (Lee, 2012. Page. 3)

Social constructivism, argued by Berger & Luckmann (1966) is a theory of knowledge incorporating philosophical constructivism into the social world. The concept adopts Mead's (1925) traditional perspective that an individual's socialization and interaction in a social context creates construct knowledge for one another, in other words, shared meaning and understanding (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). This socialization impacts significantly upon the individual's cognitive development and thus behaviour, (Creswell, 2009; 2016). The way in which the research is approached can have major impacts on the data collection and the choices adopted as well as the methodological processes. The researcher's own ontological and epistemological understanding led to the adoption of what could be considered largely a social constructivist perspective.

Theoretical Approach

Grounded theory, according to Glaser and Strauss (1967) entails the theoretical development of newly discovered data, as opposed to merging new data within existing theories. By doing so the researcher is able to uncover new data unconstrained by existing concepts, and explore new fields unhindered. However, the phenomenon of stalking is rarely grounded in existing theory, therefore I argue that existing concepts are newly uncovered, and therefore cannot be constrained as such. I therefore strongly argue that adopting the general inductive approach, which is similar to grounded theory, as an obvious choice for the research methodology. This would enable me to address and uncover stalking phenomenon in a light never before seen. Firstly, very few fields of enquiry have been discovered in the context of stalking, by prior researchers of the criminological/sociological tradition or some other closely related discipline (Creswell & Clark, 2023).

The existing research on the phenomenon of stalking has focused solely on individual aspects of the victimization such as; persistence, psychological impact, typology, and help-seeking. There has not yet been a line of enquiry into the whole of the journey of stalking victimization in the context of social construction of acknowledgement, help-seeking decisions and outcomes from the victims' perspective. Secondly, as the literature review gathered depth, I began to assess and better understand the finer details of the existing research.

While a substantial literature gap remained in the given contexts, it was nonetheless one which had been analyzed in great and considerable depth in other somewhat relevant contexts. Thus as discussed earlier, while grounded theory was desired, applying this research design outright was simply not possible on its own accord, and therefore was integrated with the general interpretive thematic analysis. According to Beck (2023) is a modern approach to the detailed investigation for the purpose of understanding experience, with research questions focused on the participants

understanding of their experience. As the researcher I fully support the investigation into experience, particularly from a victims' perspective. This is relevant especially within the context of the phenomenon of stalking as each experience is individual. Ultimately, I was able to adopt a grounded theory approach and the General Interpretive Analysis methodology for a fluid and multi-dimensional approach to the strategy of enquiry, given that literature had aided my understanding of the stalking phenomenon. I adopted an inductive approach to the research design as this was central to the development of data whereby themes would emerge from the resulting data using these two approaches and could then be compared with existing theories.

A literature review was performed prior to the data collection. This literature would then be used to either support or refute the theoretical propositions of victimization from the data. While a significant literature review had been conducted to submit a proposal to the ethics committee as part of my PhD, the literature review was continually built upon throughout the research. In an attempt to adhere to inductive inquiry, it was decided that the theoretical inquiry, would be duly applied before the final stage of analysis, once the resulting data had occurred and had been presented in the findings. This choice was made all the more difficult given that a wide range of data had been uncovered which spanned beyond the possibility of mere stalking analysis alone, penetrating into the very lives of the interviewees in a number of insightful ways. These findings have been considered from the standpoint of psychological theories of crime and victimization, rational choice, social learning, and social reaction to immerse the investigation with the data to the journey a victim experiences when being stalked. Deep-rooted issues related to marginalization, social exclusion, stereotypes, misconceptions, labelling, and feelings of self-worth and self-esteem were all prevalent throughout the data. Yet no one theory adequately covered or accounted for such diverse findings.

Therefore, given that the psychological theories in this enquiry deal primarily with individuals' reaction to the subjective interpretations of particular events or responses, it proved the ideal lens' to apply. The sheer adaptability of these theories to a variety of settings within this type of victimization gives the combined theories of a victims' journey strength which other considered theories duly lacked when considered in isolation. While some of those other theories also lacked contextual relevance regarding the study of stalking victimization and help-seeking decisions, for example Gottfredson & Hirsch's (1990) Theory of Self-Control, which perpetuates victim blame. In contrast, Tittle's (1995) Control Balance Theory proved remarkably relevant in victim's perceptions of the stalker type and motivations and has demonstrated such versatility, exploring a multitude of issues and topics on crime victimization. Furthermore, while other theories might have remained somewhat outdated, Control Balance Theory has continued to have been updated by Fox & Noble

(2014) in an effort to both refine its application and answer critiques in relation to stalking, which points out why exploring Control balance theory was favored over other theories as a theoretical lens.

Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977) addresses cognitive biases in relation to crime victimization. However, this theory initially also lacked the contextual relevance to stalking. Updated by Fox, Noble and Akers (2011) to align with the contextual reference of stalking, this theory, and particularly cognitive biases that normalize or even minimize a stalking experience. Although this updated version by Fox and colleagues focused solely on a victims' vulnerability of being stalked, the theory can be refined and applied to understand a victims' perception in acknowledgment of their own victimization and within the social attitudes that victims experienced when disclosing their victimization, which was found to be particularly relevant to this study.

The theory of social reaction as described by Ullman (2010) stated that a negative disclosure responses add to the psychological distress for the victim disclosing. In contrast Ullman also proposed that a positive social reaction can lessen the distress a victim experiences through the validation of their victimization, and this was explored in the data. Although this theory lacked contextual reference to stalking victimization, it was found to provide valuable insights in respect to the stalking victims' perceptions of others reactions to their victimization.

Furthermore, the Focal Concerns Theory originated by Steffensmeier and colleagues (1993, 1998) proposed that criminal justice representatives take 3 factors into consideration when deciding case processing, and these decisions are largely influenced by cognitive biases arising from previous experience of offenders. Furthermore, Brady and Reynolds (2024) extended the FCT to stalking victims' criminal justice help-seeking decision making. This research will be exploring the FCT in the lens of victim decision making against cognitive biases of the Social Learning theory to determine whether seriousness of offence and community protection rather than a victims' perception of the stalking plays a role in reporting to formal sources.

Whereas, the Theory of Rational Choice Perspective by Gottfredson and Gottfredson (1998) explored decisions made by both victims and perpetrators. This theory was updated to apply to the crime of stalking by Reynolds (2010) exploring the factors of traditional and cyberstalking that may or may not influence a victims decisions to seek-help. This application found that seriousness of offence and victim/offender relationship rather than typology of the stalker were the factors impacting a victims' decision to report the stalking to police. This research will be testing these 3 factors.

This research study has chosen to test multiple theories in order to gain a wider understanding of stalking victimization and the complex journey an individual undertakes when navigating this crime. Therefore, more than one line of enquiry must be made, compared to a singular theory that may not cover the intricacies of the nuances of stalking victimization and help-seeking. Qualitative studies such as this can take into account a wide range of variables from multiple sources, without significantly compromising on results according to Agnew (2013). Therefore, in order to align with the research aims, purpose and the positionality of the researcher, multiple theories have been chosen to compare, and test in order to gain an understanding of the internal perspectives and external influences of the victims' journey through the stalking experience, from initial acknowledgment and help-seeking through to the stalking outcome.

Methods

Methods are the particular procedures deployed within a strategy of a research inquiry for assisting the researcher in gathering data. Although there is the existence of a large variation of methods, the researcher will attempt to apply those most suited to the chosen research design, (Creswell, 1998, 2016; Creswell & Clark, 2023). Qualitative research as in any research approach, influences the strategy of the inquiry and therefore influences the methods deployed, (Jensen & Jankowski, 1991). Qualitative research, described in broad terms by Walia (2015), refers to research that yields findings not obtained through statistical methods or other quantification techniques. It is a contextual practice that positions the observer within their environment. This type of research encompasses a range of interpretive, practical activities that reveal the meanings embedded in the world. These activities transform these meanings into various forms of representation, including interviews and discussions. At its core, qualitative research employs an interpretive, naturalistic perspective, where researchers strive to understand and interpret phenomena based on the meanings that individuals attribute to them (Walia, 2015).

The methods adopted can also impose restrictions and or dictate which methods are available and which are not available (Yin, 2003). In this particular investigation, the methods faced challenges due to the sensitive nature of the subject matter: the experience of stalking victimization. Identifying individuals who have experienced, or are currently experiencing, such victimization often proves to be difficult, as these individuals may be reluctant to share their experiences. Additionally, even when they do choose to disclose their situations, many are hesitant to revisit the emotional trauma associated with their victimization.

As a result of the above considerations, research techniques that provide a sense of anonymity and confidentiality became essential, and guided the choice of qualitative methods employed. Consequently, the study adopted an online cross-sectional survey with open questions alongside face-to-face interviews as the primary methods for data collection. These approaches not only ensured privacy for the participants, but also promoted a more open dialogue about their experiences, thereby facilitating a more comprehensive understanding of stalking victimization.

Role of the Researcher

Social constructivism, (Berger & Luckmann, 1966), is a theory of knowledge that weaves together philosophical constructivism with the intricacies of the social sphere. Influenced by Mead (1925), which posits that an individual's socialization and interactions within their social environment are instrumental in creating shared knowledge and meanings. According to Berger and Luckmann, this process of socialization is essential for shaping an individual's cognitive development, influencing their perceptions, and ultimately guiding their behaviour (Creswell, 2009; Lee, 2012).

Moreover, the notion and practice of reflexivity within qualitative research can be traced, in part, to the foundational principles of social constructivism, which emphasize the subjective nature of social reality (Cunliffe, 2011). This perspective recognizes that our social realities are constructed through interactions and that language plays a pivotal role in framing our understanding of the world. Language not only shapes our worldview but also paradoxically limits and enhances our capacity for comprehension, influencing how we represent these understandings.

Reflexivity serves to challenge these representations (Cunliffe, 2003). It encourages researchers to critically examine the beliefs that competent observers can report on their observations of the social world, including the experiences of others. By questioning this assumption, reflexivity opens up a space for deeper inquiry into how our interpretations are influenced by our social context and personal experiences, thereby enriching the understanding of the complex nature of social realities.

In relation to the study, the social constructivism positionality enabled myself to listen and interpret participant narratives about the phenomenon of stalking. Including their experience in relation to their acknowledgement and the responses they received when disclosing their victimization. The social construction of victimization and stalking is bound in wider social and cultural concepts of crime, and impacts the sharing, negotiating, outcomes and meaning of the experience. However this required regular reflexivity to ensure that I was interpreting these experiences through the lens of the participant and not through my own social constructs.

Reflexivity is a critical concept that involves a thorough self-examination of one's own beliefs, judgments, and practices throughout the research process. It emphasizes the importance of understanding how these personal elements may shape and influence the research outcomes (Subramani, 2019). While positionality pertains to our knowledge and beliefs, which is essentially our standpoint in relation to the research subject, reflexivity takes it a step further. It concerns how we actively engage with and apply this self-awareness in our research activities. By reflecting on our biases and perspectives, we can better comprehend how they impact our interpretations and interactions within the research context, ultimately leading to more rigorous and ethical inquiry (Subramani, 2019).

Additionally, reflexivity as a concept and as a practice, it is widely recognized within social science research as researchers have a vital role in any type of research (Subramani, 2019). This role includes the creation of research instruments, data collection and analysis which all inform the scientific enquiry. The data is mediated through the human instrument, compared to inventories found in quantitative studies according to (Denzin & Lincoln, 2003). Therefore, it is of the utmost importance that a researcher reflects upon their own position, including biases and assumptions that inform their decision making throughout the process of conducting the research analysis and presenting results.

Upon reflecting throughout this research process, the positionality of myself as the researcher mentioned previously, falls within the social constructivist paradigm. As the researcher I must acknowledge my own stalking victimization and work within the field of supporting victims of stalking with the Action Against Stalking charity. Both of these roles within the field of stalking victimization have highlighted the need and desire in me to inform academia, and stakeholders about the importance of victims' perceptions, rather than my own constructs, in relation to help-seeking decisions and the implications of such decisions on the stalking outcome. To understand why the phenomenon of stalking is under-disclosed by victims to informal and formal sources.

The desire has always been to try to understand where the factors of help-seeking decisions situate in relation to stalking disclosures and outcomes through this exploratory research, and through the social constructs of the participants. Therefore the qualitative paradigm of sensibility orientation as outlined by (Braun and Clarke, 2013) was used in the creation of the research questions for both the survey and interviews. As the researcher I aimed to step out of the role of a stalking victim advocate to reflect on the shared values, relevant aspects of the self, prior experiences, potential bias and assumptions that may influence the research. Putting these aspects aside so that the research and analysis was not automatically shaped by such assumptions and

experience, taking an interest in the participants meaning over and above causal effect was of utmost importance.

As the researcher, I have aimed to focus solely on the purpose of the study, with the intent to understand the experience as a journey for victims of this crime directly from their experiences. During the creation of the research questions for the survey and face to face interviews, I reflected regularly on the content validity applicable to the survey and interview topics to ensure my own social constructs did not influence the research. During the process of analyzing results, I used grounded theory focused-coding, with the general inductive thematic analysis approach in order to stay on the investigative topic whilst coding and theme generating in the qualitative analysis, in order to compare against the relevant theories in each category. It is for this purpose that the vast majority of the survey was analyzed qualitatively, following the general inductive analysis procedures, allowing the researcher to remain as impartial as possible to the results (Davies and Fisher, 2018).

Online Survey data collection

A cross-sectional, web-based survey design was selected to effectively capture the empirical patterns present in the data collection and analysis. This approach also allows for the extraction of rich, qualitative insights through a social interpretivist lens, focusing on the experiences of victims. Given the nature of this research, which aimed to explore the entire journey of victims, from their initial acknowledgment of the stalking to the final outcomes, it was crucial to formulate the research questions with precision. The goal was to obtain a clear and representative sample of stalking victims, ensuring their experiences and perceptions directly addressed the research questions. Careful consideration was given to avoid overwhelming participants, thereby preventing participation fatigue and encouraging meaningful engagement throughout the study.

As data collection was reliant on previous stalking victims' experiences, a hypothesis was not proposed. Rather, an exploration was conducted using inductive reasoning on the data generated within the themes, patterns and theoretical lenses that emerged through the qualitative aspects of the research. The exploratory approach was determined as the best approach for the decision to include open questions in sequential order to the forced choice questions, which is supported by previous research on open-ended questions (Albudaiwi, 2017). Albudaiwi proposed the use of open questions allows the respondents to express opinions that the researcher may not have expected, and would not have gathered with the use of solely fixed or force choice questions.

The cross-sectional survey design was also the logical choice over a panel design. Cross-sectional survey designs gather data from a single point in time. Gathering data at a single point in time potentially avoids attrition. Whereas, with longitudinal research, participants may drop out at later stages, as suggested by Ruel et al (2019). Furthermore, a panel survey design in which the units of observation are interviewed on several occasions to yield the longitudinal data, are based on the objective of hypothesis testing, (Pforr and Schröder, 2016). Therefore it was determined the cross-sectional survey design the best solution to attain the relevant data for this study. The survey questionnaire function is to record participant attitudes, values and beliefs (Creswell, 2009). Creswell (1998) also pointed out that the key aims of a survey is to make the questions attractive to the respondents, to ensure that accurate answers are given and that any misunderstandings are potentially eliminated.

However, as Ruel (2016) highlights, one major limit to a web-based survey design is that there may be potential respondents that do not have internet access, omitting the potential to collect further useful data. Furthermore, there is a possibility of deception with online survey designs, where a participant may willfully fabricate their victimization. To mitigate potential fabrication of responses, the researcher screened the data for inconsistent responses. This approach is easier to do with the open-question responses, as you can check that the answers are coherent, relevant and written in the relevant language and remove at the data cleaning stage of detection. The researcher also made the decision to not gather demographic details in the survey element of the research, as these details were not under investigation. Despite these potential limitations, the decision was made that the benefits of reaching victims of stalking that may not have disclosed their experience outweighed the possibility of not reaching all potential participants.

A Pilot study of the survey questions was conducted on the survey using the Question Pro web-based software. 20 Participants were required for the survey pilot- test. As stated by Ruel et al (2016); 12-50 respondents are required for a suitable test. Analysis of the pilot test consisted of a critical examination of the survey instruments for the face and content validity, by checking open questions were relevant to the concept being observed, and response latency, which was 4 minutes, reducing any potential of participation fatigue which is commonly found within larger surveys, (Ruel et al, 2016). The pilot test of the survey questions yielding the following changes:

1. For inclusion purposes, the original wording 'Other' Category in both victim gender and stalker gender was changed to 'Any other recognized gender'.
2. For inclusion purposes, the original wording 'Other' Category in both victim gender and stalker gender was changed to 'Any other recognized gender'.

3. Skip Logic was corrected at question 19 to remove the No disclosure categories for Q16 & Q17 of the survey, after the pilot-test survey was conducted.

Once the above listed changes were highlighted from the pilot study, the survey design was amended and went live to gather the data used in the analysis, the pilot study data was not carried over into the analysis, as its purpose was used solely to test the survey instrument for its efficacy. As Ruel et al (2019) proposed, the benefits of a survey are versatility, relatively low costs to execute, and popular among social and criminology researchers because the data extrapolated is predominantly generalizable to the population in many fields of research. Furthermore, the data is reflective of the population of stalking victims through the appropriate sampling. (See Appendix 2a for survey questions)

Interview data collection

Face-to-face interviews are a type of structured interview carried out by trained professionals who adhere to a specific interview protocols (Jennings, 2005). These interviews can take place in various environments (Jennings, 2005). One of the primary advantages of face-to-face interviews is the ability to manage the interaction effectively (Jennings, 2005). Such as, interviewers can ensure that the intended participant is the one responding, which helps maintain the integrity of the data collected. Additionally, the format allows for the exploration of complex questions that may require clarification, enabling interviewers to use techniques to gather more in-depth information (Jennings, 2005).

Structured interviews are interviews which provide specific questions which have a limited range of answers. These questions and the range of answers are known in advance to the researcher as defined by (Creswell, 1998, 2016). These types of questions list possible answers so that the respondent simply answers with the appropriate reply in each case, (Creswell, 2009). As Yin (2003) pointed out, there is little freedom for flexibility in these types of questions. Although this approach is advantageous for ease of quantifying and comparing data, the lack of flexibility and richness of data makes it one which is preferable for quantitative research rather than qualitative research (Creswell, 2009, 2016). This approach was ultimately rejected as unsuitable for this study since it would not allow the participants to present subjective data for myself to record, in effect to discover emergent themes regarding the phenomena under study.

Whereas, unstructured interviews, as defined by Wimmer and Dominick (1997) are informal interviews whereby a topic of interest may be put forward for discussion. This approach allows the interviewer to be free to explore the topics of interest and to phrase the questions as they think best

(Creswell, 2009). Therefore, the richness of the data is dependent upon the interviewer. However, a disadvantage of unstructured interview techniques is that the abundance of information collected needs to be filtered and made readable. This process is arduous and can result in the researchers own subjective experience influencing the data as certain data could be given priority over other data. Thus, it was decided that adopting a total unstructured interview approach would provide too much data, much of which would be considered irrelevant and somewhat unnecessary. Therefore, I determined that a semi-structured interview method for the discussion was required, particularly given the broad spectrum of topics under investigation in this study.

The interview structure can consist of two basic types, personal interviews, and group interviews. Personal interviews are on a one-to-one basis and the researcher would usually use a small sample according to Creswell (1998). This type of structure focuses on the use of open-ended questions which allow the respondent to answer freely and the questions are not therefore standardized (Creswell, 1998, 2009). Furthermore, personal interviews are a suitable way to deal with sensitive or taboo topics as suggested by Wimmer and Dominick (1997). Whereas, the conversation in a focus group can be either structured or unstructured but either way is often guided interviewer whilst the respondents discuss and express opinions with each other, according to Wimmer and Dominick (1997). However, there are limitations to the focus group as suggested by Winner and Dominick; group interviewing can result in the potential influence of one or two respondents projected onto other members of the group, as well as the pressure to conform, and important to this study; participants may simply not wish to discuss sensitive material within a group setting. For these reasons I aimed to deployed one-to-one personal interviews in order to allow informants to speak freely, unconstrained by the above mentioned group dynamics.

Ultimately, face-to-face semi-structured interviews were chosen as the form of qualitative data gathering for this exploration following the survey questionnaire application. Interviews although a time-consuming process involving negotiating access, making contact, conducting the interview, and transcribing, analyzing and writing up the data (Alsaawi, 2014), this approach provided an opportunity to expand on the survey data that had been gathered to gain further meaningful insight into victims' experiences, where further inquiry was needed.

The researcher chose to give the survey data more context and depth with the use of interviews to fully understand the nuances of the journey a victim experiences with acknowledgement, help-seeking decisions, and stalking outcomes. This exploration required data from participants that have and have not disclosed their experience. Although the data can be anonymized in the face to face context, it cannot be completely confidential. Furthermore, a benefit of the use of open-ended

questions in an interview, in relation to this particular topic provides a way for people to communicate an experience that is sensitive, and potentially traumatizing. The face to face interviews did allow an opportunity for deeper explorations of the topics in question (Alsaawi, 2014).

The social constructivist approach to the face-to-face interviews in qualitative research as stated by Braun and Clarke (2013):

‘...validates meaning, views, perspectives, experiences and practices expression in the data’, (Braun and Clarke, 2013, pg.21)

Suggesting the interpretations of the participants experiences are priority in the research analysis. In other words, how a victim constructs meaning from their experience. This approach to the design and analysis of the face to face interviews support the researchers’ philosophical viewpoint that qualitative research is concerned with words rather than a critical approach. As Baum and Clark (2013) proposed, a critical approach concerns itself with the shape of language held within societal realities and how this language creates the participant’s world of reality, rather than a reflection of reality in a sociocultural context. The research as exploratory, aimed at uncovering the nuances of the participants stalking experience; perceptions of acknowledgment, decision making, and responses (if help-seeking was employed), and to understand if disclosing or not has any relationship with the outcome of the stalking experience.

Furthermore, it must be acknowledged that inadequate construction of interviews could possibly lead to an interview taking place where little, none, or irrelevant information is collected. The researcher wants to get the informant to be at ease and openly speak in depth about that which is being studied in a presentable and understanding manner, (Creswell, 1998). To understand how the questions were constructed it is first necessary to briefly discuss the main examples of interviews that are available for use. These are structured, semi-structured, and unstructured interviews. It was important when constructing the questions that I did not directly lead a participant or hinder their answer, rather I attempted to address the issues of interest while still being sensitive to the participants’ own characteristics and experience as suggested by Hancock and Algozzine (2006). Therefore, the use of a semi-structured interview technique was deemed more suitable for this particular study. This approach allowed for the orderly organization of the topics under study and ensured that the discussion progressed toward these issues without compromising interviewees’ responses or constraining participants. The flexibility of the semi-structure enabled the researcher to respond to any emerging themes which may have needed further inquiry.

In the normal question-response mode the researcher imposed structures in three distinct ways as suggested by (Bauer, 1996). The researcher chose the themes, arranged the questions, and also

selected the wording. Ultimately, Bauer suggested that whoever controls the questions controls the situation. This was the approach I used in order to allow for rich context from the participant, while staying within the parameters of the topics under investigation where a semi-structured interview technique constructed the setting which both encouraged and stimulated the participant to tell stories about significant events in their life with their social context.

Overall the above method allowed the participants to speak about their experience in an open and subjective manner. This allowed them to reflect upon their perceptions, prior decisions of disclosing and the responses they received, how these reflected in further help-seeking decisions and the outcomes of their stalking experience. While the topic was introduced by myself, and the conversation organized with the use of the semi-structured interview, it was very much the participant that took the lead in the discussions, to which I merely responded or enquired further when necessary.

One-to-one interviews were scheduled with consenting participants. Participants had to contact myself to register their interest, and once the Consent form was signed and received the Interview was scheduled. Interviews were arranged to take place online via Microsoft teams, at the participants preferred time. The interviews lasted anywhere from 30 minutes to approximately an hour, averaging 47 minutes. Interviews were recorded via Microsoft Teams transcribing application. (See Appendix 2b for Interview questions).

Sampling and Participants

Selecting a study sample is a crucial phase in the research process, as it is often impractical, inefficient, or even unethical to examine entire populations (Marshall, 1996). The primary goal of all quantitative sampling techniques is to obtain a sample that accurately represents the broader population under study. This allows researchers to extend their findings from the sample back to the population as a whole, thereby ensuring that the conclusions drawn are valid and applicable (Marshall, 1996).

The choice of sampling method is largely determined by the specific objectives of the study. For instance, while more rigorous sampling techniques, such as random sampling, are typically preferred for their reliability, there are instances where less stringent methods, like a convenience sampling may be utilized (Marshall, 1996). However, it's important to note that alternative approaches do not inherently ensure that the sample will be representative of the population, which can affect the validity of the research outcomes. Therefore, careful consideration must be given to the sampling strategy employed, as it directly impacts the integrity and applicability of the research findings. A

convenience sample was the chosen target sample for the survey and interviews, as respondents were required to have experienced stalking in order to be able to explore stalking victimization.

Effective sampling necessitates prior understanding of the target population, especially when engaging with hard-to-reach groups (Raifman et al, 2022), like victims of stalking. Raifman and colleagues suggested that forming partnerships with community organizations, such as the relevant charities involved in crime victimization can enhance convenience sampling and ultimately improve the research quality for this vulnerable population. Typical methods for sampling these groups often involve non-probability approaches, such as convenience sampling. Individuals from hard-to-reach, hidden, and vulnerable populations frequently experience increased social, psychological, and physical risks when identified with a specific social group, leading to greater reluctance in disclosing their identities to researchers (Ellard-Gray et al, 2015). Consequently, Ellard-Gray et al (2015) noted that sensitive research topics can further complicate efforts to engage these already elusive populations, as potential participants may be more hesitant to take part.

To address these sampling challenges from the outset of study design, researchers should refine sampling parameters and establish eligibility criteria for participants. To enhance recruitment success, it is crucial to ensure that the recruitment process is inclusive of everyone who meets the sampling criteria (Ellard-Gray et al., 2015). Furthermore, managing research materials beyond just recruitment announcements is essential. This includes careful attention to consent forms and all documented communications with participants (Ellard-Gray et al., 2015).

While qualitative design is typically associated with collecting data from small samples, an appropriate sample size 'parameters' based on the research strategy and techniques applied is recommended, (Marshall, 1996). Nevertheless, if the sample size of the study is small enough to manage and the data collected, and large enough to provide a richly textured understanding of the experience under investigation then the sample size is often viewed as adequate (Sandelowski, 1995).

Saturation is generally understood as having reached a point of satisfactory data collection. It is an established concept in sampling for qualitative research and it has long dominated the sampling process. Saturation of information occurs when the researcher reaches a point in the study where he or she begins to hear the same information being reported and therefore feels that they can no longer learn anything new, according to Marshall (1996) data saturation can be seen as a process whereby,

‘The number of required participants usually becomes obvious as the study progresses, as new categories, themes or explanations stop emerging from the data’ (Marshall, 1996, p. 523).

The sample size was calculated using an online sample size calculator (<https://www.calculator.net/sample-size-calculator.html>) which computes the minimum number of necessary sample sizes to meet the desired statistical constraints. (No information was acquired for Northern Ireland as stalking legislation was introduced 2022 and there was not yet data available at the time the survey was conducted.) Therefore, the research sample size for the Online Survey was calculated using the Crime and justice surveys conducted in Scotland, England and Wales in 2019/2021 as follows: 7197 population of stalking victims rounded up to 7200.5% margin of error, 95% confidence level and 50% sample portion. Sample size minimum 280 and maximum 365 participants were therefore required. The sample size was calculated originally with the statistical regression model in mind, however, once the decision to make the analysis qualitative rather than quantitative was made, the researcher retained the sample size calculation for the qualitative analysis.

Participants were recruited for the survey element of this research online via various social media platforms: Facebook Pages and groups, Twitter, LinkedIn, The charity Action Against Stalking’s newsletter and social media pages, Paladin, Women’s Aid in Scotland, Abused Men in Scotland and MenKind.

Survey respondents Gender Demographics

Participant gender	Male	Female	Other Identified Gender	More than 1 person (any gender)	Unknown
N=280	57	219	4		
Stalker Gender N=280	201	57	3	16	3

Gender, ethnicity, and social-class or location were by no means considered as restricting criteria to participating in the study sample. The Inclusion criteria consisted of a minimum of 18 years of age to participate in the study. The respondents were qualified for inclusion automatically after consenting, and the first two questions which qualified them as individuals who have experienced stalking. The inclusion and exclusion criteria was selected to ensure participation is ethical according to the University of The West of Scotland Ethics requirements.

No other demographic details were acquired for the survey, as I wanted to keep the survey as close as possible to the research explorations under investigation. I was also mindful as to not make

the survey to lengthy, in order to avoid participant fatigue. However, this decision was also found after the data was acquired to be a limitation which will be discussed further in the Chapter 6 limitation section.

Initially, the survey was the sole method of data collection envisioned for the study, and it was the first step undertaken in the research process. However, after gathering the initial data and conducting a pilot analysis, it became clear that the study required additional context and insights from participants to thoroughly investigate the research questions at hand. For example, in the section of the survey interview where participants indicated the stalking was still occurring, the open question was asked 'Can you tell me in your own words why you believe these unwanted contacts and behaviours are still occurring?' The participants expressed why they believed this was the case, however in some instances, the answers needed more information, available only when in an interview setting. This is exemplified by one female survey participant who answered this question 'Council and police don't want to help'. Whereas in the interviews, the researcher was able to extract more information by asking the female participant to expand on why she felt the courts were the reason she felt the stalking was still continuing, which can be seen in the following quote; 'After my case finished, there was then an appeal that he won and I'm still trying to get information about that from the courts and the stalking behaviour started again after that.' Recognizing this need when analyzing the survey data, the researcher determined that conducting interviews would be the most effective approach to enrich the study. By incorporating interviews, the researcher could gain deeper insights into the participants' experiences, thereby enhancing the overall findings of the research. This qualitative method not only provided a richer context but also facilitated a more nuanced exploration of existing theories in relation to the participants' perceptions. Ultimately, the decision to include interviews allowed for a more comprehensive understanding of the research questions, leading to stronger and more compelling conclusions.

The research sample size for the face-to-face interviews was informed from research by (Baum and Clarke, 2013). Baum and Clarke suggested when investigating qualitative experience, a small to moderate sample, approximately, 5-20 participants should be acquired. The research took the decision that because the interviews were conducted in addition to the survey to give additional depth and meaning that 20 Interviews with victims of stalking were sufficient to remain focused on the experiences and convincingly demonstrate patterns in the data in relation to the research questions.

Participants for the face-to-face interviews were recruited via the Action Against Stalking Charities' social media platforms, and newsletter, and also where participants from the survey had

contacted the researcher and indicated a desire to participate in the interviews. The advantage of convenience sampling is its efficiency in accessing hard-to-reach populations when the researcher has a good understanding of the target group. Making use of partnerships with community organizations, such as charities involved in crime victimization, can facilitate access to stalking victims and, in turn, improve the quality of the data collected (Raifman et al, 2022). In practice, these groups are often difficult to sample using probability methods, so leveraging existing networks can yield practical and timely insights. However, a key disadvantage is the potential for bias. For example, recruiting through organizational networks may produce a positivity or social desirability bias, as participants might tailor their responses to please researcher or align with perceived expectations, which can undermine representativeness. However, the researcher made the decision that collaborating with the community organizations (e.g., Action Against Stalking) can facilitate ethical and safer access to stalking victims, potentially enhancing data quality by situating research within a trusted network.

Therefore, participants were initially invited via email to confirm their desire to participate, and sent out the participation Information and consent via email before the formal interviews were arranged and conducted, keeping in line with The University of The West of Scotland Ethics requirements.

Interview Respondent demographics:

Participant Nationality & Gender N=20 (%)	British Count (%)	Scottish Count (%)	British/ Australian Count (%)	New Zealand Count (%)	British/ Indian Count (%)	British/ Canadian Count (%)
Male, N=3 (15%)		2 (67)			1 (33)	
Female, N=17 (85%)	7 (41)	7 (41)	1 (6)	1 (6)		1 (6)

Participants	Minimum Age	Mean Age	Maximum Age	Std. Deviation
N=20	25	43	65	12.81

Interview- Stalker Demographics:

Stalkers	Minimum Age	Mean Age	Maximum Age	Std. Deviation
N=20	28	40	55	8.076

Stalker Gender	Male	Female	Other Identified Gender	More than 1 stalker (any gender)
N=20	14	4	0	2

Data Analysis

While personal traits and biases were found to play a substantial role in determining the probability of each individual's responses or dispositions towards perceptions and help-seeking, more often than not these personal traits heightened the researchers coping probability and were only a small part of the individual's nature as whole. Thus, such traits often remained dormant for the most part, particularly when the individual in question remained situated within a stable social and settled environment. Yet individual traits were found to be sensitive to change or certain circumstances or situations in which the researcher may find themselves, particularly when under threat and immersed in the responses received after disclosing the victimization. These events in themselves, if viewed negatively, often fostered internalized feeling of negative emotions and stress, therefore regular reflection occurred to overcome any internal biases or negative reactions to the survey and interview data.

The importance of effectively organizing data became a crucial aspect to the data analysis. One of the main advantages of using a database is that raw data is available for independent review and with ease according to (Yin, 2003). The use of a database allows the data to be tracked and organized. Data sources can include notes, key documents, narratives, photographs, as well as audio/video files. The researcher used the key survey response document generated in excel from the question Pro-software, and the interview transcripts word documents that were generated from Microsoft Teams. Both the survey and interview documents were cleaned and then transferred to a word document for analysis.

However, Computer Aided Qualitative Data Analysis Software (CAQDAS) provides unlimited 'bins' for data to be collected and then organized. Such programs facilitate the recording of source detail, such as time, date, storage, as well as search capabilities as suggested by (Wickham & Woods, 2005). Yin (2003) suggests several techniques when analyzing data; pattern matching, logic models, explanation building, time-series analysis, cross-case synthesis, and linking data to propositions. Yin highlights the importance of returning to any propositions used, throughout the analysis phase, as this allows the researcher to remain focused; explore rival propositions in an attempt to provide alternate explanations, accepting or rejecting propositions and rival propositions. The researcher

performed the techniques of pattern matching and cross-case synthesis and linking data within the word document, and therefore CAQDAS was not required.

Attempting to shed light on any relationships within a victims' acknowledgment, help-seeking decisions, disclosure responses and outcomes of their stalking experience, the researcher had to examine the data and identify emerging themes from both the survey and interviews. This was particularly important to this study as it allowed myself to identify what factors emerged in a victims' acknowledgment, themes in help-seeking decisions and responses, and the victims' perceptions of the relationship of these elements to the stalking outcome, both in the survey data and the interview data. To simply present material without listening to participants and developing those emerging themes, the stalking journey could not be presented in any significant way.

This was in keeping with the interpretive paradigm suited to privileging the participants' voice. To preserve the anonymity of participants, particularly when presenting all verbatim excerpts, four-digit codes were used throughout, and the survey software auto-generated codes were used and then changed to pseudo names in the findings section (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005). As I wanted to explore new ideas about stalking victimization, while being realistic and acknowledging that discovery of completely new fields as perhaps unreasonable, effort was made to retain as many elements of the General Inductive Analysis approach as possible.

Interview and survey transcriptions were carried out in a multi-stage data analysis process. Initially, a conventional content analysis phase was undertaken by immersing oneself in the data which allowed for conceptual themes and sub-themes to be identified, as suggested by Creswell (2009), this stage was repeated several times until the researcher identified the necessary conceptual themes and sub-themes. A direct content analysis phase was then undertaken where the overarching themes were interpreted in light of the research questions. Therefore, the data analysis allowed emerging patterns and recurring themes to be built from the bottom up. A theoretical lens was then applied in relation to those identified themes and sub-themes in order to make sense of the data in a meaningful way (Creswell, 2009). This was done in order to retain independence, yet while still acknowledging existing research, from previous to contemporary stalking and crime literature and theories, to facilitate new concepts and ideas emerging from the data. To aid this process, the transcripts were coded for each participant for both the survey and interview methods. The below figure is an extract of the multi-stage analysis of theme and sub-theme identification. This stage occurred by repeating the analysis multiple times, and before the final stages of data organization into the overarching themes, and before the theoretical lens was applied.

Theme	Sub-theme	Quote	Explanation/ meaning	
Minimized/ Invalidated The experience	Disbelief	3658 'Or you put another word on it and change it to something else. Or when it comes to the authorities, they don't even want to address that because it's like.' 'We know things are happening, but we don't want to deal with this because then we're going to have to deal with other issues and those are the issues usually involve failures from the authorities when they've been involved. So it's a whole cycle of.' 'Just understanding that horror that was happening.'	The responses victims received after disclosing made them feel dismissed, misunderstood the fear and experience minimized, disbelieved and unsafe	
	Minimized	4839 - 'Oh, just get over it. It's just a bit of banter. You should be flattered. So I made myself come into work. I wish I hadn't. His behaviour escalated even more. He would make a point of coming over and talking to my colleague at the end of my desk.....' '.....People outside of the area treated me like I was a liar and people in the area treated me like what's your problem? Get over it.'		
	Unhelpful Escalated stalking	3499 - 'When they thought it was funny and told me to ignore it, it really minimized the danger I felt. I had no idea what this guy would do and it really shook me, so it didn't help. Once they started to realise then that was better. They took pictures and called the police.' 108348733 - 'Frustrated, no one takes the threats and behaviors seriously' 108249175 - 'Dismissive. Made excuses for the behaviour.' 108043147 - 'Told me to stay offline' 107597874 - 'They didn't believe me and blamed me for her behaviour' 107261337 - 'They were horrific, didn't believe me because the neighbors grouped together' 105956532 - Angry, I felt angry because police did not take the situation seriously, I thought they were supposed to keep people safe		Unhelpful advice from police, family & friends minimized & romanticized the experience
	Victim-blame	105774979 - Horrible, cops aren't interested at all, I feel unsafe as I don't know what this dude is going to do. 104469586 - Didn't feel taken seriously because it was cyber stalking; felt isolated as no one understood the long term impact on me, most people were scared to explore it as it was either their worst nightmare or they didn't see it having an impact		Victim-blamed Cyber stalking isolated

Figure 2.

Furthermore, in respect to the literature review conducted, which also provided a substantial amount of data, the decision had to be made whether or not to use Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software (CAQDAS). There have been a number of programs introduced which are more specific to assisting qualitative based research. One of the more popular programs is Nvivo, as suggested by Rodik and Primorac (2015). Yet while this field is gradually becoming better established, there remains a degree of skepticism. Rodik and Primorac suggested that much of the skepticism relates to the overall positivistic epistemological positions found in the creation of such software.

'computing technology assumes a positivistic approach to the natural world that sees it as being composed of objects that humans can study, understand and manipulate', but given that 'the goal of qualitative researchers is to try and see things from the perspective of the human actors' there is concerns as to the software architecture will interfere with the qualitative research process and will result in the loss of shades of meaning and interpretation that qualitative data bring'. (Roberts and Wilson, 2002. pg.5-6)

Additionally, there is danger that computers have come to be the main mediator between the interaction which occurs between the researcher and the qualitative data itself as suggested by Bringer et al (2006). I therefore decided that I would not use Nvivo or any similar software. Instead the computer itself would prove an adequate storage device in which a storage system could be setup through the use of folders in a password protected One Drive. This would simplify the process, allow for easy and trackable amendments. In addition, given that the research I was undertaking was

particularly sensitive, due to the nature of that which was being discussed, a program which was unique and only accessible to myself would prove more difficult for someone else to negotiate their way around, should the computer be hacked, stolen, or lost.

The inductive analysis of qualitative data follows procedures such as: Preparation of Raw Data Files: Standardize raw data files in a uniform format (e.g., font size, margins, highlighting questions or interviewer comments). Print and/or back up each raw data file (e.g., each interview). Close Reading of Text: After preparation, the raw text should be read thoroughly, enabling the researcher to become familiar with the content and identify emerging themes. Creation of Categories: The researcher identifies and defines categories or themes, with general categories likely derived from the research aims and specific categories emerging from repeated readings of the raw data. Overlapping Coding and Un-coded Text: Unlike quantitative coding, qualitative coding allows for one segment of text to be assigned to multiple categories, and a significant portion of the text may remain un-coded if it is deemed irrelevant to the research objectives. Ongoing Revision and Refinement of the Category System: Within each category, researchers should explore subtopics, including differing viewpoints and new insights. Appropriate quotes would be selected to convey the core essence of each category, and similar categories may be merged under a broader category (Thomas, 2003).

Therefore, I set up a secure folder which I labelled, for purposes of participant confidentiality. I then created a series of parent folders and subsequently child and grandchild folders in which data was stored. This was a similar layout to that found on Nvivo. The parent folders were named 'Raw data', 'Cleaned data', and 'analysis', with one of the folders chosen to provide any illustrations. The 'analysis' folder could then be opened with a series of internal child folders. These child folders were labelled 'Survey Transcripts' and 'Interview Transcripts', and 'Emergent Themes'. Within 'Emergent Themes' was again a number of grandchild folders. One of which was 'Acknowledgment (1)'. This folder could then be opened up and inside it contained all the discussions which were under the theme of acknowledgment. Each participant statement that related to this theme could easily be identified. Likewise, where there were subthemes, these were named. If the name reference related to another theme it contained a number in brackets. Therefore I could exit the 'acknowledgment (1)' folder and access the theme related to that number. Emerging sub-themes were identified and coded under common terms named such as social bias, fear, etc. Often these codes were also colored accordingly (see Figure.1). Each of these terms was given a detailed definition in order to help clarify what exactly these concepts referred to within the coding frame. Names were used in order to help identify themes (a number was always allocated to a theme so that sub-themes could

easily be identified). See the below extract of the data analysis at the over-arching theme stage, for example:

Interview & Survey Category & sub themes:

Acknowledgment (1)	Count (%)	
Did Acknowledge (1a) Interviews N=20 Survey N=280	20 (100%) 255(91.1%)	Q. Did you acknowledge you experience as stalking?
Did not acknowledge right away (1b) (Interviews)	17 (85%)	Quotes Interview Q: Did you acknowledge that what you were experiencing is stalking right away?
<i>Social/cultural biases/social Norms played role in misconceptions & delay of acknowledging.</i>	13(76%)	3658- ‘‘It was in a way where I couldn’t even imagine what would be happening to me. If you look at a family that’s from an Asian background, it would just be. And I’ve told people this and they oh, well, your parents just care about you and they, you know, you know, they that they just want to know you’re safe and it’s like you have no idea.’ ‘‘It’s completely different from how it usually happens, so you it’s usually from a partner or a stranger or something, but within the family aspect.’ 4839- ‘Am I? I was questioning myself. Is this really happening? Am I overreacting? Am I being overly sensitive? Am I misreading the situation so it took a while? I had PTSD about 10 years before that due to an unfortunate series of tragedies.’ ‘‘I’m watching you. He would constantly do little things and say little things that were very personal to what I was doing. I’m watching you. I’m watching you.’ ‘Once he, once he did that, and once he did that once, he kept himself in front of the manager when he realised it is that he was right next to a manager. And I looked at him afterwards every time he did it, it’s like, Oh my gosh, you’re being very careful not to do this in front of managers. Yeah’
Did not Acknowledge stalking (1c)	25 (9%)	Survey Q27. Can you tell me why you did not consider the experience as stalking?
Social Bias 11 (48%) Not following 6 (55%) <i>Perceived normative behaviours, & misconceptions of stalking behaviours</i>		105965043 -‘Not following us’ 105807757 –‘‘Didn’t follow me’ 105309261 -‘Not stalking as not waiting outside my house or work, just approaches if he sees me and messages me constantly’ 104594303 -‘There was a few occasions I received emails which were concerning. Although I had blocked the person on all social media and phone contact I still received these.’ 105964967 -‘Not stalking behaviour’ 105158473 -‘He didn’t follow me around’ 104871136 -‘Because he was not following_me places’

Figure.2

Ethical Considerations

Ethics encompasses the examination of moral dilemmas that can arise within the realm of research. According to Bos (2020), ethics can be understood as a thorough investigation into

concepts of right and wrong, as well as the obligations that researchers have in their work. This field emphasizes the importance of researchers' responsibilities toward various stakeholders, including the rights and interests of their participants, the expectations of their audience, the integrity of their academic community, and the broader implications for society as a whole. Researchers must navigate these ethical considerations to ensure that their work upholds the principles of respect, integrity, and social responsibility. By prioritizing ethical practices, researchers contribute to the advancement of knowledge while safeguarding the welfare and rights of those involved in their studies (Bos, 2020). Ethics can be considered as the application of good conduct and practice while carrying out research. The researcher must make judgements about what exactly is good conduct according to Birch et al (2002).

While a great deal of planning may be prepared prior to a research study being carried out, the researcher must also be aware that their own ethics and morality that may be drawn into question. While research is essential it must be respectful to the participants involved, as well as others who may be involved indirectly through participant association, affiliation, etc. In relation to this particular research, this issue was raised on a number of occasions as participants discussed events which may have involved harm, abuse, or other forms of victimization committed not only on themselves but also on others. To help reduce these certain issues arising, which could potentially raise questions of morality and ethics, the researcher took a number of precautions. Yet prior to putting any ethical guidelines in place I had to question whether or not the study itself was beneficial.

Given the prevalence of the crime of stalking in the UK, this research was felt to be necessary in bringing attention to a significant gap within existing literature. By shedding light on the issue of stalking victimization, it was felt that the data could not only help in preventing such a crime but also provide a basis from which future research could be carried out. Thus, it was therefore considered ethical to carry out the research despite the potential for problematic issues. However, while the research was considered to be useful, this also brought with it a number of issues relating to research responsibilities. I had to recognize: (a) a responsibility to society; (b) a professional responsibility, and (c) a responsibility to the participants as victims of this crime. To help guide these responsibilities, a pragmatic set of ethical considerations was designed which would prove useful as an overarching guideline. Yet this guideline was by no means fixed as I acknowledged those potential pitfalls highlighted by the likes of Birch et al (2002). Having a responsibility to society, I felt a need to balance professional integrity with respect for the participant's victimization, the UWS ethics board, stakeholders, and to also ensure that research did not result in the marginalization, exclusion, or generalization of any under- represented social groups.

Furthermore, having a professional responsibility meant ensuring that an appropriate research method was selected on the basis of informed professional expertise. This was achieved by seeking support and advice from the supervisory team. I endeavoured to ensure that data was accurate and avoided falsification, fabrication, suppression or misinterpretation of data. This coincided with a need to accurately reflect the participants as a whole and avoid generalizations or stereotypes. Given that the researcher is the human instrument in qualitative research this proved a challenging task, simply because I had to take subjective information, and interpret it further while trying to remain as objective and impartial as possible. While interpreting data I still had to recognize that my own potential for influencing data was not confined merely to its interpretation, but that it was possible that I may have actually influenced the data gathering process in the first place. My own subjective experience, as a stalking advocate and victim, I was aware that my values were imprinted, to some degree, upon the creation of the study.

Approval was acquired by The University of The West of Scotland Ethics Committee in November 2022 before the online invitation pages were sent out via email and any data was collected. In Addition, Ethical approval was acquired by The University of The West of Scotland Ethics Committee in March 2024 before the initial invitations were sent out to participants and any data was acquired.

Another ethical consideration was my responsibility to the participants. The participants were voluntary and had no obligation to shed light into their experience of victimization. I had to ensure that while data was being gathered it could not be done so without participant consent. I had to make sure that I was in no way being intrusive and above all respected the views, narratives, and experiences of each of the participants. Given the nature of that being discussed, confidentiality and anonymity was to be emphasized.

The Question Pro software generated random participation numbers for the survey respondents, which was explained in the participation Information screen, therefore all data generated was completely anonymous in the survey. Participants were made aware at consent that they could leave the survey at any time and once data was completed and submitted, it could not be removed. Participants were asked to click the Start Survey button to consent to the study at the end of the Participation Information and Consent screen to begin the survey.

For the interviews, participants generated their own 4 digit code for the use of anonymizing their data. This 4 digit code was created on the consent form and returned to me and verified before the interview was conducted. Participants were also made aware on the Participation and Consent forms for the interview that they could pause or withdraw from the interview at any point. Participants' 4 digit codes were changed to pseudo names for the thesis write up to adhere to strict

anonymity. Any identifying details, such as people or places that were named by participants were blocked out with 'XXXX', and/or changed to pseudo names during the data cleaning process.

One important issue that needed addressing was distress due to the topic under discussion. Participants were made aware within the Participation Information screen for the survey and interview document that although it is not likely, they may experience distress because of the nature of the questions relating to their experience of victimization from receiving unwanted behaviours or contacts, therefore links to support was provided at the start and end of the survey and interviews. These website links were made available at the end of the survey and interview debrief document and included; Woman's Aid, Rape Crisis, Abused men in Scotland. The researcher had also arranged support to be available to participants through Action Against Stalking if required following the interview process and participants were made aware they would be able to receive the support from Action Against Stalking and instructed to place 'research support' in the subject line of their email to the support team to ensure the researcher will not be supporting any participants within my role at the Charity. The Team at Action against Stalking provided permission for access to support if required. (See appendix 1. For consent and participation Information).

As a former victim of stalking and a specialized stalking advocate practitioner who supports victims of stalking, I was duly aware that during the interview process any participant may have start to feel distressed or upset, and actively engaged with sign of distress. The participants were met with compassion and empathy and made aware throughout the interviews that they could pause or stop at any time when this occurred. The pausing of the interview occurred in two separate interviews, for a period of approx. 5 minutes, the interview carried on when the participant indicated they were ready. I also gave all participants time to debrief when the interview was finished.

All data was fully anonymized and stored according to the University of the West of Scotland's Data Requirements and GDPR practices for a maximum of 3-5 years. Ethical approval was acquired by The University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee in November 2022 before the survey went live and data was collected, and in May 2024 before interviews were arranged and the data was collected.

This research is a part of a PhD program with The University of The West of Scotland, therefore, the researcher will not be profiting in any way, nor was payment offered or made of any kind to respondents.

Chapter 4: Qualitative Findings from Survey and Interview Data

INTRODUCTION

Having outlined the qualitative methodological procedures in Chapter 3, this chapter presents qualitative findings that illuminate the complexities of stalking victimization by tracing the pathways victims navigate when determining whether they are being stalked, deciding how and when to disclose, and how these processes relate to stalking outcomes. To capture these dynamics, data was collected through a cross-sectional, integrative qualitative web-based survey complemented by in-depth, person-to-person interviews with victim/survivors of stalking. The data is displayed into categories that represent the journey of stalking victimization, while the primary and secondary research questions detailed in Chapter 3 will be fully explored from the data in this chapter and in the following Chapter 5- Discussion.

The findings in this chapter will be presented under the following categories: 'Acknowledgement', 'Help-seeking decisions', 'Disclosure Responses', and 'Stalking Outcomes'. Each category was created as a heading to capture each stage of the stalking victimization journey. See Appendix 4 for the summary flow chart detailing the journey of stalking victimization. The categories, along with the themes and sub-themes that emerged from the data will be presented individually. Data gathered from the survey and interviews will be presented as combined unless otherwise stated in the relevant sections. Individual quotes used in this chapter were selected in each category, theme and sub-theme to display the varied range of ages, stalker typologies and gender of the participants. Please see the category, theme and sub-theme chart showing how the data will be presented in this chapter as follows:

Category	Theme	Sub-theme
Acknowledgment	Did not acknowledge right away	<i>Social bias</i> <i>Social normative perceptions of stalking</i>
	Non-Acknowledgement	<i>Social Bias</i>
HELP-SEEKING DECISIONS	No Disclosure Made	Ashamed/embarrassed
		Fear
DISCLOSURE DISCOURSE	Minimized/invalidated the experience	<i>Discouraged from further help-seeking</i>

	Validated the experience Invalidating court experience	<i>Wished they hadn't disclosed</i>	
	Stalker type and disclosure response	<i>Sought further help regardless of response</i>	
	The importance of staff trained in stalking	<i>Encouraged further help- seeking</i>	
	Gender bias and assumptions	<i>Predatory stalker easier to recognize</i>	
	Evidencing the amount of stalking behaviours		
STALKING OUTCOMES	Stalking still occurring	<i>Stalker persistence</i>	Control
		<i>Inaction</i>	Police Inaction Victim Inaction
	Stalking Stopped	<i>Action</i>	Police Action Victim Action

Please refer to Appendix 3 for the Summary charts of the Survey (fig. 3a) and the Summary Interview Data (Fig. 3b) of overall findings.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

What is acknowledgement? Acknowledgment is considered as a victim recognizing what they are experiencing as the crime of stalking. This is an important exploration, as it is the first step that must occur before a victim of stalking can conceivably start the process of deciding whether or not to seek help for their victimization. Therefore, in order to understand the victims stalking journey as a whole, the decision was made to explore this first process of acknowledgment including the internal thought processes/factors of consideration for those that do and do not acknowledge their experience as stalking.

The interview portion of the study found 100% of participants acknowledged their experience as stalking, albeit for the majority not right away. The survey phase of the study revealed that 255 (91%) acknowledged their experience as stalking, whilst the remaining 25 (9%) did not acknowledge at all.

Did not acknowledge right away

The Interview phase of the study showed that all participants recognized their experiences as stalking; however, 17 out of 20 (85%) did not immediately identify their experiences as such. The timing of this acknowledgment varied among participants, with data indicating that factors such as

the victims' own biases and their interpretations of what constitutes socially acceptable (normative) behaviour in the context of stalking played a role. The interviewees shared insights into why they failed to recognize they were being stalked initially, highlighting the influence of socially biased perceptions and their perceptions of what constitutes normative behaviours related to their stalking experience.

As mentioned in the literature review chapter 2, mental representations are considered as the categorization of information which is an essential cognitive process. This process enables the interpretation of information in the individuals' environment. These processes are vital for activities such as identifying experiences, objects, making decisions, and forming memories (Roads & Love, 2024). According to Trimmer (2016), a bias is a mental distortion (misconception) to a mental representation. Furthermore, misconceptions, biases, gender norms, and the romanticizing or minimizing of stalking behaviours are a phenomenon rooted within social learning that impacts both victims and society at large (Becker et al, 2020). Becker and colleagues proposed that these social learning perceptions are shaped largely by representations about stalking within news media, films, television, social media, and in general societal understandings of stalking. The analysis for the sub-themes of social bias and social normative perceptions of stalking are discussed separately as follows:

Social Bias

As part of the research into acknowledgement of their experience as stalking, it was found that interviewees either acknowledged the stalking right away or failed to do so. Concerning the interviewees that did not acknowledge right away, it was found this could be attributed to social bias for approximately 76%, (13 of 20) interview participants. The interview data was organized in the theme of did not acknowledge right away, and then coded to find the sub themes, please see the following example extract from the data analysis:

Acknowledgement of Stalking by victims (Interviews)	Count (%)			Social Bias 71% 5% social Norms
Did not acknowledge right away (1b)	17 (85%)	Quotes	Sub Themes	Key themes
Social biases and normative assumptions of stalking behaviour & stalkers <i>played role in the misconceptions & delay of acknowledging.</i>	13 (76%)	3658- 'Not right away, it was in a way where I couldn't even imagine what would be happening to me. If you look at a family that's from an Asian background, it would just be. <u>"It's completely different from how it usually happens, so you it's usually from a partner or a stranger or something, but within the family aspect."</u> 3C	Cultural normative perception -this is simply the way this cultural is with family. Unusual presentation of what is understood about stalking	Social bias Social misconception

	<p>4839-'Am I? I was questioning myself. Is this really happening? Am I overreacting? Am I being overly sensitive? Am I misreading the situation so it took a while?</p> <p>0705-'No, not in the beginning, no' 'Only when the friend pointed it out.' 'I think sometimes for for victims of of stalking that like I didn't recognise it as stalking. I think it's. I think we have a bit of a perception in a red that it's somebody in a dirty raincoat that hangs around street court and it's absolute. I just didn't see it. And I have sports people and it ties really closely. I think with coercive control and' 'I think I think they're both' 'Undersold. If that's the right phrase'</p> <p>2011-'Initially I thought it was bullying, but then I realised it was stalking.' 'He started sitting outside my house in his car and van at all hours of the day and night, looking in my windows'</p> <p>2910-'I probably didn't understand really that it probably was actually stalking do you know a claim as such?' 'Wording and stances around stalking and behaviours and things 'cause I think there's probably quite a misconception that it's, you know, people hiding outside different house and things like that.</p>	<p>Self-doubt delayed, questioning misreading situation- is their behaviour acceptable, or overreaction</p> <p>Delayed</p> <p>Social normative (Bias) understanding of stalkers & behaviour</p> <p>Social understandings within sports community</p> <p>Delayed- misunderstanding of stalking compared to bullying until escalation to recognized stalking behaviour</p> <p>Delayed</p> <p>Social misunderstanding of stalking behaviour.</p>	<p>Social Normative understanding of stalkers</p> <p>Social Bias</p> <p>Social normative understanding of stalking</p>
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The sub-theme of social bias emerged from the interviewees' prevalent misconceptions regarding different types of stalkers and their associated behaviours, including cyberstalking. These misunderstandings often impeded their ability to recognize that they were being stalked. It wasn't until they received supportive feedback from a disclosure response that they began to see their experiences through the lens of stalking. This delay in acknowledgment highlights how societal biases can cloud victims' perceptions and hinder their understanding of their situations, as one interviewee, Darlene articulated:

'No, not in the beginning, no.....Only when the friend pointed it out.....I think sometimes for, for victims of, of stalking that like I didn't recognize it as stalking. I think it's. I think we have a bit of a perception in a red that it's somebody in a dirty raincoat that hangs around street court and it's absolute. I just didn't see it. And I have sports people and it ties really closely. I think with coercive control and. I think I think they're both. Undersold. If that's the right phrase'. (Darlene, 59, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

As we can see from Darlene's quote, there was some time delay; a process before acknowledgement occurred from the misconception of stalkers in a 'dirty raincoat' to understanding that stalking was actually occurring and was linked to the 'coercive control' Darlene was experiencing. In addition, this acknowledgment was also facilitated by a friend. As we can see from the stuttering that occurred, this also elucidated emotion for the participant. In this particular instance, the social bias arose from a misconception that all stalkers fit a specific stereotype, namely,

that they are individuals dressed in a specific manner who are often seen lurking around on the streets and not readily acknowledged in the realm of domestic abuse.

This narrow view not only oversimplified the issue for this participant, but also ignored the diverse realities of stalking behaviour, which can occur in various contexts and involve a range of individuals who do not conform to this stereotypical image. As a result, this misconception hindered her understanding of the true nature of stalking and contributed to a lack of awareness about the different forms it can take. Darlene was not alone in the failure to recognize their victimization from an ex-partner, as we can see from another interview participant Jennifer:

'I probably didn't understand really that it probably was actually stalking do you know a claim as such? ... - (Jennifer, 35, female, victim of a rejected stalker).

The same social bias misconceptions were experienced by both participants by way of stereotypical representations of the stalker type and stalker behaviours such as cyberstalking. As a result of these social biases misconstruing what the victims were experiencing, it took disclosing to others to aid the recognition of the stalking in a domestic abuse context, highlighting the importance of social relationships and their influence. As we saw from Darlene's quote regarding the 'dirty raincoat' that certain social bias and perceptions impact the experience of acknowledgment and like Darlene, Jennifer supported this view:

'Wording and stances around stalking and behaviours and things...cause I think there's probably quite a misconception that it's, you know, people hiding outside different house and things like that. You know, people that I think don't realize that actually electronic contact.' (Jennifer, 35, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

This finding is quite intriguing and raises an important question about the potential generational differences in the acknowledgment of stalking experiences. With the rise of electronic methods increasingly used to stalk victims, it becomes essential to consider if perceptions vary across different age groups. However, this study did not delve into whether similar social narratives influence various demographics, primarily due to the absence of collected demographic information. Importantly, both Jennifer and Darlene took time to recognize their experiences with stalking. Yet, their ability to do so may have been impeded by prevalent misconceptions fueled by stereotypes and overarching social narratives.

In terms of these narratives, another significant sub-theme that emerged related to cultural understandings of stalking held by the victims and interviewees. This cultural lens may shape how individuals perceive and respond to their experiences, suggesting that societal biases play a crucial role in the acknowledgment and interpretation of stalking incidents. This was evident in the experience of being stalked by family members, Ishaan stated in his interview he felt the stalkers

were predatory, using him for nefarious purposes, which could also be considered an extension of domestic abuse, as interview participant Ishaan explained:

'It was in a way where I couldn't even imagine what would be happening to me. If you look at a family that's from an Asian background, it would just be. And I've told people this and they "Oh, well, your parents just care about you and they, you know, you know, they that they just want to know you're safe" and it's like you have no idea.' (Ishaan, 32, male, victim of a predatory stalker)

As a result of the cultural biased understandings, Ishaan expressed that disclosing in this case did not aid his acknowledgment of stalking, instead the cultural bias he was struggling with was reinforced when he disclosed, which resulted in the delay of acknowledgement of the experience as stalking until after some time, he spoke to a charity specific to stalking.

Therefore, it can be suggested that misconceptions, facilitated by social biases, such as stalker stereotypes, and wider social and cultural narratives prevented these victims from recognizing earlier on that what they were experiencing was actually the crime of stalking. The prevention of early recognition of stalking, delayed help-seeking decisions and removed readily available choices victims would have if otherwise educated on the realities of stalking, such as help-seeking and specialized support. Highlighting the need for social education programs, and a wider range of media coverage to tackle social/cultural biases and misrepresented narratives on the crime of stalking.

Social normative perceptions of stalking

Victims' perceptions of gender norms refers to the understanding of the socially accepted roles associated with gender, as well as the expected behaviours and reactions that are deemed appropriate for masculine and feminine identities (Donne et al, 2018). These perceptions can shape how individuals interpret their experiences in relation to societal expectations of acceptable/normative behaviours.

Furthermore, socially normative perceptions encompass the victims' insights into accepted behaviours within their community (Donne et al, 2018). Research indicates that these perceptions can significantly influence the timeline for victims to recognize their experiences as stalking (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010). Many victims may initially struggle to acknowledge the stalking behaviour they are experiencing, often delaying this realization until the situation escalates or until they engage in conversations with others. Such discussions can highlight the prevalence of stalking, particularly the phenomenon of men being stalked by women, which can help victims reframe their understanding of their own experiences. This delay in acknowledgment underscores the complex interplay between societal norms and personal experiences in the context of stalking victimization.

For example, gender role perceptions resulted in the delay of the realization of the experience of stalking as explained by the following interview participant Dave who was stalked by his ex-partner:

'I didn't realize for quite a while it was stalking, I really didn't think men could get stalked, but when the messages got really dark I realized this was more than harassment...you don't really hear much about men getting stalked by women, I mean there is some talk about men being abused by their partners but it kind of stops there. Since this has happened I have spoken about it to many of my mates, and it is a lot more common than I could have ever imagined.' (Dave, 49, male, victim of a rejected stalker)

Dave's reflections on gender roles significantly influenced his understanding of stalking. He initially believed that certain experiences, such as being stalked, were exclusive to women and could not possibly happen to men. This limited perspective contributed to his hesitance in recognizing and acknowledging his own experiences with stalking. However, when Dave began to disclose his situation to informal sources such as friends, he discovered that men are, in fact, often stalked by women. This revelation played a crucial role in helping him navigate his understanding of stalking as a phenomenon that can affect anyone, regardless of gender.

Similarly, another male victim, Alex, shared his own journey, highlighting how societal norms and expectations around masculinity also delayed his recognition of being a victim. Pointing out that prevailing perceptions about gender roles often lead men to dismiss or overlook their experiences, making it challenging for them to come to terms with being stalked. These experiences further illustrate the broader issue of how societal attitudes can impact the acknowledgment of victimization among men, as interview participant Alex articulated he was stalked after just one date:

'It took a while before I realized how obsessed he was so I guess I didn't recognize it at first, it took a few months and probably wasn't until he started following me despite there being 100s texts and gifts, at this point.' (Alex, 36, male, victim of a rejected stalker).

Both Dave and Alex experienced escalations in stalking behaviours. These victim experiences suggest that escalations in stalking behaviours, such as sinister messages helped to facilitate the understanding of the experience as stalking, forcing these victims to look beyond their normative assumptions of what was occurring to them, beyond the understandings of gender normative behaviour and perceptions of acceptable social behaviour.

Further reinforcing the influence of socially normative beliefs surrounding the nature of stalking behaviours, a delay in recognizing the experience of being stalked has been observed, particularly in the realm of cyberstalking (Becker et al, 2020). For instance, the experience of being stalked through technology, illustrates how digital platforms can enable and exacerbate the invasive stalking behaviours. One interview participant shared that the constant connectivity provided to her ex-

partner by technology made it difficult to fully acknowledge the impact of the stalking on her life, highlighting the complexities that arise when traditional notions of stalking intersect with modern digital experiences, as Sherry explained:

*'So it's the cyber guy who, who contacted me and, and, and I contacted him when this person started hacking into like, my dad's work account and then they started sending emails from me to me with screenshots of conversations I've had which **** me up.....'* (Sherry, 43, female, victim of a rejected stalker).

The misunderstandings surrounding what constitutes socially normative or acceptable behaviour contributed to Sherry's delayed recognition of her situation as stalking. Much like Dave and Alex, she did not initially identify her experiences as stalking until the behaviours intensified, particularly when the stalking behaviour began to target a family member. Sherry articulated her emotional response through her choice of words, particularly when she received emails that appeared to be sent from her own account. This alarming escalation prompted her to seek help from someone trained in recognizing cyberstalking behaviour. Through this support, Sherry was able to confront her misconceptions and ultimately understand that she was indeed a victim of cyberstalking. This journey not only illuminated her situation but also empowered her to take action.

While Sherry and Dave discovered that sharing their experiences helped them to recognize their situations as stalking, not all participants had the same outcome. In some cases, disclosing the experience actually contributed to the delay in acknowledgment, this was particularly evident when the responses the victims received reinforced existing socially normative beliefs. This was true for interview participant Ishaan, who faced cultural perceptions that shaped his understanding of what is deemed acceptable behaviour. As Ishaan explained:

'...Oh, well, your parents just care about you and they, you know, you know, they that they just want to know you're safe'' (Ishaan, 32, Male, Victim of a predatory stalker)

Ishaan's experience supports the idea that when he disclosed his situation, the reactions he received only served to prolong the stalking. Ishaan's experience highlights how societal norms and the responses to disclosures can significantly impact an individual's ability to identify and label their experiences, ultimately affecting their path toward seeking help and validation.

Similar to Ishaan, the delay in acknowledgement resulting from perceptions of normative behaviours was reinforced by disclosing, as exemplified by interview participant Anita who stated:

'No, it took me a long time to sit with it and be like because I sort of hit. I hit the victim. I hit the word. I don't know why, because I feel I don't know. It's a weird feeling where it sits with me. I don't know why.....I saw I'm very blurry sometimes, because you go backwards and forwards and thinking maybe I'm just being pride. Like maybe I'm just that, you know, and people's responses they're be like, hmm. They're just like anything. Oh, God, am I making am I blowing this into something? It's not. But when that happened, I'm like, I can't over exaggerate.' (Anita, 32, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

In this instance, Anita shares the challenges in navigating the complexities of acceptable and unacceptable reactions to the behaviours she was encountering from her ex-partner. She found herself grappling with concerns about her own pride and the possibility that she might be misinterpreting the situation. As she opened up about her experiences, the responses she received further fueled her doubts, with others expressing skepticisms about her feelings and perceptions. This reaction from her peers underscored a broader cultural narrative that often invalidates personal experiences, particularly for victims of stalking. The prevailing societal normative perceptions surrounding stalking behaviour, domestic abuse and what is deemed socially acceptable contributed to a significant delay in recognizing and validating the struggles faced by these individuals. This dynamic not only perpetuated feelings of isolation but also complicated the process of acknowledgment.

This study highlights how overlapping misconceptions, social bias, and prevailing societal narratives intersect to delay recognition of stalking. Stereotyped ideas about who “counts” as a stalker and what stalking “looks like,” is reinforced by broader norms around domestic abuse and acceptable behaviour. This lead victims to mislabel or minimize early warning signs. These biases shape victims’ expectations, favouring dramatic, stranger-danger scenarios over subtle, relational or digital patterns, so their experiences do not match the stereotype and are therefore not acknowledged as stalking. The result is a compounded delay in recognition and validation, where social bias and victim misperceptions mutually reinforce non-acknowledgment of stalking.

Non-Acknowledgment

Under the primary heading of Acknowledgment a theme emerged known as non-acknowledgment, which was reported by 25 (9%) of the survey participants. The concept of non-acknowledgment pertains to individuals who failed to recognize or identify their experiences as instances of stalking. This non -acknowledgment occurred despite answering positively for the survey’s careful criteria for defining a stalking victim. This included participants having experienced targeted and unwanted behaviours on at least two separate occasions that resulted in feelings of fear and alarm. However, these participants did not perceive their situations in that light. This definition was rooted in the legal framework provided by Scottish stalking legislation, specifically section 39, which aimed to provide clarity on what constitutes stalking behaviour.

Although this section pertains to a relatively small sample of the 280 survey respondents, the researcher included this in the analysis and findings section, because of importance of understanding stalking victimization in all its complexities. The prevalence of non-acknowledgment

among this subset of survey respondents raises important questions about awareness and recognition of stalking experiences, suggesting that many individuals may not fully understand or accept the implications of their encounters, even when they meet the legal criteria for being classified as victims of stalking. Participants were asked the open question in the survey ‘Can you tell me why you did not consider the experience as stalking?’ The survey data was organized in the category of did not acknowledge, and then coded to find the sub themes, please see the below extract from the data analysis:

Did not Acknowledge stalking (1c) 25 (9%)	Quotes	Sub-Themes	Key Themes
Social Bias 11 (48%) 6 (55%)	<p>105965043 -‘<u>Not following us</u>’</p> <p>105807757 -‘‘<u>Didn’t follow me</u>’</p> <p>105309261 -‘Not stalking as not waiting outside my house or work, just approaches if he sees me and messages me constantly’</p> <p>105964967 -‘Not stalking behaviour’</p> <p>105158473 -‘<u>He didn’t follow me around</u>’</p> <p>104634417 - ‘<u>They didn’t follow me</u>’</p> <p>108210727 -‘Although it targeted at me, fixated, he’s obsessed, it’s not stalking.’</p> <p>107754465 -‘He’s not some <u>stranger</u> behind a bush’</p> <p>108013983- ‘As it was my husband and not some stranger following me, it’s not stalking.’</p> <p>106144272 -‘It’s not some stranger in the dark’</p> <p>108307496 -‘It’s a professional Client relationship that’s ended, not a celebrity.’</p> <p>108216671-‘He’s rejected because I broke up with him, not some stranger like the movies’</p>	<p><u>Not following</u>- bias perceptions of stalking behaviour</p> <p><i>misconceptions of stalking behaviours</i></p> <p><u>Not following</u></p> <p><u>Not following</u></p> <p>Misconception of stalking</p> <p>Not a stranger</p> <p>Not a stranger, or following</p> <p>Not a stranger</p> <p>Media Bias</p> <p>Media bias</p>	<p>Stalking Behaviour misconceptions (bias)</p> <p>Bias perceptions of stalking behaviour</p> <p><i>Perceived assumptions of stalkers types & misconceptions</i></p> <p><i>Misconceptions of stalker types that are media influenced</i></p>

The key sub-theme that emerged from the data in this section was that of social bias, victims’ common misunderstandings or perceptions about what they expect stalking behaviour to be and stalker types, which influenced the non-acknowledgment for these participants. This section details how misconceptions, social bias, and dominant cultural narratives converge to not only delay the recognition of stalking as the previous section discussed, but also can impede stalking acknowledgment completely. Stereotypes about who “qualifies” as a stalker and what stalking “looks like,” prompts victims to mislabel or downplay early warning signs. The result is a failure to recognition and validate a stalking experience, as social bias and victim misperceptions continually reinforce non-acknowledgment.

Social Bias

The data collected from this study highlighted a significant sub-theme related to non-acknowledgment, which is that of social bias for approximately 48% of participants who did not acknowledge their experience as stalking. Social bias, in this context, refers to the internal perceptions and misconceptions that victims of stalking may have regarding what constitutes stalking behaviours. A particularly common misunderstanding that emerged from the data is the belief that all stalkers engage in the act of physically following their victims (Tjaden and Thoennes, 1998).

Such misunderstandings can have profound implications for how victims perceive their experiences. When individuals believe that stalking is exclusively characterized by physical following, they may inadvertently downplay or dismiss other forms of stalking, such as persistent messaging, surveillance, or harassment. This narrow definition can lead to a failure to acknowledge the seriousness of their situations, as they might not recognize non-physical behaviours as valid threats. Consequently, many victims may struggle to articulate their experiences or seek help, believing that their situation does not meet the traditional criteria for stalking.

This disconnect between the victims' experiences and societal perceptions was frequently reflected in the survey data, suggesting that social bias plays a significant role in shaping how victims understand and respond to their circumstances. The following quote from one of the participants vividly illustrates this point, highlighting the confusion and internal conflict that can arise when one's experience does not align with prevailing stereotypes of stalking behaviour. Survey participant Sadie expressed about the acquaintance that stalked her:

'Not stalking as not waiting outside my house or work, just approaches if he sees me and messages me constantly' (Sadie, 53, female, victim of an intimacy seeker stalker)

In the case of Sadie, despite enduring numerous behaviours typically associated with stalking, such as unwanted communications, obsessive tracking, or harassment, her underlying social biases prevented her from recognizing her situation as stalking. These misconceptions stem from societal stereotypes about what a stalker is supposed to look like and/or how they are expected to behave (Fox et al, 2011). For instance, many people may envision a stalker as someone who is overtly aggressive or who physically follows their target, rather than considering more subtle or nuanced forms of stalking. This can create a dangerous environment where victims question the validity of their feelings and experiences.

The disconnect between societal stereotypes and the reality of stalking behaviours can hinder victims from seeking help or taking steps to protect themselves, as they may not recognize that they

are, in fact, being stalked. Social biased perceptions in the form of stalker stereotypes (Fox et al, 2011) have also been found within the data, which have negatively influenced stalking acknowledgment, as the following survey participants expressed:

'He's not some stranger behind a bush' (Kathleen, 32, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Kathleen's quote highlights how a stereotypical representation can negatively affect stalking acknowledgment, the disconnect occurred between her understanding of who constitute stalkers, when in fact, the stalker was her ex-partner rather than a stranger. Similar to Kathleen, the disconnect was found between the realities of stalking and perceptions of stalkers, such as, stalkers are strangers and not ex-partners as Tanya also expressed a biased stereotypical representation of stalking:

'As it was my husband and not some stranger following me, it's not stalking.' (Tanya, 27, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Because the participants did not anticipate the behaviour stemming from a stranger, or because it was a partner engaging in this behaviour, their ingrained misconceptions and stereotypical representations shaped by social biases, led them to not recognize their experiences as stalking. This lack of acknowledgment can be attributed to the participants' reliance on normative beliefs about what constitutes stalkers and stalking behaviour, which often excludes actions that occur within the context of familiar relationships or from individuals they trust.

Similar to the various typologies of stalkers and the behaviors typically associated with them, the theme of social bias and socially normative assumptions regarding the nature of stalking emerged prominently in the data. Highlighting how societal expectations and preconceived notions about stalking can obscure the realities of abusive dynamics, especially when such behaviours are perpetrated by someone known to the victim. Furthermore, this indicates a broader issue where the context of the relationship can alter perceptions, leading individuals to minimize or dismiss alarming behaviours that might otherwise be recognized as stalking if they were perpetrated by an unknown individual.

The interplay between societal norms and personal experiences complicated the recognition and validation of stalking, particularly in intimate relationships where emotional ties may cloud judgment. This sub-theme served as a significant factor in the participants' failure to identify their experiences as stalking. For instance, survey participant Lisa articulated also this perspective:

'Was completely random on social media' (Lisa, 16, female, victim of an unknown resentful stalker)

Lisa's quote highlights that the unknown perpetrator who conducted the stalking online only interfered in her acknowledgment of the stalking, indicating that she also held the misconception that stalkers conduct in person behaviours only, such as lurking or following. Societal norms was also found to influence acknowledgment, similar to Lisa's expressions, where the assumption of what is acceptable normative behaviour by his male ex-partner resulted in non-acknowledgment of the stalking, as Nathan stated:

'There was a few occasions I received emails which were concerning. Although I had blocked the person on all social media and phone contact I still received these.' (Nathan, 56, male, victim of a predatory stalker)

The notion that stalking occurs exclusively on social media led these victims to overlook the reality of their cyberstalking situation. These individuals were influenced by a common societal beliefs, misconceptions that stalking is limited to in-person encounters by strangers, and not understood within cyberstalking and the domestic abuse context. Such biases represent wider social misunderstandings that can cloud people's ability to identify and acknowledge stalking behaviours.

Additionally, these social biases are frequently reinforced by various media outlets, which play a crucial role in shaping public perceptions of what stalking entails (Fox et al, 2011). This issue connects to social learning theory (Bandura, 1977), that people acquire their understandings of behaviours and norms from their surroundings. Consequently, these representations of stalking can significantly affect how individuals understand and recognize different types of stalking, particularly those occurring online, ultimately preventing victims from seeing their experiences as legitimate cases of stalking. Supporting social misrepresentations of stalking fueled by media, specifically stalker types was supported by survey participant Maria, who expressed:

'It's a professional Client relationship that's ended, not a celebrity.' (Maria, 41, female, victim of an incompetent suitor stalker)

A professional relationship coming to an end can lead to stalking behaviour, which often goes unrecognized, highlighting a significant misconception prevalent in society. The belief that only celebrities or public figures experience stalking. This misunderstanding can undermine the very real and serious experiences of individuals in various professional contexts.

Stalking is often portrayed in media as an issue that primarily affects well known personalities, leading to a perception that ordinary individuals are somehow immune to such predatory behaviours. However, this is far from the truth. Many people, can find themselves victims of obsessive behaviours. This media fueled bias misconception was also supported by survey participant Ashley who stated:

'He's rejected because I broke up with him, not some stranger like the movies' (Ashley, 25, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

In the situations involving both Maria and Ashley, their failure to recognize their experiences as stalking was significantly influenced by the media's portrayal of celebrities being pursued by unknown individuals. This kind of representation contributes to a range of biased perceptions and misunderstandings about stalking. Whether these misconceptions are reinforced by media narratives or by broader societal beliefs, they play a crucial role in a victim's ability to identify their experience as stalking.

The lack of acknowledgment stemmed from the belief that stalking only occurs in specific scenarios, namely, it involves physical following by complete strangers, typically targeting high-profile individuals. This narrow understanding fails to encompass the reality that stalking can also involve partners, ex-partners, or acquaintances. Additionally, it overlooks the prevalence of online stalking behaviours, which can occur without any physical presence. As a result, victims, along with many others, may dismiss their experiences, not recognizing them as legitimate forms of stalking due to these restrictive and misleading perceptions.

HELP-SEEKING DECISIONS

The Help-seeking base heading of the research emerged through the investigation of the factors associated with the help-seeking decisions that participants who were experiencing stalking chose to make. Help-seeking is considered as the victim's decision whether or not to disclose their victimization. Decisions to disclose a victimization are made with a potential intent of attaining help and/or support for the stalking experience (Buhi and et al, 2009).

This exploration revealed that all 20 (100%) of Interview participants chose to seek help for their experience while the survey data revealed that 223 (80%) of participants chose to make a disclosure.

Interview & Survey participants that did disclose	Formal (police/superiors)	Informal (friends/family)	Negative response	Positive response
1 st disclosure	85	158	113	130
2 nd disclosure	179	0	103	76

Gender	Negative response	Positive response
Male N=42	22 (52%)	20 (48%)
Female N=201	113 (56%)	88 (44%)

The data revealed that of the 243 participants that made disclosures, the male participants received marginally more positive disclosure responses than female participants. However, both genders experienced marginally more invalidating responses than validating. The following analysis is exploring in the next section data from the survey participants that chose not to disclose, and will then move on to explore responses received from those participants that did choose to disclose.

No Disclosure Made

The No-disclosure made theme emerged within the category of Help-seeking for 62 survey participants who declared that they chose not to disclose or to seek help (37% of these were Male, and 63% of female participants). The typology of the stalkers in this theme were 29 rejected, 17, resentful, 2 Incompetent suitors, 6 Intimacy seekers and 8 predatory stalkers, with the majority of victims experiencing either entirely online behaviours or a mix of online and offline. Participants in this category were asked the open question in the survey ‘Can you tell me why you chose not to disclose to anyone? The survey data was organized in the category of no disclosure, and then coded to find the themes and sub themes, please see the below extract from the data analysis:

No Disclosure (2b) N=280 57 (20%)		
Key themes	Sub- Themes	Quotes
<p><i>Ashamed & embarrassed due to affairs, gender norms and the stalking experience in general.</i></p> <p><i>Fear of escalations, not being believed, job loss, being ostracized and being victim-blamed</i></p>	<p>Ashamed/ Embarrassed= 23 (41%) <u>Gender norm</u></p> <p>Fear = 20 (36%)</p> <p><i>Not being believed</i></p> <p>Escalation <u>Job Loss</u></p>	<p>108179636-‘ I was ashamed and didn’t want anyone else involved’ 108091524-‘ <u>it’s not really a manly thing to do</u>’ 106019335-‘ I was embarrassed that I didn’t listen when everyone warned me about her’ 105770592-‘ I feel ashamed of what I did, <u>and ashamed her behaviour alarms me</u>’ 105630604-‘ I don’t want anyone to know I am gay’ 105109427-‘ Because of the affair I felt shame and don’t want it public’ 104677384-‘ <u>Because I am a guy, I shouldn’t be alarmed by a girl it’s embarrassing</u>’ 108173165-‘ I didn’t want anyone to know I was fearful’ 104501042-‘ <i>I was worried that anyone I told would think I had somehow asked for or encouraged this.</i>’ 104465152-‘ <i>Because it’s never believed or it’s made out to be my fault..... I know this from a similar experience...</i>’ 105770546-‘ I was too scared it would escalate his behaviour’ 105331824-‘ <u>I was afraid I would lose my profession</u>’ 105309150-‘ <u>I was frightened it would escalate, or to lose my job</u>’</p>

The data revealed the sub-themes of ‘Ashamed/embarrassed’ and ‘Fear’ as the reasons they decided not to seek help for the stalking.

Ashamed/Embarrassed

Participants who chose not to disclose their experiences of stalking often reported feelings of shame and embarrassment associated with their situations. This emotional response was prevalent, as it affected 43% of those who opted for non-disclosure. Many individuals in this group felt that admitting to being stalked could lead to judgment or misunderstanding from others. The stigma surrounding stalking, coupled with societal perceptions about vulnerability and victimhood, contributed to their reluctance to share their experiences. This is exemplified by one participant Rose who explained:

'I was ashamed and didn't want anyone else involved' (Rose, 25, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

As a result, these feelings of shame and embarrassment not only influenced the decision to remain silent but may also have hindered their ability to seek support or find effective coping mechanisms. Similar to Rose, Tom expressed feelings of embarrassment at not listening to others warnings about the stalker:

'I was embarrassed that I didn't listen when everyone warned me about her' (Tom, 25, male, victim of an intimacy seeker stalker)

Therefore, the data suggests that the perceived feeling of embarrassment or feeling ashamed about what these victims were experiencing resulted in the decision to not seek help for the stalking and to keep their victimization private.

Furthermore, some participants had perceived gender normative roles and assumptions as causing the feelings of embarrassment or shame, (Donne et al, 2018). The perceived gender normative roles and assumptions appeared to be the barriers that resulted in dissuading these victims from seeking help as explained by the following male victims:

'Because I am a guy, I shouldn't be alarmed by a girl it's embarrassing' (Roger, 28, male, victim of a rejected stalker)

Similar to Rogers' expression of gender normative assumptions or misrepresentations, Corey expressed his perception of the male role:

'It's not really a manly thing to do' (Corey, 22, male, victim of a resentful stalker)

In both of these cases, the perceived gender normative role of a male by the victim, dissuaded them from seeking help (Donne et al, 2018). This is highlighted by both participants, as they expressed feelings of embarrassment to be fearful of their female stalkers. These gender assumptions that males should not be fearful of females, were the precursor to these participants as to why they chose not to disclose their victimization, therefore the gender normative assumptions in these cases were the barrier to seeking help for their victimization.

Fear

The second child sub-theme that emerged in the heading of Help-seeking decisions was fear. There were fears expressed by 36% of participants. It emerged that they feared not being believed, fear of escalation, fear of job loss and fear of being victim blamed, if they were to choose to disclose, (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011). The fears of others reactions were enough to dissuade these victims from disclosing their victimization.

The Fear of others finding out that they were fearful, in other words, others reactions to the fear was enough to dissuade one participant from disclosing, as Ross stated:

'I didn't want anyone to know I was fearful'. (Ross, 24, male, victim of a resentful stalker)

In this example, the fear of others reactions to his own fear, a perceived potential humiliation, was the barrier that persuaded this victim to remain isolated in the stalking experience. Whereas, the fear of not being believed was the reason the Tina stated as to why she chose not to disclose:

'I did not think I would be believed' (Tina, 16, female, victim of a predatory stalker)

Many victims responded with fear of not being believed, as the barrier which created the decision to choose not to seek-help for their victimization. However, similar to Tina, another female participant went further to explain why they were fearful of not being believed:

'Because of my profession, I feel no one will believe me' (Josie, 28, female, victim of an intimacy seeker stalker)

Josie articulated that her profession played a significant role in her decision to remain silent about her experiences. She felt that, due to her job, others would not take her perceptions seriously or believe her claims regarding the stalking. This fear of being discredited or dismissed contributed to her reluctance to disclose her situation. The concern about how others might perceive her not only intensified her feelings of isolation but also compounded her anxiety about potential repercussions if she did speak out.

In a similar vein, other participants shared comparable fears regarding how their experiences would be perceived by those around them. This apprehension often stemmed from a belief that their credibility would be questioned or that they would face judgment for their experiences. Such fears can create a barrier that prevents individuals from seeking help or support, further entrenching them in their silence. The collective anxiety surrounding societal perceptions was also experienced by one female participant who felt that the perceptions of others about the stalker was the reason they would not be believed:

'I don't think anyone would believe me as he seems harmless to others' (Dana, 37, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Dana expresses in her statement that her stalker seems harmless to others, and therefore perceived that she would not be believed because of this. Therefore the fear of not being believed encompassed these victims' worries about other peoples' perceptions of themselves and their stalkers and fear of not being believed was expressed as the facilitator for the decision to not seek help for their stalking experience, and remain isolated and without support.

It also emerged in the data that some victims chose not to disclose for fear of the stalkers behaviour escalating, which has shown to be a common fear among stalking victims (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011), as one female participant Rosie stated:

'I was too scared it would escalate his behaviour'. (Rosie, 25, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

In support of fear of stalker escalation if the decision was made to disclose, the data revealed that this was not a gender specific fear, as one male participant felt fear that his disclosing would also create an escalation by the stalker that would destroy his reputation, Ian stated:

'I chose not to tell because he is threatening to publicly shame me' (Ian, 32, male, victim of a rejected stalker)

The potential of being publicly humiliated by the stalker was the perceived escalation in stalker behaviour for this victim, which facilitated the decision to not disclose his victimization. Despite the fear of what was occurring, the overriding barrier to seeking help for these participants, was the fear of what may occur. This perceived fear of what may potentially occur it can be suggested, is what facilitated the dissuading of these participants from seeking help for their stalking victimization.

However, the perceived fear of experiencing victim-blame (Crome and McCabe, 2001) also occurred in the data, as a facilitator to choosing not to disclose, as one female participant Alya described:

'I was worried that anyone I told would think I had somehow asked for or encouraged this.' (Alya, 30, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

In Alya's case the fear of victim blame is found in her expression that she may have 'encouraged' the stalking behaviour. Alya describes her worries at this perceived outcome, suggesting further psychological distress at the possibility of being victim blamed. The fear of being victim blamed was also supported by Allie who stated:

'Because it's never believed or it's made out to be my fault.....' (Allie, 18, female, victim of a predatory stalker)

This participant felt that her past experience of not being believed and victim blamed was enough evidence in her decision making to determine that keeping her victimization to herself, was the best way forward, as the quote suggested:

'...I know this from a similar experience...' (Allie, 18, female, victim of a predatory stalker)

The fear of being blamed for their victimization was enough for these stalking victims to keep their victimization to themselves rather than to seek help for the stalking, facilitating their decision to not disclose.

The Help-seeking category reveals a significant theme among participants regarding the reluctance to disclose experiences of victimization, particularly due to feelings of shame and embarrassment, as well as fear of others' perceptions (Bandura, 1977; Ullman, 2010). The way individuals believe others view them can heavily influence their behaviour, and this was evident in the responses of the participants. Many victims expressed that their fear of being judged or misunderstood by peers, family, and society at large played a critical role in their decision-making process.

This fear often overshadowed their need for support and assistance, leading them to choose silence over seeking help. Participants articulated a profound concern that revealing their experiences might lead to stigma or negative evaluations from others, which in turn reinforced their feelings of shame. This internalized stigma prevented them from reaching out to friends, family, or professional resources that could have provided crucial support during their ordeal. While some participants did acknowledge a fear that disclosing their situation might provoke an escalation in the behaviour of their stalker, this concern was secondary to their apprehension about how they would be perceived.

The overwhelming nature of societal stigma surrounding victimization meant that for many, the prospect of facing potential judgment was a more powerful deterrent than the immediate threat posed by their stalker. Thus, the findings suggest that the relational dynamics of fear and stigma significantly impact help-seeking behaviors, with the fear of negative perceptions emerging as a dominant factor that inhibits victims from taking proactive steps to seek help and support.

DISCLOSURE DISCOURSE

The disclosure discourse category emerged from both the interviews and survey data analysis. This category relates to the questions asked in both phases of the research regarding the perceptions the participants had about disclosing their stalking journey in relation to the responses

they received. The analysis also explored participant perceptions of the responses they received and whether or not these responses encouraged or dissuaded further help-seeking decisions.

All participants in this category chose to disclose their experience. For the Interviews 100% of participants chose to seek help, and 223 (80%) of the survey participants also made a disclosure. The survey and interview data was organized in the category of Disclosure discourse, and then coded to find the themes and sub themes, please see the below extract from the data analysis:

Participant	Perceptions of response Quotes	Perceptions of response to further help-seeking Quotes	Patterns	Patterns/trends	Themes
1. 0608	The actual main manager. She 'Want associated with it? She didn't want, so that was kinda discouraging. And then my assistant manager, as much as she was the one that put that in place in terms of telling everyone she was like, right. We can't just assume it's him. So let's just like we're we don't, it's not that serious and'	'my best friend, she had said, I think she may be contact the police, but I was wary of it because of my management and the shop as much as they put that safety regulation in place for me to go in the back, the actual outward outlook on it was quite.' 'Difficult'	Disclosure Management-minimizing (not serious)-not helpful Safety measures put in place when seriousness (criminal history) escalated-helpful	Upper management-minimizing (not that serious) (not wanting associated with it) Response from upper management discourage from reporting to police	minimizing-not recognizing Work minimized experience discouraged from reporting to police STRANGER STALKER-POLICE TOOK SERIOUSLY
13.0000	'Absolutely supportive. The police were absolutely, 100%.' 'Yep, they did not minimize any of this at all, but they were very calm.' 'I actually the most negative response and disclosure I had was from my mother.' 'But it is stoic to a fault. So when we told her this was happening, she said. I don't want to know.' 'And very much minimize this. It's really not that.' Which of course says everything about that person.'	'And it meant our community in our street felt much safer as well, because we knew that the police were taking it seriously.' 'So when we told other people, I mean the whole street knew so we could then say to the other street to the street. Yes, the police are involved and this is what they think.'	Police took seriously due to offender history-TAG-just released Great police response took seriously FCT-known to police and fire raising	Encouraging to disclose to community & police	Family/friends minimizing -not recognizing Known offender Validating when supportive response received
108348733	Told me to ignore it	Frustrated, no one takes the threats and behaviors seriously	minimize told to ignore	Discouraged	minimized/invalidated
108347363	The first time very supportive	Reporting to police- I can completely understand why people don't report to the police	Friends and family Supportive	Discouraged by police	Discouraged/invalidated
108279576	Friends and family were very supportive	Very validated, I would not hesitate to disclose again	Supportive /validated	Encouraged-No hesitation to disclose	Validated & Supported

Five parent themes emerged from the analysis which were; 1. Minimized/invalidated the experience, 2. Validated the experience, 3. Invalidating court experience, 4. Stalker type and disclosure response and 5. Amount of stalking behaviours. There were also three child sub-themes that emerged within the theme of minimized/invalidated which were; a) Discouraged from further help-seeking, b) Wished they hadn't disclosed and c) Sought further help regardless of response(s).

Minimized/ invalidated the experience

This theme elaborates on the perceptions of the participants regarding the responses they received when they chose to disclose their experiences of stalking. Notably, 174 (69%) of the 253 participants in the survey and interviews who disclosed felt that the reactions they encountered made their situations seem less serious than they had experienced. These minimizing responses occurred for participants when disclosing to both formal (police/employers), as well as for informal disclosures (friends and family). This sense of invalidation was a common sentiment among the participants, who articulated that the way others responded to their disclosures diminished the severity of their stalking experiences. This occurred in the data for all 5 types of stalkers with both informal (friends and family) and formal (Police) disclosures with the resentful (47%) and predatory stalkers (50%) types receiving marginally more invalidating responses, compared to the rejected (35%), Incompetent suitor (45%) and the Intimacy seeker (40%).

Many participants reported feeling as though their concerns were trivialized, leading them to question the legitimacy of their feelings and experiences. In some cases, the responses they received not only minimized their experiences but also included elements of victim-blaming, where individuals were made to feel responsible for the stalking they endured. This reaction not only compounded their trauma but also reinforced feelings of isolation and helplessness. The findings emphasize how societal attitudes and misconceptions about stalking can further exacerbate the victim's distress and hinder their ability to seek help and support (McKeon et al, 2015). For example the following interview participant Karen stated:

'Oh, just get over it. It's just a bit of banter. You should be flattered. So I made myself come into work. I wish I hadn't. His behaviour escalated even more. He would make a point of coming over and talking to my colleague at the end of my desk.....People outside of the area treated me like I was a liar and people in the area treated me like what's your problem? Get over it.' (Karen, 48, female, victim of an incompetent suitor stalker).

Karen's quote poignantly illustrates the profound impact that the informal responses received from her engineering and architectural colleagues had on her experience of stalking. She articulates that the dismissive or trivializing reactions she received served to minimize the seriousness of her situation, making her feel as though her concerns were not valid or worthy of serious attention. This lack of acknowledgment from her peers not only undermined her sense of safety but also contributed to a dangerous dynamic where the stalker, who was also a colleague, felt emboldened to escalate his behaviour. The minimization of her experience by those around her had far-reaching consequences. Instead of finding support and understanding, Karen faced an environment that

downplayed her distress, which may have inadvertently signalled to her stalker that his actions were acceptable.

This lack of intervention or recognition from her colleagues created a vacuum in which the stalker's behaviour could intensify without consequence. When victims like her do not receive validation, it not only affects their mental and emotional well-being but can also embolden perpetrators. Ultimately, Karen's experience serves as a powerful reminder of how crucial it is for professional workplaces to foster an environment of support and understanding, which can play a significant role in preventing the escalation of such harmful behaviours.

In another informal disclosure response, the victim felt invalidated and the stalking minimized by the response received much like Karen. Interview participant Elaine who works within the social work services detailed how the misunderstandings about stalking in the workplace made her feel, which impacted her confidence in reaching out again:

'So I didn't. I think I may have told that, you know, a friend at work and then maybe didn't get quite the sort of reaction I was hoping for. And then just sort of shut down a little bit. I suppose I didn't tell so many people at work..... In there so and I think there's, I think there's a lot of misunderstanding around that even within social work clearly.....and it may also at times I suppose made me feel a little as though my what was happening to me was a little belittled me.' (Elaine, 43, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

The compounding of the psychological consequences of the stalking combined with a negative disclosure response to a formal source, specifically the police was also experienced by interview participant Emelia, despite her highly educated background in therapeutic services who stated:

'Weren't interested at the time they dismissed it as no big deal.... And basically said wait and see what happens. It minimized it. It discredited me as a person, as a human being. It my expectations of the police completely dropped to 0. The attitude of the police. How they dealt with, how they dealt with me when I reported it was. And it, it triggered feelings of helplessness.' (Emelia, 51, female, victim of a sexual predatory stalker).

The emotion Emelia was describing in her interview, as a result of receiving this type of negative response, can be seen in the choice of her words, and also in the stammering within Emelia's language. Emelia's description is suggesting that receiving a negative disclosure response can negatively impact how a person views themselves, their world view, their sense of safety and confidence to continue to seek help for their stalking victimization, resulting in serious psychological consequences which have compounded with the consequence of being stalked (McKeon et al, 2015; Becker et al, 2020).

The participants in this study shared profound insights into the psychological toll that a negative response to their disclosures can have on their experiences with stalking. Many of them felt that, in addition to already enduring the trauma and victimization associated with being stalked, receiving a dismissive or skeptical reactions from others, regardless of the respondent being an informal or formal source, and regardless of their own standing within their communities as professionals, exacerbated their emotional distress. This belittling treatment not only invalidated their experiences but also fostered a sense of helplessness, shame and isolation. When individuals who are already vulnerable reach out for help, only to be met with disbelief or condescension, it can lead to a deep sense of disconnection from their criminal justice systems, social circle, colleagues and the workplace environment. This type of response can make them feel as though they are not only grappling with the fear and anxiety stemming from stalking, but that they are also facing an additional layer of psychological harm from being treated as if they were over-reacting, or dishonest about their experiences.

Dismissive or trivializing reactions in these workplaces minimize risk, discourage reporting, and foster helplessness and isolation. Highly educated professions in the fields of social work, engineering, medical practice, and therapeutic services should formalize trauma-informed policies that define stalking with concrete procedures, establish multiple confidential reporting pathways, and require prompt, validating responses from supervisors. Mandatory training, anti-retaliation safeguards, and coordinated safety planning, such as, access controls, schedule adjustments, escorts, and documentation support are essential. By making protection visible and accountability routine, these fields can affirm the legitimacy of concerns, reduce harm, and retain a safe, professional workforce.

Discouraged from further help-seeking

This sub-theme elaborates on the experiences of 105 (35%) of interview and survey participants who disclosed their stalking situations and found that the responses they received significantly discouraged them from sharing their experiences with others.

Many victims reported feeling that the responses they encountered were dismissive or trivializing, which led to a sense of invalidation. This occurred from both formal (police, employers) and informal (friends, family & colleagues) respondents. The perception of minimization not only impacted their willingness to seek support but also contributed to feelings of isolation and helplessness. The data indicates that such negative reactions can create a barrier to open communication about their experiences, further exacerbating the emotional toll of stalking. As a

result, these victims may refrain from reaching out for help, fearing that their experiences will not be taken seriously or that they are understood (Crome and McCabe, 2001).

One female interview participant, Amy, had expressed how the seriousness of the stalking experience was minimized by two of her retail shop managers at work, and this experience of disclosing to this formal source was discouraging to her:

'The actual main manager. She was only in the shop a couple of times a week and she was between two different shops and two different locations. And she had a very..... Difficult of you or not of you on it and the terms that she didn't want associated with it? She didn't want, so that was kinda discouraging. And then my assistant manager, as much as she was the one that put that in place in terms of telling everyone, she was like, right. We can't just assume it's him. So let's just like we're we don't, it's not that serious.' (Amy, 21, female, victim of an incompetent suitor)

Amy's experience describes her higher management not wanting to be associated with the stalking, while the second manager Amy referred to minimized her experience by making Amy feel as though it was not as serious Amy felt it was. Both of these responses are why Amy felt discouraged with disclosing, despite the stalking occurring within in her workplace. The result was Amy felt dismissed and trivialized. Amy's experience suggests that despite some basic safety measures enacted by the management, the reactions to her situation resulted in Amy feeling like it was not taken as seriously as it should have been and this compounded the feelings of helpless and discouragement to further disclosing.

A discouraging informal disclosure response was also experienced by female interview participant Karen who detailed the minimizing response she had received in the workplace in the above section. Karen disclosed to her colleagues and felt the response was discouraging and detailed how the minimizing response resulted in her being traumatized further by feeling unsafe from not being believed:

'I cannot tell you how traumatizing it's going to have to deal with...So I feel, I feel unsafe. Like none of you any if he starts that again, none of you are going to help all of you are contributing now to this new world view that I've got that I'm not safe. And no one cares. No one's gonna do anything.' (Karen, 48, female, victim of an incompetent suitor stalker)

So not only did Karen express how traumatizing disclosing was for her in her workplace, the emotion that this feeling elucidated can be seen through the stammer in her discourse. The compounding psychological trauma from the stalking and the disclosure experience is detailed in Karen's expressions of how this experience changed her world view, (Crome and McCabe, 2001). Negative disclosure responses as these participants detailed, discouraged these victims from seeking

help for the stalking. This data also shows that apart from discouraging in future help-seeking decisions for their victimization, the consequences of minimizing their experience result these participants not feeling safe, not being believed or cared about, which is evidence of further trauma for a victim of stalking.

There is also evidence within the data supporting that a perceived negative disclosure response facilitates an increase in negative psychological consequences, including and beyond discouraging further help seeking for the victimization. For example, interview participant Trisha expresses the impact of having to disclose her experience repeatedly to formal sources, such as police and advocacy services:

'Those things added up to me feeling like I couldn't disclose anymore. Because I felt like I had disclosed so much by that point. I didn't feel. Mentally that I could go through it anymore, rightly or wrongly..... but I decided for my mental health and preservation not to do it...' Or is that it that you're just receiving some messages that you don't appreciate?' And I felt like it completely minimized my, what was happening to me. And I came off the phone and I was terribly upset. So my mental health. But like it was in. It's, it was in tatters. It was just in tatters.....' (Trisha, 37, female, victim of a rejected stalker).

Trisha described how her experience was minimized by the police and then by a women's advocacy service, and this had compounded each time she had to make a formal disclosure and experienced a negative response. Having to repeat her victimization and the responses she received negatively affected her mental health compounding the psychological consequences she was already experiencing by the stalking. The negative psychological impact on her mental health was expressed not only her words, but also by the repetitive expression in her discourse. Trisha had described in her interview how trying to seek help from this women's advocacy service contributed to her isolating herself and not disclosing, while the stalking itself resulted in her feeling her autonomy and privacy had been taken away:

'.....So, it, it really made me feel like, why are you making such a case of this? It's nothing happening. It's not like he's strangling you or something. It's not like he's come at you with a knife. And that kind of contributed a little bit as well to, to, to retreating and not discussing more. I have had no privacy. He's violated absolutely everything in my life. But they don't seem to really recognize it. Yeah, it takes away your autonomy as an individual.... Because she, she made it sound like all that was happening was a guy was sending me some messages that I didn't like, and it was so much more than that. And, and I was like, oh, wow.' (Trisha, 37, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

This participant experienced doubt, and was completely discouraged from disclosing, similar to the cases highlighted above. These experiences supports the suggestion that a victims' autonomy, safety, sense of self and their world view can be taken away because of disclosure responses that minimizes the seriousness of the stalking experience, highlighting the serious impact of not

validating a victims' experience, (Crome and McCabe, 2001). The participants in this theme have detailed the negative consequences to not responding in a supportive manner when a disclosure of stalking is made, resulting in these victims feeling victimized further, demonstrating further negative psychological consequences of isolation, self-worth and a changed world view, ultimately dissuaded them from further help-seeking decisions for their stalking victimization.

Disbelief or condescension toward vulnerable individuals seeking assistance from both formal and informal sources can sever their connections to the criminal justice system, their social networks, and workplace environments. This response compounds the fear and anxiety associated with stalking by introducing a further dimension of psychological harm. The intersection of ongoing stalking with skepticism from social and professional spheres yields a long-lasting set of psychological consequences that impair functioning across personal and occupational domains, leaving individuals feeling trapped and unsupported.

This data highlights the need for professional bodies, police, and advocacy services to implement clear, trauma-informed procedures to validate and protect individuals who are reporting stalking. These organizations should define stalking with concrete procedures, mandatory training, and practical measures such as, risk assessment, evidence preservation guidance, protective order support, and safe contact protocols. Visible accountability and consistent follow through affirm victims' concerns and improve safety and psychological outcomes and promote help-seeking behaviours.

Wished they hadn't disclosed

The second sub-theme that emerged under the minimized or invalidated heading pertains to the sentiments expressed by victims who conveyed a strong sense of regret about disclosing their experiences. This regret stemmed primarily from the reactions they encountered following their disclosure to both formal and informal sources. Many victims reported feeling that their experiences were not taken seriously or were dismissed entirely, leading them to question the wisdom of sharing such personal and painful information. For these individuals, the act of speaking out was intended to seek support, validation, or understanding. However, when the responses they received were dismissive, belittling, or lacked empathy, it fostered a sense of isolation and shame beyond the consequences of being stalked. Consequently, these negative interactions not only invalidated their experiences but also left them feeling vulnerable and exposed, intensifying their emotional distress.

The regret associated with a formal disclosure is often manifested as a desire to retract their statements or to avoid discussing their experiences altogether in the future. This response indicates

a significant barrier to open dialogue about trauma, as victims may retreat into silence rather than risk further invalidation or minimization of their experiences. We can see this through what interview participant Ishaan expressed:

'I wish I had never disclosed to the police because I would have been safer to be like, I accept. I've lost several years, but now I just need to go and I need to live my life. I don't want to show anything out legally. I don't want to do nothing. I just want to go live my life'. (Ishaan, 32, male, victim of predatory stalker)

In Ishaan's case, he expresses how disclosing to police made him feel unsafe, how he disengaged from pursuing legal proceedings, and regretted disclosing his victimization following the response of not being believed by police (Lysova et al, 2022). The observed response signals a significant obstacle to open communication regarding trauma and victimization, prompting victims to retreat into silence to avert further invalidation or minimization of their narratives. The next statement supports Ishaan's experience of a negative disclosure response which minimized the stalking experience, and also resulted in the creation of significant obstacles to disclosing. This minimization experienced by interview participant Karen to an informal source also resulted in this victim wishing they had never disclosed at all:

'I was very careful about it because I felt that after dealing with the colleague, it only amplified the symptoms instead of every time I reached out for help, it made my life worse.' (Karen, 48, female, victim of an incompetent suitor stalker)

In her interview, the participant reported that interactions with engineering colleagues exacerbated her symptoms and diminished her quality of life, thereby reinforcing the deleterious psychological effects associated with a minimizing disclosure response, similar to the previous cases reported. This observed reaction represents a substantial barrier to open discussions of trauma and victimization, prompting victims to withdraw into silence to prevent further invalidation or minimization of their experiences, (Crome and McCabe, 2001; Lysova et al, 2022).

This sub theme revealed how experiencing these negative responses to disclosures can make the stalking situation and the life worse off, resulting in victims wishing they had never told about their stalking experience. Negative responses to disclosure from both formal and informal sources can compound the harms of stalking, leading victims to regret disclosure, withdraw from legal processes, and isolate themselves due to reluctance to seek help. The cumulative effect is heightened isolation, as victims become increasingly hesitant to articulate needs, seek further assistance, or engage with formal support networks, which in turn constrains opportunities for relief and redress. These patterns highlight critical implications for practice, underscoring the need for

supportive, validation-rich responses from institutions and communities to sustain victims' engagement with protection and advocacy resources.

Sought further help regardless of response(s).

The third sub theme that emerged from the minimized and invalidated heading is a determination to continue to seek help, regardless of the responses that had been received following a disclosure. 46 of the interview and survey participants described such determination as a result of escalating stalking behaviours, known perpetrators history of stalking and fear that the stalking will not stop. As we have seen in the above sections, an invalidating or minimizing response to a disclosure, can heighten the victim's fear and erode their sense of safety and well-being, acting like an amplifier for the trauma. Despite these setbacks, many victims remain determined to protect themselves and to end the stalking. This resolve often translates into continued help-seeking, safety planning, and persistence in contacting services, even when initial support is lacking. These dynamics highlight the importance of consistent, validating, and trauma-informed responses from responders, as well as the value of empowering victims with clear, actionable safety options. One female interview participants Joan stated:

'I wouldn't hesitate personally, because I've thought a lot. Since his arrest about the fact that. I, I before I went to police, I thought it was all online and as a result of. Him being arrested and being told information by the police. I know how much more serious it was, which was quite traumatic to find out. But you know, I, I genuinely think if I hadn't gone to the police, my life would have been at risk.....It's just a marathon. I would just. I wouldn't be, you know, I would be cycling myself up to basically have to put myself through a lot again to do it. But I would do it'. (Joan, 25 female, victim of a sexual predator)

The participant's narrative traces a progression from a perceived danger to an enacted awareness of risk that ultimately influenced help-seeking behaviour. She recounted in her interview that the stalker's targeting of her partner emerged as a critical turning point, functioning as a determining factor that compelled her to contact law enforcement and to pursue ongoing assistance. This shift occurred within the context of a formal police investigation, after which she reported a revised appraisal of danger: she recognized that her own risk was greater than she had initially understood. Her subsequent reflections indicate that the heightened awareness of risk is a central driver of her current commitment to seek protective support and to intervene promptly should stalking recur in the future. Taken together, these accounts illustrate how relative risk appraisal, exposure to investigative processes, and acknowledgement of broader risk dynamics can shape proactive help-seeking and engagement with formal protective systems. The participant's

strengthened resolve to seek help in future stalking scenarios aligns with protective-action theories, (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010), which posit that individuals are more likely to adopt preventive measures when they perceive credible risk and threat, coupled with perceived efficacy of available responses. The account demonstrates how risk perception is not static but evolves through relational dynamics and formal investigations. This type of determination to stay safe, regardless of the responses received following a disclosure was also supported by interview participant Samantha who stated:

'Given I know this person's patterns behaviour, I had a duty to report it, given that they escalate very quickly and given the history I knew about the individual, so I had no qualms about reporting it to the police.... Oh, you've got feelings for the police. Got feelings for my employer, and I've got feelings for the cops. So it just fueled me even more to that. Now I'm. I'm gonna be a dog with a bone and I am not letting this lie.' (Samantha, 52, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

Despite perceiving negative reactions from both the police and her workplace in therapeutic services, the participant described how she maintained a determinate stance, her persistence appeared not to be diminished by external dismissive responses; rather, it is shaped by what could be described as the 'pathology' of the stalker, the systematic, intensifying, and potentially escalating nature of the stalking behaviour, interpreted as increasing her own vulnerability and risk. This perceived forensic characterization of the stalker's methods (e.g., persistent surveillance, credible threats) appears to heighten her risk appraisal and, in turn, calibrate her motivation to persist in help-seeking behaviours. In this sense, the stalkers demonstrable pattern of behaviour functioned as a proximal risk cue that anchored the survivor's determination to pursue ongoing assistance, despite institutional or organizational obstacles. The interaction between a perceived high-risk profile of the stalker and perceived institutional insufficiencies (or negative responses) may illuminate a tension where survivor agency is exercised through continued engagement with protective systems as a compensatory mechanism to mitigate risk, (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010). The known pattern of stalking by a female perpetrator was also found to be a precursor to the determination in another interview victims' case who stated:

'And so now plus we then found out that one of [xxxx] colleagues had left her practice because she couldn't cope with the, the attacks. She was afraid to go into her car. She was afraid to go home for being followed. All of that kind of thing. So we now have a lot of people. We've got now 15 people who are receiving unwanted actions and behaviours by her. So now we are escalating with the police and I think.' (Kathy, 57, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

The emotive language expressed in Kathy's recollection shows the emotional impact facilitated by the stalkers previous stalking behaviour, and multiple victims. The stalkers propensity to terrorize

Kathy's community fueled her decision to seek help. Joan, Kathy and Samantha expressed that they felt the stalkers previous history of stalking and persistence to stalk and risk factors gave them no choice but to continue to seek help for their stalking experience, regardless of the minimizing and invalidating responses they had received when disclosing the stalking. The data suggests that survivor determination can endure even in the face of formal and informal skepticism regarding stalking, particularly when the stalker's pathogenic pattern amplifies their perceived risk. This underscores the importance of aligning informal and institutional responses with survivors' risk perceptions to support sustained protective action.

Validated the Experience

The second parent theme of 'validated the experience' emerged from the data for 111 (37%) of the survey and interview respondents. This section details how the disclosure responses the participants received were perceived as supportive, and their stalking experience validated. Validating responses occurred for all 5 types of stalkers, with the rejected stalker (65%), and the intimacy seeker stalker (60%) receiving marginally more validating responses compared to the resentful (53%), the predatory (50%), and the incompetent suitor (55%).

As we have seen in the previous sections, disclosure responses that are unsupportive and invalidating such as dismissive or punitive after a stalking disclosure can heighten feelings of isolation, erode self-worth, and distort the survivor's sense of safety in the world, as well as discourage further help-seeking (Reyns & Englebrecht, 2010, 2014). Such responses may re-victimize the person, fueling a cycle of psychological harm that undermines mental health and overall well-being. Whereas, validating, supportive reactions, can reduce these adverse effects and support the survivor's path to reducing the psychological consequences of stalking (Becker et al, 2020). Since the disclosure itself can be a difficult choice, ensuring a validating response is a key part of supporting victimization. In one example, survey participant Adelaine details how relieved she felt at being believed when she disclosed formally to the police:

'It made me feel relieved and believed. I was scared and living in fear but I felt supported.' (Adelaine, 49, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Adelaine's quote details how feeling believed and supported can illuminate a path to relief even when the threat of stalking persists. Being believed validates the victim's reality and experience. Furthermore, this type of support reinforces that they are not alone and that their safety matters. Relief arises not from the absence of danger, but from a shift in how the danger is interpreted, managed, and endured (Ngo, 2020).

However, disclosing victimization is not always an easy choice for a victim to make, which highlights the importance of having a validating social reaction. For example, in another case, survey participant James' discussed his perception about the reaction he received upon disclosing to a formal source, police and social work:

'It means a lot when someone believes me, because it's a really hard story' (James, 20, male, victim of a rejected stalker)

Similar to Adelaine, James felt supported and being believed validated his reality and experience. Demonstrating that this type of support reinforced that they are not alone and that their safety matters. Another participant Trisha's interview response also examples similar support for Adelaine's and James's expressions as a result of the disclosure responses stating:

'I found that really supportive' [xxx] also did. [xxx] Also spoke to me, but [xxx] didn't make me go through absolutely everything in great detail, which was a bit of a relief and. I just, I felt comforted straight away and I didn't feel alone. That was a big thing. I didn't feel alone. Yeah.' (Trisha, 37, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Trisha details how the positive response from an informal source validated the stalking experience and helped her to not feel alone, feeling comforted that she was actually believed. In all of the cases presented, the reassurance that their experiences of stalking were validated and believed significantly contributed to the victims' overall well-being. When others acknowledge the victim's experiences as real, whether it comes from a formal or informal source, it helps counteract the self-doubt, minimization, or denial that can accompany the trauma associated with stalking.

Validation played a crucial role in helping these victims feel supported during a time when they may have felt vulnerable and alone. Knowing that others took their experiences seriously allowed them to navigate their situations with a greater sense of empowerment and strength. It alleviated some of the emotional burden associated with feeling isolated in their ordeal, fostering a sense of community and understanding. Such support can be instrumental in the healing process, as it encourages victims to share their stories and seek further assistance, ultimately leading to a more positive outlook on their situation and a greater likelihood of recovery from the trauma associated with stalking (Ngo, 2020).

Encouraged further help-seeking

There was one sub-theme that emerged within the parent theme of 'Validated the experience', which was, encouraged further help-seeking. 65 of the survey and Interview participants in the validated the experience category stated they were encouraged to continue to seek help. When a victim of stalking feels heard and believed, they gain the strength to seek ongoing support and

safety. Belief from trusted people and professionals helps to plan concrete steps, such as with practical protections, confidential guidance, and reassurance as they navigate next steps. Victims deserve support, and taking these steps can reduce isolation and improve their overall wellbeing, rather than experiencing a compounding trauma and increasing isolation associated with stalking. Disclosure responses revealed that having a positive and validating response encouraged some stalking victims like interview participant Sienna to tell people what they were experiencing:

'He's taking it seriously was extremely important. It's very validating. We told friends. We told neighbours we told everybody else adult that we could do with, you know, nursery schools, things like that. So certainly I would still tell as many people as I could.' (Sienna, 47, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

Feeling validated by others can increase willingness to seek help. When a concern is treated as serious and discussed openly, others perceive it as normal to seek help. Public disclosure can reduce stigma and signals that help-seeking is a shared, acceptable response. If people hear from credible others that a concern warrants attention, they are more likely to pursue support which creates safe, validating channels. Sienna also revealed that having this validating disclosure experience encouraged further help-seeking despite feeling worried about being victim-blamed and feeling shame about being stalked:

'There was still definitely a shame. There was huge amount of shame in being stalked, as if we had brought it on ourselves on many occasions...And because you still think of someone's sitting there thinking, what have you done to deserve this? What have you, what have you done bringing this on? ...So I would always tell people to disclose as much as possible and document as much as possible. That was vital and in the trial, that was vital.' (Sienna, female, victim)

Having a validating disclosure experience encouraged further help-seeking despite feelings of worry about being victim-blamed and feelings of shame about being stalked. Genuine acknowledgment from others can transform isolation into connection. When someone believes the account, a victim can begin to feel less alone with the fear and confusion, and start to reinterpret the situation as not as a serious boundary violation that warrants support. The relief of being heard can counteract the sting of judgment and the impulse to minimize or hide what happened, making it easier to consider practical steps like documenting events, or contacting trusted authorities. This validation doesn't erase the distress or the stigma, but it creates a small safe space where fear can loosen its grip enough to explore options. Over time, repeated supportive responses can rebuild trust in others, empower agency, and sustain help-seeking even when shame resurfaces. The

experience underscores the importance of empathetic listening, and non-judgmental encouragement in facilitating protective actions and healing.

Within the data it also emerged that there are invisible barriers that can exist for some stalking victims that can delay help-seeking, and for some victims, having a validating response from a disclosure can encourage further help-seeking. Getting support to work through those barriers that some victims experience is essential in their help-seeking decisions, and reaching out to specific charities can aid a victim to work through these barriers, (Backes et al, 2020; Boehnlein et al, 2020), as interview participant Joan describes:

'There's a charity called NUM, which helps sex workers. And they kind of talked it through with me before and did some research and kind of just helped me really assess the risks of me going to the police' (Joan, 25, female, victim of a sexual predator)

In this experience the victim details how she struggled to get passed the barriers that sex work can create when getting police involved in their life, such as difficulty with future jobs, and other associated risks. However, disclosing to an informed charity helped her to overcome these barriers and seek further help with the police for the stalking. In another case, which supports Joan's experience of disclosing to a charity that is specific to the needs of the victim, interview participant Denise states:

'Not at that point. It took me. It took me another 18 months to report it again.' 'But I think through the work with action against stalking, I think it's them not the police that helped me to pursue this...' (Denise, 58, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Denise and Joan have detailed how finding help from charities specific to their needs encouraged further help-seeking. Accounts such as these highlight that supportive responses can rebuild trust in others, empower the agency in a victim, and promote help-seeking even when barriers are present. The experiences underscore the importance of empathetic listening, credible information, and non-judgmental encouragement in facilitating protective actions such as encouraging help-seeking. This encouragement through validation was also found for interview participant Caitlin who sought help for the cyberstalking from a cyber expert she experienced as a student and a young person worried about the reaction she would receive:

'But no, I wasn't really the only thing I was worried about was the because of the social media aspects of it, and I was worried that if I got a person on the phone who might not have been much of a social media user and had a view of younger people like, that's all they do, then they think it's, oh, God, first world problems like. You know these kids, they're all bothering about their Facebook and TikTok. When I was actually worried about, I was actually worried about, you know, things like being exposed

and stuff like that. So when I did speak to the person, their reaction was good. It was. It was encouraging. Yeah.....' (Caitlin, 32, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Caitlin describes how she was worried her age and the mode of stalking may influence the disclosure response. However, Caitlin then goes on to describe how encouraging to further help-seeking the response to her disclosure was for her, highlighting the importance of stalking awareness and validation when victimization from stalking occurs.

These participant cases detail how an encouraging, a validating response to a disclosure can aid a victim in continuing to seek help for the stalking, regardless of their specific needs. To overcome barriers such as feeling shame and worried about being victim-blamed, and in some cases, reaching out to charities that were specific to their needs validated their experience, giving them confidence to overcome and feel supported in seeking further help, (Backes et al, 2020; Boehnlein et al, 2020).

Invalidating Court Experience

The third parent theme that emerged in the Disclosure Discourse heading was an invalidating court experience, which occurred for 3 (15%) of interview respondents. The impact of court proceedings on the stalking experience is often deeply invalidating because the process can feel distant from the lived reality of threat and fear. Victims may be required to relive traumatic events in detail, face rigorous cross-examination, and endure delays or adjournments that prolong uncertainty and anxiety. When judges, prosecutors, or defense attorneys express skepticism or focus on technicalities rather than the harm endured, victims can interpret this as evidence that their experience isn't being taken seriously, reinforcing feelings of self-blame and isolation. Public records, media coverage, or legal jargon can strip the stalking experience of its humanity, turning it into a legal problem to be solved rather than a human story with safety and dignity at stake. This can undermine trust in the system and diminish motivation to seek further protection or support, (Tjaden, 2009).

As interview participant Amy described, she perceived the court experience as demoralizing for, as the defense attorney questioned her as to why she hadn't disclosed the stalking sooner to authorities:

'And I, I, I look back on it and I feel like I wish I'd said something straight away because, I mean, even during the case when I was on the stand as a witness. It was very much made for. Why then why didn't you do anything? Why didn't you see? You think you could have just had a wee crush on you? It was very. Demoralizing. And from that I'll look back and wish that disclosed sooner.' (Amy, 25, female, victim of an incompetent suitor stalker)

Amy's excerpt highlights how courtroom questioning can inadvertently re-traumatize a stalking victim, by shifting responsibility onto them and casting their actions as the deciding factor in a crime's occurrence. Framing the victims experiences through doubt and blame, undermining the credibility of their testimony and implying that their reactions as inappropriate or insufficient. This reflects a broader pattern in legal settings where victims' accounts are filtered through a culture of skepticism and moral judgment, rather than validated as legitimate responses to trauma. The effect is demoralizing and can erode trust in the process, reinforcing silence and discouraging future disclosures. Whereas, for another interview participant Elaine, multiple court failings, dissuaded further reporting, as Elaine described:

'And I've had a lot of people say you need to just tell the police again, and I haven't because of the whole experience I've had with the criminal justice system and the fact.....That, you know, he's got away with it again and that it was. It was also very traumatic. And so it took so long too that so, like, in terms of the overall thing, disclosing again to the police is something that I haven't done. I probably should have done and that I don't think I will like, unless I really, really feel unsafe immediately.....I am so I've, I've definitely been put off disclosing to them again, having gone through that.' (Elaine, 47, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

Elaine's statement reveals deep trauma-informed barriers to reporting, such as the prior negative experiences with the criminal justice system, feeling that the perpetrator got away with it and that disclosure is re-traumatizing. This experience eroded trust and motivation to engage with police again. The normalization of ongoing risk, coupled with fear, disbelief, and the sense that reporting may not yield safety or accountability, leads to self-blame and hesitation about seeking help unless immediate danger is present. It also highlights the tension between perceived duty to disclose and the emotional cost of recounting abuse, suggesting a need for survivor-centered, trauma-informed responses that validate fear, reduce re-traumatization, and provide clear, practical safety options outside or in addition to formal reporting. Similar to Elaine's experience, Sienna found the court experience negative due to the length of time it took for her to achieve justice, stating how she understands after going through the criminal justice system, why people would refuse to support the court process:

'You know, as you know, it took over five years for the criminal justice system to finally get through a trial, and that was appalling. So I wouldn't want anyone to go through that. I can understand why people would go; 'I don't want to do that, I'm just gonna keep my mouth shut'' (Sienna, 47, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

The experiences of these participants of going through lengthy criminal court proceedings, cases that fail to hold a stalking perpetrator accountable and cases that allow for language that proposes victim-blame to the witnesses, can be demoralizing to some victims. These types of court

experiences have resulted in a traumatic experience, dissuading these victims from disclosing further and engaging with criminal justice systems (Tjaden, 2009). A trauma-informed approach would center the victims' lived experience, avoid interrogating timing or causality, and emphasize support, safety, and validation. Additionally, court dynamics, such as the amount of adjournments, burden of proof, the credibility battle, or the use of the perpetrator's narrative can re-traumatize victims by forcing them to narrate intimate details in unsafe or unsupportive environments. The emphasis on legal labels and procedural outcomes can erase the ongoing, practical realities of risk, fear, and daily vigilance, causing a sense of helplessness or a sense that the harm will never be acknowledged in a meaningful way. To mitigate these effects, it helps when court processes incorporate survivor-centered practices, trauma-informed language, clear communication about safety planning, and access to supportive advocates who can translate legal decisions into practical steps for protection and healing.

Stalker Type and Disclosure Responses

The fourth parent theme that emerged within the Disclosure Discourse heading was stalker type and disclosure responses. Stalker Type which is also known as Typology contains 5 types: resentful stalker, rejected stalker, stranger, incompetent suitor and intimacy seeker, (Mullen et al, 1999).

Typology of stalkers for Interview and Survey data

Gender of victim	Rejected	Resentful	Incompetent suitor	Intimacy seeker	Predatory/ unknown
Male	27	22	2	7	2
Female	111	60	11	12	42
Total	138	82	12	19	44

This analysis focused on the disclosure discourse whereby questions were asked of the participants about the type of stalker being perceived as playing a role in what response was given to the victims upon disclosing their victimization.

The sub-themes that emerged within Typology was: Predatory stalkers easier to recognize, trained in stalking and domestic abuse helped discourse, and gender bias and assumptions.

Predatory stalker easier to recognize

Predatory stalkers are stalkers that are not initially known to their victims, or they are stalkers with deviant sexual motivations, (Mullen et al, 1999). These types of stalkers according to 20% (4) of the interview participants were easier to recognize themselves, as well as for those they disclosed

their victimization to, compared to stalkers they may have known, or had a previous relationship with. This is exemplified in the interview conducted with Amy who stated:

'If it'd been someone that I knew, I think it would be a lot more difficult to recognize those behaviours. Just stalking, because it would be seen as a friend or a partner or anything, I think, and everyone else probably would not be able to recognize that or find it more difficult to recognize. But I definitely think that him being a complete stranger to me. It automatically rings alarm bells when a stranger. Create that connection. So it's I think it's a lot more easily recognizable.' (Amy, 25, female, victim of an incompetent suitor stalker)

Amy's statement highlights how risk recognition can be shaped by the relationship to the perpetrator, delaying the acknowledgment of the stalking in this case. The excerpt suggests that stalking by a stranger is more readily identifiable as threatening because the stalking behaviour aligns with expectations about safety from unfamiliar individuals, triggering clearer alarm cues. In contrast, stalking by someone known, such as a friend or ex/partner can blur boundaries, is more likely to be rationalized or normalized, and may be dismissed as "normal" relationship dynamics or misinterpreted intent. This reflects how familiarity can dampen perceived threat and reduce urgency to act, even when the behaviour is coercive or invasive. The result is a differential pattern of recognition and help-seeking, easier detection and quicker responses to stranger stalking, and slower, more conflicted recognition and potentially delayed intervention when the stalker is someone the victim knows, (Becker et al, 2020). Similarly, in another interview participant's experience, the behaviours by the sexual predatory stalker was also easily recognizable as that of every woman's nightmare as Joan expressed:

'I mean, cause that's, that's the kind of direct contacts that I experienced. And then there's what I was told by the police of this stalking that I was unaware of...Sort of tries to, to be supportive, but I guess you know it is. It is a shocking thing and it's kind of particularly for women, it's sort of thing that you just, it's like a nightmare.' (Joan, 25, female, victim of a sexual predator stalker)

This participant revealed an existing stereotypical representation of stranger stalkers compared to ex-partner/close relationship typologies that influenced the immediate identification of what she was experiencing. Much like Amy, the stereotypical representation of a stranger (Fox et al, 2011) was also found in Joan's perception as a typical style of stalker, as Joan perceived as a commonly held fear for herself, and for most women. Similar to Joan's case, interview participant Emelia recognized the stalking right away due to a sexual predatory behaviours as she stated:

'I put I put a name to it right away. This is stalking. I have a stalker. I am being stalked...Didn't help because it was a male police officer on duty that day and because I didn't know at that time it was a male stalker. But given the context and the time it happened, I had to assume it was a male stalker because of the sexual orientation, orientation of the contact...' (Emelia, 65, female, victim of a sexual predator stalker)

This statement underscores how assumptions about gender and sexual orientation can shape both identification and response to stalking. The victim recognized it as stalking, but the perceived gender of the stalker and the officer's gender, seem to have impeded help or validation, suggesting that biases may have influenced the response. The remark about inferring the stalker's sex points to how contextual cues can lead to misattribution and potential minimization of the threat. In contrast to the previous two cases highlighted, Emelia experienced disbelief when she disclosed what was happening to her, despite the stated sexual orientation of the contact, which Emelia perceived as discrediting to her in the form of what can be considered as victim-blame, (Scott et al, 2019), as Emelia stated:

'You know, I got at one point, the police said to me, that's what happens to single females out there attracting the wrong type, so they'd already discredited me in every manner whatsoever...' (Emelia, 65, female, victim of a sexual predatory stalker)

Emelia's disclosure experience with law enforcement suggests inaccurate misunderstandings of stalking, (Scott et al, 2019), including gender bias, resulting in her feeling victim blamed and discredited, (Taylor-Dunn et al, 2019).

Therefore, it emerged that typology in the context of predatory stalkers were perceived as more easily recognizable by the participants, compared to stalkers known to their victims. The majority of people the victims disclosed to, validated their experience, except in Emelia's case, the typology seemed to facilitate a very negative response by a male officer, (Scott et al, 2019). This highlights the need for trauma-informed, non-judgmental responses by criminal justice systems that assess risk and provide validation and safety planning regardless of the stalker's gender or relationship to the victim ensuring that biases do not obstruct recognition or support.

This section suggests that victims and those they disclose to tend to more easily recognize stalking when the perpetrator is a stranger or shows clearly sexualized, predatory behaviour, because it matches common stranger expectations. When the stalker is someone known, an acquaintance, colleague, or ex-partner, familiarity may make the behaviour seem less threatening and more likely to be explained away as concern, jealousy, or a misunderstanding, which can delay action. This study found no clear link between other stalker types and how quickly stalking was recognized, or validated, suggesting recognition is driven more by stereotypes than by actual risk patterns. Practice implications include behaviour focused indicators, such as evidence logs, persistence, intrusion, monitoring, and escalation to facilitate earlier recognition and response.

The importance of staff training in stalking

Another sub-theme that emerged within the data was that of the disclosure discourse perceived as more positive and helpful by the 30 (10%) of interview and survey participants. This occurred when the person receiving the disclosure was trained in how to receive a disclosure, or trained in the complexities of stalking, (Taylor-Dunn et al, 2018).

For example, one interview participant Elaine, who explained that disclosing to a police officer who was trained in stalking and domestic abuse helped the discourse:

'I'd been sort of referred by a friend to somebody who already knew the community police officer who was a woman and she had recently. She told me she'd recently been on some stalking awareness training. And online stalking training as well, so I think I was really lucky to have got her and to have got her already sort of coming sort of slightly pre prepared about what she was coming to talk to me about. And her response? And she came with a male police officer and his response to they were, I found them brilliant at that point.' (Elaine, 47, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

In Elaine's case, she was fortunate enough to have her first disclosure experience with a friend who was aware of stalking, who recognized the need for assistance from a trained officer. It was this awareness of stalking in both instances that resulted in positive disclosure experiences for this victim. Similar to Elaine's experience, it had also emerged that disclosure dialogue was perceived as positive by victims when the respondent was trained in domestic abuse behaviours, which facilitated a supportive response with this rejected stalker, as interview participant Darlene explained:

'...I had a friend staying with me at the time who've been involved in. She'd been a safeguarding lead and were involved in domestic abuse... I think it were a mixture in the content of this document and the type of stalker that I had that played a role in her response' (Darlene, 59, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

This statement points to how a responder's own professional background and personal experiences can shape their reaction to stalking disclosures. The presence of a safeguarding lead with domestic abuse experience suggests that the listener may bring specialized knowledge and expectations about risk, which could both enhance recognition of danger. The excerpt implies that a combination of the document's content and the stalker's type influenced how the friend reacted, indicating that prior training or beliefs about abuse dynamics can shape risk assessment, and empathy. Similar to Darlene's experience, training in the complexities of stalking was also supported in the interview case of a positive discourse experience with a rejected stalker for Jennifer. Jennifer perceived that knowledge in the context of domestic abuse and women's safety facilitated the positive disclosure experience:

'I don't know whether that's the, I don't, I don't know if it, if it possibly did because up in Scotland they kind of follow that into domestic abuse and obviously in more recent years there's been such a huge I think focus on sort of domestic abuse and women's safety and things like that. And I don't know whether because it sort of fell under that that's why it was taken so seriously. So well it wasn't initially but you know when it got to that point where. Yeah, they, I don't know if it because it was in that sort

of, ex, sort of intimate partner and it sort of fell under that sort of domestic.’ (Jennifer, 35, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

This statement reveals how the framing of domestic violence influences perceived severity and response. The participant is unsure whether the incident was treated more seriously because, in Scotland, domestic abuse and women’s safety have become a central focus, suggesting that systemic emphasis can drive credibility and urgency. The reference to the distinction between intimate partner violence and broader stalking indicates that categorization within the domestic-abuse framework can alter how seriously authorities take a case, how quickly they act, and where resources are directed. It also hints at potential stigma or skepticism when a case isn’t immediately recognized as domestic abuse, leading to delays in intervention. Overall, the excerpt highlights the impact of policy narratives on victim experiences, reporting dynamics, and the need for clear, trauma-informed assessments that prioritize safety regardless of labels.

Therefore, these findings propose that training in the different types of interpersonal abuse, like domestic abuse and stalking can aid in the recognition of different contexts of stalking, regardless of the typology of a stalker, facilitating a positive disclosure experience for these victims, (Taylor-Dunn et al, 2018). This underscores the importance of trauma-informed, non-judgmental responses that balance professional insight with the victims lived experience, ensuring that support is validation focused and tailored to safety needs rather than constrained by assumptions.

Gender bias and assumptions

In the context of assumptions and misconceptions, gender biases also emerged in the interview data. Gender bias is considered as assumptions about stalkers and victim gender roles that can influence a stalking disclosure (Fox et al, 2011). For example, an interview participant who was stalked by a male ex-colleague who was a resentful stalker, felt his stalking experience was minimized stating when he disclosed to friends:

‘When they thought it was funny and told me to ignore it, it really minimized the danger I felt. I had no idea what this guy would do and it really shook me, so it didn’t help. Once they started to realized then that was better. They took pictures and called the police.....I think because it was a guy and I am a guy it won’t be taken that seriously’ (Alex, 36, male, victim of a rejected stalker)

Alex expresses the danger he felt was minimized when he disclosed, and this did not change until the biased opinions from others were overcome with evidence of what he was going through. This statement highlights how gender norms and bias shape both perception of risk and response to stalking. The initial reaction of others minimized the danger and left him feeling uncertain and unsafe, illustrating how disbelief from bystanders can re-traumatize victims and delay protective

actions. The shift to action only after others recognized the threat shows how validation from others can catalyse a response, but also underscores how fear is compounded when support is slow or dismissive. The worry that, as a male victim, his experience may be taken less seriously reveals how gender stereotypes about vulnerability and danger can create additional barriers to help-seeking and reporting, potentially increasing risk and eroding trust in systems meant to protect. In another interview case it emerged that gender normative assumption of a strong male figure gave the intimacy seeker stalker an advantage, as Dawn stated:

'Because he is, I suppose he would be seen as like a.' 'Like a strong kind of like male figure. So they probably would be like, well, why is he coming to make that up when, just a young girl and it's obviously just she's done something. So I do think that I think he kind of had an advantage almost with his kind of type of stalker that he was.' (Kristina, 29, female, victim of an incompetent suitor stalker)

Kristina's statement reveals how stereotypes about gender, age, and power can confer an advantage to the stalker and undermine the survivor's credibility. The speaker suggests that the stalker's presentation leads others to question the participant's claims, implying that a young girl's report to her management might be dismissed as false or exaggerated. This reflects gendered biases within the response system that privilege the stalker's perceived authority or normalcy of male aggression, complicating recognition of harm and delaying or discouraging reporting. Whereas in another case, gender normative assumption also emerged by interview participant Kathy who was stalked by a female rejected stalker and felt this was contrary to popular assumptions, (Fox et al, 2011), that only males can be stalkers that stalk female victims:

'Stalking, particularly by a woman. So I think the classic model of an ex-boyfriend stalking a woman who, who then becomes violent. I think that is the only narrative in society at the moment' (Kathy, 57 female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Gender normative assumptions and biases, (Donne et al, 2018), as we have seen in these participant perceptions, can play a large role in the disclosure dialogues that victim's experience. This was found in a range of typologies, in the Male victim with a male resentful stalker, a female victim with a female rejected stalker and in a female victim with an intimacy seeker male stalker.

These cases underscore the need for trauma-informed, bias-aware responses from professional agencies, criminal justice systems and wider society that validate the survivor's experience regardless of the perpetrator's identity, and for training that centres safety and credibility of the victim rather than stereotypes about who is "worthy" of concern.

EVIDENCING THE AMOUNT OF STALKING BEHAVIOURS

The final theme that emerged in the interview data was that victims perceived police responses as, taking the case seriously when there were multiple behaviours, particularly when the victims' displayed a log of the multiple behaviours (Nichols, 2020). The log of multiple behaviours appeared to facilitate a positive police response for 25% (5/20) of the interview participants. Victims felt that their cases were recognized as stalking and deemed serious when they present a sustained pattern of behaviour through documentation which signaled the ongoing risk rather than a one-off incident. For these participants, the police viewed the case seriously when they observed the pattern of multiple behaviours, or course of conduct, which appeared to signal the risk, seriousness, persistence and need for action.

For example, one male victim Dave explained in his interview that his ex-wife was also being targeted by his stalker, and when police visually saw the amount of attempts to contact Dave in conjunction with the amount of attempts to contact his ex-wife, they then took the case seriously. Dave stated:

'Police were shocked when they saw how many attempts at contact were on my phone and my ex-wife's phone' (Dave, 49, male, victim of a rejected stalker)

The participant has conveyed that there were a large volume of contact attempts, implying persistent behaviour by the stalker and possibly sustained risk of continued persistence. The number of contact attempts across both phones revealed a persistent risk, which surprised officers and underscored the seriousness of the situation, which resulted in a positive response. In support of this finding of a visual representation of the amount of stalking behaviours elucidating a positive police response, interview participant Denise found the initial responses not quite so positive, until she showed the officer a 19 page long log of stalking incidents stating:

'Initially, I don't think it went well at all, he said. He didn't think it was anything to do with stalking. So I gave him the stalking log, which is 19 pages long, and he looked through all of that. He looked through all the communications from her, and I think that's. Turn the meeting around, a little bit. I think you could see what I was saying in terms of her patterns of behaviour.' (Denise, 58, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Denise's quote traces a persuasive arc from dismissal to recognition, revealing both institutional skepticism and the power of documentation. The participant began with a sense of frustration, signaling that their concern of being stalked was initially minimized or misunderstood. By introducing concrete evidence the victim shifted the dynamic from subjective claim to verifiable pattern, reframing the issue as systematic behaviour rather than isolated incidents. The phrase "turn the meeting around" marks a turning point in authority and credibility, the officer was possibly compelled to acknowledge her points, once confronted with cumulative proof. The emphasis on "patterns of behaviour" underscores how stalking often becomes legible only when evidence is

aggregated over time. Overall, the passage highlights the emotional labor required by victims to be believed and the critical role of meticulous record-keeping in securing acknowledgment. The importance of presenting a log of incidents that facilitate a better disclosure discourse was also found for another interview participant Elaine who stated:

'So I had 100 pages of print outs by this point and I, I often wondered earlier whether I should get the police involved, but I just, I didn't. And I wonder if I had, whether they would have taken it quite so seriously because it was. It was when they saw this how thick the print out was, and they flicked through it that I could see they were like, oh, yeah. Right. OK, well, this is this is a thing.' (Elaine, 47, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

The experiences of Dave, Denise and Elaine suggest that the victim presenting a multiple paged, multiple log of events was crucial to incite recognition from the officers that were receiving the disclosures, regarding the stalking behaviours that were occurring.

In all of the cases presented, the amount of stalking behaviours presented to the police resulted in the victim perceiving a positive police disclosure discourse. It appears as though the police were able to recognize the persistence and serious nature of the stalking that was occurring for these victims due to the presented logs and incidents of stalking behaviours. Given that victims of stalking frequently exhibit delayed acknowledgment or fail to recognize the behaviour as stalking, as discussed in the previous Acknowledgment section, they should be supported in adopting safe, systematic documentation practices even when uncertainty exists about whether an incident qualifies. Records should include dates, locations, involved parties, potential witnesses, and any corroborating materials. The aggregation of such data over time facilitates the identification of behavioral patterns, clarifies timelines, and links discrete events, thereby facilitating early acknowledgment while enhancing the evidentiary basis of their case. This approach is critical for countering skepticism regarding credibility or intent and reflects the reality that stalking often becomes discernible through visual evidence.

STALKING OUTCOMES

The Stalking outcomes base heading relates to the participants perceptions of why stalking is either still occurring or the stalking has stopped. Analysis included both the interview and survey data. All participants were asked why they perceived the stalking had stopped, of why they perceived the stalking is still occurring. The survey and interview data was organized in the category of Stalking Outcomes, and then coded under the themes of stalking still occurring and stalking has stopped to find the sub themes, please see the below extract from the data analysis:

Participant	Perceptions of Stalking Still Occurring	Perceptions of Stalking Stopped	Patterns/still occurring	Patterns/stopped	Themes
1. 0608		'No, no, I've not heard. I've not seen him since the court case.' 'No, no, I lost the job cause of COVID.'		Change in victim circumstances, left job	-change in victim circumstances stopped
2. 1998		??? So I know now that the behaviour started without me knowing.' 'And yeah, but I I was being stalked previous, but I just didn't know.'" It could have been anywhere between one and three years, I think.' 'Not Right now.'" Has been for the last eight months on remand.' 'And.' 'So I guess we'll see soon if he's gonna continue or not.'		Not sure of stopped, stalked unaware for 1-3 years On remand	Unsure- Police action stopped
5. 0705	'Six or seven months, but the indirect the change of behaviour, stalking behaviours is still ongoing.... I contacted the police. They went out to see her...'		**police warned stalker and behaviour changed		Stalker persistence
6. 2011		'No, because I moved. I had to leave my home.'		Stopped-Victim action-moved home	Victim action-moved
108347363	Police do not know what to do, or can't be bothered to help		Police Inaction		Police Inaction
108210727	I won't get help		Victim Inaction		Victim Inaction
108210575-		Police took action		Police Action	Police Action

The following sections of the findings for the category of Stalking Outcomes begins with the victim's perception of why the stalking is still occurring and will then move on to victim's perceptions of why the stalking has stopped.

Stalking Still Occurring

This section of the analysis consisted of data from approximately 47% of all survey and interview participants. This section revealed that 4 (20%) of the N=20 interview participants and 137 (49%) of the N=280 survey participants considered the stalking to still be occurring. All of these participants were asked why they thought the stalking was still occurring. Stalker persistence emerged with control as a sub-theme, Inaction emerged with two sub-themes which were, victim inaction and police inaction.

Stalker Persistence

Stalker persistence occurs when a stalker refuses to adhere to the victim's direct and indirect requests to stop the contact attempts and behaviours and continues with the stalking behaviour

(Ngo, 2020). Furthermore, this persistence was found to be a complete refusal to respect another person's boundaries, and can also include the boundaries that the police and courts (both criminal and civil) have set out (Brady & Reyns, 2024). Stalker persistence was present in 73 (52%) of interview and survey participant cases, where the victim indicated the stalking was still occurring.

As interview participant Darlene explained, the police formally warned the stalker, the stalker then subsequently changed the mode of stalking, rather than respecting the desire for the contact to stop:

'...I contacted the police. They went out to see her, but the indirect the, the change of, of behaviour, stalking behaviours is still ongoing' (Darlene, 59, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

During the interview, Darlene's body language and emotive stammering reflected the anxiousness that the ongoing stalking behaviours were creating for this victim, further impacting her psychological health. Darlene's quote underscores stalker persistence by showing how intervention did not end the behaviour but prompted adaptation. Even after police contact, the stalker shifted from direct to indirect tactics, indicating flexibility and determination to maintain contact or control. This behavioral change suggests an escalation through subtler methods, highlighting the need for ongoing monitoring and adaptive safety strategies. The concept of stalker persistence was also found in the case of survey participant Bella, who expressed that blocking her stalker had not deterred the behaviour, and every couple of years the stalker reappears:

'I blocked him on my phone but he has tracked me down on LinkedIn and sent messages and flowers. I haven't seen this person in over 14 years. I have no idea why he is still pursuing this - it gives him a thrill to track me down perhaps. There are sometimes a year or 2 gaps between him finding a way to contact me.' (Bella, 43, female, victim of a resentful)

Bella's account illustrates long-term, adaptive persistence from the stalker despite blocking, the stalker migrates across platforms (phone to LinkedIn) and shifts tactics (messages to flowers) to reassert the unwanted contact. The multi-year pursuit, punctuated by long gaps, suggests bursts of intrusion that can sustain obsessive engagement over time. The stalker behaviour also reflects a motive to reinforce the control despite clear boundaries. Bella's case is a perfect example of stalker persistence, despite not seeing the stalker in many years, blocking phone contact, unwanted gifts and contact attempts are still occurring.

However, stalker persistence was also exemplified as a result of a court failing to hold a stalking perpetrator to account, giving the stalker an excuse to ignore the victims' wishes, as interview participant Elaine stated:

'I've, after my case finished. There was then an appeal that he won and I'm still trying to get information about that from the courts and the stalking behaviour started again after that.' (Elaine, 47, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

The criminal court in Elaine's case first found the stalker guilty, however as Elaine points out a successful appeal overturned the conviction, and as suggested by this participant, this appeal outcome in the perception of Elaine facilitated the continued stalking persistence. This persistence is shown to not only be a result of the stalkers refusal to respect another's boundaries, but can also within the boundaries that the police and courts have set out on behalf of the victim (Brady & Reynolds, 2024) However in this particular case, the court failed to set out boundaries, which may have resulted in a more positive stalking outcome for this victim.

It also emerged in the analysis that another reason for stalker persistence is perceived as a forensic pathology by some of the victims. The known pattern of stalking (previous offences) has been found to be a precursor to stalker persistence (Reynolds and Englebrecht, 2010). For example Samantha points out that her stalker has a forensic history and stated:

'Still ongoing, stalking, this individual has a forensic history and they have a profile of stalking females.' (Samantha, 52, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

Samantha's quote signals entrenched persistence and indicates chronic, unresolved stalking behaviour, while the known profile of targeting women suggests recidivism and a patterned modus operandi rather than situational conflict. Such offender histories are linked to heightened risk and durability of pursuit, often resistant to simple deterrence. The profile-based targeting underscores a predatory element, implying the need for sustained, specialist intervention and multi-agency management. Samantha's perspective of a forensic pathology to stalk was also supported by interview participant Kathy who expressed her perception that the stalker is in need of mental health intervention to stop stalking, and stated:

'...two days ago I had another friend who said I've just had a text from her. Can I just check with you? She says, yeah, she's fishing. She's fishing to find out if you're talking about her because the court case is coming up. And, and deeply manipulative and, and that is the word that I would use at the overarching word, deeply manipulative. She's not a stupid naive. Depressed, lonely woman. She's manipulative. It's, it's pathological and she needs forensic psychiatry for it to stop.' (Kathy, 57, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Kathy's quote depicts persistence through adaptive, indirect tactics, as the stalker "fishes" via third parties to monitor the victim ahead of the court case, using social engineering to bypass blocks and maintain informational control. This surveillance-by-proxy suggests strategic, goal-directed behaviour rather than impulsive unwanted contact, and indicates escalation around legal milestones. The characterization as "pathological" underscores entrenched, treatment-resistant persistence likely to continue without specialized intervention and robust protective measures.

Furthermore, the emotive language used in Kathy's discourse expressed her frustrations and fears. This type of emotion is not uncommon in victim's expressions of their fears at the stalker persistence, particularly in cases such as this where whole communities are affected by the stalkers persistence to stalk. In fact one survey participant Blake expressed her worst fear stating:

'Nobody can stop him, he will do this until i die' (Blake, 25, female, victim of an incompetent suitor)

Blake's quote conveys perceived perseverance, signalling chronic, treatment- and sanction-resistant persistence and a history of failed interventions. This sense of lifetime pursuit reflects learned helplessness and the stalker's relentless boundary violations, often reinforced by intermittent contact that sustains the victims fear. Such language indicates elevated risk, erosions of trust in authorities, and the need for sustained, multi-agency management and victim support to counter the stalker's perceived omnipotence.

Stalker persistence was not only perceived as due to a pathology of sorts, but as a never-ending cycle by these victims whereby the stalking is still occurring (Brady & Reyns, 2024). This perception is clearly expressed by the examples of the discourse that emerged in this sub-theme despite the many ways the victims have tried to get the person to leave them alone such as blocking communication, involving police and even criminal courts. The consequence we can see in these transcripts, of stalker persistence is emotions such as anxiety and fear that this will never go away, until death.

Control

The analysis also discovered that stalker persistence was also perceived by participants as a form of continued control (Tittle, 1995). Participants' accounts in this sub-theme suggest that persistence is less about the unwanted contact itself and more about sustaining power through coercive control. Stalkers use a mix of tactics such as, surveillance, unsolicited gifts, platform-hopping, third-party contact and legal processes to continue to stalk. The motivation may be to reassert dominance after rejection or relationship rupture. These behaviours create chronic uncertainty, forcing victims to anticipate intrusion and adjust daily routines, which effectively extends the stalker's influence. Intermittent contact, especially around key milestones (court dates, new relationships), serves as reinforcement, signalling that boundaries can be breached at will. The aim is not resolution but regulation of the victim's attention, movement, and emotions, with fear and unpredictability functioning as tools to preserve the stalker's sense of control. This is exemplified in the case of survey participant Bonnie who was speaking about her rejected ex-husband and stated:

'My former spouse has now utilized other people (new wife, friends) to follow, watch, and attempt contact. He remains angry and wants control back.' (Bonnie, 47, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

In this case, the victim expressed the stalker is angry at the loss of control over her, which has resulted in the stalking still occurring using third parties due to the stalkers desire to gain or maintain control over his victim. This perceived motivation, a desire to control the victim was also supported by survey participant Daisy who talks about her stalking brother and stated:

'My stalking brother has had a life-long obsession with trying to control and, in his words, "ruin" my life.....' (Daisy, 39, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

Daisy's quote makes control the explicit engine of persistence and frames the stalking as sustained domination rather than episodic contact. The familial context lowers barriers to access and accountability, enabling long-term intrusion and normalization of abuse. By defining success as the victim's harm, the stalker's motivation is self-reinforcing, resistant to deterrence, and likely to adapt across life stages and boundaries, sustaining pursuit despite time, sanctions, or no-contact. Another survey participant Cora explains that her stalker needs to control, and stated:

'He needs a sense of control over the people in his life' (Cora, 25, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

In each of these instances, the persistence exhibited by the stalkers was viewed by victims, as being influenced or motivated by a forensic pathology associated with stalking behaviours. This persistence also stemmed from the stalkers' desire to achieve or maintain a sense of control over their victims, regardless of the extensive measures the victims took to put an end to the stalking. The stalkers' behaviour was interpreted as being propelled by underlying pathological conditions (Mullen et al, 1999), and/or driven by an urgent need to dominate their victims. This relentless pursuit occurred irrespective of how victims responded or the actions undertaken by the criminal justice systems to intervene and stop the stalking. The dynamics of control and power play a crucial role in understanding the motivations behind such persistent behaviours, highlighting the challenges faced by victims in seeking safety and justice.

Inaction

The second parent theme that emerged from the data was Inaction, as a perceived reason for the stalking still occurring. This was evident in 67 (49%) of the survey participants who expressed feeling as though the stalking is still occurring because of a failure to act, either from themselves or from others they sought help from, to do anything that might provide a solution to the stalking (Ngo, 2020). As one survey participant Celeste stated:

'No one will assist' (Celeste, 42, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

This participant is indicating that there is no one to help to stop the stalking which is why in her perception, the stalking is still occurring. Participants' perceptions link stalker persistence to systemic inaction: when police, employers, platforms, or courts fail to intervene decisively, victims experience secondary victimization and erosion of trust, while offenders are tacitly emboldened to continue or adapt tactics. Similar to Celeste, the expression that no one is willing to take action was mirrored by survey participant Joanna who stated:

'If family won't believe me, no one else will either, so no one will stop him' (Joanna, 32, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Repeated non-responses or disbelief produces reporting fatigue and learned helplessness, narrowing victims' options and increasing exposure. The absence of swift, coordinated measures (e.g., evidence-led prosecution, protective orders, platform enforcement) allows harassment cycles to normalize and escalate, turning what could be disrupted patterns into chronic abuse sustained by institutional gaps. For both Celeste and Joanna, the perception that no one will take action, due to either disbelief or reluctance to get involved highlights how inaction can result in a continuation of the stalking. Similar to these cases, in the context of inaction by others, survey participant Cindy expressed how others felt bad for the stalker and therefore in her perception, no one would take action to help to stop the stalking:

'No one takes me seriously, they feel bad for him' (Cindy, 25, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Cindy's quote captures how credibility discounting and misplaced sympathy enable inaction. By not taking the victim seriously and responders reframing the stalker as vulnerable rather than harmful, minimizes risk and shifts attention away from the victim's safety. This empathy bias undermines enforcement, delays protective measures, and signals impunity, which can embolden persistence and escalation. For the victim, such responses produce isolation and self-doubt while eroding trust and reducing the likelihood of future reporting. The disbelief that Cindy and Joanna experienced was also experienced by another survey participant Miles who stated:

'Because no one believes me' (Miles, 28, male, victim of a resentful stalker)

The statement by Miles highlights how disbelief functions as a barrier to protection and a driver of stalker persistence. When victims aren't believed, reports stall, evidence isn't collected, and sanctions aren't pursued, effectively granting the stalker impunity. Stalking often relies on cumulative, context-dependent behaviours that are easy to dismiss in isolation, making credibility discounting especially damaging for victims. The result is institutional betrayal and isolation for the victim, reduced help-seeking, and a prolonged pattern of stalking that could have been disrupted with earlier validation and action.

Victims of stalking often face the painful experience of not being believed when they seek help. This lack of belief, coupled with an empathetic stance toward the stalker, can lead to significant inaction from those in a position to assist. As a result, these victims feel abandoned and helpless, which may allow the stalking behaviour to persist unchecked (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011). This indicates that the disbelief experienced by victims serves as a substantial barrier to a positive stalking outcome. When authorities or support systems fail to take decisive action, the consequences can be dire, leaving victims vulnerable and at risk of continued stalking.

Police Inaction

Police inaction was a child sub-theme that emerged in the Inaction parent theme for survey participants. Victims in this sub-theme expressed feeling as though the stalking is still occurring because of a police failure to act, or do anything that might provide a solution to the stalking (Ngo, 2020). Participants framed police inaction as a key mechanism sustaining the abuse: when reports are minimized, evidence isn't gathered, or swift measures (protective orders, bail conditions, arrests) aren't pursued, stalkers perceive low risk and continue or adapt tactics. For example, one female participant Josie expressed explicitly that she perceived the stalking is still occurring due to police inaction:

'Police do not know what to do, or can't be bothered to help.' (Josie, 32, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Although Josie did not quite understand why the police would not act, it can be suggested by her perception that she felt as though the police were either not well trained to understand stalking, or that her stalking experienced was potentially a burden on the police. For another participant Mason, he also perceived police inaction to facilitate the continued stalking and expressed:

'Police won't take it seriously and can't afford to take him to court.' (Mason, 43, male, victim of a resentful stalker)

Both of these victims perceived that police inaction is the facilitator to the stalking still occurring, and examples how considerations of taking civil action can be difficult for victims, especially when there are financial constraints (Ngo, 2020). However, lack of evidence also emerged as a perceived facilitator to the stalking still continuing, and resulting in police inaction by participants (Brady & Reyns, 2024). For example, one female participant Tess stated:

'Police could not arrest him as there was not enough evidence' (Tess, 29, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Tess's quote shows how evidentiary thresholds can translate into practical inaction that sustains stalking. Because stalking is pattern-based and often subtle and at a single point in time which delays intervention, emboldens the offender, and signals low risk of consequence. This gap shifts the burden onto victims to keep documenting, which can be exhausting and dangerous, while contact continues or adapts. It underscores the need for proactive, evidence-led policing that aggregates incidents, gathers digital and third-party corroboration, and uses protective measures even before a full criminal threshold is met. The perception of not enough evidence for police to act was also supported by another female participant Tiana who stated:

'No evidence for police to act.' (Tiana, 25, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

High evidence thresholds as found in some of these cases, and inconsistent enforcement produce reporting fatigue and learned helplessness, reducing future help-seeking. The net effect is institutional betrayal: persistence is normalized, escalation risk rises around trigger events, and victims shoulder the burden of self-protection in the absence of meaningful intervention.

The sub-theme of police inaction highlights a significant concern among these participants, regarding the effectiveness and responsiveness of law enforcement in addressing stalking incidents. Many participants felt that the police did not treat their reports of stalking with the seriousness they deserved. This perception could stem from a variety of factors, including a lack of understanding or awareness of the psychological impact of stalking, or an institutional tendency to downplay such cases as non-urgent as or less critical than other types of crimes. Additionally, participants expressed frustration over the evidence threshold that the police required to take action. They felt that the stringent standards for what constituted sufficient evidence often left their experiences unacknowledged and unaddressed. This sense of being unheard not only contributed to feelings of helplessness but also fostered an environment in which stalking behaviours could continue unabated. The perception that the police could not act effectively created a cycle where victims remained vulnerable, and perpetrators felt emboldened to persist in their harmful behaviours.

Victim Inaction

Victim inaction was the final child sub-theme to emerge within the Inaction Parent Theme for the survey participants. Victim inaction is considered as the victims' perceiving that their failure to act, or decisions of taking no steps to stop the stalking is the facilitator for the stalking still occurring (Scott et al, 2018). Often this inaction stems from rational barriers: fear of retaliation, prior dismissal by authorities, trauma fatigue, resource constraints, and a safety calculus that avoiding engagement

may reduce immediate risk. The result can inadvertently signal low consequence to the offender, reinforcing persistence. This emergent perception is exemplified by participant Tia who stated:

'I have yet to send cease and desist as advised.' (Tia, 22, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

In this case, the participant has sought help and advice, and received the advice as stated, however has chosen to not act on the advice given, resulting in the stalking still occurring. Another male participant supports the perception of a victims' failure to act, as the facilitator to the stalking still occurring, as Corey stated:

'I guess it's still ongoing because I don't want anyone else involved, he will get bored eventually I hope.' (Corey, 22, male, victim of a resentful stalker)

This participant declared the reluctance to get anyone involved in his victimization, and has chosen not to seek help and simply hope the stalking situation goes away on its own as the perceived reason that the stalking is still occurring. Not dissimilar to Corey's case, the desire to not involve anyone can also be due to the victims fear and perception of potential consequences following a disclosure. This was exemplified by one participant Ada who stated:

'Because I'm scared to lose my job so have not told anyone' (Ada, 51, female, victim of an incompetent suitor stalker)

However, although Ada declared her barrier to action was worry that there may be a direct consequences if she told anyone about the stalking. There are also perceived indirect consequences that act as barriers to action, such as shame and embarrassment that can stop victims from help-seeking, resulting in the stalking still continuing, as participant Tilly stated:

'I don't want to go to police, I'm embarrassed' (Tilly, 53, female, victim of an intimacy seeker stalker)

Tilly's quote shows how shame and anticipated stigma can suppress help-seeking, indirectly enabling persistence. Embarrassment is often fuelled by fears of not being believed, self-blame, or exposure of private details and can create a barrier to reporting, so the pattern remains undocumented and unchecked. The indirect consequence of shame and embarrassment experienced by Tilly, was the same sentiment shared by Nora who stated:

'I'm too ashamed to contact police.' (Nora, 43, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Nora's quote also detailed how shame and anticipated stigma can suppress help-seeking, indirectly enabling persistence. The participants in this section, conveyed that their ongoing experiences with stalking were closely tied to their personal decisions regarding seeking help. A significant factor influencing these choices was the fear of potential consequences, both indirect and direct, that could arise from reporting the stalking or reaching out for support. This fear was shown

to encompass a wide range of concerns: they might worry about retaliation from the stalker, the potential for escalating harassment, or even the possibility of not being believed or taken seriously by authorities. Such anxieties can create a daunting barrier, leading individuals to feel trapped in their situation, ultimately choosing silence over the risk of confrontation or further victimization. This silence can signal low consequence to the offender, reinforcing control and escalating risk over time. It underscores the need for trauma-informed, confidential reporting pathways, validation from first responders, and accessible support (advocacy, digital evidence capture) that reduce the emotional and social costs of seeking protection.

Moreover, some participants acknowledged that they had received advice on how to manage or stop the stalking, yet they found themselves hesitant or unable to follow this guidance. This could be due to a variety of reasons, including a lack of confidence in the effectiveness of the suggested strategies, feelings of overwhelm, or uncertainty about how to implement the advice in their specific circumstances. The emotional toll of living with stalking can lead to a paralyzing sense of helplessness, (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011) making it challenging for victims to take proactive steps toward their own safety. This dynamic underscores a complex interplay between fear, perceived agency, and the emotional impact of stalking.

Stalking Has Stopped

This section of the analysis consisted of data sets from approximately 51% of the research participants. 16 (80%) of the N=20 interview participants declared the stalking has stopped, and 137 (49%) of the N=280 survey participants declared the stalking has stopped. This theme was explored when participants were asked why they perceived the stalking has stopped, and the parent theme that emerged was Action with two sub themes of police action and victim action.

Action

The theme that emerged in the stalking has stopped category was Action for 68% of participants. Within this theme there were two child sub-themes that emerged from the data which were Police action & Victim action. Action is considered as the process of doing something, typically to achieve the aim of stopping the stalking from continuing, (Taber-Smith, 2017). Stalking most often stops when decisive actions raise the offender's costs and cuts off access to the victim. Effective levers include victim-led boundary hardening (comprehensive blocking, tech hygiene, evidence logs and moving), third-party coordination (employers, platforms, housing), and swift police measures such as, risk assessment, evidence aggregation across incidents, protective orders, arrest/bail

conditions. This process of doing something usually begins with the victim seeking help for the stalking and an action that follows, for example one survey participant Cassie stated:

'Student was suspended from campus' (Cassie, 34, female, victim of a resentful stalker)

This case examples Cassie first seeking help from her faculty which then resulted in the student being suspended. These steps disrupt reinforcement cycles by removing contact opportunities, signalling credible consequences, and stabilizing the victim's routines. This action by the educational facility was supported for another participant Nova who stated:

'Faculty acted swiftly' (Nova, female, victim)

In both of these participant's cases, they chose to act and to seek help from their educational institute, these participants were believed when they disclosed which facilitated the institutions to act, and these acts are the reason the victims perceive the stalking has stopped.

Police Action

Police action revealed that positive police action following a report to them by the victim resulted in the stalking behaviour stopping, (Ngo, 2020), as one female interview participant Jennifer stated:

'No. Ever since he, it all starts when once he was charged, he was put on bail with bail conditions. And at that point it stopped. But I mean, that is mad that it took to like a legal. Intervention. So he went on. He was on bail. He had bail conditions and it wasn't to contact me by any means. He wasn't allowed on my street. If he see me in public, he would have to make the effort to sort of leave or avoid me. You know, those sorts of things.' (Jennifer, 35, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

In this case, Jennifer details how positive police action is the perceived reason that the stalking has stopped, however Jennifer also expresses in an emotive manner how she cannot believe it took this drastic measure of reporting to law officials to stop the stalking. Positive police action was also perceived by a another interview participant Dave who stated,

'Police went out and spoke to her and formally warned her that she would face a stalking charge of she ever tried to contact me again. Yes sure, if police hadn't have formally warned her I'm sure she would have continued or lost her mind and followed through with her threats.' (Dave, 49, male, victim of a rejected stalker)

As Jennifer and Dave both explained, positive police action in their cases resulted in stopping the stalking. The accounts shows a clear deterrent effect once legal consequences were imposed, charging the stalker and imposing legal sanctions which created enforceable boundaries that immediately stopped the behaviour. This highlights how formal controls convert vague warnings into

credible sanctions, raising the offender's costs of persistence which underscores gaps in earlier responses and the value of timely, proportionate legal measures to halt stalking.

However, for some victims, despite positive police action, it also emerged that there is always the worry by the victim that the stalking will start again, as interview Joan stated:

'Not Right now. Has been for the last eight months on remand. And. So I guess we'll see soon if he's gonna continue or not.' (Joan, 25, female, victim of a sexual predator stalker)

Joan's quote reflects conditional, relief and anticipatory fear: the stalking has paused only because the offender is incapacitated on remand, not because he has desisted or changed. The excerpt signals uncertainty about post-release behaviour, a common anxiety when control shifts from legal containment to the victim's risk management. This worry about the stalking starting up again was mirrored by female interview participant Caitlin who stated:

'I think it stopped because he was sentenced to he was sentenced to three years in prison. He still served like 1 1/2 I think. And then he was on a tag and now he's on license till September this year. So, I, I, I don't think he wants to go back.' (Caitlin, 32, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

The discourse surrounding disclosure between these victims of stalking and law enforcement has shown to play a critical role in the management and potential cessation of stalking behaviours. For some victims, sharing their experiences with police can lead to immediate interventions that help to halt the unwanted behaviours. These proactive measures can instill a sense of safety and support, fostering a belief that the law enforcement system is responsive and effective in dealing with such complex situations.

However, as highlighted by the experiences of various participants, there remains a significant level of apprehension regarding the efficacy of police action in truly deterring stalkers. Even when law enforcement takes positive steps, some victims worry that these measures may not be sufficient to change the stalker's behaviour. This concern may stem from a variety of factors, including the stalker's history of persistence, the psychological complexities of their motivations, or the belief that the stalker may retaliate against the victim for involving the authorities.

Victim Action

The second child sub sub-theme that emerged in the data is victim action stopping the stalking, victim action can take many forms, from disclosing to police, civil action, blocking, even changing jobs or to moving home, (Reyns & Englebrecht, 2010; Geistman et al, 2013). There are some instances, where the stalking persistence requires drastic action by a victim to stop the stalking, as exemplified by a survey participant Milo who stated:

'I moved my family away' (Milo, 35, male, victim of a rejected stalker)

Milo's quote captures relocation as a drastic, last-resort safety strategy: moving an entire family reflects the scale of intrusion. While displacement can disrupt the stalker's access and routines, it imposes heavy costs such as, financial strain, social rupture, schooling/work disruption. This drastic action of moving home was mirrored by another survey participant Paige who stated:

'I moved, I had to leave my home.' (Paige, 33, female, victim of a rejected stalker)

Having to take action and move home was also mirrored by survey participant Andrew who stated:

'I moved away' (Andrew, 37, male, victim of a resentful stalker)

All three of these victims found themselves making the decision to remove themselves and their families from their known areas, and support systems. Such moves often occur when institutional responses feel inadequate, underscoring the need to pair relocation with confidentiality protections (address suppression, school/employer privacy), rigorous tech hygiene, and enforceable legal orders to prevent re-contact.

Similar to these cases, drastic action can also include hiding contact details that the stalker knows, including moving to an area unknown to the stalker which was also mirrored by interview participant Ishaan who stated:

'...Because I escaped and they have no contact with me. When I escaped, I didn't give them, they didn't have my phone number, e-mail, and they didn't know where I was going to...' (Ishaan, 32, male, victim of a predatory stalker)

Ishaan's quote illustrates a decisive strategy as the victim severed all channels (phone, email, address) and disappeared, creating an information blackout that deprives the stalker of access and reinforcement. This form of enforced no-contact often combined with relocation and secrecy can be highly effective, but it shifts a heavy burden onto the victim to maintain anonymity through strict tech hygiene, confidentiality with networks, and possibly legal/address protection schemes. It underscores how stopping stalking often requires cutting every vector of contact.

For many victims of stalking, the decision to move home represents a significant and often necessary step toward regaining control over their lives and enhancing their safety. This drastic action reflects a proactive approach to mitigating the threat posed by the stalker, as it effectively removes the stalker's convenience of access and ability to maintain contact. In the eyes of the victims, this physical separation can serve as a powerful deterrent, leading them to perceive that the stalking behaviours have ceased as a direct result of their decision to relocate.

Moving away not only eliminates the stalker's ability to easily reach them but also disrupts the stalker's established patterns of behaviour. For many stalkers, the act of stalking is often rooted in a sense of familiarity and the ability to predict the victim's movements and routines. By changing their environment, victims can effectively break this cycle, forcing the stalker to reconsider their methods and potentially leading to a reduction in stalking behaviours, highlighting the complex realities of stalking and empowering victims to reclaim their sense of safety and autonomy.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the findings underscore the complex dynamics that impede victims of stalking from recognizing and disclosing their experiences. Societal stereotypes related to gender and social behaviour contributed significantly to the misidentification of stalking. Furthermore, victims often underestimated or dismissed their situations due to ingrained misconceptions about what constitutes stalking, the finding suggest that this occurred due to social biased understanding of what constitutes stalkers, stalker behaviours, gender normative roles and socially accepted gender behaviours.

The psychological repercussions of negative societal responses to disclosures are profound, often exacerbating the trauma experienced by victims and leading to isolation and diminished self-worth. Training for professionals in recognizing the various typologies (types) of stalking and stalkers, as well as the psychological and emotional needs of victims, is essential for fostering an environment that encourages disclosure and support. Validation from both peers and professionals is crucial in helping victims navigate their experiences, combatting shame and societal stigma. Moreover, the need for systemic change within the criminal justice system was evident, as lengthy and challenging court processes can deter victims from seeking justice and further support.

The phenomenon of stalker persistence also had a profound impact on victims, who often felt trapped in a relentless cycle of anxiety and fear. Victims reported various attempts to escape stalking behaviours, including blocking communication, involving law enforcement, and seeking legal recourse, yet many feel these actions are ineffective. A significant barrier that emerged is the perception that police and authorities do not take stalking seriously, which contributes to ongoing victimization.

Some victims chose not to seek help due to fears of repercussions, while others actively pursued assistance, which can lead to a cessation of stalking behaviours. Some victims have found that drastic measures, such as relocating or altering their appearance, can diminish the stalker's motivation and opportunity to continue their actions. The data also highlighted that while police

intervention can sometimes yield positive outcomes, there remains apprehension about its effectiveness in deterring some perpetrators. Ultimately, the findings underscore the critical need for responsive support systems for victims of stalking.

The findings of this study support the application of established theories such as Bandura's Social Learning Theory and Ullman's Social Reaction Theory, illustrating the psychological barriers victims face due to the fear of negative perceptions and the potential for minimizing responses to their disclosures. The evidence suggests that both male and female victims navigate a landscape riddled with stereotypes and preconceived notions that can cloud their experiences and reduce the likelihood of seeking help for the crime of stalking.

The findings also highlight that there are areas of this research that link the social and relational influences that occurred for these victims in their stalking journey. The first relates to how victims understand stalking, what it meant to them to be stalked, and how they recognized their victimization as stalking. For example, the Bandura's (1977) Social Learning theory can be linked to perceptions of stalking that influenced acknowledgment, whether it was the victims' perceptions, or others in their social networks, either aiding or facilitating acknowledgment and help-seeking decisions, and how the disclosure was handled. The second area relates to how victims felt about the process of disclosing, how it was handled, and what they felt the implications were for them following the disclosure. For example, Ullman's (2010) Social Reaction theory can be linked to victims' help-seeking decisions, victims' perceptions of how the disclosure was handled, and what the victims felt about the implications of the disclosures, which either aided or facilitated help-seeking, including the stalking outcome.

Strengthening awareness and education around stalking behaviours and their psychological impacts is vital for enhancing the responsiveness of both legal frameworks and social support systems. By acknowledging the multifaceted nature of stalking and prioritizing victim validation and support, society can take significant strides toward better protecting and assisting those affected by this pervasive issue.

Chapter 5: Discussion

INTRODUCTION

The discussion and theoretical considerations of this chapter are framed from the findings of this research presented in Chapter 4. The aim of this qualitative study is to explore how the societal understandings of stalking play an important role in the victims' journey of stalking victimization. The journey includes the nuances of the process of acknowledgment of the stalking, the complexities of help-seeking decisions, disclosure discourse, and the barriers and facilitators of these processes to the stalking outcome (the stalking has stopped, or is still continuing). This discussion will include academic literature, theoretical perspectives, and the findings in relation to the research questions explored in the study.

The discussion will begin at the earliest of stage of the stalking victimization journey, which is that process of realization or acknowledgment that they are being stalked (Reyns and Englebrect, 2011). The Chapter will also discuss the challenges that have been found within the help-seeking decisions and behaviours for victims (Jordan et al, 2007; Buhi and et al, 2009; Reyns and Englebrect, 2014), including the responses received when the victimization has been disclosed, (Taber-Smith, 2017). This discussion will also explore help seeking behaviours and discourses that have shown to potentially create either barriers or facilitators to the stalking outcomes, from the perspective of individuals who have experienced the crime of stalking.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This discussion section addresses the victims' process of acknowledgment, or failure to do so, and explores the first research question of this study: *How do disclosure responses influence a victim's acknowledgment of stalking?* Including the secondary exploration: *Are there any gender differences?*

Acknowledgment in this research is the victim recognizing and subsequently labelling their experience as stalking, which is the first stage in the stalking victim's journey. Stalking is an intentionally repetitive and targeted crime and academic literature has suggested that some victims do not label their experience as victimization until the experience meets with the victims' stereotypical representation of the crime (Fisher et al, 2007). Additionally, cognitive biases can affect many victims of interpersonal violence such as stalking, these social bias processes or mental

representations, can create misconceptions in a victims' cognitive understandings about an experience such as stalking victimization (Trimmer, 2016).

Previous research (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011; Ngo, 2014; Scott et al, 2019) have suggested that the seriousness and type of pursuit behaviours, as well as the relationship between the victim and offender can affect a victim acknowledging what they are experiencing as stalking. The current study likewise found similar results, thus supporting the claims by Reyns and Englebrecht (2011), Ngo's (2014) and Scott et al (2019). The findings suggest that stalking behaviours, along with the variety of emotions this crime elucidates for a victim, can play a significant role in whether or not victims recognize or acknowledge their ordeal as having been stalked. The current study also supports Reyns and Englebrecht, Ngo, and Scott's arguments that the victim/stalker relationship has no relationship to acknowledgment. Rather, the findings of this study suggest that the victim's own cognitive biases in the form of stereotypical misconceptions regarding stalkers affected acknowledgment, rather than the relationship between the perpetrator and victim.

Expanding on such propositions, the current study revealed that the majority of participants would eventually acknowledge their experience as stalking. As for majority interview and survey participants (93%) acknowledgment occurred, albeit, 85% of interview participants indicated an ongoing process in which recognition and acknowledgment occurred over a period of time. This delay in acknowledgement supports previous research by Ngo (2014) and Fisher et al (2003), whom both proposed that cognitive bias played a role in victims' acknowledgment. The current study found that cognitive bias in the form of common misconceptions of stalker types and the stalking behaviours delayed the realization of the stalking, evidenced in approx. 71% of interview cases. The common misconceptions in these cases were found in the expressions of their own perceptions, whereby their mental representations or social biases interfered with acknowledging the experience as stalking. Proposing that the stereotypical representations of stalkers for these participants interfered with the acknowledgement of the experience as stalking. However, the delay in acknowledgment was corrected by friends and professionals who recognized the stalking, who pointed out to approx. 50% of the interview victims, both male and female, that what they were experiencing was in fact stalking behaviours, therefore facilitating the stalking acknowledgment.

Drawing on social learning and cognitive frameworks, bias can be understood as a distortion in the mental representations individuals use to interpret interpersonal behaviour (Trimmer, 2016). Misconceptions, gendered norms, and the romanticizing or minimization of intrusive pursuit are socially learned through repeated exposure to cultural scripts, circulating in news, film, television, social media, and everyday discourse (Becker et al, 2020). These learned representations provide

stereotypical prototypes of stalking (e.g., stranger pursuit, overt threat, and continuous surveillance) and normative courtship scripts that recode persistence as care or desirability. Applied to the present data, participants' narratives indicate that such perceptions shaped their interpretive thresholds: their pre-existing representations and social biases disrupted recognition, constraining the acknowledgement of their experiences as stalking when those experiences deviated from the stereotype (e.g., known perpetrator, intermittent contact, digitally mediated monitoring, or behaviour framed as romantic).

Cognitive bias was primarily presented in the form of stereotypical portrayals of stalkers in this study. This is something which contributed to misunderstandings in regard to common stalking behaviours. In the interviews, this was found for 20% of participants who experienced a delay in acknowledgment, particularly in the context of cyberstalking, which hindered their ability to recognize and acknowledge the stalking they were experiencing. Given that the stalking behaviour occurred online directly impacted stalking acknowledgment. Participants indicated that they were unaware that stalking could ultimately occur solely through electronic means. Similar to other participant cases noted in the prior chapter, it was not until professionals who were trained in stalking intervened, and helped reframe the social bias and misconceptions, that the victims then began to recognize their own situation. This highlights how societal bias can impact on ones' understanding of stalking incidents. In these cases, the participants struggled to interpret their experiences accurately due to prevailing misconceptions as to what constitutes stalking. Only following the disclosure of their experiences were they able to acknowledge stalking as having occurred.

Additionally, and in light of the findings presented in this study, the results are at odds with the conclusions drawn by Becker et al (2020), concerning perceptions of stalking and the typologies of stalkers. Becker and colleagues posited that factors such as stalking typology, the gender of the stalker, and the attitudes of observers can significantly influence how victims perceive their stalking experiences. Their research indicated that women are generally more inclined than men to view cyberstalking as unacceptable. However, the current study offers a contrasting perspective. A notable contrast in the area of cyberstalking as the cyberstalking behaviours did not serve as a catalyst for recognizing stalking incidents among both male and female victims. Instead, the key factor that facilitated the recognition of stalking was the act of disclosing their experiences to others, having been greatly influenced by discussions with trained responders familiar with cyberstalking behaviours. These responders played a crucial role in helping to clarify misconceptions surrounding the behaviours the victims experienced, ultimately leading to a realization that they were indeed victims of stalking. It was only through this process of disclosure and social discourse that victims

were able to overcome their misconceptions and acknowledge the severity of their experience, as stalking.

It can therefore be suggested that disclosure discourse can impact acknowledgment of stalking, for both genders. This was evidenced despite the existence of barriers such as social biases, and stereotypical representations, as the responders to the discourse was shown to aid victims in overcoming these misconceptions in some of the cases presented. It can therefore be argued that a victims discourse with another, can facilitate social learning. Specifically the reframing and correcting previously learned perceptions, biases and misconceptions and aid in the acknowledgment of stalking for a victim, particularly when the responder is trained in stalking awareness. These findings emphasize the need for fostering environments that encourage disclosures and raise awareness about stalking. This is crucial, as not all victims recognize that they are being stalked, and not everyone feels comfortable sharing their experiences.

Non-Acknowledgment of stalking

The importance of fostering environments that encourage stalking awareness and therefore disclosures is underscored in this study by the 25 of the male and female survey participants, whereby the stalking was not acknowledged at all. Non-acknowledgment was evident despite the participants positively answering the stalking qualifying questions as a person who had experienced targeted, unwanted behaviours on at least two occasions, resulting in experiencing fear and alarm. The non- acknowledgment was found to be a result of social biased perceptions, and misconceptions of stalking, supporting the Fisher et al (2003) study previously mentioned, who argued that cognitive biases play a role in stalking acknowledgement. For example, the misconception that stalkers present behaviours in a stereotypical manner, such as waiting outside, and that stalkers are only strangers. Additionally, the findings from this research also lend support for the work of Fox et al (2011) who proposed that social learning misconceptions are the result of representations from news media coverages, films and television, social media representations and common social understandings of the crime of stalking, highlighting the importance of fostering awareness within wider society and the importance of accurate media portrayals on the realities of stalking.

To support the argument and reinforce Fisher et al's (2003) claim that being physically followed is a frequent misunderstanding among victims where the stalker's actions do not align with predefined understanding of the definition of stalking. Such common misconceptions can have serious implications for recognizing stalking, particularly in relation to stereotypical images of stalkers and their behaviours. Because the experiences did not fit their mental representations,

some victims, did not perceive their situations as stalking. These misconceptions were often driven by societal biases and cognitive distortions, leading these individuals to fail to recognize their experiences as stalking.

Cognitive biases are considered as mental distortions, or mental representations according to Trimmer (2016) and are developed through learning in the environment, and within social interactions, a similar suggestion to the Fox et al (2011) literature. Social learning can create misconceptions as we have seen evidenced in the current research, which can lead to a delay in acknowledgement or failing to acknowledge that what the individual is experiencing is actually stalking victimization. The findings of this research support the argument that cognitive biases can affect many victims of interpersonal crime, such as stalking. Fisher et al (2003) argued that behaviours which are commonly assumed to coincide with a crime, such as stalking, are often the stereotypical representations, for example, being followed, watched or spied on, and is supportive of the Albert Bandura (1977) Social Learning Theory (SLT).

Social learning theory (SLT) emphasizes the role of observation, imitation, and vicarious modelling in learning behaviours, and are a result of interactions in the social environment, which have been exemplified throughout in the participant's expressions of stereotypical representations and social bias (Todd et al, 2021). This framework can be applied to understanding these stereotypical representations and cognitive biases related to the crime of stalking in several ways. Individuals often learn about social norms and behaviours through media, peer interactions, and societal narratives. Additionally, SLT can explain how a victims' cognitive biases, such as victim-blaming or the belief that stalking is not serious, can be reinforced through social interactions and cultural narratives. Specifically, if individuals observe that stalking victims are often blamed for the behaviour of their stalkers, they may adopt this bias, leading to a lack of empathy and support for victims. The theory also suggests that behaviours that are rewarded are more likely to be repeated. If stalking behaviors are romanticized or rewarded in social contexts, like gaining attention, individuals may be more likely to engage in or tolerate such behaviours. This reinforcement can perpetuate stereotypes and biases surrounding stalking.

Social Learning and Stalking Acknowledgment

In the course of this study so far, we have examined various case examples related to the acknowledgment of stalking. These cases have highlighted how social learning processes have contributed to the development of cognitive biases and stereotypical representations concerning

both stalker types and stalking behaviours. These biases and stereotypes have shown to influence how victims perceive their own experiences, the interactions with others, both of which have either hindered or promoted the acknowledgment of stalking. Specifically, the cases presented illustrate that social learning mechanisms, such as observation of societal narratives and media portrayals, have led to the internalization of certain beliefs about stalking. For instance, victims may adopt the notion that they are somehow responsible for the stalking behaviour, or they may believe that such behaviours are not serious enough to warrant concern due to gender and cultural normative perceptions. Or they may believe that all stalkers fit a specific stereotype, or misconceptions that stalking is limited to in-person encounters. They may also have the belief that only celebrities or public figures experience stalking. All of these cognitive biases in this study prevented or delayed these victims from recognizing that what they were experiencing was actually the crime of stalking.

These ingrained perceptions can create substantial barriers to acknowledging the reality of stalking, as victims may feel shame or doubt regarding their experiences. Conversely, the same social learning processes can also serve as facilitators of acknowledgment. When victims see positive representations of those who speak out against stalking or find support from peers and communities, they may feel empowered to recognize and address their situations. Ultimately, the interplay of these cognitive biases and societal representations plays a crucial role in shaping victims' experiences and their ability to seek help and validation in the face of stalking.

Additionally, the Social Learning Theory (SLT) was applied to victims' acknowledgment of stalking in the context of cognitive biases similar to those set out by Trimmer (2016) and Fox and colleagues (2011) in this research. A cognitive bias can be considered as a distorted mental representation according to Trimmer (2016), and Fox et al (2011) argued that victimization can occur as a result of overlaps with some conceptual frameworks regarding victimization, such as stalking when perceived as ordinary, common, and socially acceptable behaviour (Todd et al, 2021). However, the current study suggests that the social learning did not appear to elucidate the stalking, as indicated by Fox and colleagues, but rather delayed or even failed the victim's realization of their experience as the crime of stalking. Furthermore, this finding supports the Becker et al (2020) proposition that cognitive biases can affect perceptions of stalking acknowledgment. This study found support for cognitive biases, but also in the form of gender normative roles, delaying acknowledgment, until the bias was reframed through disclosure discourse as exemplified in the cases described above. Therefore, as exemplified so far in the current research, stalking acknowledgment can in some cases be facilitated through social learning.

In contrast, to the finding of social learning facilitating stalking acknowledgment through discourse, there is also support that can be suggested for social learning playing a role as a barrier in the context of cognitive biases delaying stalking acknowledgment. Arguing further that social learning can create misconceptions, or cognitive distortions in relation to the types of stalking behaviours and contact attempts experienced by the victims. This was exemplified in the above mentioned sections, whereby the stalking was not acknowledged despite receiving hundreds of stalking contact and pursuit behaviours. The acknowledgment of the stalking did not occur until the stereotypical representation of stalking was met, such as being followed by the stalker, which facilitated the acknowledgment of stalking. This suggests support for the potential barriers of SLT in relation to stalking perspectives of stereotypical behaviours and representations, as proposed by researchers such as (Fisher et al, 2003; Ngo, 2014; Becker et al, 2020). Therefore, these findings suggest that the SLT can be applied within the context of cognitive normalizations within the paradigm of stalking, as suggested by Fisher et al (2003). Perceptions can delay, acting as barriers to acknowledgment of what a victim is actually experiencing. This has been evidenced in this study, particularly when the stalking behaviours have been normalized, or deemed common and acceptable.

Additionally, the Reyns and Englebrecht study, approximately 40% of men and 39% of women did acknowledge their experience as stalking (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011). However, in the current study, 99% of males, and 90% of females acknowledged the stalking. The difference in recognition between the two studies may be due to an increase in stalking awareness following the implementation of stalking laws in the UK compared to the USA where in many states stalking is not a stand-alone criminal offence. This difference may also be due to media and news coverage in the decades between the studies, which may have facilitated social learning in the context of stalking, which in itself would make for an interesting study, although out of scope for this particular research.

The current study of acknowledgment proposes that there are differences between male and female genders in the context of the types of misconceptions experienced by each gender that may affect stalking acknowledgment, such as gender representations and stereotypical representations. However, disclosure discourse can facilitate acknowledgment equally. This proposition was evidenced in the female participant cases who expressed common stalking misconceptions, or normalizations about stalker behaviours. In the cases of the male participants, they exemplified having experienced gender and cultural normative assumptions. For both genders, this delay in acknowledgement occurred until speaking to others who aided the victims to reframe their cognitive distortions, therefore facilitating the acknowledgment of the stalking. The evidence suggests that

social learning in the context of common misconceptions can either act as a barrier in failing or delaying, or act as a facilitator to stalking acknowledgment, regardless of gender.

The evidence also suggests that there is a relationship between disclosure discourse and acknowledgment, evidenced in the cases where acknowledgment was facilitated by the responders to the disclosure, particularly when the responder was trained in stalking awareness. This is an important point to highlight because previous research conducted by (Nicastro et al, 2000; Baum et al, 2009; Ngo, 2014; Monkton-Smith et al, 2017; Todd et al, 2021), which has indicated that only half of all the stalking episodes experienced are reported to police, despite the psychological, social, financial, severe physical and even lethal risk factors which are known consequences that stalking has on victims. Highlighting the importance of understanding the nuances of the stalking victimization journey to the barriers and facilitators of help-seeking behaviours for victims of stalking.

HELP-SEEKING DECISIONS

This section of the research emerged from the data exploring help-seeking decisions that victims make in their stalking journey and resulted in a secondary examination of the factors that may potentially influence a victims' decision not to disclose their stalking victimization. Although the majority of participants in this study chose to seek help for the stalking, 20% of survey participants declared that they chose not to disclose or seek help, of the 20% non-disclosures; 37% were Male participants, and 63% were female participants. The gender difference in the numbers of non-disclosures in this study may be due to the disproportionate numbers of female participants (N=223) compared to males (N=57), and certainly warrants an investigation, although out of scope of the current study.

Previous literature (Buhi et al, 2009; Lysova et al, 2022) have suggested the factors of why stalking is so under disclosed is predominantly due to victims perceptions such as; did not feel the situation was serious enough to disclose, wanted to handle the situation on their own, felt it was a private/personal matter, fearful of revenge, and felt police would not believe them, fear for their safety and were worried they would be re-victimized within the criminal justice systems. The literature (Reyns and Englebrect, 2009; Logan and Walker, 2009) have also argued that stalking is an under-disclosed crime, and investigations understanding the influential factors of victims' help-seeking decisions is vital to improve reporting.

Psychologically, perception driven minimization of their stalking experience led some victims to appraise the stalking behaviour as not serious, normalize handling it privately, or prioritize

autonomy, while threat appraisal balanced fear of retaliation against the anticipated benefits of reporting. Socially, learned relationship scripts and norms of self-reliance framed stalking as a personal matter, and anticipated stigma or disbelief from informal networks which discouraged disclosure. Systemically, low perceived police efficacy, credibility discounting, and expectations of secondary victimization within the criminal justice system elevated the perceived costs of reporting, reducing behavioural intentions to seek formal support. Applied to the present data, the reasons cited by participants such as minimization of their experience, preference for self-management, privacy concerns, fear of revenge, and skepticism about police belief map onto these mechanisms, jointly constraining acknowledgment, disclosure, and help-seeking. Consistent with prior work identifying stalking as under-disclosed (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2009, 2011; Logan and Walker, 2009; Lysova, 2022), this integrated framework indicates that interventions should target appraisal processes (risk and harm), reshape social norms through informed education, and strengthen institutional trust and procedural protections to shift the cost–benefit calculus toward disclosure.

Did Not Disclose

Some of the participants who chose not to disclose, expressed feelings of shame and embarrassment as the perceived barrier to reaching out for help, and therefore chose to not disclose their victimization. Understanding the barriers to help-seeking is vital to addressing support for victims of stalking, considering the evidence of the adverse psychological consequence of stalking, as proposed by Logan & Walker (2009). Additionally, previous research, such as Brady (2022) has also suggested that seeking help, particularly from formal sources such as the police can be a significant factor to the stalking stopping.

Fear of Others Reactions

The current study found that victims' feelings of not wanting others involved in the stalking can occur from feelings of shame and/or embarrassment, creating barriers for victims in their help-seeking decisions, despite the evidence of the psychological consequences of being stalked (Logan & Walker, 2009; Dardis et al, 2021). For example, the feelings of shame and embarrassment dissuaded 41% of both male and female participants in this category from disclosing their stalking experience. This suggests support for the Logan & Walker (2009) and the Dardis et al (2021) studies that concluded the psychological consequences of stalking itself can pose barriers to seeking support, due to victims experiencing shame, anxiety and depression. These findings are supported by the

participants who declared feeling ashamed about being stalked, and chose to remain isolated in their experience. Social cognitive and reaction frameworks explain how gendered courtship scripts and victim-blaming norms are internalized, converting anticipated social judgment into self-reproach (Edwards et al, 2014; Dworkin et al, 2019). These mechanisms increase perceived responsibility, heighten threat to identity, and suppress disclosure and help-seeking, even when the perpetrator's conduct meets legal or clinical criteria for stalking.

This study found evidence that fear of others' reactions, expressed as gender normative roles and assumptions were also a facilitator for causing the embarrassment or shame, and these fears resulted in dissuading some victims from seeking help. Specifically, the perceived gender normative male role caused embarrassment for male participants, despite clear references being made in respect of being fearful of their stalker, these fears resulted in the worry of others perceptions which dissuaded help seeking for the stalking. Respectively, the fear of others perceptions overrode the fear of the stalkers. However, fear has shown in previous research as the most common impact disclosed as a result of stalking; fear of that stalking would never stop, physical harm, and death by the stalker (Baum et al, 2009; Logan and Walker, 2009). Within help-seeking models (Donne et al, 2018), this dynamic operates as a help-negation effect; the distress (e.g., fear that the stalking will never stop, fear of physical harm or death) and can even decrease intentions to seek assistance to both formal and informal sources when the self-identity and conformity to masculine norms are strong. Thus, embarrassment functions as an identity-protective barrier that outweighs risk appraisal, explaining why pronounced fear coexists with non-disclosure among male participants.

However, this study argues that for victims of both male and female genders, the primary barrier to seeking help lies in the fear of how others will react to their situation, rather than a direct fear of the stalker themselves. This finding aligns with Ullman's (2010) Social Reaction Theory (SRT), which posits that the informal reactions to disclosures of victimization can fall into two categories: positive responses that are validating and supportive, or negative responses that involve disbelief or victim-blaming.

The implications of this study suggest that the Ullman (2010) SRT is not only applicable to actual responses from others, but also extends to the anticipated or projected reactions that victims fear. This means that even when a victim has not disclosed their experience, the mere possibility of how others might respond can evoke feelings of embarrassment and shame. These emotions can significantly influence their decision-making process regarding whether to seek help. In essence, the fear of potential negative reactions from peers, family, or society at large can be a powerful

deterrent, overshadowing even the fear of the stalker. Victims may grapple with internalized stigma and the worry that they will not be believed or will be blamed for their victimization, which can prevent them from reaching out for much needed support (Edwards et al, 2014; Dworkin et al (2019). As such, addressing these social perceptions and fostering an environment of understanding and validation is crucial in encouraging victims to seek help.

As previously mentioned, and in support of the previous literature (Baum et al, 2009; Edwards et al, 2014; Dworkin et al, 2019), victims perceived fear of the stalkers' behaviour escalating, the potential of being physical harmed, the stalking never stopping, or even fear of death are commonly experienced by victims of stalking. However, the consequences of the unwanted stalking contacts and pursuit behaviours on the victims have shown to result in; feelings of anxiety and concern, feeling helpless, depression and suicidal ideation because of the stalking (Logan & Walker, 2009). Understanding these perceived fears and what motivates a victim to remain isolated is an important part in understanding the victims' stalking journey.

The fears expressed by the majority of victims in this section of the study (36%) who chose not to disclose, were due to fear of not being believed, fear of escalation, fear of job loss and fear of being victim blamed, if they were to choose to disclose. Concluding that the fears of others reactions, similar to the barriers discussed in the above section, were enough to dissuade these victims from disclosing their victimization. Furthermore, some victims expressed feelings of fear about others finding out that they were fearful of the stalker. It can therefore be surmised that the assumptions of others' potential reactions to the stalking created a barrier to seeking support. Fear of others reactions to the stalking suggests support for SRT and previous research by (Buhi et al, 2009; Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011; Dworkin et al, 2019) in the context of fear of not being believed, as a barrier to help-seeking, and that victims chose not report to police due to the fear they would not be believed.

Fear of professional consequences

However, this research also suggests that the fear of not being believed also arose in a professional context from the disclosure, which can also create barriers to help-seeking. For example, Jutasi and McEwan (2021) argue that victims commonly felt their employers were unhelpful when a disclosure occurred in the workplace for male and female participants. This argument was supported in this study by approximately 15% of participants who declared that they felt their profession was the reason they would not be believed, and in expressions whereby the fear

in the context of others perceptions about the stalker was the reason they would not be believed. Therefore, the fear of not being believed was the barrier for these victims' who worried about other peoples' perceptions of either themselves and/or their stalkers. This fear of not being believed supports the SRT and previous research which suggests fear of not being believed is a dominant barrier for victims to seeking formal and informal support for the stalking, (Buhi et al, 2009; Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011; Jutasi and McEwan, 2021).

Fear of what may occur as a consequence if the stalking is disclosed, specifically, a victims' fear of job loss, occurred as well. The fear of job loss, or loss of profession is an important barrier to understand for victims, as this outcome may carry not only a reduction in professional reputation, but also financial consequences and potentially social consequences, which was expressed in the cases of Ian and Josie. This fear occurred as a possibility for victims, a projected perception of the potential consequences if they chose to disclose their experience. Therefore, and in contrast to the Lysova et al, (2022) study, it was not the fear of not being believed by others, as Lysova suggested, but rather the fear of the consequences following the disclosure, due to others' perceptions or biases of stalking that created barriers to seeking support. This can be considered as a fear of escalation of a negative consequence to the experience of stalking, in some cases, rather than the fear of an escalation of the stalker behaviours.

Fear of Escalation

However, previous studies have exemplified the existence of victims' fear of stalker escalations in stalking behaviour if the stalking is disclosed. This study supports these previous arguments by the Buhi and colleague's (2009), Ngo (2014) and more recently, the Lysova and colleagues (2022) studies, as 20% of victims in the fear category of this current study expressed that they chose not to disclose for fear of the stalkers behaviour escalating. However, an important factor to highlight in this context, is that despite the victims fear of what was actually occurring to them (the stalking itself), the fear of what may occur by the either those they disclosed to (80%), or by the stalker (20%), the dominant barrier to help-seeking for the majority of the non-disclosure participants was others reactions. This fear of others social reactions this study argues, was strong enough to dissuade victims from seeking help for their stalking victimization and remain isolated in their experience.

Social Reactions are theoretically described by Ullman (2010) as informal reactions, which are both verbal and/or non-verbal reactions to a disclosure, made by the respondent of the disclosure,

and these reactions can either minimize or affirm a victims' experience. Ullman proposed that negative/unhelpful responses can potentially impact on the attributions and meaning of a victims' experience, which can result in negative consequences for help-seeking behaviours and ultimately on the victims coping mechanisms and help-seeking decisions. As we have seen, the current study argues support for the Ullman (2010) Social Reaction Theory (SRT) in the context of stalking victimization and the imagined fear of others reactions to a disclosure, as a barrier to help-seeking. As we have explored in this non-disclose section, the fear arising from the victims own imagined perceptions or assumptions of what may occur by the either from those they disclosed to both formally and informally, their professions, or even by the stalker was enough of a potential negative social reaction in their minds to dissuade seeking help. This evidences support for Ullman (2010), in the context that victims' coping mechanisms and help-seeking behaviours are impacted by social reactions, suggesting that this occurs even through imagined or predicted negative responses in the context of stalking victimization.

Further support was found in the current research for the Ullman (2010) SRT as a barrier to support in the context of a victims imagined/predicted negative reactions to the fear of experiencing victim-blame. This has been evidenced in cases from both male and female participants, whereby the victims' described their worry that others' would think it was their fault, or that they had encouraged the stalking, which can be considered a form of predicted victim-blame. This support for the SRT also includes where there were expressions of previous experiences of disclosing resulted in passive victim-blame language. This evidences support for the Ullman SRT that a negative social reactions can have negative consequences on help-seeking behaviour for a victim. Social reaction theory posits that anticipated and actual interpersonal responses to disclosure shape victims' subsequent coping and help-seeking. When victims expect blame, minimization, or invalidating reactions, based on prior experiences or observed norms, they engage in anticipatory self-protection, withholding disclosure to avoid secondary victimization and identity threat. Empirical work on social reactions (Ullman, 2010; Dardis et al (2021) shows that negative responses erode perceived support, worsen psychological outcomes, and reduce both informal and formal reporting; critically, anticipated negativity alone can deter first disclosures. Applied here, the projection that others would fault them for the stalking reconfigures the cost-benefit calculus of seeking help, making silence a rational response to a hostile social ecology even when risk and fear are high.

The Help-seeking category revealed support for Boehnlein et al (2020) study, the fear of not being believed, and with the Ullmans (2010) SRT in the context of stalking victimization and perceived negative social reactions. Victims' expressions of feeling ashamed and/or embarrassed by

being stalked, and the fear of others reactions detailed in the participants' responses, as the imagined/predicted or experienced fear of others negative perceptions about their victimization dominated their help-seeking decisions and dissuaded these victims from the choice to seek-help for the stalking experience. Although fear of escalation in stalker behaviour if a disclosure had been made occurred for some, supporting Lysova and colleagues 2022 study, the victims fear of others perceptions or fear of the potential social reactions if they had chosen to disclose, dominated over the fear of stalker behaviour escalating. Therefore, this study argues that the Ullman (2010) Social Reaction Theory applies not only to actual negative responses received at the point of disclosure, as suggested by Ullman, but applies also in the context of predicted negative social reactions as a barrier to stalking victims' help-seeking decisions.

A nuanced understanding of non-disclosure and the determinants of help-seeking underscores concrete practice and policy priorities. Implementing trauma-informed, culturally responsive, and confidentiality-protected pathways to care; proactive outreach and psychoeducation that normalize help-seeking and counter minimization; training for first responders and gatekeepers (healthcare, campus staff, employers) to recognize diverse stalking patterns; victim-centered referral and reporting mechanisms are likely to reduce shame, anxiety/depression, and PTSD symptoms, mitigate suicidality risk, and enhance perceptions of procedural fairness. By lowering practical and psychological barriers to disclosure and increasing trust in formal systems, these measures can improve both reporting rates and case outcomes.

DISCLOSURE DISCOURSE

Disclosure discourse for the context of this research, is the communication between a stalking victim and another person (responder), whereby the victim is disclosing the stalking experience. The majority of interview and survey participants (81%) in this study chose to seek help for their victimization, by disclosing, however, they received varying responses from the responders.

Rational choice theory posits that victims weigh the costs and benefits of disclosing stalking and seeking help (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010; Fissel, 2021). The data in this research highlighted that participants were more likely to seek help from formal sources such as family and friends when initially disclosing. When deciding where to seek assistance, victims compare informal sources (family and friends) with formal institutions (police, shelters, courts) in terms of accessibility, credibility, emotional support, privacy, and the likelihood of a beneficial outcome. Informal disclosures tend to offer immediate, empathetic support within trusted relationships, lower barriers

to disclosure, and less risk of bureaucratic procedures or stigma, making them appear to provide higher utility at a lower cost, which may explain the decisions to informally disclose in the first instance. Conversely, formal channels are often perceived as costly, such as risk of disbelief or retaliation, procedural delays, potential escalation, and uncertain, therefore so many victims first disclose to informal networks to gain safety and encouragement before considering police or legal remedies.

Across initial disclosures to informal sources, victims reported receiving marginally more validating than invalidating responses, family and friends were slightly more likely to listen, believe, and offer practical or emotional support. Conversely, when victims escalated to formal systems such as police, marginally more invalidating responses were reported, including skepticism, minimization, or procedural barriers. This pattern suggests that the perceived and experienced supportiveness of informal networks may be modestly higher at first contact, whereas formal pathways, while potentially necessary for protection and legal remedies, carry a slightly greater risk of invalidation.

This section of the research discussion will disseminate the disclosure discourse that resulted in victims perceiving the responders reactions as having minimized/invalidated the experience, validated the experience, perceptions of stalker type and the amount of stalking behaviours, and the relationship of these responses to further victim help-seeking decisions. This section of the discussion addresses Research Question Two: *How does a positive and negative disclosure response impact further help-seeking decisions? Including, are there any gender differences?*

Minimized/ invalidated the experience

There has been a marginal amount of research conducted exploring the barriers a victim of stalking may experience when disclosing. These barriers can occur from the responses received following disclosures to family, friends, law enforcement, advocates and support agencies, as suggested by (Jordan et al, 2003; Reyns and Englebrecht, 2010; Weller et al, 2013; McKeon et al, 2015; Ngo, 2020; Hulley et al, 2022).

Having a minimizing and/or invalidating experience with the responses received when the victims disclosed, were evidenced by 69% of all participants in this study who disclosed. Many victims expressed that the responses to their disclosures made them feel as though the stalking they were experiencing was made out to be not as serious as it had felt to them. These minimizing responses made them feel invalidated, the stalking experience minimized, even victim-blamed for some, supporting studies conducted by (Crome and McCabe, 2001; McKeon et al, 2015; McEwan et

al (2018). This minimization of the stalking experience following the disclosure was shown to also romanticize the stalking behaviour, particularly in the ex-intimate context of stalking, supporting the proposition made by McKeon et al, (2015) that the romanticizing a victims stalking experiencing creates barriers to further help-seeking. Furthermore, these social reactions, in some cases resulted in bolstering the stalker to escalate the stalking behaviour, supporting arguments made by Mullen et al, (1999) that non- intervention in some types of stalkers can escalate the stalking. This suggestion is further supported by Becker et al (2020) that stalking behaviours are socially accepted and romanticized, can perpetuate the stalking behaviour.

To expand further on these propositions, a negative work response was also experienced by participants who detailed how the cognitive misunderstandings about stalking in the work place made them feel belittled, and in turn impacted confidence in reaching out again, supporting the Crome and McCabe, (2001) study, which suggested that negative disclosures can be harmful to a victim, as the other person may minimize or victim blame. Applying social reaction theory (Ullman, 2010) to workplace stalking suggests that the quality of others' responses to disclosure carries significant psychological consequences. When disclosures elicit negative reactions, such as, minimization, skepticism, or victim blaming, the victims experience secondary wounding that compounds the primary harm of the stalking. Participants who encountered dismissive responses reported feeling invalidated, helpless, and isolated, amplifying anxiety, hypervigilance, and distress. These adverse reactions can erode self-concept, undermine trust in others, and constrict a person's worldview, diminishing their sense of safety, efficacy, and confidence at work and beyond. In this way, negative disclosure responses do not merely fail to help, they actively intensify victimization's impact and shape trajectories of coping and help-seeking. (Ullman, 2010; Edwards, 2014; McKeon et al, 2015; Becker et al, 2020).

Therefore, The current study argues that a minimizing and/or invalidating disclosure response is psychologically damaging to a victim of stalking, supporting the research conducted by Edwards et al (2014) who concluded negative disclosure reactions were related to an increase in psychological distress, compounding the psychological consequences of not being believed, along with the psychological consequences of being stalked. This study also argues further support for the Ullman (2010) Social Reaction Theory that a negative response to a disclosure carries vast consequences on the attributions and meaning of victims' experiences, resulting in further negative consequences for help-seeking behaviours which will be discussed in relation to the research question in the following section.

Discouraged from further help-seeking

This study asserts, that when the responses following a disclosure are perceived by a victim as invalidating and minimizing, this not only compounds psychological distress as the above section highlighted, but also has an adverse effect on further help-seeking decisions and behaviours, as suggested by Crome and McCabe (2001), highlighting the importance of a supportive and/or validating disclosure responses as 15% of participants in this study who chose to disclose their stalking experience, felt discouraged from disclosing to anyone else. Furthermore, 26% of participants did not go on to disclose their victimization again. This suggests that there is a relationship between a negative/unhelpful disclosure response and further help-seeking decisions.

Research has argued that early intervention is necessary to mitigate the negative consequences of stalking, as proposed by (Taylor-Dunn et al, 2018). However, this study proposes that negative consequences occur when early intervention is enacted by the victim and combined with a disclosure response that is minimizing or unhelpful. This proposition is evidenced by victims who despite enacting interventions such as safety measures early on by workplace management following the initial disclosure, the negative reactions to the situation from the respondents such as management, family, friends and police resulted in the victims feeling minimized, discouraged and unsafe. The feeling of regret from disclosing resulted in disengagement from further action, following the responses of not being believed. This finding supports research by Lysova et al (2022) who argued that victims were worried they would be re-victimized within the criminal justice system. Therefore, the current research supports the argument by McKeon et al, (2015) who proposed that the perceptions of others can minimize the stalking episode for a victim, creating barriers to disclosures and help-seeking behaviours and decisions. Specifically, negative disclosure responses which are perceived by a stalking victim as minimizing and invalidating, discourages future help-seeking decisions for victims, leaving them isolated and vulnerable, (Crome and McCabe, 2001; Ullman, 2010 and Fissel, 2021).

Previous literature (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2014) has indicated the responses received from friends and family may influence whether a victim discloses their experience to the police or other organizations such as support agencies, this research has indicated support for this analysis. However, this study also highlights for victims that are having to repeat their story multiple times, particularly when receiving minimizing responses, can be detrimental to their psychological health, as victims have detailed the negative consequences of not responding in a supportive manner when a disclosure of stalking is made, highlighting the importance of a supportive response as suggested by the Ullman (2010) Social reaction theory. Therefore, in answering this portion of the research question, this study asserts that a negative/unhelpful disclosure response impacts further help-

seeking, which has resulted in these victims feeling victimized further, reluctant and discouraged to continue to seek-help, demonstrating further negative psychological consequences of isolation and self-worth, as previous argued by (Ngo, 2014).

Gender and discouragement

The results from previous studies have also highlighted how under disclosed the crime of stalking is by both male and female victims, as suggested by Proctor (2019). Studies and theories similar to this that include gender differences, such as: Proctor (2018; 2019) and Lombard & Proctor (2023) aid in the understanding of the nuances specific to stalking, including the consequences for the victims of this crime. Literature on specific gender (male) help-seeking behaviours and barriers with stalking victimization are limited, however, Donne et al (2018) asserted the male barriers to disclosures and help-seeking were mainly due to gender norms, shame, and perceived identity impacts, including finding a trustworthy and relatable professionals to disclose to for support is crucial. Whereas, studies investigating female victimization like the Buhi et al (2009) research found women did not feel the situation was serious enough to disclose, wanted to handle the situation on their own, felt it was a private/personal matter, they did not disclose to police as they were fearful of revenge, and felt police would not believe them.

The current study highlights the importance of perceptions in the help-seeking decisions stalking victims make regardless of gender. This study revealed that for some victims, the disclosure experience resulted in a regret in disclosing which occurred regardless of gender. In other words, the victims' wished they had never disclosed at all. This portion of the current research supports the research conducted by Geistman et al (2013). Geistman and colleagues found that although the majority of victims that enlisted informal help felt it helped their situation, many felt it made the situation worse. These feeling of regret were derived from the responses following disclosures to police which made them feel unsafe, and disengaged from pursuing further help-seeking following the response of not being believed, as suggested by Lysova et al (2022). Victims described that dealing with colleagues as a disclosure respondent amplified the psychological symptoms, and made life more difficult, further supporting negative psychological impacts from a minimizing disclosure response (Crome and McCabe, 2001; Lysova et al, 2022).

Therefore, this study argues that even when early intervention is enacted, when it is combined with a disclosure response that is minimizing or unhelpful, this elicits further negative consequences for victims. Supporting the proposition that others' perceptions can minimize the stalking episode for a victim, creating barriers to disclosures and help-seeking behaviours. These findings demonstrate further support for Ullman (2010) Social reaction theory, and Edwards et al (2014)

study, and answers a part of research question two; that a negative/unhelpful disclosure response does impact further help-seeking decisions, regardless of the victims gender, as a minimizing and invalidating disclosure experience appears to compound the negative psychological effects of stalking, discouraging further help-seeking behaviours which ultimately results in further trauma and isolation, for both male and female victims. Practically, these findings call for trauma-informed, validation-focused responses across both informal and formal help systems to prevent secondary harm and a decline in help-seeking. Organizations such as, employers, HR teams, healthcare providers, campus/security services, and police should offer multiple low-barrier reporting pathways (anonymous/digital, third-party, peer advocates), and referrals to specialist services to counteract the deterrent effect of a prior negative responses. Public education can equip friends, family, and co-workers to respond supportively. Services must be explicitly gender-inclusive, and hold units accountable for invalidating practices. Collectively, these steps can reduce isolation, sustain engagement with support, and mitigate further trauma for all victims.

Sought further help regardless of response(s).

This study proposes that there are circumstances whereby a victim has no choice but to continue to seek help for their stalking victimization. Applied through a rational choice lens, the finding that some victims felt they “had no choice” but to keep seeking help reflects constrained and dynamic decision-making: as stalking escalates, the expected costs of inaction (harm, job loss, reputational damage, lethal risk) come to dominate, shrinking viable alternatives despite prior negative responses. Victims naturally update beliefs about effectiveness after each disclosure; when informal or initial formal avenues fail, the perceived probability of safety without further action drops, making continued help-seeking the option with the highest expected utility under severe constraints. This is bounded rationality under risk and coercion: choices are path-dependent, shaped by limited options, urgent safety needs, and sometimes mandates (workplace policies, legal requirements), so persistence in help-seeking is a rational adaptation to escalating threat rather than a contradiction of rational choice theory (Reyns and Englebrecht 2014, Fissel, 2021).

This continuance of help-seeking has shown in the current study, to occur regardless of what disclosure response the victims had received, this finding was highlighted within all typologies of stalkers and within all genders of victims. Specifically, victims are determined to take action to stop the stalking and to mitigate the psychological consequences, as was suggested by Galeazzi et al (2009). Galeazzi and colleagues proposed that if a victim receives a response from an informal source that minimizes their experience, and when they continue to be fearful for their life, they may make the rational decision to pursue seeking formal help. Rational decisions can also include taking

action, such as victims having to move home, and/or change their daily routines in order to avoid the stalker and/or stalker behaviours. These rational decisions are based on the victims' knowledge of previous offences of the stalker and is related to the victims' perceived seriousness of the stalking, according to Reyns and Englebrecht (2014); Fissel (2021), and The Theory of Rational Choice Perspective by Gottfredson & Gottfredson (1998).

This study found support for the previously mentioned studies and is demonstrated in the cases which described a determination to continue to seek help, regardless of the negative disclosure responses they had received. The determination was found to be particularly due to the perceived risk to life, and the determination to stay safe. Furthermore, the forensic pathology of the stalker, or known history to stalk heightened the risks, as suggested by The Theory of Rational Choice, but also facilitated the determination to continue to seek help for the stalking. The known pattern of stalking (previous offences) was also found to be a precursor to determination. The stalkers propensity to terrorize communities, previous history of stalking, persistence to stalk and the risk factors gave victims no choice but to continue to seek help for their stalking experience, regardless of the minimizing and invalidating responses they had received when disclosing the stalking.

This study demonstrates support for both the Reyns and Englebrecht study (2010, 2014; Fissel, 2021) as well as the Theory of Rational choice by Gottfredson & Gottfredson (1998), whereby the decisions a victim makes when seeking help with their victimization may go beyond a disclosure response and promote further disclosing when risk factors are high for threat to life, and previous stalker history is known. Theoretically, these findings align with rational choice by showing how offender information recalibrates a victims' cost to benefit calculations. Knowledge of a stalker's forensic profile and prior stalking offenses increases the perceived probability and severity of future harm, raising the expected costs of inaction beyond the costs of continued help-seeking, even after invalidating responses to disclosures were experienced. As victims update beliefs with cues (history, persistence, community impact, salient risk factors), the utility of persisting with formal and informal avenues surpassed disclosure disengagement, creating a no alternative threshold. Thus, prior offending and demonstrated persistence function as risk signals that shift victims' decision, set and sustain the determination to seek help.

Validated the experience

In contrast to the above section that discussed how a minimizing and invalidating disclosure experience can dissuade victims from further reporting and help-seeking decisions, this study suggests that disclosure responses which are helpful and positive can make a victim feel supported,

and validated. Whereby, approximately 46% of participants in the current study indicated that victims require both emotional and practical assistance from their social support, support agencies and law enforcement to facilitate the minimization in psychological distress from the stalking, detailing how the positive and helpful disclosure responses made them feel supported, and their stalking experience validated.

Previous research along with the current study have shown the necessity for victims to be believed, validated, and supported by a system that does not downplay their experiences of stalking, as suggested by (Boehnlein et al, 2020). The positive responses victims received validated the stalking experience and helped them to not feel alone, as well as comforted. The feeling that their stalking experience was validated and believed made very positive psychological impacts to the victim's well-being, helping them to feel supported and less isolated in their stalking experience. This suggestion can be evidenced by victims who described how difficult disclosing can be, and how being believed and supported elucidated feelings of relief despite still living in fear, which supports the Ngo (2020) argument that a supporting disclosure discourse can lessen the barriers to support for victims.

This section of the current study also proposes further support for the Ullman (2010) Social Reaction Theory that a validating disclosure response supports coping mechanisms for victims and encourages the mechanics of help-seeking behaviours, for male and female victims. However, the current study also argues a contrast the Edwards et al (2014) study. Edwards and colleagues argued that positive reactions to disclosures were unrelated to psychological distress, whereas, this study counters that a positive, validating disclosure response, even when the victims are still living in fear, reduces psychological distress for all typologies experienced and all victim genders.

Ullman's Social Reaction Theory implies that validating disclosure discourses, such as, believing the victim, expressing empathy activate adaptive coping pathways that sustain help-seeking for both male and female victims. Validation reduces self-blame and shame, bolsters perceived control and self-efficacy, and strengthens trust in others and in systems, which in turn promotes approach coping (documenting incidents, safety planning, evidence preservation) and willingness to engage with formal services. These supportive reactions also mitigate psychological distress, making further help-seeking more likely and more effective. For men, validation further counters gendered stigma about victimhood, narrowing barriers to disclosure, whilst for women validation feeds the mechanisms for empowerment. Overall, positive social reactions function as a catalyst that transforms disclosure into ongoing support, and protective action.

Encouraged further help-seeking

This research proposes that disclosure responses that are positive and validating can also encourage victims to continue to seek help for the stalking. This section of the discussion address research question two: *That a positive/helpful or negative/unhelpful disclosure responses impacts further help-seeking behaviours, are there any gender differences?* This important question to answer because victims of stalking must take a proactive approach as legal systems and offenders cannot be relied upon to stop the stalking behaviour, as suggested by (Nichols, 2020).

This study presents a compelling argument regarding the importance of validating disclosure experiences for both male and female victims of stalking. It highlights how such experiences foster a willingness to seek help, illustrated through the narratives of participants. As expressed by victims in this category, having someone take their concerns seriously, was validating and encouraged to seek further help. Despite their concerns about potential victim-blaming and feelings of shame associated with their experiences, these victims found that a supportive response encouraged them to pursue assistance.

Additionally, an essential aspect of the help-seeking process is addressing the barriers that many victims face. The study emphasizes that obtaining support is crucial for overcoming these obstacles. Such as the case of a female sex-worker who was experiencing many nuanced barriers in relation to her profession, having a validating and supportive environment helped her to overcome the barriers and seek criminal justice for the stalking. Previous concerns regarding future employment, reputation and legal barriers were overcome. This highlights the important point that victims can benefit significantly from reaching out to specific charities designed to help individuals with their individual situations. Affirming the findings of Boehnlein et al (2020), this research underscores the need for support agencies to provide both emotional and practical assistance within a framework that respects and validates the victims' experiences, rather than minimizing them. The study also notes that victims who are professionals, such as social workers and counsellors, often encounter skepticisms and disbelief regarding their experiences. In these instances, charities play a pivotal role in helping victims navigate the challenges of reporting their experiences. These organizations empowered these victims to confront barriers that their workplace environments may not address, thus facilitating a path toward help and justice.

Moreover, this research aligns with Ullman's (2010) Social Reaction Theory and the findings of Edwards et al (2014). Both of these studies suggest a significant connection between receiving a positive and supportive response to a disclosure and the likelihood of pursuing further help. A

validating response to disclosures of stalking as this research has shown, not only encourages victims, regardless of gender and typology of the stalker, to seek additional assistance but also helps them overcome feelings of shame and fear of victim-blame. In many cases, victims were able to establish connections with charities that acknowledged their experiences, enhancing their confidence and sense of support as they continued to seek help.

Therefore, this study proposes that there is a relationship between a positive and encouraging disclosure response to further help-seeking behaviours for victims of stalking, regardless of gender. The findings of this study advocate for a more empathetic and validating approach to supporting victims of stalking. By recognizing and addressing their unique challenges, support agencies can play a transformative role in the help-seeking journey, ultimately fostering resilience and recovery among victims through validating the stalking experience and fostering confidence and encouragement to continue to seek help.

Amount of Stalking Behaviours

Previous research regarding stalking victimization has proposed that victims will experience more than one hundred behaviours before reaching out for help, and at this stage the victims life has already been adversely affected by the stalking, (Sheridan et al, 2003). This study supports this proposition as 65% of the Males and 52% of the females in this study experienced the one hundred plus behaviours. This section of the study explored the third research question: *Are the amount of stalking behaviours a factor in what disclosure response is received, and are there gender differences?*

Research has acknowledged that cyberstalking has increased immensely with technological advances, and the psychological consequences for the victims are found to be similar to 'traditional' stalking, as Worlsey et al, (2017) suggested. Worsley and colleagues described comorbid anxiety and depression as the dominant psychological consequences, and victims had to move home and/or make changes to their work or life patterns, which are important considerations when exploring the help seeking behaviours of stalking victims. This study found (see appendix 3), that cyberstalking by gender revealed male participants were stalked online 7%, offline 30% and a mixture of offline and offline occurred for 63%. Female participants reported experiencing online at 12%, offline 36% and a mixture of online and offline at 56%. Suggesting that female victims are still experiencing marginally more offline stalking behaviours. Similar to the Brady (2022) study, this research revealed the majority of male and female stalking victims are experiencing a mixture of offline and online stalking,

which can be considered as facilitated by modern technological advances, and increased usage by individuals, according to (Worlsey et al, 2017).

It has also been argued by previous literature that law enforcement react more positively to a victim's disclosure when there are multiple behaviours being reported, and especially when the victim can present a log of the multiple behaviours, as suggested by (Backes et al, 2020; Nichols, 2020). This study demonstrates support for the suggestion that multiple behaviours elicit a positive police response in the context of law enforcement taking the complaint of the victim more seriously. This was evidenced in the cases where the police were able to visually see the amount of attempts to contact, which resulted in the complaint being taken seriously. Although there were cases where the initial response was not quite so positive, when the victim was able to produce a long log of incidents, the officers then recognized the stalking. Presenting a log of the course of stalking conduct supports the Theory of Rational Choice Perspective explored by Gottfredson and Gottfredson (1988) who had proposed that the more serious the offence, the more likely the police would engage in criminal justice action. This suggests that the logs of events presented the seriousness of the offences occurring, and were crucial to facilitate and incite recognition from the officers that were receiving these disclosures that what they were viewing was in fact stalking.

However, collecting one's own evidence of stalking is fraught with safety, legal, and emotional complexities (Cho et al, 2023). Victims must document rapidly disappearing or mutable digital traces while avoiding actions that could escalate the stalker's behaviour or violate privacy and recording laws, which vary by jurisdiction. Ensuring admissibility (authenticity, metadata, chain of custody) is challenging without guidance, as is securing storage when devices may be compromised or monitored (Fissel, 2021). The task imposes significant cognitive and time burdens for maintaining logs, screenshots, and downloads, while simultaneously coping with fear, hypervigilance, and potential re-traumatization (Cho et al, 2023). Together, these factors make self-evidence gathering risky and exhausting, even as it is often necessary to access protection and legal remedies.

Furthermore, the majority of victims of stalking in this study experienced the stalking behaviours and unwanted contacts for two years and over, as suggested by Sheridan et al (2003); Backes et al (2020), and Garthe et al (2025), this is a substantial amount of time to experience repeated, targeted victimization. This is especially true when the result is the victim living in continuous fear, alarm and distress. As a result of this sustained victimization, many victims resort to changing their daily routines to attempt to mitigate the stalking, as suggested by (Donne et al, (2018). This study proposes that there is a relationship between the amount of stalking behaviours experienced and the disclosure response received, regardless of gender, and particularly when the responder is a law

enforcement official. It appears as though the police were able to recognize the persistent and serious nature of the stalking with the aid of the logs, evidencing support for the Rational Choice Theory. This study has evidenced support for the suggestion that victims, regardless of gender when evidencing multiple behaviours, can elicit a positive disclosure response, particularly in police considerations (Backes et al, 2020).

Stalker Type and Disclosure Responses

This section is also focused on the disclosure discourse, whereby questions were asked of the participants about the type of stalker being perceived by the victims as playing a role in what response was given upon disclosing the stalking. The type of stalker is determined by the victim/offender relationship and motivations for the stalking, and contains five recognized types: the resentful stalker, rejected stalker, stranger, incompetent suitor and intimacy seeker, as proposed by Mullen and colleagues, 1999. This part of the discussion addresses research question four: Does typology (stalker type) impact the disclosure response? *Including, are there gender differences?*

This exploration occurred because previous research into stalking victimization in the UK, Australia, and the USA has suggested that both victims and law enforcement are more likely to recognize the crime of stalking when victims are targeted by a stranger or predatory stalker, rather than the rejected ex-partner (Tjaden and Thoennes, 1998; Jordan et al, 2007; Scott et al, 2018; Becker 2020). This study has shown some support for this suggestion, as the predatory stalkers, according to 20% of female interview participants, were easier to recognize. According to Mullen et al (1999) predatory stalkers are not known to their victims, and/or they are stalkers with deviant sexual motivations.

The suggestion that a stranger is more easily recognized as a stalker was supported by the current research. This was evidenced in cases where the victims felt that if the stalker had been someone they had been in an intimate relationship with, they would have found it more difficult to recognize the experience as stalking. The perception was, because of the fear induced when a female victim is targeted by a stranger, it can be perceived as a woman's worst imagined nightmare. In these cases, it can be suggested the seriousness of the crime committed by these strangers facilitated a positive disclosure experience, specifically law enforcement. These cases also suggests support for the Theory of Rational Choice, proposed by Gottfredson and Gottfredson (1988), which was brought in to context with the crime of stalking by Reyns and Englebrecht in (2010) and Fissel (2021). This study found support that a stranger stalker would be more likely to facilitate victim

reporting to law officials as previous research proposed. To further the support for The Theory of Rational Choice, in the context of the seriousness of the offence, and in respect to specific behaviours, cases in the current research which evidenced that it was the sexual orientation of the stalking behaviour conducted by the unknown predator, facilitated not only immediate recognition of the stalking, but reporting to police as well by the victims.

However, it must be acknowledged, there were also cases experienced where the victims experienced disbelief by law enforcement when disclosed, despite the sexual orientation of the contact by the unknown sexual predator. Therefore, this study also argues that the negative/unhelpful disclosure response was due to inaccurate misunderstandings of stalking, as suggested by (Scott et al, 2019), which may have included a gender bias for these male and female victims. The gender bias resulted in victims feelings of being victim blamed and discredited, which was recognized by (Taylor-Dunn et al, 2019). Therefore, Theory of Rational choice was supported in the recognition and reporting, however, the misconceptions and biases by police, did not entirely support The Focal Concerns Theory by (Steffensmeier et al, 1993; 1998), whereby seriousness of offences and behaviours would facilitate criminal justice action.

Therefore, typology (type of stalker) in the context of predatory stalkers were perceived as more easily recognizable by female victims, and the majority of people the victims disclosed to, validated their experience, supporting the (Scott et al, 2019) study. Furthermore, in support to the proposition made by Gottfredson and Gottfredson (1998), the victim/offender relationship, as in these cases of no previous relationship, carried influence on the victims' reporting behaviours, whether they were 'traditionally' stalked, or 'cyberstalked' by promoting disclosure to counteract the seriousness of threat.

Notwithstanding, the current and existing research has exemplified mixed findings between the perceptions and the realities of stalking, as proposed by (Donne et al, 2018; Scott et al, 2019). Suggesting the differences between perceptions and realities are mainly due to victim, public and law-enforcements' inaccurate misconceptions and understandings of the crime of stalking and the victimization that results from experiencing targeted and unwanted behaviours, as suggested by (Becker et al, 2020).

Gender Bias

Gender bias, for the purpose of this study, are assumptions about stalkers and victim gender roles that can potentially influence a stalking disclosure, as argued by (Fox et al, 2011). This has been

evidenced in this current study whereby victims' experiences were made out as a joke, and this occurred for both genders. Therefore, it can be suggested that the misconceptions arose because of a misconception that male stalkers only targets female victims, and female stalkers only target male victims, as previously suggested by (Lysova et al, 2022). This study argues that gender biases can occurred for female victims as well, particularly when there was a large age gap between the stalker and the victim. The gender normative assumption of strong male figures, which resulted in the intimacy seeker stalker gaining an advantage, when it was assumed the young victim made up the story of victimization. This suggests that gender normative assumptions and biases, can play a large role in the disclosure dialogues that victim's experience. This was found in a range of typologies, in the Male victim with a male resentful stalker, a female victim with a female rejected stalker and in a female victim with an intimacy seeker male stalker. Supporting the current and previous research that suggests misconceptions are influencing all victims stalking experiences and disclosure discourse, (Donne et al, 2018; Scott et al, 2019).

The current research has evidenced throughout this research, that cognitive biases, and misconceptions about the crime of stalking and stalker types are affecting both male and female victims. This section has highlighted that these misconceptions occur in the form of gender stereotyping particularly for male victims, which is another form of cognitive bias, (Fisher et al, 2003). Whereas, female victims tended to experience more normative assumptions from others in regards to their stalkers and stalking experiences.

These biases evidence support, similarly to previous section of this chapter, the Bandura (1977) Social Learning Theory in the context of learned perceptions of stalker types. This study has evidenced that stalkers regardless of gender can target anyone, and any victim gender can become the target, and both victim genders can experience stereotyping and misconceptions in their disclosure discourse. Therefore this study argues that the stalker type does not necessarily impact the disclosure response received for either gender, rather cognitive biases in the form of stereotypes and misconceptions about stalker type's impact the responses received, for both genders.

Theoretically, these findings shift explanatory focus from offender/victim demographics to perceiver cognition, disclosure outcomes appeared driven less by stalker type and more by social and cognitive based biases, such as gender stereotypes held by the responders. When a case did not match the stereotyped scripts (e.g., male perpetrator/female victim, intimate ex-partner), responders were prone to minimize, misattribute blame, or misclassify risk, producing similar invalidating responses across victim genders. This supports social-cognitive models over typological ones, suggesting that interventions should target belief updating and bias interruption such as

training, rather than relying on offender-type categories. In short, stereotypes about who counts as a real stalker mediate the social reaction, shaping validation or invalidation irrespective of actual stalker characteristics.

Trained in stalking helped discourse

Existing research exploring stalking victimization has suggested that victims who acknowledge their experience as stalking are more likely to disclose to law enforcement when their relational dynamic to the stalker involves power and control, as suggested by (Taber-Smith, 2017). Power and control are motivational factors found within the rejected, and resentful stalker typologies (Mullen et al, 1999). Some victims will respond to the stalking by trying to gain the balance of control back by reporting retaliating type behaviours, when perceiving the behaviour motivations are due to power and control particularly from an ex-partner (Taber-Smith, 2017). This is also a contrast to the proposition made by Gottfredson and Gottfredson (1998) that the closer the victim/offender relationship is, the less likely the crime would be reported. However, this study found that approx. 81% of all participants chose to disclose their victimization, regardless of stalker type.

As we have seen so far within this Chapter, victims have received varying responses to their disclosures. This study has found that the disclosure discourse was perceived as more positive and helpful by 10% of participants who disclosed to a person who was trained in interpersonal crimes like stalking, (Taylor-Dunn et al, 2018). However, previous research by Jordan et al (2003) has also shown that law enforcement, victim service workers and advocates often have difficulties identifying stalking. Jordan and colleagues argued that misconceptions or misunderstandings about the crime of stalking can defeat the purpose of providing supportive responses in the context of victimization, as some do not perceive the crime of stalking to be serious or dangerous in nature, and the current study has also evidenced support for this suggestion.

This study also found support for the Taylor-Dunn's (2018) proposition that trained individuals provide a more positive disclosure experience. For example, disclosing to community police officers who had received specific training in the crime of stalking helped the discourse. Furthermore, disclosure dialogues that were perceived as positive by victims when training in Women's Safety and domestic abuse behaviours, which facilitated a supportive response. Therefore, these findings support Taylor-Dunn (2018) study and argue that training in the different types of interpersonal abuse, like domestic abuse and stalking can aid in the recognition of different contexts of stalking, regardless of the typology of a stalker, or a victims gender, facilitating a positive disclosure experience for victims experiencing the crime of stalking, which this study proposes, can facilitate

more positive stalking outcomes. Applying the theoretical lens of the Social Reaction Theory, training equips responders (informal and formal) to deliver validating, non-blaming reactions that can positively shape victims' coping and continued help-seeking. Education on stalking and related interpersonal abuses recalibrates cognitive understandings beyond narrow typologies or gendered myths, reducing minimization and misclassification. With clearer recognition of diverse stalking contexts, responders are more likely to believe, name the behaviour accurately, offer concrete options, and provide key elements of supportive social reactions. This validation lowers shame and increases self-efficacy, fostering engagement with safety planning and legal remedies. Thus, targeted training functions as a mechanism to transform disclosure encounters into positive trajectories and, as this study proposes, supports more favourable stalking outcomes regardless of stalker type or victim gender.

STALKING OUTCOMES

The stalking outcome is considered as whether or not the stalking has ceased or is continuing. This section of the current study explored the factors involved in victim's perceptions of why the stalking was either continuing or had stopped. There was only a marginal difference in the percentages in each of these two categories (48% had stopped and 52% continuing) and therefore highlighted the need for an exploration while addressing research question Five; *Does disclosing impact whether or not the stalking behaviour stops or continues? Including, are there gender differences?*

Stalking literature and research conducted previously details the importance of help-seeking decisions on the stalking outcome. For example, Brady (2022) proposed that a victim contacting law enforcement was the main significant predictor as to why the victim perceived the stalking had stopped. However, in contrast to the Brady study, Ngo (2018) reported that only a moderate amount of victims reported to police, and only a moderate amount reported the stalking had ceased after police involvement. This study along with a study conducted by Backes et al's (2020) supports the Brady (2022), assertion that documenting the stalking creates a greater likelihood of a positive police discourse and court outcome to help stop the stalking. However, previous research has also shown that reporting to police is not the only recourse a victim will take to mitigate the stalking behaviours. For example, Baum et al (2009), reported victims changing their daily routines, taking time off work, and avoiding social interactions. Previous studies have also found that victims of stalking employ many different types of strategies to mitigate the stalking, such as avoidant coping, ignoring

perpetrators, confrontation, seeking support, help-seeking and cognitive reframing, (Worsley et al's, 2017). Therefore, this section will explore the participant perceptions of why the stalking is still occurring and then why they perceive the stalking has stopped.

Stalking still occurring

Stalkers persistence, occurs when a stalker continues to stalk the victim, and is considered as a refusal to acknowledge or adhere to the victims request to stop the behaviour, (Ngo, 2020). The victim's requests to stop can be either direct or indirect, and this refusal to respect another's boundaries can also include the boundaries that the police and courts have set out on behalf of the victim (Brady & Reynolds, 2024). Stalker persistence was present in 52% of cases in the current study, where participants claimed that the stalking is still occurring.

The stalker persistence is evidenced in the cases where the stalkers, although aware of the victims not wanting contact, changed the modes of behaviours to be more indirect and harder to detect. The changes in behaviour occurred following victim action, such as; blocking routes of communication, refusing unwanted gifts and also after police intervention. However, there were cases whereby the court failings emboldened the stalker to persist in the stalking. Academic research into the phenomenon of stalker persistence has shown mixed result for victims of violent and non-violent stalking episodes, whom either responded to the stalker themselves or enlisted help, as suggested by (Geistman et al, 2013). Geistman and colleagues argued that for some victims conducting indirect and direct behaviours to mitigate the stalking, made the stalking worse, while for others it has helped to stop the stalking.

Stalker persistence can be assumed to be a pathology of sorts, as suggested by Mullen et al (1999), but as a never-ending cycle for victims, proposed by Brady & Reynolds (2024). The results from the current study support the Mullen, and Brady and Reynolds claims that stalker persistence in certain cases can be due to a type of pathology. This has been evidence in cases where the stalker has a forensic history of stalking. In these cases, the stalking is still continuing and these stalkers are known to have targeted other victims. What is a serious consideration in all stalking cases is the psychological impact, however, when the stalking is particularly persistent, despite attempts to stop the stalker, this can carry long term impacts for victims which have been found as both psychological and social, such as isolation, anxiety and continued fear (Nicastro et al, 2000).

The current study argues that stalker persistence is also perceived by victims as a form of continued control over the victim, evidencing support for the Control Balance Theory, (Tittle, 1995). Participants in the current study, who perceived the stalkers motivations to continue to stalk, in

order to maintain a sense of control. This was evidenced in victims' expressions of the stalkers' anger at the loss of control, which has resulted in the stalking still occurring, and even using third parties due to the desire to gain or maintain control over the victims.

Stalker persistence, is an important consideration and has shown to carry serious consequences for the targets of stalking behaviours, far beyond the psychological and social consequences already mentioned. In fact, in the United Kingdom, the vast majority of homicides have not appeared as spontaneous, instead, an unfolding mental state with strong correlations between homicide and stalking behaviours (Monkton-Smith et al, 2017). According to Monkton Smith and colleagues, the stalking behaviours common to homicide are control, fixation, obsession, surveillance and escalations, and affects women disproportionality.

The current study is supportive of the Tittle (1995) Control Balance theory and theoretically applicable to stalking victimization and its relation with a perpetrators desire to control their target. In this study, the stalker persistence was perceived as facilitated and/or motivated by a pathology to stalk or by the stalkers desire to either attain or maintain a sense of control over their victims, regardless of the victims' response, or criminal justice systems attempts to stop the stalking. Control Balance theory posits that deviant behaviour emerges when individuals experience imbalances in control, especially control deficits that motivate efforts to dominate others to restore a sense of agency. Applied to stalking, offenders' persistence can be interpreted as control-seeking: a perceived deficit (rejection, loss of access, status threats) propels ongoing surveillance, contact, and intimidation to attain or maintain control over the target. Victim resistance and criminal justice interventions may paradoxically intensify this drive by further signalling the lost control, producing escalation, tactic-switching, and persistence despite sanctions. Thus, in these circumstances, stalking reflects a control-restorative feedback loop rather than mere situational opportunism, explaining why persistence occurs regardless of victim gender, response, or formal system involvement and why simple deterrence may be insufficient without altering the offender's perceived control imbalance.

Inaction

Inaction was also found to be a facilitator to the stalking still occurring for the remaining 47% of the participants in the current study. For some of these participants they felt as though no one would help, or believe them, or others would even sympathize with their stalker. This was exemplified in the cases as where victims expressed feeling as though the stalking is still occurring because of a

failure to act, or do anything that might provide a solution to the stalking, (Ngo, 2020). Inaction was found to be a result of police failure to act and victim failure to act.

Police Inaction

It has been reported that the crime of stalking is misunderstood and even un-recorded by police officers and the Crown Prosecution Service, (HMIC, 2017). This claim is supported by a study that explored the responses victims received when victims disclose to police, (Taylor-Dunn et al, 2019). Taylor-Dunn suggested that victims are much more likely to experience barriers to receiving help when reporting to the police. Evidencing support for the Taylor Dunn (2019) study, a great deal of male and female victims with varied typologies of stalkers in the current research had expressed their dissatisfaction with the prevalence in which victims are responded to with 'there is nothing we can do', or 'no criminal offence has occurred'.

Supporting the findings of the Taylor-Dunn and colleagues' (2019) this study found the majority of the respondents received the poor responses from police such as; police inaction, inappropriate action, feeling blamed, and not taken seriously. The current study expressed victims feeling as though the stalking is still occurring because of a police failure to act, or do anything that might provide a solution to the stalking because they don't take it seriously (Ngo, 2020). However, lack of evidence also emerged as a perceived facilitator to the stalking still continuing, and it was the lack of evidence that resulted in police inaction (Brady & Reys, 2024). This was exemplified in the cases of the current study that suggest police are not taking the stalking seriously, or just simply cannot act due to the evidence threshold. These findings suggest an alignment with the Focal Concerns Theory (FCT), (Steffensmeier et al., 1993, 1998) that proposes criminal justice actors consider availability of evidence, among other concerns when deciding to act on a victims crime reports.

Focal Concerns Theory (FCT) suggests that criminal justice outcomes are shaped not only by evidence but also by decision-makers' perceptions of blameworthiness, community protection needs, and practical constraints, perceptions that are filtered through conscious and unconscious cognitive biases (Steffensmeier et al., 1993, 1998). The present study, consistent with Korkodeilou (2016), indicates that myths and stereotypes about stalking strongly influence these perceptions, producing disparities in case handling and responses. A key mechanism sustaining these biases is inadequate stalking specific training, which leaves officers reliant on normative scripts rather than empirically grounded risk cues (Ngo, 2020). Consequently, even when victims are encouraged and validated to report, their access to protection hinges on discretionary judgments within a system structured by FCT logics (Brady & Reys, 2024). Theoretically, this underscores that improving

outcomes requires not only stronger evidence collection but also interventions that recalibrate focal concerns through training, structured risk tools to reduce stereotype driven disparities in stalking cases.

Responses to stalking have shown to be dependent on the seriousness of the offence and the offender in some cases (Ngo, 2020). However, these considerations can become obstacles for victims, which can be overcome by validation actions, as evidenced above, such as police taking a formal report and both victim and police logging every incident. These positive actions have shown to improve the stalking outcome, whereas, this study suggests that non-action can dissuade victims, compromising their safety.

Victim Inaction

Victim inaction is considered as victims' perceiving that their own failure to act, or decisions of taking no steps, such as disclosing to stop the stalking as the facilitator for the stalking still occurring (Scott et al, 2018). This emergent perception was evidenced in cases where victims chose not to act on the advice given, or reluctance to instruct help from another. This reluctance to get others involved this study suggests, can stem from a fear of consequence, shame and embarrassment. As evidenced by expressions that the reason they perceive that the stalking is still occurring, is due to their own choice to either not seek help because of the fear of indirect or direct consequences if they do, as seen in the help-seeking decisions section. Some researchers (Scott et al, 2018; Brady & Reynolds, 2024). have argued that victims will be reluctant to report because they fear not being believed or that the offence is a private matter, and this reluctance has been experienced by both male and female participants in the current study. This study found support for the suggestion that fear of not being believed played an important role in the decision to not take action, regardless of the victims' gender.

Furthermore, the psychological consequences of stalking can in itself pose a barrier to seeking support, as the victim can experience shame, anxiety and depression (Logan & Walker, 2009). This study highlights the importance of perceptions in the help-seeking decisions that stalking victims' make, as inaction has shown to facilitate the stalking still occurring, meaning these victims' are left in a continuance cycle of fear and isolation.

Theoretically, this finding links disclosure decisions to core mechanisms of deterrence. Under Social Reaction Theory, supportive responses to a disclosure enables victims to mobilize protective actions and formal controls. Under the rational choice perspective, disclosure activates capable

guardians (friends, supervisors, police), which raises the offender's perceived risk and effort, and can reduce opportunity thereby increasing the expected costs of continued stalking. Conversely, inaction such as, no disclosure, no response, or disclosure without action signals low support and low sanction risk, leaving the offender's cost-benefit calculus unchanged and facilitating persistence. The balance of genders of victims in this section suggest these processes are driven more by situational controls and social responses than by victim demographics. This study highlights the importance of prompt, validating, and action-oriented responses by victims and responders to disclosures to disrupt stalking trajectories.

Stalking has stopped

The explored theories and research have suggested that once a victim has made the journey to acknowledge the stalking, the majority are in a heightened sense of fear, anxiety and in many cases depression (Baum et al, 2009; Bray & Reynolds, 2024). It is at this stage, that some will make the decision to take action, either indirectly or directly to rectify the situation, and some also choose to seek criminal justice as per the Rational Choice Perspective, (Gottfredson & Gottfredson, 1998). It is here, at this stage, as this study argues, that victims, friends and family, support agencies, law enforcement and criminal justice systems have the ideal opportunity to help create positive outcomes despite this abhorrent crime, with a purpose of mitigating the long-term negative psychological and financial impacts through validating social reactions and in turn actions.

The current research explored the factors involved with victim's perceptions of why the stalking has stopped. The stalking had stopped for just over half of the participants in this study. The reasons varied for participants and many declared having to take action, such as move home, change jobs, or change their daily routines in order to avoid the stalker and/or stalker behaviours, or seek help from others, such as law enforcement, supporting previous research on help-seeking behaviours, (Reynolds and Englebrecht, 2010; Brady & Reynolds, 2024).

Action

Action is considered as the process of doing something, typically to achieve the aim of stopping the stalking from continuing, according to Taber-Smith (2017). Action in this study, was the perceived reason by participants in this section that the stalking had stopped. Specifically police action and victim action. For example, the process of doing something as evidenced in this research usually begins with the victim taking action themselves, or seeking help for the stalking, such as

involving help from their educational institutions, workplace, friends and family and police whereby the responders acted swiftly, and aided these victims to cease the stalking behaviours.

Furthermore, previous research, (Boehnlein et al, 2020; Backes et al, 2020) argue that addressing help-seeking behaviours have exhibited the importance of validating experiences through believing discourses, not minimizing the victims' stalking experience, as exemplified and supported in previous sections of this study. Notwithstanding, if those receiving the disclosure react in a positive and supportive manner, more victims would come forward, minimizing the shame that is felt and removing the barriers at each stage, and potentially aiding the behaviours to cease, in turn creating a positive stalking outcome; freedom from this abuse.

Police Action

Previous research has suggested that contacting the police can be a significant predictor to why the stalking had stopped, (Brady, 2022; Brady & Reynolds, 2024), evidencing the importance of formal help-seeking decisions on the stalking outcome. This study supports this and previous research by (Ngo, 2018; Nicastro et al, 2000; and Brady, 2020), that suggests responses to stalking disclosures in relation to stalking outcomes whereby the victims who had reported to police, and police either spoke with/warned the perpetrator, or initiated criminal justice action and the stalking had ceased.

In further support for the Ullman (2010) Social Reaction Theory, this study argues that positive police action resulted in the stalking behaviour stopping, also evidencing support for (Ngo, 2020). Previous literature has revealed that approximately 30% to 50% of victims will seek police support to aid in the stalking, (Reynolds and Englebrecht, 2014; Ngo, 2014). This topic as a research focus is important as a long term stalking experience can lead to long-term psychological harm, where recognition and action early on can help to mitigate these consequences (Nicastro et al, 2000).

The current research argues that intervention is necessary to help mitigate the negative consequences of stalking. This is because, if a victim, or the person they are disclosing to does not realize the experiencing is stalking, then seeking help for the victimization will not be a positive experience. Previous research by Taylor-Dunn et al (2018) suggested one way for police to mitigate long-lasting episodes of stalking is for the investigating officers to shift their investigative focus from the perpetrators' behaviours to the psychological consequence of the victims, which may result in faster police acknowledgment of the stalking. This would be a shift from the focal concerns (Steffensmeier et al, 1993; 1998) that criminal justice systems are required consider, in order to make decisions within the limits of practical constraints and considerations.

As it has been suggested by Brady and Reynolds (2024), and supported by this study, if law enforcement can shift the focus away from focal concerns and bias misunderstandings of stalking, to a victim standpoint, such as the victims' concern for the seriousness of the perpetrators' behaviour, and the consequences of the pursuit type, the duration, frequency, co-occurring crimes, and personal and or professional consequences for the victim.

Theoretically, consistent, action-oriented law enforcement responses transform disclosure into effective guardianship, disrupting stalking trajectories. Through Social Reaction Theory, validated disclosures bolster victims' coping and engagement; through rational choice perspectives, coordinated action raises perceived risk and effort for offenders, promoting deterrence. As these practices become uniform across jurisdictions, they also build institutional legitimacy and recalibrate community norms, reducing societal misconceptions about stalking and encouraging earlier reporting. The study thus argues that stalking cessation can be facilitated by disclosure discourse, regardless of victim gender, particularly when disclosures reliably trigger concrete protective actions.

Victim Action

Victim action can take many forms, as we have evidenced, from disclosing to police, civil action, blocking, even changing jobs or to moving home, to attempt to stop the stalking, (Reynolds & Englebrecht, 2010; Brady & Reynolds, 2024). Victims of stalking must take a proactive approach, because legal systems and offenders cannot always be relied upon to stop the stalking behaviour, as exemplified in cases of stalker persistence. Therefore, if a victim can shift their focus to safety, and proactive measures, this can give a sense of control back to the victim, potentially lessening the psychological impacts of the crime, as suggested by (Nichols, 2020).

The current research proposes that there are some instances, where the stalking persistence requires drastic action by a victim to stop the stalking, this is evidenced by the cases where the victims had to move home, sometimes with their family, change jobs, and completely hide their locations in order to get away from their stalkers. Moving home and taking away any convenience of access, or contact for the stalker, in the victims' perceptions, this drastic action stopped the stalking behaviours. This area of the study supports the theory of Rational Choice perspective as key indicators of harm, persistence and social perceptions influence a victims' decision whether or not to

disclose, and what actions if any influence the stalking outcome, (Gottfredson and D. M. Gottfredson, 1988; Bradford and Reynolds, 2010).

Theoretically, this section illustrates rational choice and situational crime prevention dynamics from the victim's perspective. When perceived seriousness and imminent risk rise, victims update their cost to benefit estimation and adopt high-cost measures (relocation, job change, secrecy) that sharply increase the stalker's effort, risk, and uncertainty while removing convenient access and routine convergence settings. Such drastic actions function as capable protective, disrupting offender routines and reducing opportunities even without criminal justice intervention. Although the personal costs are substantial, bounded rationality under threat makes these choices optimal when the expected costs of inaction (continued harm) exceed the burdens of relocation.

Summary

In summary, this study has emphasized the significant role that social learning plays in shaping cognitive biases and societal misconceptions that affect stalking victims throughout their entire victimization journey. The study has revealed how these factors can create barriers to a victims' acknowledgment of their situation and hinder their willingness to seek help, impacting both male and female victims alike. The research has further illustrated the potential harmful effects of invalidating social reactions that victims may encounter when they disclose their experiences of stalking. Such reactions, often rooted in social learning, can intensify the psychological distress that victims endure and simultaneously discourage them from pursuing the support they need. In contrast, it has also been illustrated that positive social reactions which are validating, can facilitate acknowledgment, and potentially encourage help-seeking, which may facilitate more positive stalking outcomes.

The findings underscore the critical need for action when an individual is experiencing the crime of stalking. It is essential for professionals working in the field of stalking, as well as for law enforcement and the wider communities, to enhance their understanding and training regarding these issues to help facilitate action to stop the stalking, such as logging and reporting. By fostering environments that encourage positive disclosures, which validates the realities of victims, we can then work towards more constructive outcomes. This will not only help to alleviate some of the emotional burdens faced by victims, but also promote a culture of support and understanding. The implications of these findings, along with strategies for improving responses to stalking cases, will be explored in greater detail in the next chapter.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

INTRODUCTION

This chapter will conclude the study by summarizing the key research findings in relation to the research aims and questions and discuss the value and contribution thereof. This chapter will begin with a summary of the study aims, the significance of key findings for the topics of stalking acknowledgment, help-seeking behaviours and disclosure discourse and finally the stalking outcome. It will also review the limitations of the study, policy and practice implications and finally propose opportunities for future research.

STUDY AIMS

The significance of this research lies in its exploration of the complex journey that victims of stalking navigate, shedding light on a critical issue in contemporary society where interpersonal crimes, such as stalking are alarmingly prevalent. Victims face a myriad of challenges as they confront their victimization, balancing personal safety with various considerations that affect their health, finances, and overall wellbeing. By investigating the process of acknowledgment and the subsequent help-seeking behaviours, this study not only highlights the emotional and psychological turmoil experienced by victims but also offers insights into the factors that influence their decisions. Understanding these dynamics is essential for developing effective support systems and interventions, ultimately aiming to improve outcomes for victims. This study aimed to explore victims of stalking journey from acknowledging they are being stalked, to the factors and decisions relating to help-seeking, including how these decisions relate to the stalking outcome.

This research addresses significant gaps in stalking studies by exploring the factors influencing victims at various stages of their experiences, particularly how disclosures impact acknowledgment, help-seeking, and the stalking outcomes. It applies relevant theories, such as social learning, social reactions, rational choice, control balance, and focal concerns to understand these influences, thereby filling a critical void in existing literature.

The study highlights the intersectionality of social sciences, psychology, victimology, and criminology in comprehending stalking and its implications. It stresses the need for evolving societal perceptions to recognize that stalking can affect anyone, regardless of gender, and that all victims deserve validation. Suggesting collaboration among employers, practitioners, researchers, and policymakers is essential for developing comprehensive training and policies on interpersonal

violence, particularly stalking. By addressing misconceptions, reducing stigma, and enhancing support networks, we can create an environment that fosters healing for victims.

This study attempted this exploration using a qualitative research design using an online cross-sectional survey and face to face interviews. This research approach was used to address the gaps in stalking research, such as understanding the factors that influence victims at all stages of the stalking journey. To date there has not been a study conducted that explores the entire journey for stalking victims, taken from the victims perspectives to understand the complexities that each stage of this journey can entail.

SIGNIFICANCE OF KEY FINDINGS

The journey of stalking for a victim begins with acknowledging the experience of stalking as the first step towards help-seeking decisions and behaviours (Reyns and Englebrecht, 2011). This study explored whether or not there is a relationship between disclosure responses and victims' acknowledgment of their experience as stalking, including any potential differences between genders. This work reveals the intricate relationship between social biases, misconceptions about stalking, and the acknowledgment of victims' experiences. It fills a gap in the literature that non-acknowledgment and delays can stem from social learning processes that reinforce stereotypes and misunderstandings, indicating that societal norms shape individual perceptions. Arguing that male victims appeared to experience more cognitive biases in the context of gender normative assumptions, whilst female victims appeared to experience more normative assumptions about the stalkers and stalker behaviours. These assumptions were found to be barriers to their acknowledgment that what they were experiencing was in fact stalking. This suggestion also supports both the Fisher et al (2003) and Becker et al (2020) propositions that cognitive biases play a role in stalking acknowledgement.

In fact, non- acknowledgment and a delay in acknowledgment was found to have a relationship with social bias perceptions, misconceptions of stalking. This finding suggests support for the Bandura's (1977) theory of social learning. As the social learning appeared to create the misconceptions. These misconceptions arose from a variety of social representations and common stereotypes creating misunderstandings about the crime of stalking, a similar finding to the Fox et al (2011) study. On the other hand, despite the evidence that social learning can create failures or delays in acknowledgment, disclosure discourse has shown in this study to be a facilitator for the understanding about the experience as the crime of stalking, and this occurred for both male and female victims. Suggesting that there is a relationship between disclosure responses and

acknowledgment. The findings underscore the need for practical interventions to clarify misconceptions and enhance acknowledgment rates. However, there is a gap in longitudinal studies to monitor how these perceptions evolve over time among various populations. This research contributes to victimology by deepening the understanding of victim experiences and the psychological effects of social stigma related to stalking. It also informs social psychology regarding social learning and bias perception.

Furthermore, the research reveals the complex relationship between societal perceptions and stalking victimization, advocating for transformative changes in community and criminal justice approaches. Validating victims, educating responders, and implementing systemic changes are crucial for improving support. By prioritizing victim perspectives and reducing stigma, society can develop a more informed approach to stalking, leading to better outcomes for all involved. It can be also surmised that cognitive distortions can not only heavily influence victims' perceptions, but also the responses to stalking, suggesting that societal stereotypes about what constitutes stalking often fail to encompass the complex realities faced by victims. The implications of these distortions can create scenarios whereby the victim is left in isolation with their victimization and this exemplifies the importance of stalking awareness as a facilitator to stalking acknowledgment, which can then lead to the victim attaining support for their experience. However, not all victims of stalking seek help once the stalking has been acknowledged and previous literature has suggested the factors of why stalking is so under disclosed is predominantly due to victims perceptions (Fox et al, 2011).

This research has shown, those who have experienced stalking victimization may face additional challenges in the world due to a lack of social education on stalking, resulting in a lack of support and action to stop the stalking. Scholarly research argues that stalking is a gender based crime, affecting female victims considerably more than males (Proctor, 2018). This study found support for stalking as a dominantly female targeted crime, supporting the proposition made by Proctor (2018). This study also argues that victims not only grapple with their own feelings of shame, embarrassment, and anxiety but also with a pervasive fear of social stigma, which ultimately discourages them from seeking help (Logan and Walker, 2009). Both male and female victims have shown to suffer these fears of social stigma as imagined or projected reactions to their victimization by other people. However, there were differences between genders in the perceptions. These differences were found to be normative gender assumptions, mainly for the male victims, whereas the societal normative assumptions were found mainly for female victims. Specifically, males suffered with internal misconceptions of what constitute a masculine reaction to victimization, and societal assumptions about gender roles. Whilst females suffered with internal and commonly held

beliefs such as stereotypical representations of stalkers and stalker behaviours. This finding is supportive of the Bandura (1977) social learning theory. Whereby misconceptions are a result of exposure to commonly held societal beliefs and suggestions (Bandura, 1977; Fox et al, 2011).

Additionally, in cases where non-disclosure decisions were made, these decisions arose from victims' fears of imagined negative reactions from potential confidants, which supports the Ullman's (2010) Social Reaction Theory. However, such barriers were compounded by the psychological distress victims endured as a direct consequence of stalking itself. This created a vicious cycle that has shown to lead to further isolation, vulnerability and psychological distress. Therefore, the present study supports the view that Ullman (2010) proposed, that a negative and unhelpful response can potentially impact on the attributions and meaning of a victims' experience, which can result in further negative consequences for help-seeking behaviours and ultimately on the victims coping mechanisms and help-seeking decisions in the context of stalking victimization.

Furthermore, the Ullman (2010) Social Reaction Theory applies not only to actual negative responses received at the point of disclosure, as suggested by Ullman, but also in the context of predicted negative social reactions as a barrier to stalking victims' help-seeking decisions. Fear has shown in previous research as one of the most common impacts disclosed by victims as a result of stalking, such as fear that stalking would never stop, physical harm, and death by the stalker (Baum et al, 2009; Logan and Walker, 2009). However, this study argues that the Ullman (2010) social reaction theory applies even when the reaction is projected by the victim, resulting in a fear of stigma. As Jutasi and McEwan (2021) had suggested, the fear of not being believed, fear of escalation, fear of job loss and fear of being victim-blamed can occur if a victim were to choose to disclose, however, this research has shown that the resulting embarrassment and shame occurs even when a disclosure has not been made, but is perceived as a likely possibility during the victims' process of deciding whether or not to seek help, ultimately dissuading these decisions.

The study also emphasizes the importance of validation for victims, suggesting that supportive responses can significantly increase their likelihood of engaging with the criminal justice system. However, reliance on systemic action can yield mixed results; positive law enforcement responses can enhance safety, while inadequate reactions may deter help-seeking. This indicates a need for further exploration into how demographic factors shape victims' experiences and interactions within the justice system. In relation to help-seeking decisions, there have been studies (Edwards et al, 2014) that demonstrate when victims of stalking do choose to seek-help and disclose their victimization to a variety of sources, they receive varying responses. Victims can perceive the response they receive as a minimizing or invalidating experience, or a helpful and validating

experience, as Ullman (2010) Social reaction theory suggested. This research chose to explore whether or not there is the relationship between a positive, helpful and a negative, unhelpful disclosure response to further help-seeking decisions, including potential gender differences.

Additionally, the research underscores the role of positive responses in alleviating psychological distress, advocating for trauma-informed approaches among professionals. It examines the interplay between victims' psychological distress, fear of negative reactions, and help-seeking behaviours, supporting Ullman's (2010) Social Reaction Theory. By demonstrating how negative responses can hinder disclosure, the study enriches our understanding of the barriers stalking victims face. Moreover, the research revealed media portrayals of stalking and the influence on public perceptions and victim acknowledgment, suggesting avenues for future research on social learning and victim experiences, supporting the application of Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory to stalking victimization.

This study found support for the Ullman (2010) social reaction theory that minimizing responses to stalking disclosures led victims to feel invalidated and victim-blamed, reflecting findings from several studies, (Crome and McCabe, 2001; McKeon et al, 2015; McEwan et al, 2018). This minimization, invalidation and even romanticizing the stalking behaviour, created obstacles, such as dissuading decisions of seeking further help for the stalking victimization. Therefore this study suggests that there is a relationship between a negative and unhelpful disclosure response and further help-seeking behaviour, for both genders.

In fact, a minimizing and/or invalidating disclosure response was found to be psychologically damaging to the victims, supporting Edwards et al (2014), who concluded negative disclosure reactions were related to an increase in psychological distress. As the compounding the psychological consequences of not being believed, along with the psychological consequences of being stalked. This promotes further support for the Ullman (2010) Social Reaction Theory that a negative response to a disclosure carries vast consequences on the attributions and meaning of victims' experiences, resulting in these victims feeling victimized further, reluctant and discouraged to continue to seek-help, and negative psychological consequences of isolation and self-worth increased, as previous argued by Ngo (2014).

However, the findings in respect to validating and helpful responses present a contrast to the findings of Edwards et al (2014), who claimed that positive reactions to disclosures had no connection to psychological distress. In contrast, this study argues that a positive and validating response, even while victims continue to live in fear, can alleviate some of the psychological distress for individuals of all genders and promote help-seeking decisions. In light of these vulnerabilities,

there is a real need to ensure that the crime of stalking and its impacts are understood within wider society, and professionals that may be a respondent to a disclosure. It is important to take a trauma sensitive approach that validates what the victim is experiencing and is supportive when dealing with stalking disclosures. Furthermore, the negative ramifications of minimizing or invalidating responses to victims' disclosures are evident, resonating with (Ullman, 2010; Edwards et al, 2014), and underscoring the necessity for supportive and affirming reactions from peers and authorities, as negative social reactions can occur in close social circles, such as family and friends, in the workplace and with law enforcement.

This study also corroborated the findings of the Reyns and Englebrecht (2010) study and aligned with the Theory of Rational Choice (Gottfredson and Gottfredson, 1998). Support for this is evident where victims demonstrated a strong commitment to seeking help despite encountering negative responses to their disclosures, particularly when the fear of the stalker existed, or when the stalker was known to have a history of stalking. This determination stemmed from the victims perceptions of perceived risk to life and a desire to ensure their own safety. The stalker's forensic pathology and previous history of stalking increased these risks, which was suggested by the Theory of Rational Choice, while also driving the victims' resolve to seek assistance, reinforcing the Reyns and Englebrecht arguments. Additionally, the known patterns of stalking, such as prior offenses, were identified as factors contributing to this determination, as indicated by Reyns and Englebrecht. Furthermore, this study found the stalker's tendency to in-still fear within communities, along with their history of persistence and various risk factors, left victims with little option but to continue pursuing help for their stalking experiences, regardless of the minimizing and invalidating responses they faced when disclosing the situation.

This study also examined whether there is a relationship between the amount of stalking behaviours to the responses received upon disclosure, as well as potential gender differences. Many stalking victims endured hundreds of the behaviours and unwanted contacts for five years or longer, which was also suggested by Sheridan et al (2003). This is a significant duration to experience ongoing fear and distress. However, it was noted in this study that law enforcement recognized the persistence and severity of stalking due to the documentation of the multiple stalking behaviours, lending support to the Theory of Rational Choice (Gottfredson & Gottfredson, 1998). The documentation of stalking incidents supports the Backes et al (2020) study and further argues this point by advocating for the documentation of stalking incidents and behaviours, as it increases the likelihood of more favourable disclosure outcomes by providing a comprehensive overview of the stalking conduct. Additionally, this study argues the responses from law enforcement aligned with the Focal Concerns Theory (Steffensmeier et al., 1993, 1998), suggesting that criminal justice

representatives, such as police, consider specific focal concerns like evidence, perpetrator culpability, the seriousness of the offense, and community safety.

However, this support for a relationship existing between the amount of stalking behaviours experienced with the disclosure response was primarily related to the evidence threshold, which considers the seriousness of the crime, especially when a detailed log of incidents is presented, resulting in a more supportive response for both male and female victims. However, control and power as suggested by the Tittle's (1995) Control Balance Theory did not appear as a factor in victim decisions to log and report. Rather, as previously stated, the persistence and duration as well as fear were the determining factor to victims presenting a log of behaviours to police. In other words, there was no evidence to support the victims desire to retain or regain control as a defining factor in these decisions. Therefore this study proposes that there is a relationship between the amount of stalking behaviours and the response received when the disclosure included the victim producing a log of incidents.

In examining the relationship between stalker type and disclosure responses, it was found that gender differences, normative assumptions, and social biases significantly influenced the dialogues experienced by victims of both genders across various typologies. Moreover, this research demonstrated further, the presence of cognitive biases and misconceptions surrounding the crime of stalking and different stalker types. These stereotypical biases align with Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory, highlighting how perceptions of stalker types are learned. Indicating that stalkers, regardless of their motivations or gender, can target anyone, and any victim, regardless of gender can become a target. The typology exploration also found support for the Theory of Rational Choice, (Gottfredson and Gottfredson, 1988) and contextualized by Reyns and Englebrecht (2010) in relation to stalking, that victims were more likely to report a stranger stalker to law enforcement, aligning these findings with Reyns and Englebrecht. Additionally, the current research further reinforces the Theory of Rational Choice and Reyns and Englebrecht work, showing that the sexual orientation of the stalking behaviour exhibited by an unknown predator not only led to immediate recognition of the stalking but also prompted victims to report to police.

Furthermore, in contrast to the Control Balance Theory (Tittle, 1995), which is theoretically relevant to stalking victimization and the perpetrator's control over the target, power and control are identified as key motivational factors in the rejected and resentful stalker typologies (Mullen et al, 1999). Some victims may respond to stalking by attempting to regain control, often by reporting retaliatory behaviors, especially when they perceive the motivations behind the stalker's actions to be rooted in power and control, particularly in cases involving an ex-partner (Taber-Smith, 2017).

This finding diverges from Gottfredson and Gottfredson (1998) assertion that a close victim/offender relationship decreases the likelihood of reporting the crime, as the vast majority of victims chose to disclose their victimization, regardless of the type of stalker involved. Consequently, the study concluded that there is no direct relationship between the typology of the stalker and the response to a victims' disclosure, for either gender.

The psychological theories in this enquiry have dealt primarily with individuals' reactions to the subjective interpretation of particular events or responses, however, it proved the ideal lens' to also apply the exploration to the relevance of the stalking outcome, addressing a substantial gap in the literature. While a substantial gap remains in this given context, the investigation attempted to address this gap by exploring whether or not there is a relationship between disclosing and the stalking behaviour stopping or continuing, and whether there were any gender differences. Arguing that actions such as disclosing was found to facilitate the stalking stopping, for both genders. In contrast, inaction by the victim and law enforcement was found to facilitate the continuance of the stalking, for both genders. This study also found that both genders experienced many different types of stalking victimization and societal biases, highlighting the need for a paradigm shift within society and law enforcement agencies. Adopting a victim-centric approach that prioritizes the seriousness of the perpetrator's behaviour and the unique consequences of the stalking. There is potential if this paradigm shift occurs, not only to empower victims but also to enhance the response to stalking incidents in a way that validates victims' experiences.

Additionally, it has been argued, when victims receive validation and encouragement to report stalking, they become dependent on the decisions and actions of the criminal justice system, which is significantly influenced by the Focal Concerns Theory (Brady and Reynolds, 2024). Positive actions can lead to improved outcomes for victims, while a lack of action can undermine their safety and deter them from seeking help. Brady and Reynolds suggested that law enforcement should shift their focus to a victim-centered perspective rather than current focal concerns to foster a more consistently positive discourse around disclosures, ultimately leading to less persistent stalking outcomes for all victims.

Research also indicates that negative responses to a victim's disclosure can hinder further help-seeking, while positive reactions can encourage additional disclosures (Crome and McCabe, 2001; Reynolds and Englebrecht, 2011; Ullman, 2010; Edwards et al., 2014). This study argues that, in some instances, police do not take stalking seriously or are unable to act due to evidence thresholds. This aligns with Focal Concerns Theory (FCT) (Steffensmeier et al., 1993, 1998), which posits that criminal justice actors consider the availability of evidence, among other factors, when determining whether

to act on a victim's report. The FCT also suggests that disparities in case outcomes arise from cognitive biases that may be consciously or unconsciously applied during criminal justice processing and decision-making (Steffensmeier et al., 1993, 1998). Current research, along with the Korkodeilou, (2016) study, supports this disparity, indicating that myths and cognitive biases significantly influence responses to stalking behaviours. Another crucial factor contributing to police inaction identified as the lack of formal training on stalking for law enforcement, which can help counter normative perceptions (Ngo, 2020).

In addition, Sheridan et al, (2003) observed that victims often endure many behaviours before seeking assistance, while Jordan et al, (2003) noted that interactions with law enforcement frequently leave victims feeling that their experiences are not taken seriously, with police inaction often exacerbating the stalking situation. Achieving a consistently positive police response to stalking disclosures remains a significant challenge for both male and female victims, as highlighted studies conducted by Fisher et al, (2003) and Taylor-Dunn, (2019), and throughout this study.

This research has shown that reporting to the police is not the only strategy victims use to address stalking behaviours. Supporting the Baum et al (2009) study whom found that victims often altered their daily routines, took time off work, and avoided social interactions. Additionally, Worsley et al, (2017) noted that victims employ various strategies to cope with stalking, including avoidant coping, ignoring the perpetrator, confronting them, seeking support, help-seeking, and cognitive reframing. This aspect of the study aligns with the Rational Choice Theory, which suggests that key indicators of harm, persistence, and social perceptions influence a victim's decision to disclose their experience and the actions they take, if any, that affect the stalking outcome (Gottfredson and D. M. Gottfredson, 1988; Bradford and Reys, 2010). This study highlights that victims' decisions to take action against stalking do not always rely on criminal justice interventions. It also supports the notion (Reys and Englebrecht, 2011) that the more serious a crime is perceived to be by the victim, the more likely they are to take significant action.

In summary, this work identifies critical gaps in literature regarding how societal norms shape perceptions and emphasizes the need for practical interventions. By enhancing our understanding of victim experiences and the psychological effects of stigma, this research informs victimology, criminology and social psychology.

LIMITATIONS OF THIS STUDY

There are always limitations to be considered within any research study, and this study is no different and the limitations are evident. Research limitations may include issues of sampling,

location, interpretation, and labelling, amongst others. Ultimately, limitations are inherent to any research study, yet the importance is not only in acknowledging such limitations, but building upon such insights when carrying out future research. It is hoped that by pointing out these limitations future research can avoid such potential pitfalls.

Due to the need to access stalking victims as the cohort for this study, it was not possible to provide a random sample of participants, therefore having to adopt a convenience sampling strategy instead, which can impact the generalizability of findings and therefore reflects a limitation of the study. However, this can also be considered a strength of the study, given that this research was exploring the stalking victims' journey from the victims' perspective, the convenience sample approach combined with the qualifying criteria ensured that participants were in fact victims of stalking behaviours.

Online surveys offer several advantages, including easy distribution and creation, along with minimal to no administrative costs (Andrade, 2020). However, it is important to recognize the limitations of online surveys. One significant issue is Sampling Bias, which can occur if the survey only reaches individuals who are literate and sufficiently interested in the topic (Andrade, 2020). For instance, recruitment efforts involved targeting specific charities like Action Against Stalking and Paladin for participant involvement. To address Sampling Bias, the researcher chose not to mention the term "stalking" in the recruitment materials or the survey until the final question. Additionally, recruitment was conducted through general social media pages and groups unrelated to stalking, aiming to enhance the generalizability of the findings to individuals who have experienced stalking.

Additionally, there are strengths found in face to face interviews, such as that they are ideally suited to experience-type research investigations and research questions. Interviews are also suited for the exploration of perception and social constructions for understanding experience. Face to face interviews can generate rich and detailed data about the individual experiences, and ideal for exploring sensitive issues such as the topic of stalking particularly when the researcher is skilled in interview techniques (Braun and Clarke, 2013). However, face to face interviews also carry limitations, they are time consuming for the researcher when organizing, conducting and analyzing. Face to face interviews are time consuming for the participant, lack of anonymity may be discouraging to some victims of stalking. This may be a valid reason that I was unable to attract interview participants who had decided not to disclose their victimization. Furthermore, interviews are not necessarily empowering for the participant, as they have less control over the data generated, compared to qualitative survey and email interviews as suggested by Braun and Clarke (2013).

This study also did not gather many participants from the LGBTQ+ cohort, which would have made for a much more in-depth gender exploration than just having to consider the male/female differences. Although, this study did gather some valuable insight into the differences in gender perceptions and normative assumption that male and female victims experience.

Demographic information was not gathered during the cross-sectional survey, which poses a limitation as it prevents an analysis of the participants' demographics. This realization highlights an intriguing learning opportunity and raises the question of potential generational differences in acknowledgment, especially given the rising use of electronic methods for stalking victims, which could be explored in future research. On the positive side, the study benefited from a substantial amount of data from participants who opted not to disclose their demographics, and it was determined that this information was not necessary to address the research questions being investigated.

Due to the amount of participants that took part, this study was not able to conduct regression analysis to understand any category membership predictions, similar to the majority of stalking research that has been conducted. However, although the researcher intended to include regression analysis as a mixed method design originally, there were simply not enough participants to avoid errors in the data, and therefore a qualitative design was adopted. The strength to the qualitative design is in the context of the victim perspectives, gained through the open ended question in the survey and the interviews that were conducted, as the information was received from the victims' experiences and perspectives, and therefore was rich in context and applicable to the research questions.

A qualitative study can also be subject to researcher bias compared to a mixed method study. The research attempted to mitigate any potential researcher bias by taking the time, at regular intervals, to reflect on any pre-conceived notions and expectations regarding the analysis outcomes, particularly as a stalking victim advocate, and a stalking victim, the researcher was mindful not to analyze the data in a way that may have been informed through the experience and practice of advocacy, but rather from the voice of the participants, which is why the categories were created after the data was collected.

IMPLICATIONS OF FINDINGS ON PRACTICE AND POLICY

In an era where social dynamics and support systems are crucial for addressing stalking victimization, the impact of research on training programs for informal support networks cannot be

overstated. By emphasizing the vital role of social support, these initiatives address the often-overlooked issue of gendered victimization, fostering a more inclusive understanding of victimhood.

This research advocates for victim-centered approaches, ensuring that the needs and experiences of victims are prioritized in both educational initiatives for victims and training for helping professions in the workplace. Additionally, it challenges prevailing misconceptions through targeted social education, ultimately shifting the focus of law enforcement towards more empathetic and effective practices. Collectively, these efforts not only empower victims but also cultivate a more informed and compassionate society, capable of supporting all individuals in their healing journeys. This research has the potential to significantly benefit various organizations, such as charities supporting stalking victims, NHS practitioners, and social workers within local councils, as well as police and criminal justice actors.

Charities such as Action Against Stalking whom support victims of stalking can develop training programs incorporating findings for volunteers and staff, organizations can better equip supporters with the tools to provide effective emotional and psychological assistance, focusing on the nuances of victim experiences. This research can also inform campaigns that challenge misconceptions about stalking, fostering a more empathetic public response and reducing stigma for victims. These programs can also include discussions on the impact of negative social reactions and how to counteract them, fostering a more supportive environment for victims. Furthermore, initiatives that encourage positive social engagement and understanding can help mitigate the adverse effects of victimization. The current lack of social education regarding stalking has contributed to pervasive misconceptions that can hinder victims' journeys. The study sheds light on the often-overlooked issue of male victimization in stalking scenarios. By identifying specific predictors of help-seeking behaviours among male victims, the research offers valuable insights for practitioners and policymakers. This understanding is vital for developing targeted support systems that cater to the unique needs of male stalking victims.

To effectively combat inter-personal violence in the workplace, it is imperative to investigate the prevalence of such incidents and the adequacy of existing workplace policies in the UK. By implementing targeted research and policy initiatives, organizations such as Scottish Governments Councils and Social work can better understand the dynamics of stalking and related forms of violence, ultimately fostering a safer work environment. Recommendations may include the establishment of clear reporting mechanisms, training programs for management and staff, and support systems for victims, ensuring that workplaces not only acknowledge the issue, but also actively work towards prevention and response strategies.

Furthermore, in respect to councils and social work policy development, the research findings can inform local government policies aimed at enhancing support systems for victims, ensuring that social workers are equipped with the knowledge to advocate for victim-centered approaches for service users.

This study suggests policy changes for NHS Scotland, with insights from the research to guide NHS professionals in offering tailored support to victims, recognizing the psychological impact of stalking and addressing mental health needs more effectively for both staff and for the service users. Training programs can be developed that emphasize the importance of workplace support in recovery, helping affected practitioners understand how to involve their managers in safety planning.

Addressing the gaps in understandings and responding to stalking requires a shift in perspective, particularly regarding how victims are perceived and how the Scottish criminal justice systems interact with them. Promoting a victim-centered approach can help reduce stigma and encourage more nuanced and supportive responses to disclosures. By prioritizing the perspectives of victims, criminal justice systems can cultivate a more informed and empathetic approach to stalking victimization, ultimately leading to healthier outcomes for all individuals affected. It is suggested that law enforcement agencies such as Police Scotland, should transition to a victim-centered perspective, moving away from traditional focal concerns. This shift can foster a more positive discourse surrounding disclosures of stalking, ultimately resulting in less persistent and more effective resolutions for victims. By emphasizing empathy and support in law enforcement practices, we can create a safer environment for all individuals affected by stalking.

This research can also be leveraged to push for amendments to existing laws or the introduction of new legislation that prioritizes victim needs, particularly in relation to emotional and psychological support. In Scotland, this could involve advocating for laws that recognize the unique challenges faced by stalking victims and ensure that support services are accessible and responsive in all stalking cases. By highlighting the critical role of social support, this research can guide legislative frameworks to empower victims, allowing them to have a voice in the legal process and access the support they need. It can also inform training and resources for police and practitioners, promoting a more empathetic approach to handling stalking cases.

In summary, the insights gained from this research can profoundly influence how organizations, practitioners, and policymakers approach stalking victimization. By promoting victim-centered practices, educating informal support networks, and advocating for legislative changes, we can create a more informed and compassionate society that better supports individuals in their stalking

journeys. In the UK, particularly in Scotland, these efforts can empower victims and enhance the effectiveness of those who serve them, fostering a holistic approach to addressing the complexities of stalking and fostering better outcomes.

FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

This study proposes that more research is needed to facilitate a better understanding of the Ullman (2010) Social Reaction theory in the paradigm of stalking, particularly in the context of male victimization and help-seeking decisions, as there is little research conducted in this area.

This study suggests that there is very little up to date research conducted to understand stalking victimization in the United Kingdom and would require a large national crime survey to better understand stalking prevalence between genders, help-seeking and societal views on stalking perceptions.

This study also proposes a large scale study investigating more in-depth gender exploration that includes the LGBTQ+ cohort of victims, and comparing demographic differences.

This study suggests that there may be generational differences in perceptions of stalking in the context of traditional and cyberstalking. Highlighting that the importance of exploring whether the same social narratives are in play across age groups.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1a) Survey Consent and Participation Information:

An Exploration of Disclosure Responses

Informed Consent

Participation Information:

You are invited to take part in a research study investigating disclosure responses following the experience of unwanted behaviors and contacts you may have received from a person(s) on 2 or more occasions. The goal of this study is to understand how disclosure responses can potentially impact further help-seeking decisions. The purpose of this study is to inform academia, education materials, legislative stakeholders, support agencies and law-enforcement agencies and wider societies regarding the importance of positive responses when an individual discloses a personal circumstance or situation. This study is being conducted as part of a PhD research studentship with The University of The West of Scotland. Participating in this study may not benefit you directly, however, it will add to the growing social science research on disclosures and the importance of positive responses. However because this study is asking questions of the experience of unwanted contacts and/or behaviors targeted at yourself, you may find yourself feeling distress, if this occurs you can withdraw your participation at any time during the survey. At the end of the survey you will be provided with links to support if you so require.

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary, if you agree to participate in this study, you will be required to complete multiple choice and open questions, which will take 5-10 minutes.

Confidentiality:

This survey includes questions of a personal nature, and the information you share will be kept completely confidential to the full extent of the law, your data will be allocated automatically an anonymous number to ensure complete confidentiality in the analysis and reporting. Therefore you can withdraw participation at any time throughout the survey, however once completed the data will be unavailable for withdrawal. To address any questions or complaints you may have please contact the researcher at [REDACTED]

As this study includes open questions, requiring you to write in your own words about individual experiences, you may find answering these upsetting. If you find answering this survey has caused you distress, you can withdraw your participation at any time during the survey, or you can access emotional support if required at support@actionagainststalking.org, quoting 'Research Support' in the subject area.

Data Use:

The data that will be collected will include demographics such as age, gender and country of residence for statistical comparisons, and the open answers to the survey questions will be analyzed using qualitative approaches using themes and coding. All data will be stored according to the University of the West of Scotland's Data requirements. and GDPR practices. Data will be fully anonymized and held securely for 5 years following the data analysis. Results will be published for academic peer-review.

Inclusion criteria: You must be 18 years of age to participate in this study. The survey will qualify you for inclusion automatically after the first few sets of questions.

Exclusion criteria: You must not participate in this study if: you do not consent, you are under the age of 18, or you cannot read, write, or comprehend the English language or if you have been diagnosed with serious mental health disorder(s) or illness, to ensure participation is ethical according to the University of The West of Scotland Ethics Committee.

Consent:

I have read and understand the above consent form, by completing this survey, I indicate my willingness to voluntarily take part in this study.

I wish to participate ____ I do not wish to participate ____

Appendix 1b) Interview Consent and Participation information:

An Exploration of the Relationship between Disclosures and Responses on Help-seeking Behaviours for Victims of Stalking

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

1) Invitation

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information. Ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether you wish to take part. *Thank you for reading this.*

2) Who am I and what is the purpose of the study?

I am conducting research as part of my PhD at the University of the West of Scotland on the topic of help-seeking decisions, responses received to stalking outcomes. I want to learn more about the perceptions of victims' experiences of help-seeking decisions and whether this reflects stalking victims' experiences so that individuals and organizations can understand the importance of help-seeking decisions and responses have on stalking victims and wider society.

I will be focusing my research on stalking victims' experiences and whether they feel disclosing (or not) of their stalking experiences harms or benefits the stalking outcomes.

It is hoped that the research will provide more knowledge and understanding in the following areas:

- Victims' experiences of stalking including the reporting, and receiving support.
- Victims' experiences of disclosing and if the responses received either harms or benefits the stalking outcomes.
- Victim's experiences of not disclosing and if these decisions either harms or benefits the stalking outcomes.

3) Why have you been invited to take part?

I want to conduct a semi-structured interview and I am seeking volunteers who have previously experienced stalking as a victim to participate in this stage of my PhD research. I have shared my early thoughts of my research with you informally and understand you have such experience. You also indicated that you may be interested in being interviewed for the research.

4) Do you have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep. You will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm that you have read and understood the information, have had the opportunity to ask questions about the research and interview, and agree to take part in the study. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

5) What will taking part involve?

You sign the consent form for the interview to proceed.

You will be given a copy of this information sheet and signed consent form to keep along with a support leaflet.

I will agree a time and date suitable to you and arrange a formal interview via the telephone or video conferencing. The interview will take approximately 30 minutes.

The interview will be treated in strictest confidence. You will be asked to create a four-digit code so that if you choose to withdraw your participation, your transcripts can be identified.

6) What do I have to do?

You will be asked a range of questions as part of the interview.

You will be asked if you agree to the interview being recorded. If not, only written notes will be taken. All notes and recordings will be kept secure and only seen by the researcher and only identifiable through the four-digit code you create.

You do not need to do any preparation work for this.

7) What are the possible risks of taking part?

You may become uncomfortable with the interview. If this happens, the interview will pause or stop as appropriate.

If you become uncomfortable before, during or after the interview, you can contact Action Against Stalking's Throughcare Support Service for support at the below email. You will also be given a support leaflet with Action Against Stalking's contact details.

Action Against Stalking Freephone Helpline: 0800 820 2427

Action Against Stalking Email: support@actionagainststalking.org

Alternatively, you may choose to contact Samaritans for advice as Action Against Stalking is not a 24/7 service:

Samaritans – 116 123 or <https://www.samaritans.org/?nation=scotland>

8) **What are the possible benefits of taking part?**

You will be contributing to research which may:

- Give stalking victims a voice in sharing their experiences.
- Explore the functions of the help-seeking decisions informing public opinions associated with stalking.
- Assist the public in recognising and understanding stalking.
- Assist with future anti-stalking legislation, policy, and funding for support services.

9) **Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?**

All information which is collected about you during the research will be kept strictly confidential.

You will be given a case number and only this number will be used in any written material. The coded list will be submitted in strictest confidence only to the supervisor purely to verify and act as proof that the interview has taken place. The list will not form part of any published document.

The data from the interviews will be described for the entire interviewee population. Individual stories will not be described in full, but anonymised quotes may be used, so that they cannot be tracked back to the individual. Individuals will not be named in any documentation, only the case number will be indicated.

Confidentiality applies to all data, written and recorded.

10) **What will happen to the results of the research study?**

The data will contribute to the thesis for submission for my PhD. The anonymized data will be discussed with my supervisor(s) during the period of my research.

The anonymized thesis will be assessed by two examiners, one of whom will be a member of staff at University of the West of Scotland, the other will be from another University - both will be senior academics.

When the PhD is granted, a copy of the anonymized thesis will be kept in the library of University of the West of Scotland.

I may produce further publications and/or make presentations on my findings. Data from the thesis to be used will be similarly anonymized.

11) Who you should contact for further information

PhD Research Student:

Amanda Morrison
 University of the West of Scotland
 [Redacted]
 Amanda Morrison
 2024

Lead Supervisor:

Dr. Robert Mclean
 University of the West of Scotland
 [Redacted]

Appendix 2a) Survey questions

Disclosure & Response Survey Questionnaire

Researcher: Amanda Morrison

Thank you for consenting to take part in this study.

I would like to ask you some questions about times when you may have experienced unwanted contacts or behaviours' that were targeted at you by the same person (s). I would like to remind you that the information you provide is completely confidential.

When answering, please think of anyone who may have done these things, including current or former spouses, partners, acquaintances, colleagues, neighbours, clients or other people you may know, or strangers, please **DO NOT** include bill collectors, solicitors, telemarketers or sales people.

A. Have you ever experienced any targeted and unwanted contact or behaviours on 2 or more occasions?	1. Yes 2. No
B. Did any of the unwanted contacts or behaviours result in you feeling fear, distress or alarm?	1. Yes 2. No

1. Can you tell what age you were when you started to experience the unwanted contacts or behaviours?	_____
2. What gender do you consider yourself to be?	1. Male 2. Female 3. Other recognised gender
3. What country did you reside in when these unwanted contacts or behaviours began?	_____

4. What is the gender of the person(s) who have done these things to you?	1. Male 2. Female 3. Other recognised gender 4. Mixture of recognised gender(more than 1 person) 4. Don't know
5. How old would you say this person is when the unwanted contact or behaviours began? (please mark <u>unknown</u> if you do not know the person(s))	<hr/>
6. How did you know person who committed these unwanted contacts or behaviours when they first began? (please mark <u>Unknown</u> if you do not know who)	<hr/>
7. Were the targeted unwanted contacts and behaviours online, offline or a mixture or both?	1. Online 2. Offline 3. Mixture of both online & offline
8. How long have/did these unwanted contacts or behaviours happen to you?	1. 1-6 months 2. 6months-2 years 3. 2 years-5 years 4. 5+ years
9. How many times would you say these unwanted contacts or behaviours occurred?	1. 2-10 times 2. 11-50 times 3. 50-100 times 4. 100+ times
10. Tell me in your own words why you think this person(s) started doing these things to you? (for example; rejection, retaliation, revenge, affection, power & control)	<hr/>
11. Did you disclose these unwanted contact or behaviours to anyone?	1. Yes 2. No
11a. If you answered Yes to this question, Who did you first disclose the experience to? (family/friends, support agency or police)	<hr/>
11b. What was the response you received when you first disclosed the unwanted contact and behaviours?	<hr/>
11c, if you answered No to this question, can you tell me why you chose not to disclose to anyone?	<hr/>

<p>12. Is there anyone else you disclosed the experience to?</p> <p>12a. If you answered Yes to this question, can you tell me who it was you disclosed to?(family/friends, support agency and/or police)</p> <p>12b. What was the response you received after this disclosure (s)?</p>	<p>1. Yes 2. No</p> <hr/> <hr/>
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<p>13. Can you tell me in your own words how the response(s) you received impacted how you felt about disclosing to anyone else?</p>	<hr/>
<p>14. Are the unwanted contacts or behaviours still occurring?</p> <p>a. If you answered Yes to this questions, can you tell me in your own words why you believe these unwanted contacts and behaviours are still occurring?</p> <p>b. If you answered No to this question, can you tell me why you think the unwanted contacts or behaviours stopped?</p>	<p>1. Yes 2. No</p> <hr/> <hr/>

<p>15. Do you consider the targeted unwanted contacts and behaviours you experienced as stalking?</p> <p>If you answered No to this question, can you tell me why?</p>	<p>1. Yes 2. No</p> <hr/>
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Appendix 2b) Interview Questions

Stalking victims experiences of Disclosures & Responses

Consent received?

4 Digit Code-

Qualifying Questions

1. Did you experience unwanted behaviours or contact attempts targeted at you on 2 or more occasions?
2. Did you experience fear, alarm or distress because of the targeted contact attempts/behaviours?

Interview Questions

1. Can you tell me what gender you consider yourself to be?
2. Can you tell me what age you were when the unwanted contacts/behaviours started?
3. Can you tell me the gender of the person that targeted you with the unwanted contacts/behaviours?
4. How old was the person that targeted you when the behaviours began?
5. How did you know the person who committed these unwanted behaviours and contacts?
6. Were the targeted unwanted behaviours/contacts conducted online, offline or a mixture of both?
7. For how long (months/years) did/have the unwanted behaviours happen to you?
8. How many unwanted behaviours (approximately) did you receive?
9. Can you tell why you think this person targeted/fixated on you?
10. Did you disclose the experience to anyone?
 - a). if you disclosed, can you tell me who you first disclosed to? Researcher note Go to Q.11
 - b). if you did **not** choose to disclose, can you tell me why? Researcher note Go to Q.15
11. Can you tell what the response was that you received from this disclosure?
 - a. If you received a positive/helpful response can you tell me why you think the person responded in this way?
 - b). If you received a negative/unhelpful response can you tell me why you think the person responded in this way?
 - c). do you feel that the type of stalker played a role in what response you received?
 - d.) do you feel the amount of behaviours you endured played a role in what response you received?
12. Can you tell me how the response made you feel about disclosing to anyone else?
13. Is there anyone else you did disclosed to?

- a). if you disclosed, can you tell me who you first disclosed to? Researcher note [Go to Q.14](#)
- b). if you did **not** choose to disclose, can you tell me why?
14. What was the response you received from the 2nd disclosure?
15. Are the unwanted contacts/behaviours still occurring?
- a.) can you tell me why you think the contact/behaviours are still occurring?
- b.) do you feel your decision to disclose played a role in the behaviours continuing?
Researcher note [Go to Q.16](#)
- c.) can you tell me why you think the contact/behaviours stopped?
- d.) do you feel the decision **not** to disclose played a role in the unwanted behaviours/contacts continuing?
16. Do you consider the unwanted contacts/behaviours you experienced as stalking?
- a.) If yes and you disclosed, did you acknowledge the experience as stalking before you disclosed or after?
- b). If **yes and you did not disclose**, when during this experience did you realise it was stalking? Researcher note [Go to Debrief document](#)
- c). If **No** to acknowledging the unwanted contact/behaviours as stalking, why did/do you not consider the experience as stalking?
- d.) If **No** and you **disclosed** do you feel the response you received played a role in you not recognizing the experience as stalking? Researcher note [Go to Debrief document](#)

Appendix 3a) Survey Data Summary Chart

Victim Gender N=280	Stalker Gender	Stalker behaviour	Length of time stalked	Amount of behaviours	Type of stalker	Stalking still occurring?
Male N= 57	Male= 26 Female= 29 Other identified= 0 Gender 1+ Stalker (any gender)= 2	Online= 4 Offline= 18 Mixture= 35	0-6 months= 17 7months- 2years= 23 2-5 years= 10 5+ years= 7	2-10= 3 11-50= 10 50-100= 11 100+ = 33	Rejected= 25 Resentful= 22 Intimacy seeker= 7 Incompetent Suitor= 2 Predatory/unknown= 1	Yes= 29 No= 28
Female N= 219	Male= 174 Female= 27 Other identified Gender= 1 1+ Stalker (any gender)= 14	Online= 17 Offline= 80 Mixture= 122	0-6 months= 60 7months- 2years= 68 2-5 years= 39 5+ years= 52	2-10= 26 11-50= 41 50-100= 39 100+ = 113	Rejected= 104 Resentful= 55 Intimacy seeker= 12 Incompetent Suitor= 8 Predatory/unknown= 40	Yes= 109 No= 110
Other identified gender N= 4	Male= 1 Female= 1 Other identified Gender= 2 1+ Stalker (any gender)= 0	Online= 1 Offline= 1 Mixture= 2	0-6 months= 2 7months- 2years= 0 2-5 years= 2 5+ years= 0	2-10= 0 11-50= 1 50-100= 0 100+ = 3	Rejected= 2 Resentful= 2 Intimacy seeker= 0 Incompetent Suitor= 0 Predatory/unknown= 0	Yes= 2 No= 2
Victim Gender N=280	Made 1st disclosure	Disclosed to who? 1stdisclosure N= 223	Response Received N=223	Made 2nd disclosure	Stalking Acknowledged N=280	
Male N=57	Yes= 36 No= 21	Family/friend= 23 Advocacy= 1 Police= 7 Other= 5 Council/housing=0	Positive/ Helpful= 17 Negative/ Unhelpful=19 N=36	Yes= 26 No= 31	Yes= 56 No= 1	
Female N=219	Yes= 183 No= 36	Family/friend= 115 Advocacy= 12 Police= 35 Other= 21 Council/housing=0	Positive/ Helpful= 104 Negative/ Unhelpful=79 N=183	Yes= 131 No= 88	Yes= 195 No= 24	
Other identified gender N= 4	Yes= 4 No= 0	Family/friend= 2 Advocacy= 0 Police= 1 Other= 1 Council/housing=0	Positive/ Helpful= 1 Negative/ Unhelpful= 3 N=4	Yes= 2 No= 2	Yes= 4 No= 0	

Appendix 3b) Interview Data Summary Chart

Summary of Interview Findings:

Participant (Victim) #	Victim gender	Victim age	Victim Nationality	Victim age when stalking started	Stalker Age when started	Stalker gender	Stalker typology	Amount of Stalking behaviours	Type of behaviour	Stalking still occurring or not
1.0608	Female	25	Scottish	21	28	Male	Incompetent suitor Stranger/ customer	9-12	Offline	No
2. 1998	Female	25	British	22 approx.	40's approx.	Male	Sexual predator/ Rejected	60 approx.	mixture	No?
3. 3658	Male	32	British/ Indian	17	Late 40's/50's	Male & Female	Predatory/ family	100's	mixture	no
4. 4839	Female	48	New Zealand	43	Colleague- late 30's Director- Late 50's	Male & Male	Incompetent suitor Intimacy seeker colleagues	100+ Unknown	both offline	No No?
5. 0705	Female	59	British	55	42	Female	Rejected Ex-partner	100+	mixture	Yes
6. 2011	Female	61	Scottish	42	Mid 50's	Male	Resentful neighbour	100+	Offline	No
7. 2910	Female	30	British Scottish	25/26	30	Male	Rejected Ex-partner	50-100	Mixture	No
8. 1806	Female	32	White British	29	29	Male	Rejected Ex-partner	30-35	Mixture	No
9. 1171	Female	47	Scottish	43	48	Male	Resentful	100	Mixture	No?
10. 0814	Female	58	Scottish	40	33	Female	Rejected/ Intimacy seeker	100+	Online	No?
11. 1003	Female	65	British	51	45-50	Male	Sexual predator	100+	offline	No
12. 4969	Female	37	Australian/British	37	38	Male	Rejected/Resentful Ex-partner	100+	Online	No?
13.0000	Female	47	British/ Canadian	40	40	Male	Resentful/ medical/therapeutic client	11	Offline	No
14.7221	Female	52	Scottish	50	unknown	Male	Resentful-/ medical /therapeutic client	100+	Offline	Yes
15.2207	Female	29	British	26	47	Male	Incompetent suitor/ Colleague	23-30	Mixture	No
16. 1980	Female	43	British	41	48	Male	Rejected/ Ex-partner	100+	Mixture	No?
17. 7075	Female	32	British	29	29	Male	Rejected/ Ex-partner	12+	mixture	No?
18.5541	Female	57	Scottish	55	45-50	Female	Resentful/ Acquaintance	100	Mixture	Yes
19.3499	Male	36	Scottish	32	35	Male	Rejected/ Intimacy seeker (1 date)	100+	Mixture	No
20.5200	Male	49	Scottish	45	35	Female	Rejected/ Ex=girlfriend	100+	Mixture	No

Appendix 4- Journey of Stalking Victimization Chart

